

Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients¹

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, *basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci squence, Triangular numbers, etc.* Some *binomial coefficient-type patterned selfie numbers* are also studied. This paper works with *binomial coefficient type selfie numbers*. This work is reorganized version of author's previous work [16] done in 2018.

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¹This work is reorganized author's work <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a102.pdf> [16] done in 2018.

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1 Introduction

Recently, author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, etc. are also given.

1.1 Selfie Numbers with Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial. See below some examples:

$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$	$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$
$733 := 7 + 3!! + 3!$	$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$
$5177 := 5! + 17 + 7!$	$403199 := 40319 + 9!$

$1463 := -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!!$	$361469 := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$
$10077 := -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!$	$364292 := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$
$40585 := 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!$	$397584 := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$
$80518 := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$	$398173 := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$
$317489 := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$	$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$
$352797 := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$	$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$
$357592 := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$	$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$
$357941 := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$	

For more details refer author's work [11, 18].

1.2 Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial and/or square-root. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}. \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{aligned}$$

Examples given above are with **factorial** and **square-root** [11, 18]. First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**.

1.3 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence

The examples given in subsections, 1.1 and 1.2 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 235 &:= 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 &:= F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3. & 54128 &:= 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)).
 \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [13, 14, 19].

1.4 Selfie Numbers with Triangular Numbers

The examples given in subsections, 1.1 1.2 and 1.3 are with **factorial**, **square-root** and **Fibonacci sequence** numbers. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & 874 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 1081 &:= T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & 0105 &:= 50 + T(10) \\
 2887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & 1155 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & 1224 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1 \\
 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) & 2418 &:= T(81) - T(42) \\
 99545 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & 99632 &:= 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 99546 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & 99633 &:= 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).
 \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [21].

1.5 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 1.3 and 1.4 are with **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [15]. For summary of author's work on numbers refer [20]. Also refer [1, 4] for historical books on numbers. Some initial study on selfie numbers are given in [2, 3].

The above result done previously by author [15], and are up to 5 digits. The work extend it to six digits. The results appearing in [15] are also included in this work. Due to high quantity of numbers, we have divided it in two parts. One part works with digit's order selfie numbers and another part with reverse order selfie numbers. This paper is with binomial coefficient type selfie numbers in reverse order of digits.

2 Digit's Order Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients

This section brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** in different situations. Results are in terms of digit's order. First only with **basic operations**. Secondly, with use of **factorial** and then with used of **square-root**. Results based on using together **factorial** and **square-root** are also obtained but only up to 5 digits. All other types are up to 6x digits. In all cases, binomial coefficients are always present.

Remark 2.1. *In some cases, we don't need to write in terms of "C". The numbers can be written directly. See below:*

$$C(n,1) := n \times 1;$$
$$C(n,n) := n/n.$$

For example, $C(8,1) = 8 \times 1$ and $C(5,5) := 5/5$. We kept them as they appeared in calculations.

2.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** just with basic operations. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10 or 100. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.1.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$117650 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 0$$

$$117651 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 1$$

$$117652 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 2$$

$$117653 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 3$$

$$117654 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 4$$

$$117655 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 5$$

$$117656 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 6$$

$$117657 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 7$$

$$117658 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 8$$

$$117659 := 1 + 1 \times 7^{C(6,5)} + 9$$

$$117660 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 0$$

$$117661 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 1$$

$$117662 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 2$$

$$117663 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 3$$

$$117664 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 4$$

$$117665 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 5$$

$$117666 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 6$$

$$117667 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 7$$

$$117668 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 8$$

$$117669 := 11 + C(7,6)^6 + 9$$

$$263640 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 0$$

$$263641 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 1$$

$$263642 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 2$$

$$263643 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 3$$

$$263644 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 4$$

$$263645 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 5$$

$$263646 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 6$$

$$263647 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 7$$

$$263648 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 8$$

$$263649 := 26^3 \times C(6,4) + 9$$

$$293930 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 0$$

$$293931 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 1$$

$$293932 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 2$$

$$293933 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 3$$

$$293934 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 4$$

$$293935 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 5$$

$$293936 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 6$$

$$293937 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 7$$

$$293938 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 8$$

$$293939 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9 + 3) + 9$$

$$319770 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 0$$

$$319771 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 1$$

$$319772 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 2$$

$$319773 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 3$$

$$319774 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 4$$

$$319775 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 5$$

$$319776 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 6$$

$$319777 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 7$$

$$319778 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 8$$

$$319779 := C(3 + 19, 7 + 7) + 9$$

$$466520 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 0$$

$$466521 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 1$$

$$466522 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 2$$

$$466523 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 3$$

$$466524 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 4$$

$$466525 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 5$$

$$466526 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 6$$

$$466527 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 7$$

$$466528 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 8$$

$$466529 := (-4 + 6^6) \times C(5, 2) + 9$$

$$972450 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 0$$

$$972451 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 1$$

$$972452 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 2$$

$$972453 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 3$$

$$972454 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 4$$

$$972455 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 5$$

$$972456 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 6$$

$$972457 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 7$$

$$972458 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 8$$

$$972459 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 9$$

2.1.2 Non Symmetrical Representations

$$3125 := (C(3, 1) + 2)^5$$

$$6435 := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5)$$

$$9576 := C(9, 5) \times 76$$

$$11429 := -11 + C(4^2, 9)$$

$$12376 := C(1 + 23 - 7, 6)$$

$$12645 := C(-1 + 26, 4) - 5$$

$$12871 := 1 + C(2 \times 8, 7 + 1)$$

$$19447 := -1 + C(9 + 4 + 4, 7)$$

$$21252 := C(2 \times 12, 5) / 2$$

$$22875 := 2 \times C(2 \times 8, 7) - 5$$

$$24288 := C(24, 2) \times 88$$

$$31827 := 3 + C((1 + 8) \times 2, 7)$$

$$32805 := C(3, 2)^8 \times 05$$

$$39366 := 3^9 \times (3 - C(6, 6))$$

$$53255 := ((5^3) + C(25, 5))$$

$$54262 := C(5 + 4^2, 6) - 2$$

$$54264 := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4))$$

$$59054 := 5 + 9^{C(05, 4)}$$

$$69498 := 6 \times 9 \times C(4 + 9, 8)$$

$$69984 := 6^{(-C(9, 9) + 8)} / 4$$

$$83755 := (-C(8, 3) + 7^5) \times 5$$

$$94752 := C(9, 4) \times 752$$

$$95760 := C(9, 5) \times 760$$

$$98415 := C(9, 8)^4 \times 15$$

$$113849 := -1 + C(1 + 3 \times 8, 4) \times 9$$

$$114686 := -1 - 1 + 4^6 \times C(8, 6)$$

$$114921 := (C(11, 4) + 9)^2 \times 1$$

$$115829 := -1 + C(15, 8) \times 2 \times 9$$

$$115836 := (1 + C(15, 8) \times 3) \times 6$$

$$116275 := C(C(C(1, 1) + 6, 2), 7) - 5$$

$$116281 := 1 + C(C(1 + 6, 2), 8 - 1)$$

$$116488 := (1 + C(16, 4) \times 8) \times 8$$

$$117649 := 1 - 1 + 7^{C(6, 4) - 9}$$

$$117672 := 1 + 1 + 7^6 + C(7, 2)$$

$$117673 := -11 + 7^6 + C(7, 3)$$

$$117676 := -1 + C(1 + 7, 6) + 7^6$$

$$117766 := 117 + C(7, 6)^6$$

$$118755 := C(1 - 1 + 8 + C(7, 5), 5)$$

$$125958 := -12 + C(5 \times (9 - 5), 8)$$

$$125968 := -1 \times 2 + C(5 + 9 + 6, 8)$$

$$134596 := C(1 \times 3 \times (4 - 5 + 9), 6)$$

$$138996 := C(13, 8) \times (9 + 9) \times 6$$

$$139966 := 1 - 3 \times (C(9, 9) - 6^6)$$

$$144144 := C(14, 4) \times 144$$

$$147492 := (1 + 4^7 / 4) \times C(9, 2)$$

$$163275 := -1 + 6^{3+2} \times C(7, 5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 163842 &:= (1 + C(6, 3) \times 8^4) \times 2 \\ 167959 &:= -1 + C((6 + 7 - 9) \times 5, 9) \\ 177147 &:= (1 + C(7, 7) + 1)^{4+7} \\ 184755 &:= -1 + C(-8 + 4 \times 7, 5 + 5) \\ 194488 &:= 1 + C(9 + 4 + 4, 8) \times 8 \\ 203485 &:= C(20 - 3 + 4, 8) - 5 \\ 212515 &:= (C(2 \times 12, 5) - 1) \times 5 \\ 212535 &:= (C(2 \times 12, 5) + 3) \times 5 \\ 216864 &:= (C(21, 6) - 8 \times 6) \times 4 \\ 219375 &:= C((2 + 1) \times 9, 3) \times 75 \\ 225398 &:= -2 + C(25, 3) \times 98 \\ 229376 &:= 2^{(2 \times 9 - 3)} \times C(7, 6) \\ 235487 &:= (C(23, C(5, 4)) - 8) \times 7 \\ 235543 &:= C(23, 5) \times (-5 + 4 \times 3) \\ 235574 &:= (C(23, 5) + 5) \times 7 - 4 \\ 235627 &:= (C(23, 5) + 6 \times 2) \times 7 \\ 238328 &:= (23 + 8)^{C(3, 2) \times 8} \\ 242880 &:= C(24, 2) \times 880 \\ 245157 &:= C(24 - 5 - 1 + 5, 7) \\ 245237 &:= 2^4 \times 5 + C(23, 7) \\ 248834 &:= 2 + (4 + 8)^{C(8 - 3, 4)} \\ 249318 &:= (2 + 4 \times 9) \times C(3, 1)^8 \\ 249856 &:= 2^4 \times (-C(9, 8) + 5^6) \\ 251975 &:= (2 + 5 + C(19, 7)) \times 5 \\ 251977 &:= 2 + 5 \times (C(19, 7) + 7) \\ 251978 &:= -2 + 5 \times (C(19, 7) + 8) \\ 256256 &:= 2^5 \times C(6 + 2 \times 5, 6) \\ 262118 &:= -26 + C(2, 1)^{18} \\ 262136 &:= -2 - 6 + C(2, 1)^{3 \times 6} \\ 262144 &:= C((2 + 6) \times 2, 1)^4 \times 4 \\ 262688 &:= (2^{C(6, 2)} + 68) \times 8 \\ 268322 &:= -2 + (6 + 8^{C(3, 2)})^2 \\ 274274 &:= C(2 \times 7, 4) \times 274 \\ 276327 &:= C(27, 6) - 3^{2+7} \\ 277991 &:= C(2 \times 7, 7) \times 9 \times 9 - 1 \\ 279657 &:= -279 + C(6, 5)^7 \\ 279841 &:= (2 \times 7 + 9)^{C(8 - 4, 1)} \\ 279934 &:= -2 + (7 - C(9, 9))^{3+4} \\ 279937 &:= C(2 + 7, 9) + (9 - 3)^7 \\ 291602 &:= 2 + (C(9, 1) \times 60)^2 \\ 293915 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) - 15 \\ 293924 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) - 2 - 4 \\ 293926 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 2 - 6 \\ 293955 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 5 \times 5 \\ 293966 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 6 \times 6 \\ 294753 &:= (-29 + C(4 \times 7, 5)) \times 3 \\ 294768 &:= 2 \times 9 \times (4^{C(7, 6)} - 8) \\ 294912 &:= 2^{9+4} \times C(C(9, 1), 2) \\ 296344 &:= 2 \times (C(9, 6)^3 / 4 - 4) \\ 296346 &:= 2 \times C(9, 6)^3 / 4 - 6 \\ 296353 &:= (2 + C(9, 6)^3) / (5 - 3) \\ 314432 &:= ((3 + 14) \times 4)^{C(3, 2)} \\ 319768 &:= -3 + 1 + C(9 + 7 + 6, 8) \\ 323584 &:= (C(3^2, 3) - 5) \times 8^4 \\ 325566 &:= (-3 + C(C(2 + 5, 5), 6)) \times 6 \\ 326627 &:= (C(3, 2) + 6^6 + 2) \times 7 \\ 327680 &:= (-C(3, 2) + 7)^6 \times 80 \\ 327695 &:= (3 + 2^{C(7, 6) + 9}) \times 5 \\ 328050 &:= C(3, 2)^8 \times 050 \\ 329232 &:= 3 \times (2 + C(9, 2))^3 \times 2 \\ 346107 &:= 3 + C(C(4 \times 6, 1), 07) \\ 352719 &:= 3 + C((5 - 2) \times 7, 1 + 9) \\ 354347 &:= ((3 \times 5)^{C(4, 3)} - 4) \times 7 \\ 354375 &:= (3 \times 5)^4 / 3 \times C(7, 5) \\ 356265 &:= 3 \times C(5 + (6 - 2) \times 6, 5) \\ 375168 &:= 3 \times (7 + C(5, 1)^6) \times 8 \\ 376866 &:= 3 \times 7 \times 6 + C(C(8, 6), 6) \\ 408595 &:= C(40 / 8 \times 5, 9) / 5 \\ 413736 &:= (41^3 + C(7, 3)) \times 6 \\ 425984 &:= (4 \times 2)^5 \times (C(9, 8) + 4) \\ 433768 &:= (-43 + C(3 \times 7, 6)) \times 8 \\ 438933 &:= -43 + (-8 + C(9, 3))^3 \\ 458748 &:= -C(4, -5 + 8) + 7 \times 4^8 \\ 474552 &:= (4 + 74)^{C(5, 5) + 2} \\ 497469 &:= 49 + C(7 \times 4 - 6, 9) \\ 524288 &:= (C(5, 2) - 4 - 2)^8 \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 524298 &:= C(5,2) + 4 \times 2^{9+8} \\
 524328 &:= (5 + 2^{C(4,3)^2 \times 8}) \\
 524392 &:= (52 + C(4,3)^9) \times 2 \\
 531396 &:= -C(5 \times 3,1) \times 3 + 9^6 \\
 531433 &:= -5 + C(3,1)^{4 \times 3} - 3 \\
 531438 &:= 5 + C(3,1)^{4 \times 3} - 8 \\
 538364 &:= (-5 + C(3 \times 8, 3 \times 6)) \times 4 \\
 554253 &:= -5 + C(5 \times 4, 2 \times 5) \times 3 \\
 554283 &:= 5 + C(5 \times 4, 2 + 8) \times 3 \\
 577364 &:= C(5 + 7, 7) \times 3^6 - 4 \\
 581375 &:= 5 \times (C(8 + 13, 7) - 5) \\
 592763 &:= 59 + C(2 + 7, 6)^3 \\
 593775 &:= 5 \times C(9 \times (-3 + 7) - 7, 5) \\
 594594 &:= C(5 + 9, 4) \times 594 \\
 614648 &:= C(-6 + 14, 6)^4 - 8 \\
 627232 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - 32 \\
 627264 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^{(2+6)/4} \\
 627265 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 + 6 - 5 \\
 627271 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 + 7 \times 1 \\
 629946 &:= (C(6, 2) + (9 + 9)^4) \times 6 \\
 646646 &:= C(6 + 4 + 6 + 6, 4 + 6) \\
 652596 &:= (6^5 - 2 - 5) \times C(9, 6) \\
 684684 &:= C(6 + 8, 4) \times 684 \\
 697578 &:= 6 \times (-9 + C(C(7, 5), 7) - 8) \\
 712215 &:= C(7, 1 + 2) \times C(21, 5) \\
 712956 &:= (71 + C(29, 5)) \times 6 \\
 715822 &:= 71^{C(-5+8,2)} \times 2 \\
 724724 &:= C(7 \times 2, 4) \times 724 \\
 728993 &:= -7 + (C(2 + 8, 9) \times 9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 729021 &:= C(7,2) + 90^{2+1} \\
 734825 &:= C(7 \times 3, 4 + 8) / 2 \times 5 \\
 735398 &:= -73 + C(5 \times 3 + 9, 8) \\
 735471 &:= C((7 - 3) \times 5 + 4, 7 + 1) \\
 735478 &:= 7 + C(35 - 4 - 7, 8) \\
 741125 &:= (C(7,4) \times 11)^2 \times 5 \\
 759155 &:= -C(7 + 5, 9) + 15^5 \\
 763783 &:= 7 + C(6 \times 3, 7) \times 8 \times 3 \\
 765625 &:= C(7,6) \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) \\
 765667 &:= (C(7,6) \times 5^6 + 6) \times 7 \\
 774774 &:= C(7 + 7, 4) \times 774 \\
 776887 &:= 7^7 - 6^{(-C(8,8)+7)} \\
 781257 &:= 7 + (C(8,1) + 2) \times 5^7 \\
 786383 &:= 7 + 8^6 \times 3 - C(8,3) \\
 786411 &:= (-7 + 8^6) \times C(4 - 1, 1) \\
 817239 &:= (8 - 1) \times 7 + C(23, 9) \\
 823537 &:= -8 + 2 + (-3 + C(5, 3))^7 \\
 837550 &:= (-C(8, 3) + 7^5) \times 50 \\
 864864 &:= C(8 + 6, 4) \times 864 \\
 912673 &:= (C(9, 1 + 2) + 6 + 7)^3 \\
 947520 &:= C(9, 4) \times 7520 \\
 954954 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 954 \\
 957600 &:= C(9, 5) \times 7600 \\
 972414 &:= 9 + C(7, 2)^4 \times (1 + 4) \\
 972435 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 - 3) \times 5 \\
 972495 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 + 9) \times 5 \\
 984150 &:= C(9, 8)^4 \times 150
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial**. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10 or 100. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.2.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$\begin{aligned}
 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 & 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 \\
 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 & 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37440 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 0 \\ 37441 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 1 \\ 37442 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 2 \\ 37443 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 3 \\ 37444 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 4 \\ 37445 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 5 \\ 37446 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 6 \\ 37447 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 7 \\ 37448 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 8 \\ 37449 &:= 3!! \times (7 \times 4 + 4!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95760 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 0 \\ 95761 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 1 \\ 95762 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 2 \\ 95763 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 3 \\ 95764 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 4 \\ 95765 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 5 \\ 95766 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 6 \\ 95767 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 7 \\ 95768 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 8 \\ 95769 &:= (C(9, 5) + 7) \times 6! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 113760 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 0 \\ 113761 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 1 \\ 113762 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 2 \\ 113763 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 3 \\ 113764 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 4 \\ 113765 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 5 \\ 113766 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 6 \\ 113767 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 7 \\ 113768 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 8 \\ 113769 &:= (C(11, 3) - 7) \times 6! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 134600 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 00 \\ 134601 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 01 \\ 134602 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 02 \\ 134603 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 03 \\ 134604 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 04 \\ 134605 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 05 \\ 134606 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 06 \\ 134607 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 07 \\ 134608 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 08 \\ 134609 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 09 \\ 134610 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 10 \\ 134611 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 11 \\ 134612 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 12 \\ 134613 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 13 \\ 134614 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 14 \\ 134615 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 15 \\ 134616 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 16 \\ 134617 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 17 \\ 134618 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 18 \\ 134619 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 19 \\ 134620 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 20 \\ 134621 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 21 \\ 134622 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 22 \\ 134623 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 23 \\ 134624 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 24 \\ 134625 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 25 \\ 134626 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 26 \\ 134627 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 27 \\ 134628 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 28 \\ 134629 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 29 \\ 134630 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 30 \\ 134631 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 31 \\ 134632 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 32 \\ 134633 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 33 \\ 134634 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 34 \\ 134635 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 35 \\ 134636 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 36 \\ 134637 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 37 \\ 134638 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 38 \\ 134639 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 39 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 134640 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 40 \\ 134641 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 41 \\ 134642 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 42 \\ 134643 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 43 \\ 134644 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 44 \\ 134645 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 45 \\ 134646 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 46 \\ 134647 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 47 \\ 134648 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 48 \\ 134649 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 49 \\ 134650 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 50 \\ 134651 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 51 \\ 134652 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 52 \\ 134653 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 53 \\ 134654 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 54 \\ 134655 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 55 \\ 134656 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 56 \\ 134657 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 57 \\ 134658 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 58 \\ 134659 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 59 \\ 134660 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 60 \\ 134661 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 61 \\ 134662 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 62 \\ 134663 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 63 \\ 134664 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 64 \\ 134665 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 65 \\ 134666 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 66 \\ 134667 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 67 \\ 134668 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 68 \\ 134669 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 69 \\ 134670 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 70 \\ 134671 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 71 \\ 134672 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 72 \\ 134673 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 73 \\ 134674 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 74 \\ 134675 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 75 \\ 134676 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 76 \\ 134677 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 77 \\ 134678 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 78 \\ 134679 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 79 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 134680 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 80 \\ 134681 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 81 \\ 134682 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 82 \\ 134683 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 83 \\ 134684 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 84 \\ 134685 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 85 \\ 134686 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 86 \\ 134687 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 87 \\ 134688 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 88 \\ 134689 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 89 \\ 134690 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 90 \\ 134691 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 91 \\ 134692 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 92 \\ 134693 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 93 \\ 134694 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 94 \\ 134695 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 95 \\ 134696 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 96 \\ 134697 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 97 \\ 134698 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 98 \\ 134699 &:= 1 + 3 + C(4!, 6) + 99 \\ 154440 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 0 \\ 154441 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 1 \\ 154442 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 2 \\ 154443 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 3 \\ 154444 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 4 \\ 154445 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 5 \\ 154446 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 6 \\ 154447 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 7 \\ 154448 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 8 \\ 154449 &:= C(15, 4 + 4) \times 4! + 9 \\ 181440 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 0 \\ 181441 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 1 \\ 181442 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 2 \\ 181443 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 3 \\ 181444 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 4 \\ 181445 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 5 \\ 181446 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 6 \\ 181447 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 7 \\ 181448 &:= (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$181449 := (1 + 8)! / (1 + C(4, 4)) + 9$$

$$230230 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 0$$

$$230231 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 1$$

$$230232 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 2$$

$$230233 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 3$$

$$230234 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 4$$

$$230235 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 5$$

$$230236 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 6$$

$$230237 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 7$$

$$230238 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 8$$

$$230239 := C(-2 + 30 - 2, 3!) + 9$$

$$230350 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 0$$

$$230351 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 1$$

$$230352 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 2$$

$$230353 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 3$$

$$230354 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 4$$

$$230355 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 5$$

$$230356 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 6$$

$$230357 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 7$$

$$230358 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 8$$

$$230359 := C(2 + (3 + 0)!, 3!) + 5! + 9$$

$$238330 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 0$$

$$238331 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 1$$

$$238332 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 2$$

$$238333 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 3$$

$$238334 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 4$$

$$238335 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 5$$

$$238336 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 6$$

$$238337 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 7$$

$$238338 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 8$$

$$238339 := 2 + (3! + C(8, 3))^3 + 9$$

$$244400 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 0$$

$$244401 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 1$$

$$244402 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 2$$

$$244403 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 3$$

$$244404 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 4$$

$$244405 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 5$$

$$244406 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 6$$

$$244407 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 7$$

$$244408 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 8$$

$$244409 := 2 + C(4!, 4) \times (4! - 0!) + 9$$

$$252720 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 0$$

$$252721 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 1$$

$$252722 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 2$$

$$252723 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 3$$

$$252724 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 4$$

$$252725 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 5$$

$$252726 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 6$$

$$252727 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 7$$

$$252728 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 8$$

$$252729 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(27, 2) + 9$$

$$292320 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 0$$

$$292321 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$292322 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 2$$

$$292323 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 3$$

$$292324 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 4$$

$$292325 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 5$$

$$292326 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 6$$

$$292327 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 7$$

$$292328 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 8$$

$$292329 := C(29, 2) \times (3 \times 2)! + 9$$

$$298970 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 0$$

$$298971 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 1$$

$$298972 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 2$$

$$298973 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 3$$

$$298974 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 4$$

$$298975 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 5$$

$$298976 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 6$$

$$298977 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 7$$

$$298978 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 8$$

$$298979 := C(29 - 8, 9) + 7! + 9$$

$$308880 := (3 + 0)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 0$$

$$308881 := (3 + 0)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 1$$

$$308882 := (3 + 0)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 308883 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 3 \\ 308884 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 4 \\ 308885 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 5 \\ 308886 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 6 \\ 308887 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 7 \\ 308888 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 8 \\ 308889 &:= (3 + 0!)! \times C(8 + 8, 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 317520 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 0 \\ 317521 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 1 \\ 317522 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 2 \\ 317523 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 3 \\ 317524 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 4 \\ 317525 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 5 \\ 317526 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 6 \\ 317527 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 7 \\ 317528 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 8 \\ 317529 &:= 3!! \times C(1 \times 7, 5)^2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322680 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 0 \\ 322681 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 1 \\ 322682 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 2 \\ 322683 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 3 \\ 322684 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 4 \\ 322685 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 5 \\ 322686 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 6 \\ 322687 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 7 \\ 322688 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 8 \\ 322689 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)!) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345240 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 0 \\ 345241 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 1 \\ 345242 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 2 \\ 345243 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 3 \\ 345244 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 4 \\ 345245 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 5 \\ 345246 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 6 \\ 345247 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 7 \\ 345248 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$345249 := (-C(3!, 4) + 5!^2) \times 4! + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 346110 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 0 \\ 346111 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 1 \\ 346112 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 2 \\ 346113 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 3 \\ 346114 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 4 \\ 346115 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 5 \\ 346116 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 6 \\ 346117 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 7 \\ 346118 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 8 \\ 346119 &:= 3! + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 1) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354690 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 0 \\ 354691 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 1 \\ 354692 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 2 \\ 354693 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 3 \\ 354694 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 4 \\ 354695 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 5 \\ 354696 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 6 \\ 354697 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 7 \\ 354698 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 8 \\ 354699 &:= -C(3 \times 5, 4) \times 6 + 9! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362870 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 0 \\ 362871 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 1 \\ 362872 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 2 \\ 362873 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 3 \\ 362874 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 4 \\ 362875 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 5 \\ 362876 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 6 \\ 362877 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 7 \\ 362878 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 8 \\ 362879 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - C(8, 7) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362890 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 0 \\ 362891 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 1 \\ 362892 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 2 \\ 362893 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 3 \\ 362894 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 4 \\ 362895 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 5 \\ 362896 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$362897 := (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 7$$

$$362898 := (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 8$$

$$362899 := (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 8, 9) + 9$$

$$363240 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 0$$

$$363241 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 1$$

$$363242 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 2$$

$$363243 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 3$$

$$363244 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 4$$

$$363245 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 5$$

$$363246 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 6$$

$$363247 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 7$$

$$363248 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 8$$

$$363249 := (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 2) \times 4! + 9$$

$$377460 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 0$$

$$377461 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 1$$

$$377462 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 2$$

$$377463 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 3$$

$$377464 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 4$$

$$377465 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 5$$

$$377466 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 6$$

$$377467 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 7$$

$$377468 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 8$$

$$377469 := 3!! + C(-7 + C(7, 4), 6) + 9$$

$$378450 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 0$$

$$378451 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 1$$

$$378452 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 2$$

$$378453 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 3$$

$$378454 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 4$$

$$378455 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 5$$

$$378456 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 6$$

$$378457 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 7$$

$$378458 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 8$$

$$378459 := (3! + 7!) \times (C(8, 4) + 5) + 9$$

$$382590 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 0$$

$$382591 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 1$$

$$382592 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 2$$

$$382593 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 3$$

$$382594 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 4$$

$$382595 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 5$$

$$382596 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 6$$

$$382597 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 7$$

$$382598 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 8$$

$$382599 := (3! + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 9 + 9$$

$$405390 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 0$$

$$405391 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 1$$

$$405392 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 2$$

$$405393 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 3$$

$$405394 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 4$$

$$405395 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 5$$

$$405396 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 6$$

$$405397 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 7$$

$$405398 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 8$$

$$405399 := C(4!, 05) + 3! + 9! + 9$$

$$480700 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 00$$

$$480701 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 01$$

$$480702 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 02$$

$$480703 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 03$$

$$480704 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 04$$

$$480705 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 05$$

$$480706 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 06$$

$$480707 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 07$$

$$480708 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 08$$

$$480709 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 09$$

$$480710 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 10$$

$$480711 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 11$$

$$480712 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 12$$

$$480713 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 13$$

$$480714 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 14$$

$$480715 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 15$$

$$480716 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 16$$

$$480717 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 17$$

$$480718 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 18$$

$$480719 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 19$$

$$480720 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 20$$

$$480721 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 21$$

$$480722 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 22$$

$$480723 := C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 23$$

$$\begin{aligned} 480724 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 24 \\ 480725 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 25 \\ 480726 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 26 \\ 480727 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 27 \\ 480728 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 28 \\ 480729 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 29 \\ 480730 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 30 \\ 480731 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 31 \\ 480732 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 32 \\ 480733 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 33 \\ 480734 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 34 \\ 480735 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 35 \\ 480736 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 36 \\ 480737 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 37 \\ 480738 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 38 \\ 480739 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 39 \\ 480740 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 40 \\ 480741 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 41 \\ 480742 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 42 \\ 480743 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 43 \\ 480744 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 44 \\ 480745 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 45 \\ 480746 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 46 \\ 480747 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 47 \\ 480748 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 48 \\ 480749 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 49 \\ 480750 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 50 \\ 480751 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 51 \\ 480752 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 52 \\ 480753 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 53 \\ 480754 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 54 \\ 480755 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 55 \\ 480756 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 56 \\ 480757 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 57 \\ 480758 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 58 \\ 480759 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 59 \\ 480760 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 60 \\ 480761 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 61 \\ 480762 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 62 \\ 480763 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 63 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 480764 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 64 \\ 480765 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 65 \\ 480766 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 66 \\ 480767 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 67 \\ 480768 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 68 \\ 480769 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 69 \\ 480770 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 70 \\ 480771 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 71 \\ 480772 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 72 \\ 480773 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 73 \\ 480774 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 74 \\ 480775 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 75 \\ 480776 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 76 \\ 480777 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 77 \\ 480778 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 78 \\ 480779 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 79 \\ 480780 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 80 \\ 480781 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 81 \\ 480782 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 82 \\ 480783 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 83 \\ 480784 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 84 \\ 480785 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 85 \\ 480786 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 86 \\ 480787 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 87 \\ 480788 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 88 \\ 480789 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 89 \\ 480790 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 90 \\ 480791 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 91 \\ 480792 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 92 \\ 480793 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 93 \\ 480794 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 94 \\ 480795 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 95 \\ 480796 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 96 \\ 480797 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 97 \\ 480798 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 98 \\ 480799 &:= C(4! + (8 \times 0)!, 7) + 99 \\ \\ 483840 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 0 \\ 483841 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 1 \\ 483842 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 2 \\ 483843 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483844 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 4 \\ 483845 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 5 \\ 483846 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 6 \\ 483847 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 7 \\ 483848 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 8 \\ 483849 &:= 4 \times 8! \times C(3, 8/4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 504690 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 0 \\ 504691 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 1 \\ 504692 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 2 \\ 504693 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 3 \\ 504694 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 4 \\ 504695 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 5 \\ 504696 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 6 \\ 504697 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 7 \\ 504698 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 8 \\ 504699 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 9) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 518360 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 0 \\ 518361 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 1 \\ 518362 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 2 \\ 518363 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 3 \\ 518364 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 4 \\ 518365 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 5 \\ 518366 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 6 \\ 518367 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 7 \\ 518368 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 8 \\ 518369 &:= -C(5, 1) \times 8 + 3!! \times 6! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 599760 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 0 \\ 599761 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 1 \\ 599762 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 2 \\ 599763 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 3 \\ 599764 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 4 \\ 599765 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 5 \\ 599766 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 6 \\ 599767 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 7 \\ 599768 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 8 \\ 599769 &:= (5! - C(9, 9)) \times C(7, 6)! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604800 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 00 \\ 604801 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 01 \\ 604802 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 02 \\ 604803 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 03 \\ 604804 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 04 \\ 604805 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 05 \\ 604806 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 06 \\ 604807 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 07 \\ 604808 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 08 \\ 604809 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 09 \\ 604810 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 10 \\ 604811 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 11 \\ 604812 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 12 \\ 604813 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 13 \\ 604814 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 14 \\ 604815 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 15 \\ 604816 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 16 \\ 604817 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 17 \\ 604818 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 18 \\ 604819 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 19 \\ 604820 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 20 \\ 604821 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 21 \\ 604822 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 22 \\ 604823 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 23 \\ 604824 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 24 \\ 604825 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 25 \\ 604826 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 26 \\ 604827 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 27 \\ 604828 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 28 \\ 604829 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 29 \\ 604830 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 30 \\ 604831 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 31 \\ 604832 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 32 \\ 604833 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 33 \\ 604834 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 34 \\ 604835 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 35 \\ 604836 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 36 \\ 604837 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 37 \\ 604838 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 38 \\ 604839 &:= C(6, 04) \times 8! + 39 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604840 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 40 \\ 604841 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 41 \\ 604842 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 42 \\ 604843 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 43 \\ 604844 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 44 \\ 604845 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 45 \\ 604846 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 46 \\ 604847 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 47 \\ 604848 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 48 \\ 604849 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 49 \\ 604850 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 50 \\ 604851 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 51 \\ 604852 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 52 \\ 604853 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 53 \\ 604854 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 54 \\ 604855 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 55 \\ 604856 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 56 \\ 604857 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 57 \\ 604858 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 58 \\ 604859 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 59 \\ 604860 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 60 \\ 604861 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 61 \\ 604862 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 62 \\ 604863 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 63 \\ 604864 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 64 \\ 604865 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 65 \\ 604866 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 66 \\ 604867 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 67 \\ 604868 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 68 \\ 604869 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 69 \\ 604870 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 70 \\ 604871 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 71 \\ 604872 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 72 \\ 604873 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 73 \\ 604874 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 74 \\ 604875 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 75 \\ 604876 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 76 \\ 604877 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 77 \\ 604878 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 78 \\ 604879 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 79 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 604880 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 80 \\ 604881 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 81 \\ 604882 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 82 \\ 604883 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 83 \\ 604884 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 84 \\ 604885 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 85 \\ 604886 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 86 \\ 604887 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 88 \\ 604888 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 88 \\ 604889 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 89 \\ 604890 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 90 \\ 604891 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 91 \\ 604892 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 92 \\ 604893 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 93 \\ 604894 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 94 \\ 604895 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 95 \\ 604896 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 96 \\ 604897 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 98 \\ 604898 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 98 \\ 604899 &:= C(6,04) \times 8! + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 627240 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 0 \\ 627241 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 1 \\ 627242 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 2 \\ 627243 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 3 \\ 627244 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 4 \\ 627245 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 5 \\ 627246 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 6 \\ 627247 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 7 \\ 627248 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 8 \\ 627249 &:= C(6 \times 2,7)^2 - 4! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 635760 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 0 \\ 635761 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 1 \\ 635762 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 2 \\ 635763 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 3 \\ 635764 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 4 \\ 635765 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 5 \\ 635766 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 6 \\ 635767 &:= C(6 + 3,5) \times 7! + 6! + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$635768 := C(6 + 3, 5) \times 7! + 6! + 8$$

$$635769 := C(6 + 3, 5) \times 7! + 6! + 9$$

$$637560 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 0$$

$$637561 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 1$$

$$637562 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 2$$

$$637563 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 3$$

$$637564 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 4$$

$$637565 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 5$$

$$637566 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 6$$

$$637567 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 7$$

$$637568 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 8$$

$$637569 := (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6) + 9$$

$$679590 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 0$$

$$679591 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 1$$

$$679592 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 2$$

$$679593 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 3$$

$$679594 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 4$$

$$679595 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 5$$

$$679596 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 6$$

$$679597 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 7$$

$$679598 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 8$$

$$679599 := (-6 + 7!) \times (C(9, 5) + 9) + 9$$

$$684720 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 0$$

$$684721 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 1$$

$$684722 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 2$$

$$684723 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 3$$

$$684724 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 4$$

$$684725 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 5$$

$$684726 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 6$$

$$684727 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 7$$

$$684728 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 8$$

$$684729 := -6! - 8! \times (4 - C(7, 2)) + 9$$

$$735480 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 0$$

$$735481 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 1$$

$$735482 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 2$$

$$735483 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 3$$

$$735484 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 4$$

$$735485 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 5$$

$$735486 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 6$$

$$735487 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 7$$

$$735488 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 8$$

$$735489 := 7 - 3 + 5 + C(4!, 8) + 9$$

$$771120 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 0$$

$$771121 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 1$$

$$771122 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 2$$

$$771123 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 3$$

$$771124 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 4$$

$$771125 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 5$$

$$771126 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 6$$

$$771127 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 7$$

$$771128 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 8$$

$$771129 := 7! \times C(7 + 11, 2) + 9$$

$$847230 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 0$$

$$847231 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 1$$

$$847232 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 2$$

$$847233 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 3$$

$$847234 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 4$$

$$847235 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 5$$

$$847236 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 6$$

$$847237 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 7$$

$$847238 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 8$$

$$847239 := (8! + 4!) \times C(7, 2) + 3! + 9$$

$$944620 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 0$$

$$944621 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 1$$

$$944622 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 2$$

$$944623 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 3$$

$$944624 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 4$$

$$944625 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 5$$

$$944626 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 6$$

$$944627 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 7$$

$$944628 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 8$$

$$944629 := -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 2)) + 9$$

$$949670 := -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 0$$

$$949671 := -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 1$$

$$949672 := -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 949673 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 3 \\ 949674 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 4 \\ 949675 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 5 \\ 949676 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 6 \\ 949677 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 7 \\ 949678 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 8 \\ 949679 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 6 + 7! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972450 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 0 \\ 972451 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 1 \\ 972452 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 2 \\ 972453 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 3 \\ 972454 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 4 \\ 972455 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 5 \\ 972456 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972457 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 7 \\ 972458 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 8 \\ 972459 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4) \times 5 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 984940 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 0 \\ 984941 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 1 \\ 984942 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 2 \\ 984943 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 3 \\ 984944 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 4 \\ 984945 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 5 \\ 984946 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 6 \\ 984947 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 7 \\ 984948 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8 \\ 984949 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.2 Non Symmetrical Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 3591 &:= 3!! \times 5 - C(9, 1) \\ 3599 &:= 3!! \times 5 - C(9, 9) \\ 3723 &:= 3!! + C(7 \times 2, 3!) \\ 4494 &:= -C(4!, 4) + 9!/4! \\ 5035 &:= -5 + (0! + C(3!, 5))! \\ 5765 &:= 5 + 7! + C(6, 5)! \\ 10000 &:= 100^{0!+0!} \\ 10624 &:= -1 - 0! + C((6 - 2)!, 4) \\ 10626 &:= C((10 - 6)!, -2 + 6) \\ 11346 &:= C((C(1, 1) + 3)!, 4) + 6! \\ 12143 &:= -1 + (2 + 1)! \times C(4!, 3) \\ 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) \\ 13248 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 2) \times 48 \\ 13456 &:= 1 + C(3 + 4!, 5)/6 \\ 15123 &:= 1 + (C(5, 1) + 2)! \times 3 \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) \\ 15631 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + C(3, 1)! \\ 15939 &:= C(-1 + (-5 + 9)!, 3) \times 9 \\ 16583 &:= (1 + 6!) \times (-5 + C(8, 3!)) \\ 17424 &:= (-1 + 7 + C(4, 2)!) \times 4! \\ 18563 &:= -1 + C((8 - 5) \times 6, 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) \\ 20474 &:= -2 + 0! + C(4 \times 7, 4) \\ 22433 &:= (2 + C(24, 3!))/3! \\ 22880 &:= 2 \times C(2 \times 8, 8 + 0!) \\ 24308 &:= -2 + C(4! - 3! - 0!, 8) \\ 24312 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times 12 \\ 24396 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 6 \\ 24752 &:= 2 \times C(4! - 7, (5 - 2)!) \\ 24754 &:= 2 + C(4! - 7, 5) \times 4 \\ 24768 &:= 2 \times (C(4! - 7, 6) + 8) \\ 25275 &:= (C((-2 + 5)!, 2) + 7!) \times 5 \\ 25373 &:= -2 + (5 + 3!) \times C(7, 3) \\ 26684 &:= -C((-2 + 6)!, 6) + 8! \times 4 \\ 28878 &:= -2 - C(8 + 8, 7) + 8! \\ 31818 &:= -3! + C(18, -1 + 8) \\ 31830 &:= 3! + C(18, 3! + 0!) \\ 32175 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 1 \times 7) \times 5 \\ 32384 &:= C((3! - 2)!, 3) \times (-8 + 4!) \\ 32645 &:= -3 + 2^{C(6, 4)} - 5! \\ 32835 &:= (C(3, 2)^8 + 3!) \times 5 \\ 33655 &:= 3! + C(3 \times 6 + 5, 5) \\ 33839 &:= -C(3, 3) + 8! - 3!! \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34368 &:= 3! \times (-C(4,3) + 6!) \times 8 \\ 34392 &:= 2 \times (-C(9,3) + 4! \times 3!!) \\ 34497 &:= 3!! \times (4! + 4!) - 9 \times 7 \\ 34776 &:= (-3 \times 4! + 7!) \times C(7,6) \\ 35273 &:= (-3!! + C(5,2)!) \times 7/3!! \\ 35287 &:= -3 + C(5,2) + 8! - 7! \\ 35943 &:= C(3!,5) + (9 + 4!)^3 \\ 36431 &:= 3 \times 6 \times C(4!,3) - 1 \\ 36432 &:= (3 + 6) \times C(4!,3) \times 2 \\ 36882 &:= -C(3 \times 6,8) + 8! \times 2 \\ 37454 &:= -3! - 7! + C(4!,5) - 4 \\ 37457 &:= -3!! \times 7 + C(4!,5) - 7 \\ 37461 &:= -3 - 7! + C(4!,6 - 1) \\ 37998 &:= -3!! - 7! + C(9 + 9,8) \\ 38318 &:= -C(3! + 8,3! - 1) + 8! \\ 38416 &:= (3! + 8)^{C(4,1^6)} \\ 38883 &:= 3 + 8! - 8!/C(8,3!) \\ 38886 &:= 3! + 8! - 8!/C(8,6) \\ 39468 &:= -3! - C(9,4) - 6! + 8! \\ 39528 &:= -C(3 + 9,5 + 2) + 8! \\ 40038 &:= -C(4!,0! + 0!) - 3! + 8! \\ 40044 &:= -C(4!,0! + 0!) + (4 + 4)! \\ 40048 &:= -C(4!,0! + 0!) + 4 + 8! \\ 40194 &:= (4 \times (0! + 1))! - C(9,4) \\ 40278 &:= -C(4,02) \times 7 + 8! \\ 40315 &:= -4 - 0! + (C(3,1) + 5)! \\ 40325 &:= 4 + 0! + (C(3,2) + 5)! \\ 40344 &:= 4! + (C(4,3) + 04)! \\ 40441 &:= (4 + 0!)! + (4 + 4)! + 1 \\ 41268 &:= 4! + C(12,6) + 8! \\ 41428 &:= 4 \times (1 + C(4!,2)) + 8! \\ 42336 &:= C(4,2)^{3!} - 3! \times 6! \\ 42453 &:= -4! \times 2 + C(4!,5) - 3 \\ 42454 &:= -4! - 2 + C(4!,5) + 4! \\ 42456 &:= -42 + C(4!,5) - 6 \\ 42502 &:= C(4!,(-2 + 5)! - 0!) - 2 \\ 42504 &:= C(4!,2 \times 5 - 0! - 4) \\ 42528 &:= (C(4!,2) + (5 + 2)!) \times 8 \\ 42544 &:= 4 \times (2 \times 5 + C(4!,4)) \\ 43224 &:= C(4!,3 + 2) + (2 + 4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43226 &:= C(4!,3 + 2) + 2 + 6! \\ 43233 &:= C(4!,3 + 2) + 3^3! \\ 43632 &:= (4!^3 + 6!) \times C(3,2) \\ 43734 &:= C(4! - 3!,7 + 3) - 4! \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!,7 - 5 + 8) \\ 43824 &:= 4! \times (3! + C(8 \times 2,4)) \\ 43854 &:= C(4! - 3!,8) + 5! - 4! \\ 44184 &:= C(4!,4 + 1) + 8!/4! \\ 44416 &:= (4 + 4)! + C(4,1)^6 \\ 45504 &:= C(4!,5) + 5! \times (0! + 4!) \\ 46638 &:= 4 \times 6! + C(6 \times 3,8) \\ 47336 &:= C(4! - 7,3) + 3!^6 \\ 47545 &:= -4 + 7! + 5 + C(4!,5) \\ 47872 &:= 4^7 + C(8,7)! \times 2 \\ 48328 &:= C(4! - 8,3 \times 2) + 8! \\ 48432 &:= 4! \times (-8 + C(4!,3) + 2) \\ 48555 &:= C(4!,8) \times 5 - (5 + 5)! \\ 49428 &:= (4! + 9) \times C(4!,2) + 8! \\ 50379 &:= C(-5 + (0! + 3)!,7) - 9 \\ 50624 &:= -(5 \times 0)! + C(6,2)^4 \\ 53125 &:= -5 + C((3! - 1)^2,5) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1},3! - 0!) \\ 53135 &:= 5 + C(31 - 3!,5) \\ 53145 &:= 5 \times 3 + C(1 + 4!,5) \\ 53154 &:= C(5^{3-1},5) + 4! \\ 53625 &:= (-5 + 3!!) \times C(6,2) \times 5 \\ 54375 &:= (C(5,4) + 3!!) \times 75 \\ 56568 &:= 5! + (6^5 - 6!) \times 8 \\ 56951 &:= -5^6 + 9!/C(5,1) \\ 59169 &:= 5! + C(9,1)^6/9 \\ 59436 &:= (C((-5 + 9)!,4) - 3!!) \times 6 \\ 60396 &:= (6! - (0 \times 3)!) \times C(9,6) \\ 62496 &:= (6! + 24) \times C(9,6) \\ 63748 &:= 6 \times C((-3 + 7)!,4) - 8 \\ 63756 &:= 6 \times C((-3 + 7)!,5!/6) \\ 64468 &:= 6! + C(4!,4) \times 6 - 8 \\ 72576 &:= (7 + 2)!/C(5,7 - 6) \\ 72577 &:= (7 + 2)!/5 + C(7,7) \\ 73998 &:= 7! \times 3! + C(9 + 9,8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74256 &:= C(-7 + 4!, (-2 + 5)!) \times 6 \\74319 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 3 + 1) - 9) \\74376 &:= 7 \times C(4!, -3 + 7) - 6 \\74382 &:= 7 \times C(C(4, 3)!, 8/2) \\74403 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 03) \\74424 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 2 + 4) \\74431 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 3! + 1) \\74438 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, C(4, 3)) + 8) \\74445 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 4 + 5) \\74452 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + C(5, 2)) \\74466 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 6 + 6) \\74468 &:= 86 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74473 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 7 + 3!) \\74487 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 4) + 8 + 7) \\74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) \\75145 &:= 7^{5+1} - C(4!, 5) \\75333 &:= C(7 + 5 \times 3, 3!) + 3!! \\75525 &:= (7! - 5) \times (C(5, 2) + 5) \\75605 &:= (C(7, 5) \times 6! + 0!) \times 5 \\75645 &:= (7! - 5) \times C(6, 4) + 5! \\75675 &:= (7! + 5) \times C(6, 7 - 5) \\76327 &:= 7 + 6! + C(3!, 2) \times 7! \\77595 &:= 7! - C(7, 5) + 9!/5 \\80652 &:= (8! + C(06, 5)) \times 2 \\80664 &:= 8! \times (0! + C(6, 6)) + 4! \\80752 &:= (8! + C(0! + 7, 5)) \times 2 \\84078 &:= 8! + C(4! + 0! - 7, 8) \\84448 &:= (-C(8, 4) + C(4!, 4)) \times 8 \\84672 &:= 8!/(4 + 6) \times C(7, 2) \\86372 &:= -C(8, 6) + 3!! \times (7 - 2)! \\86976 &:= 8! + 6^{C(9, 7)/6} \\87355 &:= (C(8, 7) + 3!!) \times 5! - 5 \\88368 &:= C(8 + 8, 3!) \times 6 + 8! \\90594 &:= -C(9, 05) + 9!/4 \\90734 &:= (9! + C(0! + 7, 3))/4 \\92459 &:= 9^2 + C(4! - 5, 9) \\93321 &:= 9 + 3!^3 \times C(2, 1) \\95544 &:= 9 \times (-5 - 5 + C(4!, 4)) \\95634 &:= 9 \times C(5 \times 6 - 3!, 4) \\96957 &:= (9 + 6!) \times (C(9, 5) + 7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98334 &:= (9 \times 8^{3!} + 3!!)/4! \\100800 &:= 10!/C(0! + 8, 0! + 0!) \\100824 &:= 10!/C(0! + 8, 2) + 4! \\100946 &:= -1 + C(-(00 \times 9)! + 4!, 6) \\103596 &:= 10!/35 - C(9, 6) \\105987 &:= C(-1 + (-0! + 5)!, 9 + 8) + 7! \\113367 &:= (C(11, 3) - 3!) \times (6! - 7) \\113652 &:= C(11, 3!) \times (6 + 5! \times 2) \\114920 &:= (C(11, 4) + 9)^2 - 0! \\115367 &:= -1 + C((-1 + 5)!, 3!) \times 6/7 \\115794 &:= (-1 + (-1 + 5)!) \times 7! - C(9, 4) \\115833 &:= (1 + C(15, 8) \times 3!) \times 3 \\116273 &:= -1 + C(C(1 + 6, 2), 7) - 3! \\116280 &:= C(C(C(1, 1) + 6, 2), 8 - 0!) \\116424 &:= C(11, 6) \times (C(4!, 2) - 4!) \\116593 &:= 1 - C(16, 5) + 9!/3 \\117573 &:= -C(1, 1) - 75 + 7^3! \\118305 &:= C(11, 8) \times (-3 + (0! + 5)!) \\118363 &:= (-C(1, 1) + 8)^{3!} + 6! - 3! \\118369 &:= (-C(1, 1) + 8)^{3!} + (-6 + 9)!! \\118376 &:= (-C(1, 1) + 8)^{3!} + 7 + 6! \\118635 &:= C(11, 8) \times (6! - 3! + 5) \\118754 &:= -1 + C(1 \times 8 + C(7, 5), 4!) \\118800 &:= C(11, 8) \times (8 - 0! - 0!)! \\118824 &:= C(11, 8) \times (8 - 2)! + 4! \\119574 &:= -11 \times C(9, 5) + 7! \times 4! \\120768 &:= (1 + 2 + 0!)! \times (C(7, 6)! - 8) \\120942 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((-0! + 9)! - C(4, 2)) \\120987 &:= (1 + 2) \times (09 + C(8, 7)!) \\120988 &:= 1 + (2 + 0!) \times (C(9, 8) + 8!) \\122845 &:= (1 + 2)! \times C(28, 4) - 5 \\122850 &:= (1 + 2)! \times C(28, 5 - 0!) \\123201 &:= C((1 + 2)^3, 2)^{0!+1} \\124272 &:= 12 \times (C(4!, 2) + 7! \times 2) \\124326 &:= (12^4 - C(3!, 2)) \times 6 \\124398 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 4!^3) \times C(9, 8) \\125970 &:= C(1 + 2 \times 5 + 9, 7 + 0!) \\127440 &:= 12 \times (-7 + C(4!, 4) + 0!) \\127512 &:= C((-1 - 2 + 7)!, 5) \times (1 + 2)\end{aligned}$$

- 128836** := $-(1+2)!! \times 8 + C(8 \times 3, 6)$
129435 := $-1 - (-2+9)! + C(4!, 3!) - 5!$
129556 := $-1 \times (-2+9)! + C(5!/5, 6)$
129645 := $(1+2) \times (-9+6! + C(4!, 5))$
130276 := $C((1+3)!, (0!+2)!) - 7! + 6!$
130321 := $(1+3!!/(-0!+3))^{C(2,1)}$
132436 := $C((1+3)!, 2+4) - 3 \times 6!$
132480 := $C((1+3)!, 2) \times 480$
132698 := $C(1+C(3,2) \times 6, 9) + 8!$
133156 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - (1+5)! - 6!$
133444 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - (4!+4!) \times 4!$
133579 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) + (-5!+7) \times 9$
133636 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 6!/3 - 6!$
133684 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 6! - 8 \times 4!$
133734 := $(-1+3!!) \times 3! \times (C(7,3) - 4)$
133735 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 7 \times (3+5!)$
133753 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 7 \times 5! - 3$
133756 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 7! \times 5!/6!$
133798 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 798$
133848 := $C(13, 3!) \times (C(8,4) + 8)$
133863 := $-13 + C(3 \times 8, 6) - 3!!$
133864 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - 8 - 6! - 4$
133868 := $-1 \times 3!! + C(3 \times 8, 6) - 8$
133876 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) - (8-7) \times 6!$
133893 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) + 8 + 9 - 3!!$
133973 := $C((1+3)!, 3!) + 97 - 3!!$
134064 := $(C((1+3)!, 4) - (0!+6)!) \times 4!$
134106 := $(1+3!!) \times (-4! + C(10, 6))$
134246 := $1 - C(3+4!, 2) + C(4!, 6)$
134343 := $-(1+3)^4 + 3 + C(4!, 3!)$
134344 := $1 + 3 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^4$
134346 := $-(1+3)^4 + 3! + C(4!, 6)$
134352 := $-1 - 3 + C(4!, 3!) - 5! \times 2$
134353 := $-(-1+3!)! + C(4!, 3!) - 5! - 3$
134355 := $-1 + C(3! \times 4, 3!) - 5! - 5!$
134363 := $1 + 3! + C(4!, 3!) - 6!/3$
134373 := $(-1+3!)! + C(4!, 3!) - 7^3$
134386 := $-(1+3)!/4! + C(3 \times 8, 6)$
134388 := $-(-1+3!)! + C(4!, 3!) - 88$
134415 := $-1 - 3!!/4 + C(4!, 1+5)$
134416 := $(-1 \times 3!!)/4 + C(4!, 1 \times 6)$
134417 := $1 - 3!!/4 + C(4!, -1+7)$
134428 := $-(1+3!) \times 4! + C(4!, -2+8)$
134451 := $-1 - 3! \times 4! + C(4!, 5+1)$
134452 := $-1 \times 3! \times 4! + C(4!, (5-2)!)$
134461 := $-134 + C(4!, 6) - 1$
134462 := $-134 + C(4!, (6/2)!)$
134465 := $1 - 3 \times 4 + C(4!, 6) - 5!$
134466 := $-(-1+3!)! - 4 + C(4!, 6) - 6$
134468 := $(1-3!) \times 4! + C(4!, 6) - 8$
134473 := $-(-1+3!)! + C(4!, (-4+7)!) - 3$
134475 := $-1 + C(3! \times 4, (-4+7)!) - 5!$
134476 := $-(-1+3!)! + C(4!, (-4+7) \times 6)$
134498 := $C((1+3)!, 4!/4) - 98$
134516 := $1 - 3^4 + C((5-1)!, 6)$
134543 := $(1-3) \times 4! - 5 + C(4!, 3!)$
134546 := $1 - 3! - 45 + C(4!, 6)$
134549 := $-1 + C(3! + 4 \times 5, 4) \times 9$
134572 := $-(1+3)! + C(4!, (5+7)/2)$
134583 := $-13 + C(4!, -5+8+3)$
134585 := $-1 \times 3! + C(4!, (-5+8)!) - 5$
134586 := $-1 - 3 + C(4!, (-5+8)!) - 6$
134587 := $1 - 3 + C(4!, (-5+8)!) - 7$
134588 := $C((1+3)!, (4!+5!)/8) - 8$
134589 := $-1 - 3! + C(4!, 5-8+9)$
134590 := $-1 \times 3! + C(4!, 5+(9 \times 0)!)$
134591 := $1 - 3! + C(4!, (-5+9-1)!)$
134592 := $-1 - 3 + C(4!, -5+9+2)$
134593 := $C((1+3)!, 4+5+9) - 3$
134594 := $1 - 3 + C(4!, 5+9+4)$
134595 := $-1 + C(3! \times 4, -5! + C(9, 5))$
134597 := $1 + C(3! \times 4, (5-9+7)!)$
134598 := $-1 + 3 + C(4!, 5+9-8)$
134599 := $1 \times 3 + C(4!, 5+C(9, 9))$
134708 := $(-1+3!)! + C(4!, 7-0!) - 8$
134713 := $(-1+3!)! + C(4!, 7-1) - 3$
134715 := $-1 + C(3! \times 4, 7-1) + 5!$
134716 := $(-1+3!)! + C(4 \times (7-1), 6)$
134743 := $(-1 \times 3+4!) \times 7 + C(4!, 3!)$
134746 := $-1 + 3! \times 4! + 7 + C(4!, 6)$

$$\begin{aligned} 134946 &:= 1 + 349 + C(4!, 6) \\ 135316 &:= C((1 + 3)!, (5 - 3 + 1)!) + 6! \\ 135346 &:= 1 \times 3! \times 5^3 + C(4!, 6) \\ 135433 &:= (1 + 3!) \times 5! + C(4!, 3!) - 3 \\ 135435 &:= -1 + 3! \times 5! + C(4!, 3!) + 5! \\ 135436 &:= 13 \times 5! + C(4!, 3!) - 6! \\ 135655 &:= C((1 + 3)! - 5, 6) \times 5 - 5 \\ 135660 &:= C((1 + 3)! - 5, 6) \times (6 - 0!) \\ 135665 &:= (1 + C((-3! + 5!)/6, 6)) \times 5 \\ 136036 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 6) + (-0! + 3) \times 6! \\ 136269 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times (C(6, 2) + 6) \times 9 \\ 136276 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 6) + 2 \times 7!/6 \\ 136516 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 6) + 5! \times 16 \\ 136763 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 6) + 7 + 6! \times 3 \\ 136836 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 6) + 8!/(3 \times 6) \\ 138034 &:= 13 \times (-8 + C((0! + 3)!, 4)) \\ 138216 &:= (-1 + 3!! \times 8) \times (-C(2, 1) + 6)! \\ 138431 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times 8 \times C(4, 3)! - 1 \\ 138433 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times 8 \times 4! + C(3, 3) \\ 139535 &:= -1^3 + 9 \times C(5!/3!, 5) \\ 140361 &:= (1 + C(4! + 0!, 3)) \times 61 \\ 141268 &:= 1 + C(4! - 1^2, 6) + 8! \\ 142272 &:= (C(1 \times 4!, 2)^2 - 7!) \times 2 \\ 143236 &:= C(1 \times 4!, 3!) + 2 \times 3! \times 6! \\ 143237 &:= 1 + C(4!, 3!) - 2 \times (3!! - 7!) \\ 143423 &:= -1 + 4! \times (3!! + C(4!, 2)) \times 3! \\ 143424 &:= (-1 + 4)! \times (3!! + C(4!, 2)) \times 4! \\ 143448 &:= 1 \times 4! \times C(-3 + 4!, 4) - 8 \\ 143450 &:= C(-1 + 4!, 3!) + C(4!, 5) - 0! \\ 143451 &:= C(-1 + 4!, 3!) + C(4!, C(5, 1)) \\ 143548 &:= (1 + C(4!, 3 + 5))/4 - 8! \\ 143775 &:= (1 + C(4!, 3)) \times (-7 \times 7 + 5!) \\ 143875 &:= (1 + C(4, 3)!) \times (8!/7 - 5) \\ 144143 &:= -1 + (4! + 4!) \times C(14, 3!) \\ 144672 &:= -1 \times 4 + C(4!, 6) + 7! \times 2 \\ 144677 &:= 1^4 + C(4!, 6) + 7! + 7! \\ 144865 &:= (-1 - C(4!, 4) + 8! - 6!) \times 5 \\ 145704 &:= (C(1 \times 4!, 5)/7 - 0!) \times 4! \\ 145746 &:= (1 + C(4!, 5)/7) \times 4! - 6 \\ 147094 &:= (-1 + C(4!, 7 + 0!))/(9 - 4) \\ 147095 &:= -1 + (C(4!, 7 + 0!) + 9)/5 \\ 147246 &:= C(1 + 4!, C(7, 2)) + C(4!, 6) \\ 147885 &:= (-1 + 4!) \times C(7 + 8, 8) - 5! \\ 148396 &:= (-1 + 4!) \times (-C(8, 3!) + 9 \times 6!) \\ 148445 &:= (-1 - 4 + 8! - C(4!, 4)) \times 5 \\ 148644 &:= -(1 + 4)! + (8 + 6) \times C(4!, 4) \\ 149743 &:= (-1 + 4) \times (9 + 7!) + C(4!, 3!) \\ 150359 &:= -1 - 5 \times C((0! + 3)!, 5) + 9! \\ 151194 &:= -1 + (-5! + (C(1, 1) + 9)!)/4! \\ 151230 &:= ((1 + ((C(5, 1) + 2)))! \times 30) \\ 151584 &:= (1 - 5! + C(15, 8)) \times 4! \\ 152352 &:= C((-1 + 5)!, 2)^{-3+5} \times 2 \\ 153184 &:= (-C((-1 + 5)!, 3) \times 1 + 8!) \times 4 \\ 153496 &:= -C((-1 + 5)!, 3) + 4! \times 9 \times 6! \\ 154344 &:= (C(15, 4 + 3) - 4) \times 4! \\ 154564 &:= (1 - 5! + C(4 \times 5, 6)) \times 4 \\ 154575 &:= C(1 + 5, 4)^5 - 7! \times 5! \\ 154944 &:= ((1 + C(5, 4))! \times 9 - 4!) \times 4! \\ 158391 &:= (-1 + 5) \times (8! - 3!!) - C(9, 1) \\ 158399 &:= (-1 + 5) \times (8! - 3!!) - C(9, 9) \\ 159389 &:= -1 - C((-5 + 9)! - 3, 8) + 9! \\ 159390 &:= C(-1 + (-5 + 9)!, 3) \times 90 \\ 159745 &:= 1 + (5! + C(9, 7)) \times 4^5 \\ 160473 &:= (-1 + 6! + C(0! + 4!, 7))/3 \\ 161275 &:= C(16, 1) \times 2 \times 7! - 5 \\ 161282 &:= (1 + (C(6, 1) + 2)! + 8!) \times 2 \\ 161284 &:= (1 + (C(6, 1) + 2)!) \times (8 - 4) \\ 163295 &:= -1 + (6 \times 3!)^2 \times C(9, 5) \\ 163639 &:= -1 - 6! \times 3! + C(C(6, 3), 9) \\ 163943 &:= -1 + (6 + 3) \times 9 \times C(4!, 3) \\ 164158 &:= 1 \times 6! + C(4!, 15)/8 \\ 164645 &:= (-1 \times 6! + C(4!, 6)/4) \times 5 \\ 164736 &:= ((-1 + 6)! - 4!) \times C(7 + 3!, 6) \\ 165648 &:= C(16, 5 + 6) + 4 \times 8! \\ 167239 &:= -1 - 6! + C(7 \times 2 + 3!, 9) \\ 168483 &:= (1 + 6! \times (C(8, 4) + 8)) \times 3 \\ 169323 &:= (1 + 6) \times (9!/C(3!, 2) - 3) \\ 169342 &:= (1 + 6) \times 9!/C(3!, 4) - 2 \\ 169344 &:= ((1 + 6)! + C(9, 3) \times 4!) \times 4! \\ 170169 &:= -1 + 7 \times C(0! + 16, 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 170178 &:= 1 + 7 \times (0! + C(17, 8)) \\
 170527 &:= -17 + C((-0! + 5)! - 2, 7) \\
 171292 &:= (-1 + 7! - 1) \times (-2 + C(9, 2)) \\
 171361 &:= (C(1 + 6, 3) - 1) \times 7! + 1 \\
 172999 &:= -1 + 7! + C(2 + 9 + 9, 9) \\
 173472 &:= (1 \times 7!/3! + C(4!, 7))/2 \\
 173772 &:= (-1 + 7)! + C((-3 + 7)!, 7)/2 \\
 173775 &:= C(1 \times 7, 3) \times (7! - 75) \\
 173844 &:= (1 - 7) \times (3!! - 8! + C(4!, 4)) \\
 174384 &:= (C(1 \times 7 \times 4, 3) + 8!) \times 4 \\
 174843 &:= 1 - 74 + 8! + C(4!, 3!) \\
 174846 &:= -C(1 + 7, 4) + 8! + C(4!, 6) \\
 174916 &:= (1 + 7)! + C(4!, (C(9, 1) - 6)!) \\
 175036 &:= (1 + 7)! + 5! + C((0! + 3)!, 6) \\
 175572 &:= (1 \times 7! + C(5!/5, 7))/2 \\
 175874 &:= -1 + (7! - 5!/8) \times C(7, 4) \\
 176064 &:= (C(17, 6) - (0! + 6)!) \times 4! \\
 176336 &:= C(1 + 7, 6 - 3)^3 + 6! \\
 176358 &:= C(17, 6) \times (-3! + 5!)/8 \\
 176399 &:= -1 + 7! \times (6 \times 3! - C(9, 9)) \\
 176475 &:= ((1 + 7)! + C(6, 4) - 7!) \times 5 \\
 176574 &:= (-1 + C(7, 6)!) + 5 \times C(7, 4) \\
 176575 &:= (-1 + 7! + C(6, 5)) \times 7 \times 5 \\
 176904 &:= C(1 + 7, 6)! \times 9/(0! + 4)! \\
 179143 &:= -1 - 7! + 91 \times C(4!, 3) \\
 179375 &:= (1 + 7! + C(9, 3)) \times 7 \times 5 \\
 179946 &:= -1 + 7! \times 9 - 9 + C(4!, 6) \\
 179956 &:= 1 \times 7! \times 9 + C((9 - 5)!, 6) \\
 180792 &:= (-18 + (07)!) \times C(9, 2) \\
 181692 &:= (-1 + 8 + (1 + 6)!) \times C(9, 2) \\
 182161 &:= (1 + 8)!/2 + 1 + C(6, 1)! \\
 182304 &:= C(1 + 8, 2) \times ((3! + 0!)! + 4!) \\
 182376 &:= C(1 + 8, 2) \times (3! + 7!) + 6! \\
 182439 &:= (-1 + C(8, 2) \times (4 + 3!!)) \times 9 \\
 182592 &:= ((-1 + 8)! + 2^5) \times C(9, 2) \\
 182736 &:= (C(1 + 8, 2) + 7!) \times 36 \\
 183699 &:= (-1 + C(8, 3!) \times (6! + 9)) \times 9 \\
 183844 &:= (1 + C(8 \times 3, 8))/4 - 4! \\
 184323 &:= (1 + 8^4 \times C(3!, 2)) \times 3 \\
 184446 &:= C(1 + 8, 4) + 4^4 \times 6! \\
 185313 &:= (1 + C(8, 5))^3 + (-1 + 3)! \\
 186179 &:= -1 + 8! + 6 \times C(17, 9) \\
 186585 &:= (-C(1 + 8 + 6, 5) + 8!) \times 5 \\
 188362 &:= -1 \times 8 + C(C(8, 3!), 6)/2 \\
 188383 &:= -1 + (8 + 8!/3!) \times C(8, 3!) \\
 189437 &:= C(18, 9) \times 4 - 3 - 7! \\
 192337 &:= 1 + 9! - C(2 + C(3!, 3), 7) \\
 192384 &:= (C((-1 + 9) \times 2, 3!) + 8) \times 4! \\
 194344 &:= (1 + 9 + C(4!, 3) \times 4!) \times 4 \\
 195853 &:= 1 - (C(9, 5) - 8^5) \times 3! \\
 196512 &:= (1 - 9 + 6!) \times C((5 - 1)!, 2) \\
 200875 &:= -(2 + 0)!! + (-0! + C(8, 7)!) \times 5 \\
 201605 &:= ((C(2, 01) + 6)! + 0!) \times 5 \\
 203332 &:= (C(23, 3!) + 3!! - 0!) \times 2 \\
 203470 &:= -20 + C(-3 + 4!, 7 + 0!) \\
 203482 &:= -(2 + 0)!! + C(-3 + 4!, 8) - 2 \\
 203483 &:= (-2 + 0!) + C(-3 + 4!, 8) - 3! \\
 203484 &:= -2 + C(-03 + 4!, 8) - 4 \\
 203486 &:= 2 + C(-03 + 4!, 8) - 6 \\
 203487 &:= -2 - 0! + C(-3 + 4!, C(8, 7)) \\
 203488 &:= -2 + C(0! + 3 \times 4 + 8, 8) \\
 203490 &:= C(20 - 3 + 4, 9 - 0!) \\
 203491 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(-3 + 4!, 9 - 1) \\
 204838 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(4!, 8)/3 - 8! \\
 205342 &:= -2 + ((-0! + 5)! + 3!!) \times C(4!, 2) \\
 205342 &:= -2 + (4! + 3!!) \times C((5 - 0)!, 2) \\
 211600 &:= (-2 + C(11, 6))^{0!+0!} \\
 211624 &:= (-2 + C(11, 6))^2 + 4! \\
 212545 &:= (2 + 1 + 2) \times (5 + C(4!, 5)) \\
 213456 &:= C(21, 3!) \times 4 - 5 \times 6! \\
 215586 &:= -C(-2 + (-1 + 5)!, 5) + 8! \times 6 \\
 216456 &:= C(21, 6) \times 4 + 5! - 6! \\
 217048 &:= C(21, 7 - 0!) \times 4 - 8 \\
 218805 &:= (2 + C(18, 8) + 0!) \times 5 \\
 223833 &:= (C(22, 3!) - 8 + 3!) \times 3 \\
 223863 &:= (C(22, 3!) + 8) \times (6 - 3) \\
 226805 &:= ((C(2, 2) + 6)! + 8! + 0!) \times 5 \\
 227386 &:= C(22, 7)/3! \times 8 - 6 \\
 227392 &:= C(22, 7) \times 3!/9 \times 2 \\
 230228 &:= -2 + C((3 + 0)!) + 2, -2 + 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 230243 &:= 2 \times 3! + 0! + C(2 + 4!, 3!) \\ 230246 &:= 2^{3+0!} + C(2 + 4!, 6) \\ 230253 &:= 23 + C(0! + 25, 3!) \\ 230254 &:= C(2 + (3 + 0!)!, (-2 + 5)!) + 4! \\ 230732 &:= 2 \times (C((3 + 0!)!, 7)/3 - 2) \\ 230733 &:= 2 \times C((3 + 0!)!, 7)/3 - 3 \\ 230734 &:= -2 + C((3 + 0!)!, 7)/3! \times 4 \\ 230736 &:= 2 \times C((3 + 0!)!, 7)/(-3 + 6) \\ 232546 &:= -2 + 3! \times (-2 + C(5 \times 4, 6)) \\ 232632 &:= (-2 + 3!!) \times (C(6, 2) + 3)^2 \\ 233292 &:= 2 \times 3! + 3!! \times (2 \times 9)^2 \\ 233298 &:= (2 + 3!! \times 3!^2) \times C(9, 8) \\ 233345 &:= (-2 + 3!^{3!} + C(3!, 4)) \times 5 \\ 233355 &:= C(23 + 3, 3!) + 5^5 \\ 233376 &:= 2 \times C(C(3!, 3) - 3, 7) \times 6 \\ 233856 &:= (-(-2 + 3!)! + 3!!) \times C(8, 5) \times 6 \\ 233892 &:= (-2^{3!} + 3^8) \times C(9, 2) \\ 234002 &:= 2 + 3!! \times C(4! + 0! + 0!, 2) \\ 234632 &:= (-(-2 + 3!)! \times 6! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2 \\ 235508 &:= (C(23, 5) - 5) \times (-0! + 8) \\ 236544 &:= C(2 \times 3!, C(6, 5)) \times 4^4 \\ 236796 &:= (2^3)! \times 6 - 7! - C(9, 6) \\ 236876 &:= 2 - 3! + 6 \times 8! - C(7, 6)! \\ 237216 &:= (-2 + 3!) \times (7! + C(21, 6)) \\ 237430 &:= -2 + 3!^7 - C(4!, 3! - 0!) \\ 237432 &:= (2 \times 3)^7 - C(4!, 3 + 2) \\ 237454 &:= -2 + 3!^7 - C(4!, 5) + 4! \\ 237597 &:= C(23, 7) - 5! \times 9 \times 7 \\ 237636 &:= (C(2^3, 7)! - 6! + 3!) \times 6 \\ 237642 &:= ((2^3)! + 7 - 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 238896 &:= (-C(2 \times 3!, 8) + 8! - 9) \times 6 \\ 239976 &:= ((2^3)! - 9 \times C(9, 7)) \times 6 \\ 239978 &:= 2 + 3! \times (-9 \times C(9, 7) + 8!) \\ 241344 &:= (2 \times (C(4, 1) + 3)! - 4!) \times 4! \\ 241368 &:= -2 \times C(4!, -1 + 3) + 6 \times 8! \\ 241794 &:= (2 \times 4)! \times (-1 + 7) - C(9, 4) \\ 241926 &:= ((2 \times 4)! + 1) \times C(9, 2)/6 \\ 241982 &:= -2 + C(4, 1)^9 - 8!/2 \\ 242382 &:= (C(-2 + 4!, 2) + 3 \times 8!) \times 2 \\ 242398 &:= -2 + C(4, 2) \times (3!!/9 + 8!) \\ 242468 &:= 2 \times C(4!, 2) - 4 + 6 \times 8! \\ 242470 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 2) + 4! \times 7! - 0!) \\ 242471 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 2) + 4! \times 7!) - 1 \\ 242472 &:= 2 \times C(4!, 2) + 4! \times 7! \times 2 \\ 242586 &:= (C(-2 + 4!, 2) - 5! + 8!) \times 6 \\ 242638 &:= -2 + C(4, 2)! + (6 - 3)! \times 8! \\ 242642 &:= (2 \times 4)! \times 6 + 2 + C(4, 2)! \\ 242642 &:= 2 + (4 \times 2)! \times 6 + C(4, 2)! \\ 242668 &:= C(2 \times 4, 2) + 6! + 6 \times 8! \\ 243120 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times 120 \\ 243144 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times (1 + 4)! + 4! \\ 243355 &:= (-2 + C(4!, 3) + 3!) \times 5! - 5 \\ 243363 &:= (2 \times 4)! \times 3! + 3!! + 6! + 3 \\ 243593 &:= 2 + C(4!, 3) \times 5! - 9 + 3!! \\ 243788 &:= 2 - 4! + C(3 \times 7, 8) + 8! \\ 243792 &:= 2 \times 4! \times (3 + 7! + C(9, 2)) \\ 243808 &:= -2 + C(4! - 3, 8) + (08)! \\ 243838 &:= -2 + (C(4!, 3) + 8) \times (-3 + 8)! \\ 243840 &:= (C(24, 3) + 8) \times (4 + 0)! \\ 243946 &:= 2 + C(4!, 3) + 9! \times 4/6 \\ 243954 &:= -2 + (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 5! - 4 \\ 243955 &:= (C(24, 3) + 9) \times 5! - 5 \\ 243956 &:= 2 + (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 5! - 6 \\ 243960 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 60 \\ 244398 &:= C(24, 4) \times (3! + 9 + 8) \\ 244414 &:= 2^4 + C(4!, 4) \times (-1 + 4!) \\ 244437 &:= -(2 + 4)! + C(4! - 4 + 3, 7) \\ 244444 &:= (2 + C(4!, 4)) \times (-C(4, 4) + 4!) \\ 244944 &:= ((2 \times 4)!/4 + C(9, 4)) \times 4! \\ 245047 &:= (2 - 4!) \times 5 + C(-0! + 4!, 7) \\ 245147 &:= (2 - 4) \times 5 + C(-1 + 4!, 7) \\ 245183 &:= 2 + 4! + C((5 - 1)!, 8)/3 \\ 246192 &:= 2 \times (-4! + 6! \times C(19, 2)) \\ 246242 &:= ((2 \times 4)! + 6!) \times (2 + 4) + 2 \\ 246242 &:= 2 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 247520 &:= 2 \times C(4! - 7, 5) \times 20 \\ 247562 &:= 2 + (4^7 + 5!) \times C(6, 2) \\ 247596 &:= 2 \times 4! \times (7! + 5!) - C(9, 6) \\ 247648 &:= ((2 + 4) \times 7! + 6! - 4) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 247673 &:= (2 + 4)! - 7 + 6! \times 7^3 \\ 247873 &:= C(-2 + 4!, 7) - 8! + 7^{3!} \\ 247944 &:= 2 \times 4! \times (7! + C(9, 4)) - 4! \\ 247959 &:= 2 \times 4! \times (7! + C(9, 5)) - 9 \\ 249489 &:= (-2 + 4!) \times 9! / (4 \times 8) + 9 \\ 251942 &:= 2 + 5 \times C(19, 4! / 2) \\ 252750 &:= (C((-2 + 5)!, 2) + 7!) \times 50 \\ 253428 &:= 2 \times (5! \times 3!! - C(4, 2) + 8!) \\ 253952 &:= 2^{5+3!} \times (C(9, 5) - 2) \\ 254304 &:= -(-2 + 5)!! + C(4!, 3 + 0!) \times 4! \\ 254306 &:= 2 + (-5! + C(4!, 3! - 0!)) \times 6 \\ 254316 &:= 2 - 5! + C(4!, 3! - 1) \times 6 \\ 254336 &:= 2^5 + 4!! / C(3!, 3)! - 6! \\ 254424 &:= (-25 + C(4!, 4)) \times 24 \\ 254448 &:= (-2 + 5) \times (C(4!, 4) - 4!) \times 8 \\ 255036 &:= (2 + C(5! / 5, -0! + 3!)) \times 6 \\ 255056 &:= 2^5 + C((5 - 0!)!, 5) \times 6 \\ 255685 &:= C(2^5 - 5, 6) - 8! - 5 \\ 255690 &:= C(2^5 - 5, 6) - (9 - 0!)! \\ 255744 &:= (-2 + 5)!! / 5 \times 74 \times 4! \\ 256932 &:= (2 + 5!) \times 6 \times C(9 \times 3, 2) \\ 258975 &:= (-C(2 \times 5, 8) + 9! / 7) \times 5 \\ 259578 &:= (-2 + 5)! \times C((9 - 5)!, 7) / 8 \\ 262088 &:= (2^{C(6, 2)} + 0! - 8) \times 8 \\ 262469 &:= C(26, 2) + (4! / 6)^9 \\ 262836 &:= -C(2 + 6, 2) + 8^{3!} + 6! \\ 263144 &:= C(26, 3! - 1) \times 4 + 4! \\ 263432 &:= -(2 + 6) \times 3!! + C(4!, 3!) \times 2 \\ 263678 &:= 2 - C(6 \times 3, 6) + 7 \times 8! \\ 264595 &:= -C(-2 + 6 + 4!, 5) + 9! - 5 \\ 264832 &:= 2^{-6+4!} + 8! / C(3!, 2) \\ 264862 &:= -2 + (6! - 8) \times (4! + 6!) / 2 \\ 265424 &:= (C(26, 5) + 4!^2) \times 4 \\ 265964 &:= (C(26, 5) - 9 + 6!) \times 4 \\ 267842 &:= 2 - (6! - 7! - 8!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 267862 &:= (2 + 6!) \times (-7 + C(C(8, 6), 2)) \\ 268462 &:= -2 - 6! - 8 + C(4!, 6) \times 2 \\ 268562 &:= 2 - 6! \times (5 - C(C(8, 6), 2)) \\ 268798 &:= -2 + 6 \times (C(8, 7)! / 9 + 8!) \\ 269192 &:= C((-2 + 6)!, C(9, 1) + 9) \times 2 \\ 269246 &:= 2 \times (6 \times 9 / 2 + C(4!, 6)) \\ 269346 &:= 2 \times (6! / 9 - 3 + C(4!, 6)) \\ 269432 &:= ((2 - 6 + 9)! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2 \\ 270632 &:= (C((-2 + 7 - 0!)!, 6) + 3!!) \times 2 \\ 270646 &:= 2 \times ((7 + (06)!) + C(4!, 6)) \\ 273714 &:= ((-2 + 7)! - 3!) \times C(7, 1)^4 \\ 274945 &:= C(27, 4!) \times 94 - 5 \\ 274950 &:= C(27, 4!) \times (95 - 0!) \\ 275238 &:= -2 + 7 \times (-C(5, 2)^3 + 8!) \\ 276396 &:= 2^7 \times 6! \times 3 - C(9, 6) \\ 276465 &:= (2 + 7)! - C(6, 4) + 6! \times 5! \\ 276473 &:= 2 \times (7! + 6!) \times 4! - C(7, 3!) \\ 276498 &:= 2 \times ((7! + 6!) \times 4! + C(9, 8)) \\ 277338 &:= -2 - 7! + 7 \times (C(3!, 3) + 8!) \\ 278676 &:= -2 \times 7! / 8 + 6^{C(7, 6)} \\ 279747 &:= 27 \times (9! / C(7, 4) - 7) \\ 279927 &:= -2 - 7 + (C(9, 9) + 2)!^7 \\ 280657 &:= (-2 + 8)! + 0! + C(6, 5)^7 \\ 281372 &:= (2 \times 7! - 31) \times C(8, 2) \\ 281857 &:= 2 + (8! + 1 - C(8, 5)) \times 7 \\ 281927 &:= 2 + (8! - C(1 + 9, 2)) \times 7 \\ 282198 &:= -2 \times (8! + 21) + C(9, 8)! \\ 282226 &:= (-2 + 8!) \times (-C(2, 2) + 2 + 6) \\ 282228 &:= (-2 + 8!) \times C(2 + 2, 2) + 8! \\ 282231 &:= -2 + (8! - C(2, 2)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 282238 &:= -2 - 8! \times (C(2, 2)^3 - 8) \\ 282239 &:= -2 \times 8! - C(2, 2)^3 + 9! \\ 282242 &:= 2 - 8! \times (C(2, 2) - 4 \times 2) \\ 282247 &:= (2 + 8! - C(2, 2)^4) \times 7 \\ 282256 &:= 2 + (8! + 2) \times C(2 + 5, 6) \\ 282261 &:= (2 + 8! + C(2, 2)) \times (6 + 1) \\ 282287 &:= -2 + (8 - C(2, 2) + 8!) \times 7 \\ 282347 &:= 2 + (8! + C(2 \times 3, 4)) \times 7 \\ 282476 &:= 2 \times (C(8, 2) \times (4 + 7!) + 6) \\ 282576 &:= C(2 \times 8 / 2, 5) \times (7! + 6) \\ 282618 &:= C(28, 2) + (6 + 1) \times 8! \\ 282624 &:= 2^8 \times C((-2 + 6)!, 2) \times 4 \\ 283448 &:= -C(2 \times 8, 3!) + 4!^4 - 8! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 283472 &:= 2 \times C(8, 3!) \times (4! + 7! - 2) \\
 283698 &:= 2 \times (-8! + 3^6) + C(9, 8)! \\
 287850 &:= (2 + 8 + 7!) \times (C(8, 5) + 0!) \\
 291438 &:= 2 \times 9 \times (-1 + C(4!, 3) \times 8) \\
 292310 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! - 10 \\
 292313 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! - 1 - 3! \\
 292314 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! - (-1 + 4)! \\
 292315 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! - 1 \times 5 \\
 292319 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! - 1^9 \\
 292332 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! + 3! \times 2 \\
 292335 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! + 3 \times 5 \\
 292342 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! + 4! - 2 \\
 292368 &:= C(29, 2) \times 3!! + 6 \times 8 \\
 293132 &:= C(29, 3 - 1) \times (3!! + 2) \\
 293328 &:= (-C(29, 3) + (3! + 2)!) \times 8 \\
 293418 &:= -2^9 + C(-3 + 4!, 1 + 8) \\
 293942 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 4!/2 \\
 293947 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 4! - 7 \\
 293959 &:= 29 + C(-3 + (9 - 5)!, 9) \\
 293986 &:= C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 8!/6! \\
 294407 &:= 2^9 \times (4! \times 4! - 0!) + 7 \\
 294911 &:= 2^{-9+4!} \times 9 - C(1, 1) \\
 294996 &:= 2^{-9+4!} \times 9 + C(9, 6) \\
 295335 &:= (-2 + 9^5 + C(3!, 3)) \times 5 \\
 295462 &:= (2 \times (9! - 5!) - C(4!, 6))/2 \\
 296342 &:= 2 + (C(9, 6)^3 - 4!)/2 \\
 297024 &:= C(2 \times 9, 7 - 0!) \times 2^4 \\
 297329 &:= -2^{9+7} - C(3!, 2) + 9! \\
 297537 &:= (2 - 9 \times 7 + 5!) \times (3 + 7!) \\
 297545 &:= -2 \times 9 + 7 \times (5 + C(4!, 5)) \\
 297577 &:= (C((2 + 9 - 7)!, 5) + 7) \times 7 \\
 298970 &:= C(29 - 8, 9) + (7 + 0)! \\
 302400 &:= C(3! - 0!, 2)! / (4! / (0! + 0!)) \\
 302424 &:= C(3! - 0!, 2)! / (4!/2) + 4! \\
 302526 &:= C(3! + 0!, 2) \times (5!^2 + 6) \\
 302868 &:= C(3! \times (0! + 2), 8) \times 6 + 8! \\
 303744 &:= (3! + C(0! + (-3 + 7)!, 4)) \times 4! \\
 303840 &:= 3!! \times (0! + 3! \times C(8, 4) + 0!) \\
 304224 &:= (- (3! - 0!)! + C(4!, 2)^2) \times 4 \\
 304464 &:= 3!! + (C(0! + 4!, 4) + 6) \times 4! \\
 304644 &:= -C(-3! + 0! + 4!, 6) + 4!^4 \\
 305778 &:= -3! + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - 7! \times 8 \\
 305780 &:= -3 + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - 8! - 0! \\
 305781 &:= -3 + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - C(8, 1)! \\
 305782 &:= C((3 + (0 \times 5)!)!, 7) - 8! - 2 \\
 305785 &:= 3! + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - 8! - 5 \\
 305787 &:= 3 + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - C(8, 7)! \\
 305790 &:= 3! + C((-0! + 5)!, 7) - (9 - 0)! \\
 306348 &:= (3! + 0!) \times (6 + C(-3! + 4!, 8)) \\
 307224 &:= 3! \times (-0! + 7 \times C(22, 4)) \\
 312249 &:= -3! - C((1 + 2)!, 2)^4 + 9! \\
 317517 &:= 3 \times (-1 + C(7, 5) \times 1 \times 7!) \\
 320485 &:= 3!! + C(-2 + (04)!, 8) - 5 \\
 320490 &:= 3!! + C(-2 + (04)!, 9 - 0!) \\
 321648 &:= -3!! + ((C(2, 1) + 6)! - 4!) \times 8 \\
 321750 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 1 \times 7) \times 50 \\
 321896 &:= (3! + 2) \times (1 + 8! - C(9, 6)) \\
 322284 &:= -C((3! - 2)!, 2) + 2 \times 8! \times 4 \\
 322476 &:= (3!! - 22) \times C(4 + 7, 6) \\
 322557 &:= -3 + 2^{(2+C(5,5))!} \times 7! \\
 322559 &:= -(3 \times 2 + 2)! - C(5, 5) + 9! \\
 322648 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)! - 4) \times 8 \\
 322695 &:= C(3!, 2) - (2 + 6)! + 9! + 5! \\
 322728 &:= ((3 \times 2 + 2)! + C(7, 2)) \times 8 \\
 322836 &:= C((3! - 2)!, 2) - 8! + (3 + 6)! \\
 322839 &:= C((3! - 2)!, 2) - 8! + 3 + 9! \\
 322896 &:= (3! - 2) \times (2 \times 8! + C(9, 6)) \\
 323289 &:= C(3, 2)^{3 \times 2} - 8! + 9! \\
 323960 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 3) \times (-9 + 6! + 0!) \\
 324807 &:= -3 + C(-2 + 4!, 8) + (07)! \\
 324813 &:= 3 + C(-2 + 4!, 8) + (1 + 3)! \\
 324816 &:= 3! + C(-2 + 4!, 8) + (1 + 6)! \\
 324817 &:= 3! + C(-2 + 4!, 8) + 1 + 7! \\
 324885 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 4) + 8 \times (8! + 5!) \\
 325344 &:= (3!! + 2 \times (5 + 3)! - 4!) \times 4 \\
 325584 &:= C(3 \times (2 + 5), 5) \times (-8 + 4!) \\
 326487 &:= (-C(3!, 2) + 6^{4!/8})! \times 7 \\
 326607 &:= C(3!, 2) + 6^6 \times 07 \\
 326613 &:= (C(3, 2) + 6^6) \times (1 + 3!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 326637 &:= C(3,2) + (6^6 + 3!) \times 7 \\ 326676 &:= (3! \times 2 + 6^6) \times C(7,6) \\ 326693 &:= 3 + (-2 + 6!) \times C(6+9,3) \\ 326856 &:= (C((3! - 2)!, 6 + 8) - 5!)/6 \\ 326876 &:= C((3! - 2)!, 6 + C(8,7))/6 \\ 326943 &:= (C(3,2) + 6)! - (9 + 4!)^3 \\ 326952 &:= (3^2)! + (6! - 9!/5)/2 \\ 327585 &:= (-C(3,2) + 7! \times (5 + 8)) \times 5 \\ 327598 &:= C(3,2) + 7! - 5 + 9! - 8! \\ 327632 &:= 32 + 7! \times (63 + 2) \\ 327665 &:= (3 - 2 + C(7,6)!) \times 65 \\ 327675 &:= (C(3!,2) + 7! \times (6 + 7)) \times 5 \\ 327705 &:= C(3!,2) \times (7! + 7^{05}) \\ 328317 &:= -C(3,2) + (8! + 3!!) \times (1 + 7) \\ 328335 &:= C(3!,2) + (8! + 3!!) \times (3 + 5) \\ 328350 &:= (C(3,2)^8 + 3!) \times 50 \\ 328368 &:= (-C(3,2) + 8! + 3^6) \times 8 \\ 328376 &:= (3! + 2) \times (8! + 3!! + C(7,6)) \\ 328383 &:= C(3!,2) + 8 \times (3! + 8! + 3!!) \\ 328384 &:= 3!! + (2 + 8! + 3) \times 8 + 4! \\ 328389 &:= -C(3,2) + 8 \times (3!! + 8! + 9) \\ 328832 &:= (3! + 2) \times (8! + C(8,3!)^2) \\ 329231 &:= 3! \times (2 + C(9,2))^3 - 1 \\ 329235 &:= 3! - 2 + 9! - C(23,5) \\ 329562 &:= (-3 + C(2 + 9,5)) \times (6! - 2) \\ 331134 &:= (3 + 3!!) \times (C(11,3!) - 4) \\ 331923 &:= 3 + 3!! \times (-1 + C(9 + 2,3!)) \\ 331926 &:= 3! + 3!! \times (-1 + C(9 + 2,6)) \\ 332637 &:= -3 + (C(3,2) + 63) \times 7! \\ 332655 &:= 3 \times (C(3! \times 2,6) \times 5! + 5) \\ 332667 &:= 3^{C(3,2)} + 66 \times 7! \\ 332748 &:= 3! \times (3 \times (-2 + 7!) + 4! + 8!) \\ 332784 &:= 3! \times (C(3,2) \times 7! + 8! + 4!) \\ 332794 &:= (C(3!,3) + 2) \times (7 + 9!/4!) \\ 333147 &:= 3 \times (-3!! \times 3! + 1) + C(4!,7) \\ 333360 &:= 3!! \times (C(33/3,6) + 0!) \\ 333438 &:= (3!! - 3!) \times (3!! - C(4!,3)/8) \\ 333453 &:= 3 + C(3^3,4!) \times (5! - 3!) \\ 333456 &:= 3! + C(3^3,4!) \times (5! - 6) \\ 334278 &:= 3! + (-3!! + C(4!, -2 + 7)) \times 8 \\ 334458 &:= -3! + (-3!! + 4! + C(4!,5)) \times 8 \\ 334492 &:= (-3!! + 3! + C(4! - 4,9)) \times 2 \\ 334795 &:= 3! \times C(-3 + 4!,7) - 9! - 5 \\ 334844 &:= C(3 \times 3!,4) + 8 + 4!^4 \\ 334970 &:= 3!! + C(-3 + 4!,9) + (7 + 0)! \\ 335544 &:= 3!! \times (C(3! + 5,5) + 4) + 4! \\ 335556 &:= (3 - 3!!) \times (C(5 + 5,5) - 6!) \\ 335784 &:= -3! + (-3^5 + 7!) \times C(8,4) \\ 336140 &:= C(3!,3) \times (6 + 1)^{4+0!} \\ 336324 &:= C(3^3,6) - 3! + (2 \times 4)! \\ 336325 &:= C(3^3,6) + (3! + 2)! - 5 \\ 336328 &:= C(3^3, (6 - 3)!) - 2 + 8! \\ 336330 &:= C(3^3,6) + (3 \times 3 - 0)! \\ 336348 &:= C(3^3,6) - 3! + 4! + 8! \\ 336354 &:= C(3^3,6) + (3 + 5)! + 4! \\ 336378 &:= C(3^3,6) + (3! + 7!) \times 8 \\ 336492 &:= (-3! + 3! \times 6!) \times C(4 + 9,2) \\ 336747 &:= 3 - 3! \times 6! - 7! + C(4!,7) \\ 336942 &:= 3! \times (-3 + 6! \times C(9 + 4,2)) \\ 336963 &:= 3 + 3! \times 6! \times (C(9,6) - 3!) \\ 336966 &:= 3! + 3! \times 6! \times (C(9,6) - 6) \\ 336984 &:= C(3!,3) \times 6! + 9! - 8! + 4! \\ 337494 &:= (-3! - 3!!) \times C(7,4) + 9! + 4! \\ 337559 &:= -C(3,3) - 7! \times 5 - 5! + 9! \\ 337575 &:= (3 \times 3)! - (C(7,5) + 7!) \times 5 \\ 337580 &:= -(C(3!,3) + 7!) \times 5 + (8 + 0)! \\ 337613 &:= (-C(3,3) + 7!) \times (61 + 3!) \\ 337655 &:= (3 \times 3)! - (C(7,6)! + 5) \times 5 \\ 337660 &:= -C(3!,3) + 7! \times (66 + 0!) \\ 337673 &:= -C(3,3) + 7! \times 67 - 3! \\ 337679 &:= -C(3,3) - 7! \times 6 + 7! + 9! \\ 337681 &:= C(3,3) + 7! \times (68 - 1) \\ 337698 &:= 3 \times (3! + C(7,6)!) + 9! - 8! \\ 337747 &:= (C(3,3) + 7!) \times (74 - 7) \\ 337845 &:= -(-3 + 3!)^7 + 8 \times C(4!,5) \\ 338395 &:= -3!! \times (3! + C(8,3!)) + 9! - 5 \\ 339507 &:= (C(3 \times 3!,9) - 5! + 0!) \times 7 \\ 339597 &:= (-3 - 3!!) \times 9 + C((-5 + 9)!,7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 339627 &:= 3 - 3!! \times 9 + C((6-2)!, 7) \\ 339996 &:= -3!! \times 3! + 9! - C(9+9, 6) \\ 340038 &:= 3! + C(4!, 0! + 0! + 3) \times 8 \\ 340338 &:= -3! + C(4!, 0! + 3!) - 3!! \times 8 \\ 340344 &:= C(-3! + 4!, -0! + 3!) + 4!^4 \\ 340496 &:= (-3 + 4 + C(0! + 4!, 9))/6 \\ 340688 &:= 3!! + (C(4!, -0! + 6) - 8) \times 8 \\ 341067 &:= 3 + C(4!, 1 + 06) - 7! \\ 341768 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 1 + 7!) \times 68 \\ 341777 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 1 \times 7) - 7! - 7 \\ 342144 &:= 3!^{C(4,2)-1} \times 44 \\ 342529 &:= -C(C(3+4, 2), 5) - 2 + 9! \\ 342788 &:= 34 \times 2 \times (7! + C(8, 8)) \\ 342792 &:= (3 \times C(4!, 2))^{-7+9}/2 \\ 343198 &:= -(3+4!)^3 + 1 + C(9, 8)! \\ 343199 &:= 3! - 4 - C(3, 1)^9 + 9! \\ 343227 &:= -3!! \times 4 + 3 + C((2+2)!, 7) \\ 343596 &:= -C(-3! + 4!, C(3!, 5)) + 9! - 6! \\ 343680 &:= 3! \times (-C(4, 3) + 6!) \times 80 \\ 343720 &:= 3!! + ((4+3!) \times 7)^{2+0!} \\ 343749 &:= 3 \times C(4!, 3!) \times 7/4 - 9! \\ 343896 &:= (3! + 4^{3!} - 8) \times C(9, 6) \\ 343947 &:= (-3!! + 4) \times 3 - 9 + C(4!, 7) \\ 343973 &:= -C(-3! + 4!, 3!) + 9! - 7^3 \\ 344609 &:= -C(3+4!, 4) - 6! - 0! + 9! \\ 344736 &:= 3 \times 4! + C(4!, 7) - 3!! - 6! \\ 344739 &:= 3 \times (C(4!, (-4+7)!) - 3^9) \\ 344754 &:= -3!^4 + C(4!, 7) - 54 \\ 344773 &:= -3!^4 + C(4!, 7) - C(7, 3) \\ 344778 &:= -3!! + 4! + C(4!, 7) - 7!/8 \\ 344784 &:= -3!^4 + C(4!, 7) - (8-4)! \\ 344804 &:= -3!^4 + C(4!, 8-0!) - 4 \\ 344808 &:= -3!^4 + C(4!, 8 - (0 \times 8)!) \\ 344858 &:= 3 \times 4 + C(4!, 8) - 5^8 \\ 345234 &:= -3! + 4! \times (5!^2 - C(3!, 4)) \\ 345257 &:= -3!! + C(4!, 5+2) - 5! - 7 \\ 345292 &:= -3!! + C(4!, 5+2) - 92 \\ 345377 &:= -3!! + C(4!, C(5, 3) + 7) - 7 \\ 345382 &:= -3!! + C(4!, 5 \times 3 - 8) - 2 \\ 345384 &:= -3!! + C(4!, -5 + 3 \times (8-4)) \\ 345403 &:= -3!! + 4! - 5 + C(4!, 0! + 3!) \\ 345413 &:= -3!! + 4! + 5 + C(4!, 1 + 3!) \\ 345429 &:= -3!! \times 4! - C(-5 + 4!, 2) + 9! \\ 345465 &:= 3 \times (C(4! + 5, 4) - 6!) \times 5 \\ 345475 &:= -3!! - 4! - 5 + C(4!, 7) + 5! \\ 345579 &:= 3 - C(4!, 5) + 5 \times 7! + 9! \\ 345587 &:= 3!! \times 4 \times 5! - 5 - C(8, 7) \\ 345591 &:= 3! \times 4 \times 5! \times 5! - C(9, 1) \\ 345594 &:= -3! + ((4+5)! \times 5!)/C(9, 4) \\ 345599 &:= 3! \times 4 \times 5! \times 5! - C(9, 9) \\ 345615 &:= C(3!, 4) + 5! \times 6! \times (-1 + 5) \\ 345620 &:= 3!! \times 4 \times 5! + C(6, 2 + 0!) \\ 345627 &:= 3 - 4 \times 5! + C((6-2)!, 7) \\ 345636 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 5! \times C(6, 3) + 6) \\ 345732 &:= 3! \times (C(4!, 5) + 7! \times 3 - 2) \\ 345740 &:= -3 + (4! + 5!) \times 7^4 - 0! \\ 345743 &:= (3!! \times 4! + 7) \times 5 \times 4 + 3 \\ 345747 &:= -(3! + 45) \times 7 + C(4!, 7) \\ 345792 &:= (3!! + C(4!, 5)) \times (7+9)/2 \\ 345852 &:= (3!! + C(4!, 5)) \times 8 + 5!/2 \\ 345944 &:= 3 \times C(4!, 5)/9 + 4!^4 \\ 345957 &:= -3 - 4! - 5! + C((9-5)!, 7) \\ 346043 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 4^3 \\ 346047 &:= 3 \times (-4! + 6 - 0!) + C(4!, 7) \\ 346052 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 0!) - 52 \\ 346055 &:= 3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 55 \\ 346058 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 5 \times 8 \\ 346059 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 0!) - 5 \times 9 \\ 346062 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 6^2 \\ 346074 &:= -3! + C(4 \times 6, 07) - 4! \\ 346075 &:= 3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 7 \times 5 \\ 346082 &:= 3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - C(8, 2) \\ 346085 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 8 - 5 \\ 346088 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 0!) - 8 - 8 \\ 346089 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + (0 \times 8)!) - 9 \\ 346090 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 9 + 0! \\ 346091 &:= -3 + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 9 - 1 \\ 346092 &:= 3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 9 \times 2 \\ 346094 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - 9 - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 346097 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + (0 \times 9)!) - 7 \\
 346098 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 0!) - C(9, 8) \\
 346099 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 0!) + C(9, 9) \\
 346100 &:= -3 + C(4!, 6 + 1) - (00)! \\
 346101 &:= -3 + C(4!, C(6, 1) + 01) \\
 346102 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 1) - 02 \\
 346103 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 1) - (0 \times 3)! \\
 346104 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 1^0 4) \\
 346105 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 1) + (0 \times 5)! \\
 346106 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 1) - (0 \times 6)! \\
 346108 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 1) + (0 \times 8)! \\
 346109 &:= -3 + C(4!, 6 + 1) - 0! + 9 \\
 346122 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 1) + (2 + 2)! \\
 346124 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6 + 1) + 2 + 4! \\
 346131 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6 + 1) + (3 + 1)! \\
 346134 &:= C(3! \times 4, 6 + 1) + 3! + 4! \\
 346137 &:= 3 + 4! + 6 + C((1 + 3)!, 7) \\
 346147 &:= -3 + 46 \times 1 + C(4!, 7) \\
 346247 &:= 3^4 + 62 + C(4!, 7) \\
 346277 &:= 3!!/4 + C((6 - 2)!, 7) - 7 \\
 346315 &:= 3!! \times (4! \times C(6, 3) + 1) - 5 \\
 346347 &:= 3^4 \times (6 - 3) + C(4!, 7) \\
 346352 &:= 3!! + 4 \times (6 + 3!! \times 5! + 2) \\
 346474 &:= 346 + C(4!, 7) + 4! \\
 346524 &:= C(3 \times 4, 6) + 5!^2 \times 4! \\
 346704 &:= 3!! + C(4 \times 6, 7) - (0! + 4)! \\
 346705 &:= 3!! + C(4 \times 6, 7) + 0! - 5! \\
 346762 &:= 3!! + C(4 \times 6, 7) - 62 \\
 346817 &:= 3!! + C(4 \times 6, 8 - 1) - 7 \\
 346822 &:= 3!! + C(4!, (6 + 8)/2) - 2 \\
 346824 &:= 3!! + C(4 \times 6, C(8, 2)/4) \\
 346847 &:= C(3!, 4) + 6! + 8 + C(4!, 7) \\
 346896 &:= 3!^4 + 6! \times 8!/C(9, 6) \\
 347034 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + (0! + 3)!/4! \\
 347049 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + (0! + 4!) \times 9 \\
 347058 &:= -3! + C(4!, 7) + 05! \times 8 \\
 347063 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) - 0! + 6!/3 \\
 347253 &:= 3 \times 4! \times 7! - 2 - 5^3! \\
 347364 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 3 \times 6!/4 \\
 347394 &:= -3! + C(4!, 7) + 3! \times 9 \times 4! \\
 347400 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 4!^{0!+0!} \\
 347407 &:= 3!^4 + 7 + C(4!, 07) \\
 347424 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 4!^2 + 4! \\
 347432 &:= -3!! + C(4!, 7) + 4^3!/2 \\
 347443 &:= 3!^4 + C(4!, 7) + 43 \\
 347469 &:= -C(3!, 4) + (7! - 4) \times 69 \\
 347471 &:= 3 \times ((-4 + 7!) \times 4! - 7!) - 1 \\
 347473 &:= -3 + C(4!, 7) + 4 \times 7^3 \\
 347478 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 4! + 7!/8 \\
 347533 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) - 5 - 3! + 3!! \\
 347536 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) - 5 - 3 + 6! \\
 347537 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 5! \times 3! - 7 \\
 347539 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) - 5 + (-3 + 9)! \\
 347543 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) - 5 + 4 + 3!! \\
 347544 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + (5 + C(4, 4))! \\
 347657 &:= 3!! + C(4!, 7) + 6! + 5! - 7 \\
 347742 &:= 3 \times ((4! \times 7! - 7!) - C(4, 2)) \\
 347775 &:= 3 \times ((4! - C(7, 7)) \times 7! + 5) \\
 347841 &:= 3^4 + 7! \times (C(8, 4) - 1) \\
 348473 &:= 3!! \times 484 - C(7, 3!) \\
 349374 &:= -3!! \times 4 + 9! - C((-3 + 7)!, 4) \\
 349392 &:= (3!! - 4!) \times (9!/(-3 + 9)! - 2) \\
 349536 &:= 3!! - 4! + 9 \times C(5!/3!, 6) \\
 349635 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 9!/6!) \times (3!! - 5) \\
 349839 &:= -3^4 - 9!/C(8, 3!) + 9! \\
 349920 &:= 3^4 \times 9!/C(9, 2 + 0!) \\
 351147 &:= 3 + (5 + 1 + 1)! + C(4!, 7) \\
 352296 &:= (3!! - C(5 + 2, 2)) \times 9!/6! \\
 352377 &:= -3 + C(5, 2) \times (-3! + 7!) \times 7 \\
 352710 &:= -3! + C((5 - 2) \times 7, 10) \\
 352716 &:= C(-3! + 5^2, 7) \times (1 + 6) \\
 352737 &:= (-3 + C(5, 2) \times 7! - 3!) \times 7 \\
 352773 &:= (-3 + C(5, 2) \times 7!) \times 7 - 3! \\
 352787 &:= -3! + C(5, 2) \times (-7! + 8!) - 7 \\
 352788 &:= C(3!, 5) \times (-2 + 7!) + 8 \times 8! \\
 352791 &:= 35 \times 2 \times 7! - C(9, 1) \\
 352799 &:= 35 \times 2 \times 7! - C(9, 9) \\
 352803 &:= 3 + (5 + 2)! \times C(8, 0! + 3) \\
 352807 &:= -3 + C(5, 2) \times (8! + 0! - 7!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$353432 := 3!! \times (5! - 3) + C(4!, 3!) \times 2$$

$$353436 := C(3! + 5 \times 3, 4 + 3!) + 6!$$

$$353567 := (3^{C(5,3)} - 5!) \times 6 - 7$$

$$353574 := (3^{C(5,3)} - 5!) \times (7 - 4)!$$

$$353875 := 3!^5 + C(3 \times 8, 7) - 5$$

$$353880 := 3!^5 + C(3 \times 8, 8 - 0!)$$

$$354264 := ((3 + 5!) \times C(4, 2)! + 6) \times 4$$

$$354295 := 3! - 5 + C(4, 2) \times 9^5$$

$$354342 := (3^{C(5,4)+3!} + 4!) \times 2$$

$$354363 := (3 + 5!) \times (4 \times 3!! + C(6, 3!))$$

$$354396 := (3 + 5! + 4^{3!}) \times C(9, 6)$$

$$354465 := 3 \times (C(5 + 4!, 4!) - 6! + 5!)$$

$$354475 := C(3 + 5, 4) \times (4! + 7!) - 5$$

$$354480 := C(3 + 5, 4) \times (4! + (8 - 0!)!)$$

$$354744 := (3 \times 5! + C(4!, 7)/4!) \times 4!$$

$$354792 := (3!! - 5! + C(4!, 7) + 9!)/2$$

$$354996 := -3!^5 - 4! + 9! - C(9, 6)$$

$$355098 := -3!^5 - 5 - 0! + C(9, 8)!$$

$$355104 := -3!^5 + (C(5, 1) + 04)!$$

$$355129 := -3!^5 + C(5, 1)^2 + 9!$$

$$355473 := 3 \times 5^5 + C(4!, 7) - 3!$$

$$355938 := -C(3! + 5, 5) + 9 \times (-3!! + 8!)$$

$$356145 := 3 \times C(5 \times 6 - 1, 4!) - 5!$$

$$356283 := 3 - 5! + C(6 \times 2, 8) \times 3!!$$

$$356286 := 3! - 5! + C(6 \times 2, 8) \times 6!$$

$$356298 := 3! \times (5^6 + C(2 \times 9, 8))$$

$$356394 := -3! + 5! \times 6 \times C(3 + 9, 4)$$

$$356398 := 3 - 5 + 6! \times C(3 + 9, 8)$$

$$356523 := (-3 + C(5!/6, 5)) \times 23$$

$$356643 := 3^5 + C(6 + 6, 4) \times 3!!$$

$$356859 := -3 \times (5 + C(6 + 8, 5)) + 9!$$

$$356976 := -3!!/5 - 6! + 9! - C(7, 6)!$$

$$356994 := -(3 + 5) \times 6! + 9! - C(9, 4)$$

$$357336 := -3! \times C(5 + 7, 3!) + (3 + 6)!$$

$$357339 := 3 - C(5 + 7, 3!) \times 3! + 9!$$

$$357366 := 3! \times (5^7 - C(3 \times 6, 6))$$

$$357693 := -3!!/5 - C(7, 6)! + 9! - 3$$

$$357749 := -3! - 5! - 7! + C(7, 4) + 9!$$

$$357791 := -(3! \times 5! + 7) \times 7 + C(9, 1)!$$

$$357798 := -35 - 7! - 7 + C(9, 8)!$$

$$357834 := -C(3!, 5) - 7! + (8 - 3 + 4)!$$

$$357840 := 3! \times 5! \times 7 \times (C(8, 4) + 0!)$$

$$357841 := 3! - 5 + 7! \times (C(8, 4) + 1)$$

$$357854 := C(3!, 5) - 7! + 8 + (5 + 4)!$$

$$357855 := 3 \times 5 - 7! + (8 + C(5, 5))!$$

$$357859 := C(3!, 5) - 7! + 8 + 5 + 9!$$

$$357869 := 3! - 5 - 7! + C(8, 6) + 9!$$

$$357952 := -C(3!, 5) - 7! + 9! + 5! - 2$$

$$357953 := 3 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3)$$

$$357953 := 3 + 5! - 7! + 9! - C(5, 3)$$

$$357958 := C(3!, 5) - 7! + 9! + 5! - 8$$

$$357995 := -C(3 + 5 + 7, 9) + 9! + 5!$$

$$358479 := (3! - 5 + C(8, 4)) \times (7! + 9)$$

$$358559 := -3!! \times (-5 + 8)! - C(5, 5) + 9!$$

$$358749 := -35 - C(8, 7)^4 + 9!$$

$$358801 := (3!! - 5! - C(8, 8))^{0!+1}$$

$$359196 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! - C(1 \times 9, 6)$$

$$359216 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! - C(2, 1)^6$$

$$359259 := -3!! \times 5 - C(9 - 2, 5) + 9!$$

$$359263 := 3!! - 5 + 9! - (2 + 6!) \times 3!$$

$$359271 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! - C(2 + 7, 1)$$

$$359277 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! - 2 - C(7, 7)$$

$$359279 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! - C(2 + 7, 9)$$

$$359291 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! + C(2 + 9, 1)$$

$$359298 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! + 2 \times C(9, 8)$$

$$359359 := -3!! \times 5 + C(9, 3) - 5 + 9!$$

$$359400 := -3!! \times 5 + 9! + (4 + (00)!)!$$

$$359424 := (-3 + 5!) \times (C(9, 4) + 2) \times 4!$$

$$359432 := 3!! - 5! + 9! - C(4!, 3) \times 2$$

$$359639 := -3 \times 5! \times 9 - C(6, 3!) + 9!$$

$$359832 := -3 \times 5! + 9! - 8!/C(3!, 2)$$

$$359859 := (3 \times 5! - C(9, 8)!)/5! + 9!$$

$$359866 := -3! - 5 + 9! - C(8 + 6, 6)$$

$$359875 := 3 - 5 + 9! - C(8 + 7, 5)$$

$$359880 := 3 - C(5 + 9, 8) + (8 + 0!)!$$

$$359945 := -C(3! + 5, 9) + 9! - 4! \times 5!$$

$$359946 := -C(3!, 5) \times 9 + 9! - 4 \times 6!$$

$$359991 := 3!! \times (5 - 9) + 9! - C(9, 1)$$

$$359994 := -C(3!, 5) + 9! - 9!/C(9, 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 359995 &:= 3!! \times (-5 + C(9,9)) + 9! - 5 \\ 359999 &:= 3!! \times (5 - 9) - C(9,9) + 9! \\ 360495 &:= -C(3 \times 6 - 0!, 4) + 9! - 5 \\ 360721 &:= -3 \times 6! + 0! + C(7 + 2, 1)! \\ 360863 &:= (3 + 6)! - 0! - 8! / C(6, 3) \\ 360864 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(0! + 8, 6) \times 4! \\ 360969 &:= 3 \times (-6! - 0! + C(9, 6)) + 9! \\ 361236 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(12, 3!) - 6! \\ 361239 &:= 3 - 6! - C(12, 3!) + 9! \\ 361515 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(15, -1 + 5) \\ 362059 &:= -C(3 \times 6, 2 + 0!) - 5 + 9! \\ 362069 &:= -3! \times C(6, 2) - 0! - 6! + 9! \\ 362093 &:= -C(3! + 6, 2) - 0! + 9! - 3!! \\ 362098 &:= -3!! - 62 \times 0! + C(9, 8)! \\ 362152 &:= -3! - 6! - 2 + (-1 + C(5, 2))! \\ 362161 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 - 1 - C(6, 1)! \\ 362180 &:= -3!! + C(6, 2 + 1) + (8 + 0!)! \\ 362254 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(2, 2) - 5^4 \\ 362265 &:= (-3 \times 6! + C(22, 6)) \times 5 \\ 362289 &:= 3 + (-C(6 \times 2, 2) + 8!) \times 9 \\ 362298 &:= -3! - (6 - 2)!^2 + C(9, 8)! \\ 362319 &:= -C(3 \times 6 - 2, 3) - 1 + 9! \\ 362368 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2^{C(3+6,8)} \\ 362369 &:= C(3!, 6) - 2^{3+6} + 9! \\ 362380 &:= -3!! + C(6 \times 2, 3) + (8 + 0!)! \\ 362398 &:= (-3 - 6!) \times 2/3 + C(9, 8)! \\ 362419 &:= -3! - C(C(6, 2), 4 - 1) + 9! \\ 362429 &:= -3^6 + 2 + C(4!, 2) + 9! \\ 362475 &:= 3 \times (-C(6, 2) + 4! \times 7! - 5!) \\ 362529 &:= -C(3^{6/2}, 5^2) + 9! \\ 362598 &:= 3! - 6! \times 2/5 + C(9, 8)! \\ 362609 &:= -3 \times C(6, 2) \times 6 - 0! + 9! \\ 362649 &:= -C(3 \times (6 - 2), 6) / 4 + 9! \\ 362719 &:= -C(3 \times 6, 2) - 7 - 1 + 9! \\ 362727 &:= -C(3 \times 6, 2) + 72 \times 7! \\ 362747 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(2 + 7, 4) - 7 \\ 362749 &:= C(3!, 6) - 2^7 - 4 + 9! \\ 362751 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - 7 - C(5, 1)! \\ 362752 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(2 + 7, 5) - 2 \\ 362754 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(2 \times 7 - 5, 4) \\ 362756 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 - C(7, 5) \times 6 \\ 362760 &:= (3 + 6)! + (2 + C(7, 6) + 0)! \\ 362761 &:= C(3!, 6) + (2 + 7)! - (6 - 1)! \\ 362762 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 - (C(7, 6) - 2)! \\ 362764 &:= -3!! / 6 + (2 + C(7, 6))! + 4 \\ 362765 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 + C(7, 6) - 5! \\ 362767 &:= -3!! / 6 + (2 + C(7, 6))! + 7 \\ 362768 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 \times C(7, 6) \times 8 \\ 362790 &:= (-3 + (6 + 2)! - 7) \times (9 + 0) \\ 362793 &:= 3 - 6 + (2 + 7)! - C(9, 3) \\ 362796 &:= (3 + 6)! - C(2 + 7, 9 - 6) \\ 362814 &:= -3! \times C(6, 2) + (8 + 1)! + 4! \\ 362818 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 - C(8, 1) \times 8 \\ 362827 &:= -3 \times C(6, 2) - 8 + (2 + 7)! \\ 362854 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 \times (8 + C(5, 4)) \\ 362867 &:= C(3 \times 6/2, 8)! - 6 - 7 \\ 362901 &:= -3 + (6 - 2)! + C(9, 01)! \\ 362913 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2 + 9, 1) \times 3 \\ 362922 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 \times C(9 - 2, 2) \\ 362934 &:= (3! + (6 + 2)!) \times 9 \times (-3 + 4) \\ 362942 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 + C(9, 4) / 2 \\ 362952 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 \times C(9, 5 + 2) \\ 362961 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 + C(9, 6) - 1 \\ 362962 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 + C(9, 6/2) \\ 362963 &:= (3 + 6)! + 2 + C(9, 6) - 3 \\ 362970 &:= 3! \times C(6, 2) + (9 + 7 \times 0)! \\ 362991 &:= 3 + 6 \times 2 \times 9 + C(9, 1)! \\ 362993 &:= (3 + 6)! + 29 + C(9, 3) \\ 362994 &:= 3 - C(6, 2) + 9! + C(9, 4) \\ 362995 &:= (3 + 6)! - 2 - 9 + C(9, 5) \\ 363015 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(3!, 0! + 1) + 5! \\ 363027 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(3! + 0!, 2) \times 7 \\ 363033 &:= C(3 \times 6, 3 - 0!) + (3 \times 3)! \\ 363035 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(3! + 0!, 3) + 5! \\ 363049 &:= C(3!, 6) + (3! + 0!) \times 4! + 9! \\ 363059 &:= 3 \times C(6, 3) - 0! + 5! + 9! \\ 363095 &:= C(3! + 6, 3) + 09! - 5 \\ 363098 &:= 3 + 6^3 - 0! + C(9, 8)! \\ 363100 &:= C(3! + 6, 3) + (10 - 0)! \\ 363118 &:= (-3! + 6!) / 3 + (C(1, 1) + 8)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363159 &:= 36 + C(3,1)^5 + 9! \\ 363225 &:= (3+6)! + C(3!,2)^2 + 5! \\ 363229 &:= C((3+6) \times 3,2) - 2 + 9! \\ 363292 &:= 3! + (6+3)! + C(29,2) \\ 363339 &:= (-3 + C(6,3)) \times 3^3 + 9! \\ 363340 &:= (3+6)! + C(3!,3) \times (4! - 0!) \\ 363380 &:= 3!! - C(6+3!,3) + (8+0!)! \\ 363409 &:= (3 + C(6,3)) \times (4! - 0!) + 9! \\ 363432 &:= (3 + C(6,3)) \times 4! + (3^2)! \\ 363443 &:= (3+6)! + 3 + C(4 \times 4,3) \\ 363453 &:= -3 + (6+3)! + 4!^{5-3} \\ 363465 &:= (3+6)! - C(3!,4) + 6! - 5! \\ 363468 &:= 3 \times C(C(6,3) + 4,6) - 8! \\ 363495 &:= C(3+6+3,4) + 9! + 5! \\ 363497 &:= (3! + C(6,3)) \times 4! + 9! - 7 \\ 363565 &:= (3+6)! - 35 + C(6,5)! \\ 363569 &:= -3 + 6! - C(3+5,6) + 9! \\ 363587 &:= 3!! + (6+3)! - 5 - C(8,7) \\ 363589 &:= (3+6)! - 3! + C(5+8,9) \\ 363591 &:= 3 \times (-6 + 3^5) + C(9,1)! \\ 363598 &:= 3! + 6! - 3 - 5 + C(9,8)! \\ 363693 &:= (3+6)! + 3^6 + C(9,3) \\ 363696 &:= (3+6)! + C(3 \times 6,9-6) \\ 363719 &:= 3! \times C(6,3) \times 7 - 1 + 9! \\ 363789 &:= C(3! + 6,3!) - 7 - 8 + 9! \\ 363795 &:= 3 + C(6+3!,7) + 9! + 5! \\ 363802 &:= C(3! + 6,3!) + (8+0!)! - 2 \\ 363804 &:= C(3! + 6,3!) + (8 + (0 \times 4))! \\ 363894 &:= 3! + (6+3)! + 8 \times C(9,4) \\ 363954 &:= (3+6)! - 3! + 9 \times C(5,4)! \\ 364096 &:= C(3! + 6,4) + 0! + 9! + 6! \\ 364140 &:= C(3 \times 6,4) \times ((1+4)! - 0!) \\ 364143 &:= 3 + 6!/4 \times (-1 + C(4!,3)) \\ 364209 &:= 3 \times (6! - C(4!,2) - 0!) + 9! \\ 364239 &:= (3^6 - C(4!,2)) \times 3 + 9! \\ 364255 &:= (3+6)! + C(4!,2) \times 5 - 5 \\ 364259 &:= -3!/6 + C(4!,2) \times 5 + 9! \\ 364260 &:= (3+6)! + C(4!,2) \times (6-0!) \\ 364284 &:= (3+6)! - C(4!,2) + 8!/4! \\ 364314 &:= -3! + 6! \times C(4!,3 \times 1)/4 \\ 364315 &:= (36 \times C(4!,3) - 1) \times 5 \\ 364323 &:= 3 + 6! \times C(4!,3)/(-2+3!) \\ 364329 &:= 3^6 + C(C(4,3),2)! + 9! \\ 364335 &:= (36 \times C(4!,3) + 3) \times 5 \\ 364344 &:= 3! \times 6! \times C(4!,3)/4! + 4! \\ 364536 &:= (3+6)! + C(4!,5-3) \times 6 \\ 364904 &:= (3+6)! + C(4!,9/(-0!+4)) \\ 364991 &:= 3 \times 6! - 49 + C(9,1)! \\ 364992 &:= 3 \times (6! - 4) + 9! - C(9,2) \\ 365391 &:= (-3 + 6! + 5!) \times 3 + C(9,1)! \\ 365824 &:= -(3! + 6)^5 + C(8,2)^4 \\ 365883 &:= (3+6)! + C(5!/8,8-3) \\ 365889 &:= 3! + C(C(6,5) + 8,8) + 9! \\ 366336 &:= 3! \times (6^6 + C(3!,3) \times 6!) \\ 366465 &:= (3+6)! - C(6,4) + 6! \times 5 \\ 366759 &:= 3 \times (6 + C(6+7,5)) + 9! \\ 366798 &:= 3! \times (6! - 67) + C(9,8)! \\ 366942 &:= (3+6!) \times 6 + 9! - C(4!,2) \\ 367191 &:= -3^6 + 7! + C(1 \times 9,1)! \\ 367198 &:= -3 - 6! + 7! + 1 + C(9,8)! \\ 367395 &:= (3+6)! + C(7,3) \times (9+5!) \\ 367416 &:= 3^6 \times 7!/(C(4,1) + 6) \\ 367632 &:= C(3! + 6,7) \times 6 + (3^2)! \\ 367745 &:= (3+6)! + 7! - C(7,4) \times 5 \\ 367794 &:= (3! + 67) \times 7! - C(9,4) \\ 367797 &:= -3 - (6 - C(7,7))! + 9! + 7! \\ 367845 &:= (3+6)! + 7! - C(8,4) - 5 \\ 367849 &:= -3!/6 + 7! - C(8,4) + 9! \\ 367850 &:= (3+6)! + 7! - C(8,5-0!) \\ 367857 &:= (3+6)! + 7! - C(8,5) - 7 \\ 367885 &:= (3+6)! + C(7+8, (8-5)!) \\ 367891 &:= (-3+6!) \times 7 - 8 + C(9,1)! \\ 367892 &:= (3+6)! + 7! + 8 - C(9,2) \\ 367899 &:= (-3+6!) \times 7 + (8+C(9,9))! \\ 367919 &:= (3+6)! + 7! - C(C(9,1),9) \\ 367920 &:= (3+6)! + (7+92 \times 0)! \\ 367921 &:= C(3!,6) + 7! + C(9,2-1)! \\ 367922 &:= C(3!,6) + 7! + 9! + C(2,2) \\ 367926 &:= (3+6)! + 7! + C(9,2)/6 \\ 367933 &:= 3! + 6 + 7! + 9! + C(3,3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367943 &:= -3!/6 + 7! + 9! + C(4,3)! \\ 367951 &:= 36 + 7! + 9! - C(5,1) \\ 367952 &:= (3! + 6!) \times 7 + 9! - C(5,2) \\ 367955 &:= 36 + 7! + 9! - C(5,5) \\ 367962 &:= (3 + 6)! + 7! + C(9,6)/2 \\ 367963 &:= 3^6 \times 7 + 9! - C(6,3) \\ 367976 &:= 3^6 \times 7 + 9! - C(7,6) \\ 367983 &:= (3 + 6)! + 7 \times C(9,8)^3 \\ 367984 &:= -3! + 6! \times 7 + 9! + C(8,4) \\ 367985 &:= (3 + 6)! + 7! + 9 + C(8,5) \\ 367995 &:= -36 + 7! + 9! - 9 + 5! \\ 368464 &:= 3 \times 6! + 8! + C(4!,6) \times 4 \\ 368480 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(8,4) \times 80 \\ 368637 &:= C(3 + 6,8)! + 6! - 3 + 7! \\ 368649 &:= 3^6 + (C(8,6)/4)! + 9! \\ 368668 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(8,6) + 6! \times 8 \\ 368712 &:= 3^6 \times 8 + (C(7,1) + 2)! \\ 368856 &:= (3 + 6) \times (8! - C(8,5)) + 6! \\ 368859 &:= 3 + 6! + (8! - C(8,5)) \times 9 \\ 368928 &:= 3!^6 + (8! - C(9,2)) \times 8 \\ 369216 &:= 3!^6 + 9! - (C(2,1) + 6)! \\ 369438 &:= C(3!,6) + 9! - 4 + 3^8 \\ 369439 &:= C(3!,6) + 9^4 - 3 + 9! \\ 369441 &:= (3 + 6)! + 9^{C(4,4-1)} \\ 371432 &:= (3!! \times 7! + C(4!,3!)) \times 2 \\ 371519 &:= 3!! \times (C(7,1) + 5) - 1 + 9! \\ 371889 &:= 3 \times C(7 - 1 + 8,8) + 9! \\ 372054 &:= 3! \times (-7 + C(20,5) \times 4) \\ 372096 &:= (-3 + 7)! \times C(20,9 + 6) \\ 372459 &:= 3 - 7! \times 2 + C(4!,5) \times 9 \\ 372930 &:= 3!! \times 7 \times 2 + 9! - 30 \\ 372942 &:= (-3! + 7!) \times 2 + 9! - C(4,2) \\ 372954 &:= (-3 + 7!) \times 2 + C(9,5 - 4)! \\ 372955 &:= (-3 + 7!) \times 2 + 9! + C(5,5) \\ 372975 &:= (-3 + 7!) \times 2 + 9! + C(7,5) \\ 373035 &:= (-3! + C(7 \times 3 + 0!,3!)) \times 5 \\ 373065 &:= C(3 \times 7 + (3 \times 0)!,6) \times 5 \\ 373368 &:= C(3 + 7,3) + 3!^6 \times 8 \\ 373495 &:= -3! + C((7 - 3)!,4) + 9! - 5 \\ 373498 &:= C(3 \times 7 + 3,4) + 9! - 8 \\ 373509 &:= 3 + C((7 - 3)!,5 - 0!) + 9! \\ 373545 &:= 3 \times (7! + 3!! + C(5 + 4!,5)) \\ 373679 &:= 3!! + 7! - C(3!,6) + 7! + 9! \\ 373833 &:= -3^7 - 3!! + C(C(8,3)!,3!) \\ 373944 &:= 3! \times 73 + 9! + C(4!,4) \\ 374299 &:= -3 \times 7 + C(4^2,9) + 9! \\ 374395 &:= (37 \times C(4!,3) - 9) \times 5 \\ 374465 &:= (3!! + 7! + C(4,4)) \times 65 \\ 374544 &:= 3!^7/4! + (C(5,4) + 4)! \\ 374549 &:= 3!^7/4! + C(5,4) + 9! \\ 374553 &:= -3^7 + C(4 + 5!/5,3!) \\ 374568 &:= (-3 + 7! + C(4!,5) - 6!) \times 8 \\ 374586 &:= (-3!! + 7! + C(4!,5)) \times 8 - 6 \\ 374850 &:= 3!! \times C(7,4)/8 \times (5! - 0!) \\ 374994 &:= 3!! \times (-7 + 4!) + 9! - C(9,4) \\ 375375 &:= C(3 + 7 + 5,3!) \times 75 \\ 375765 &:= 3!! + (C(7,5) + 7!) \times 65 \\ 376347 &:= 3 + 7! \times 6 + C(3! \times 4,7) \\ 376735 &:= C((3 + 7 - 6) \times 7,3!) - 5 \\ 376740 &:= C((3 + 7 - 6) \times 7, (4 - 0)!) \\ 376743 &:= 3 + C((7 - 6) \times 7 \times 4,3!) \\ 376746 &:= 3! + C((7 - 6) \times 7 \times 4,6) \\ 376764 &:= C((3 + 7 - 6) \times 7,6) + 4! \\ 376824 &:= C(3 \times 7,6) + 8 \times (2 \times 4)! \\ 376888 &:= C(3 \times 7,6) + (8 + 8!) \times 8 \\ 377280 &:= C(3 + 7,7)^2 + (8 + 0)! \\ 377436 &:= -(-3 + 7)! + C(7 \times 4,3!) + 6! \\ 377446 &:= 3!! - 7 - 7 + C(4! + 4,6) \\ 377459 &:= -37 - 7! + C(4!,5) \times 9 \\ 377475 &:= 3 \times (7! - 7) \times (4 + C(7,5)) \\ 377769 &:= 3 \times (-77 + C(7,6)!) + 9! \\ 377964 &:= 3 \times (7! - 7) + 9! - C(6,4) \\ 377972 &:= 3 \times 7! - 7 + 9! - C(7,2) \\ 377979 &:= 3 \times 7! - C(7,9 - 7) + 9! \\ 377987 &:= 3 \times (7! - 7) + 9! + C(8,7) \\ 377995 &:= 3 \times 7! \times (7 + 9 + 9) - 5 \\ 377998 &:= 3 \times 7! + 7 + 9! - C(9,8) \\ 378216 &:= 3!^7 + C(C(8,2), -1 + 6) \\ 378225 &:= (3 + 7!) \times C(8 - 2,2) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 379545 &:= (-3 + 7!) + 9! + C(-5 + 4!, 5) \\ 380358 &:= 3! + 8! + C((0! + 3)!, 5) \times 8 \\ 382509 &:= (-3 + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 09 \\ 382533 &:= -3 + C((8/2)!, 5) \times 3 \times 3 \\ 382536 &:= C(3! \times 8/2, 5) \times (3 + 6) \\ 382944 &:= 3!! \times C(8, 2) + 9! - 4! \times 4 \\ 382970 &:= 3!! \times C(8, 2) + 9! - 70 \\ 382983 &:= (-3! + 8!)/2 \times (-9 + C(8, 3!)) \\ 382995 &:= 3!! \times C(8, 2) + 9! - 9 \times 5 \\ 383349 &:= -3! + C(C(8, 3 + 3), 4) + 9! \\ 383646 &:= 3 \times (-8!/3! + 6 + C(4!, 6)) \\ 383755 &:= 3!! \times (8^3 + C(7, 5)) - 5 \\ 383760 &:= 3!! \times (8^3 + C(7, 6 - 0!)) \\ 384382 &:= 3! \times C(-8 + 4!, 3!) \times 8 - 2 \\ 384384 &:= C(3! + 8, 4) \times 384 \\ 384639 &:= (3 + 8!) - C(4! - 6, 3!) + 9! \\ 386308 &:= C(3 \times 8, 6 + 3!)/(-0! + 8) \\ 386418 &:= -3! + 8! + C(6 \times 4, -1 + 8) \\ 386427 &:= 3 + 8! + C((6 - 4 + 2)!, 7) \\ 386430 &:= 3! + 8! + C(6 \times 4, 3! + 0!) \\ 386478 &:= 3! + 8 \times 6 + C(4!, 7) + 8! \\ 386547 &:= -3 + 8! + 6 + 5! + C(4!, 7) \\ 386897 &:= C(3! + 8, 6) \times 8 + 9! - 7 \\ 387137 &:= 3!! + 8! - 7 + C((1 + 3)!, 7) \\ 387147 &:= 3 + 8! + (7 - 1)! + C(4!, 7) \\ 387365 &:= 3!! - 8! + C(7, 3!)^6 \times 5 \\ 387569 &:= -3! + C(8, 7)! - 5^6 + 9! \\ 387996 &:= (-3 + 8) \times 7! + 9! - C(9, 6) \\ 388647 &:= C(3 \times 8, 8) - 6! - C(4!, 7) \\ 390587 &:= -39 + 0! + 5^{C(8, 7)} \\ 392769 &:= 39 \times (2 \times C(7, 6)! - 9) \\ 392847 &:= (3 + C(9, 2)) \times (8!/4 - 7) \\ 392994 &:= 3! \times (9 - 2)! + 9! - C(9, 4) \\ 393120 &:= (-3! + C(9, 3)) \times ((1 + 2)! + 0!)! \\ 393174 &:= (-3! + C(9, 3)) \times (1 + 7!) - 4! \\ 393243 &:= 3 + 9! + C(3!, 2) \times C(4!, 3) \\ 393273 &:= (-3! + C(9, 3)) \times (2 + 7!) - 3 \\ 393744 &:= (-3! + C(9, 3)) \times (7! + 4 + 4) \\ 393828 &:= 3! + 9 \times C(3 \times (8 - 2), 8) \\ 393849 &:= 3!! + 9 + 3 \times 8!/4 + 9! \\ 393984 &:= 3! \times 9!/3! + 9!/C(8, 4) \\ 394257 &:= 3 + 9! + C(4! - 2, 5) + 7! \\ 394584 &:= -3!! + 9! + C(4!, 5) - 8!/4 \\ 394674 &:= -3! + 9! + C(4! - 6, 7) - 4! \\ 394707 &:= 3 + 9! + C(4! - 7 + 0!, 7) \\ 394875 &:= C(3 \times 9, 4!) \times (8 + 7 + 5!) \\ 395283 &:= 3 + 9! + C(C(5, 2), 8) \times 3!! \\ 395286 &:= 3! + 9! + C(C(5, 2), 8) \times 6! \\ 395436 &:= 3 \times (-9!/5! + C(4!, 3!)) + 6! \\ 395585 &:= (3!! \times 9 + 5) \times (5 + C(8, 5)) \\ 395645 &:= -3 + 9! + (5!/C(6, 4))^5 \\ 396423 &:= 3^9 + C(6!/4! - 2, 3!) \\ 396843 &:= 3! + 9^6 - 8 - C(4!, 3!) \\ 397947 &:= -3! + 9!/7 + 9 + C(4!, 7) \\ 398432 &:= -3!! + 9! + 8! - C(4!, 3) \times 2 \\ 398796 &:= 3!! + 9! + 8! - 7! - C(9, 6) \\ 398947 &:= 3^{C(9, 8)} + 9! + 4^7 \\ 398970 &:= C(3! + 9, 8) \times (9 \times 7 - 0!) \\ 399672 &:= 39 \times (C(9, 6) + 7!) \times 2 \\ 402895 &:= -C(4! + 0!, 2) + 8! + 9! - 5 \\ 402924 &:= -C(4!, 02) + 9! + (2 \times 4)! \\ 402948 &:= -C(4!, 02) + 9! + 4! + 8! \\ 403200 &:= 4 \times (0! + 3!)! \times (20 + 0) \\ 403564 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 56) \times 4 \\ 403743 &:= -4! + 03 \times (-7 + C(4!, 3!)) \\ 403744 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 7 - 4) \times 4 \\ 403763 &:= -4! - 0! + C((-3 + 7)!, 6) \times 3 \\ 403764 &:= C(4!, 0! + 3!) \times 7/6 - 4! \\ 403767 &:= (4 - 0!) \times (C((-3 + 7)!, 6) - 7) \\ 403784 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) + 7 - 8) \times 4 \\ 403812 &:= (C(4!, 03!) + 8) \times (1 + 2) \\ 403844 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) + 8) \times 4 + 4! \\ 403863 &:= 4! + 0! + C(3 \times 8, 6) \times 3 \\ 403935 &:= (C(4!, 03!) + 9) \times 3 + 5! \\ 404364 &:= 4 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 3!) + 6 \times 4!) \\ 404436 &:= (-4 + 0!) \times (4! - C(4!, 3!)) + 6! \\ 404659 &:= C(4!, 0! + 4) - 6! - 5 + 9! \\ 404804 &:= (C(4! + 0!, 4) \times 8 + 0!) \times 4 \\ 404804 &:= 4 \times (0! + 8 \times C(4! + 0!, 4)) \\ 405381 &:= C(4!, 05) - 3 + (8 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 405384 &:= C(4!, 05) + (3^{8/4})! \\ 405389 &:= C(4!, 05) - 3 + 8 + 9! \\ 405408 &:= C(4!, 05) + 4! + (0! + 8)! \\ 405409 &:= C(4!, 05) + 4! + 0! + 9! \\ 406638 &:= (4 - 0! + 6)! + C(6 \times 3, 8) \\ 406644 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 6) + 6!) \times 4 - 4! \\ 413275 &:= (4 + C(13, 2)) \times 7! - 5 \\ 413280 &:= (C(4, 1) + 3)! \times (2 + 80) \\ 414439 &:= 4! + 1 + C(4!, 4) \times 39 \\ 414464 &:= -C(4, 1)^4 + 4! \times 6! \times 4! \\ 414537 &:= C(4!, (-1 + 4)!) + 5 + 3!^7 \\ 414675 &:= 4! \times (-1 + 4! \times 6!) - C(7, 5) \\ 414744 &:= 4! \times (1 + 4! \times (7 - C(4, 4)))! \\ 415919 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) - 91 + 9! \\ 415929 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) - 9^2 + 9! \\ 415955 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) + 9! - 55 \\ 415975 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) + 9! - 7 \times 5 \\ 415982 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) + 9! - C(8, 2) \\ 415983 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) + 9 \times (8! - 3) \\ 415992 &:= C(4! + 1, 5) + 9! - 9 \times 2 \\ 416009 &:= C(4! + 1, 6 - 0!) - 0! + 9! \\ 416787 &:= C(4!, 1 \times 6) + (-7 + 8!) \times 7 \\ 419275 &:= (4! + 1) \times (-C(9, 2) + 7^5) \\ 419863 &:= -41 + C(9, 8) \times 6^3! \\ 423084 &:= -C(4!, 2) + (3! + 0!)! \times 84 \\ 423196 &:= 4 + (-2 + (3! + 1)!) \times C(9, 6) \\ 423363 &:= (4!^2 + 3! + 3!) \times 6! + 3 \\ 423378 &:= C(4, 2) \times (3 + 3! \times 7! + 8!) \\ 423696 &:= (-4 + (-2 + 3 + 6)!) \times C(9, 6) \\ 425040 &:= C(4!, -2 + 5 + 0!) \times 40 \\ 425280 &:= (C(4!, 2) + (5 + 2)!) \times 80 \\ 425520 &:= C(4, 2)! \times (5 \times (5! - 2) + 0!) \\ 425796 &:= (4 + 25 + 7!) \times C(9, 6) \\ 426636 &:= C(4!, -2 + 6) \times 6 + (3 + 6)! \\ 426639 &:= C(4!, -2 + 6) \times 6 + 3 + 9! \\ 427975 &:= (C(4, 2) + 79) \times (7! - 5) \\ 428376 &:= -4! + (2 + 83) \times C(7, 6)! \\ 430353 &:= C(4!, 3 + 0!) \times 3^5/3! \\ 431424 &:= 4! \times (3!! + (-1 + C(4, 2)))! \times 4! \\ 431976 &:= -4! + 3!! \times (-C(1 + 9, 7) + 6!) \\ 432432 &:= (4! + 3) \times C(2^4, 3!) \times 2 \\ 433352 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + 3!! \times (-3! + 5!)) \times 2 \\ 434128 &:= (C(4! - 3, (4 - 1)!) + 2) \times 8 \\ 434352 &:= (4 \times C(-3 + 4!, 3!) - 5!) \times 2 \\ 434376 &:= 4! \times (3 - (C(4!, 3) - 7!)) \times 6 \\ 434688 &:= (C(4!, 3) \times 4! + 6!) \times 8 + 8! \\ 435744 &:= (-C(4!, 3) + (5 + 7!) \times 4) \times 4! \\ 435831 &:= (C(4!, 3 \times 5) - 8)/3 - 1 \\ 435832 &:= (C(4!, 3 \times 5) - 8)/C(3, 2) \\ 435833 &:= (C(4!, 3 \times 5) - 8 + 3)/3 \\ 436996 &:= C(4!, 3!) + (6 \times 9! - 9!)/6 \\ 437184 &:= C(4!, 3 \times 7) \times (1 + 8) \times 4! \\ 437469 &:= -4! + C(-3! + 7 \times 4, 6) + 9! \\ 437472 &:= (4! + 3!!) \times 7 \times 4 \times C(7, 2) \\ 437584 &:= (C(4!, 3!) - 7! \times 5) \times (8 - 4) \\ 437888 &:= (-4! \times 3 + 7! + 8) \times 88 \\ 437968 &:= (C(4!, 3) + 7!) \times (9 \times 6 + 8) \\ 438476 &:= -4 + (3 + 84) \times C(7, 6)! \\ 438737 &:= -C(4, 3) + 87 \times (3 + 7!) \\ 439208 &:= C(4!, 3) \times (9 + 208) \\ 439344 &:= 4! \times 3! \times (-9 + C(-3! + 4!, 4)) \\ 440395 &:= C(4! - 4, 0! + 3!) + 9! - 5 \\ 443256 &:= (-4! + (C(4, 3) \times 2)!) \times (5 + 6) \\ 443476 &:= (-4 + (4!/3)!) \times (4 + C(7, 6)) \\ 443496 &:= -4! + (4 + 3)! \times (4 + C(9, 6)) \\ 443508 &:= -C(4, 4) + (3! + 5) \times (-0! + 8!) \\ 443516 &:= -4 + (4!/3)! \times (C(5, 1) + 6) \\ 443529 &:= (4! + 4^3) \times (5 + 2)! + 9 \\ 443531 &:= (4 + 4 + 3) \times ((5 + 3)! + 1) \\ 443579 &:= -4! + C(4! + 3, 5) - 7 + 9! \\ 443598 &:= -4 + C(4! + 3, 5) + 9! - 8 \\ 443772 &:= C(4!, 4) \times 3! \times 7 - 7!/2 \\ 444276 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 4! \times 2) \times 7 \times 6 \\ 444599 &:= C(4!, -4 + 4 \times 5)/9 + 9! \\ 444693 &:= 4!/4 \times C(4!, 6) - 9! - 3 \\ 444696 &:= 4!/4 \times (C(4!, 6) - 9!/6) \\ 445242 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 5^2) \times 42 \\ 445536 &:= 4! \times C(4 \times 5 - 5 + 3, 6) \\ 445698 &:= C(4!, 4! - 5) - 6 + 9! + 8! \\ 445728 &:= 4! + C(4!, 5) + (7 + 2)! + 8! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 446257 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times (6/2)! - 5) \times 7 \\ 446274 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 - 2) \times 7 - 4 \\ 446291 &:= C(4!, 4) \times 6 \times (-2 + 9) - 1 \\ 446292 &:= C(4!, 4) \times (6 \times 2 + 9) \times 2 \\ 446313 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3) \times (1 + 3!) \\ 446327 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3 + 2) \times 7 \\ 446334 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3!) \times (3 + 4) \\ 446376 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 6/3) \times 7 \times 6 \\ 446397 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3! + 9) \times 7 \\ 446403 &:= 4! \times (4! + 6!) \times (4! + 0!) + 3 \\ 446460 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 4!) \times (6 + 0!) \\ 446535 &:= (4! + (4! + 6!) \times 5! + 3) \times 5 \\ 446789 &:= -C(4!, 4)/6 + 7! \times 89 \\ 446796 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 \times 7! + 9!)/6! \\ 446883 &:= (4! + (4 + 6)!)/8 - 8!/3! \\ 446957 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 95) \times 7 \\ 447832 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 7) \times 8 + (3^2)! \\ 447884 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 7! + 8!) \times 8 - 4 \\ 447888 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 7!) \times 8 + 8 \times 8! \\ 448528 &:= (-4^4 - 8! + C(5, 2)!)/8 \\ 448608 &:= C(4!, 4) \times 8 + 6! + (0! + 8)! \\ 448609 &:= C(4!, 4) \times 8 + 6! + 0! + 9! \\ 449256 &:= -4! + 4 \times (C(9, 2) + 5!) \times 6! \\ 449276 &:= -4 + C(4 + 9, 2) \times (7! + 6!) \\ 449568 &:= 4 \times (4! \times C((9 + 5), 6) + 8!) \\ 450553 &:= (C(4!, 5) + 0!)/5 \times 53 \\ 451467 &:= (-4 + C(5, 1)^4) \times (6! + 7) \\ 451577 &:= C(4!, 5 - 1) \times 5! - 7^7 \\ 452856 &:= -4! + C(5, 2)!/8 - 5! \times 6 \\ 452868 &:= -4 + C(5, 2)!/8 - 6! - 8 \\ 452876 &:= (4! + C(5, 2)!)/8 - 7 - 6! \\ 452877 &:= (-4! + C(5, 2)!)/8 - 7!/7 \\ 452883 &:= 4 + (C(5, 2)! - 8)/8 - 3!! \\ 452893 &:= 4 + C(5, 2)!/8 + 9 - 3!! \\ 453476 &:= -4 - 5! + C(3!, 4) \times 7! \times 6 \\ 453491 &:= C(4! - 5, 3 + 4) \times 9 - 1 \\ 453528 &:= ((4! - 5!) \times 3! + C(5, 2)!)/8 \\ 453543 &:= (-4! + (C(5, 3)! + 5!)/4!) \times 3 \\ 453576 &:= (-4 + (C(5, 3) + 5) \times 7!) \times 6 \\ 453580 &:= -4 + (C(5, 3)! - 5!)/8 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 453581 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)! - 5!)/8 - 1 \\ 453583 &:= 4 + (C(5, 3)! - 5!)/8 - 3! \\ 453584 &:= (4! + C(5, 3)! - 5!)/8 - 4 \\ 453585 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)!/5)/8 \times 5 \\ 453591 &:= -4! + ((C(5, 3))! + 5!)/(9 - 1) \\ 453596 &:= -4 + C(5, 3)!/(5 + 9 - 6) \\ 453603 &:= (4! + C(5, 3)!)/(6 - 0! + 3) \\ 453608 &:= (4 + C(5, 3)! + 60)/8 \\ 453622 &:= 4! + C(5, 3)!/(6 + 2) - 2 \\ 453624 &:= 4! + C(5, 3)!/(6 - 2 + 4) \\ 453683 &:= -4 + (C(5, 3)! + 6!)/8 - 3 \\ 453687 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)! + 6!)/C(8, 7) \\ 453688 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)! + 6! + 8)/8 \\ 453888 &:= (C(4!, 5)/3! + 8) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 453945 &:= (C(4!, 5 - 3) + 9!)/4 \times 5 \\ 455232 &:= (C(4!, 5) + 5!^2) \times (3! + 2) \\ 455409 &:= (4 \times C(5 \times 5, 4) + 0!) \times 9 \\ 455538 &:= (C(4 \times 5, 5) + C(5, 3)!)/8 \\ 455736 &:= (-4 + (5! + 5 \times 7!) \times 3) \times 6 \\ 455784 &:= C(4!, 5) + (-5! + 7!) \times 84 \\ 455897 &:= C(4! - 5, 5) \times 8 + 9! - 7 \\ 455932 &:= -C(4!, 5) + (-5 - 9 + 3!!)^2 \\ 456254 &:= 4 + (C(5, 2) + 6!) \times 5^4 \\ 456338 &:= C(4!, 5 + 6)/3! - 3! + 8! \\ 456344 &:= C(4!, 5 + 6)/3! + (4 + 4)! \\ 456348 &:= C(4!, 5 + 6)/3! + 4 + 8! \\ 457432 &:= (4 + (5! - 7) \times C(4!, 3)) \times 2 \\ 458514 &:= (4 + 5) \times (8! + C((5 - 1)!, 4)) \\ 458565 &:= (C(4!, 5)/8 + 5! \times 6!) \times 5 \\ 459624 &:= (4! - 5) \times 9!/C(6, 2) - 4! \\ 459644 &:= (4! - 5) \times 9!/C(6, 4) - 4 \\ 459936 &:= 4! \times (-5! + C(9 + 9, 3!) + 6!) \\ 460455 &:= (C(4!, 6) - 0! - C(4!, 5)) \times 5 \\ 461471 &:= C(4!, 6) \times 1 \times 4!/7 - 1 \\ 462816 &:= 4! \times (6! + C(2 \times (8 + 1), 6)) \\ 463417 &:= -4! \times 6! - 3 + C(4! + 1, 7) \\ 463683 &:= 46 \times 3!! \times (6 + 8) + 3 \\ 463684 &:= 4 + 6! \times (-3! + 6! - C(8, 4)) \\ 463827 &:= C(4!, 6) \times 3!/8 + (2 + 7)! \\ 463829 &:= C(4!, 6) \times 3!/8 + 2 + 9! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}463968 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times (-3 + C(9, 6)) \times 8 \\464376 &:= 4 \times (-6 + C(4! - 3, 7)) - 6! \\464544 &:= 4! \times (-6 + C(4 \times 5, 4)) \times 4 \\464574 &:= 4! \times (-6! + 4! + 5^7) / 4 \\464976 &:= (-4! + C(6! / (4 \times 9), 7)) \times 6 \\466398 &:= (4! \times 6! - 6) \times 3 \times C(9, 8) \\466559 &:= 4! \times 6 \times 6! - C(5, 5) + 9! \\466944 &:= 4^6 \times (-6 + C(9 - 4, 4)!) \\467064 &:= C(4 \times 6, 7) + (0! + 6)! \times 4! \\467544 &:= C(4!, 6 - 7 + 5) \times 44 \\467566 &:= C(4!, 6) + (7! + 5) \times 66 \\467824 &:= C(4!, 6) + (-7! + 8!) / 2 \times 4 \\469396 &:= C(4!, 6) + 9! - 39 \times 6! \\469728 &:= 4!! / (6! / C(9, 7))! \times 2 - 8! \\469792 &:= (C(4 \times 6, 9) - 7! - 9!) / 2 \\470575 &:= 4 \times 7^{0!+5} - C(7, 5) \\472896 &:= (4!! / C(7, 2))! + 8! \times 9 + 6! \\473793 &:= (C(4!, 7) / 3! - 7!) \times 9 - 3 \\473796 &:= (C(4!, 7) - 3! \times 7!) \times 9 / 6 \\474296 &:= -4 - (7 - 4)!! + C(29, 6) \\474546 &:= -474 + C(5 + 4!, 6) \\474721 &:= (-4! + (7 - 4)!! - 7)^{C(2, 1)} \\474794 &:= (-4! + C(7, 4) + 7!) \times 94 \\474973 &:= -47 + C(4 \times 9 - 7, 3!) \\474996 &:= -4! + C(7 + 4 + 9 + 9, 6) \\475016 &:= -4 + C(-7 \times (-5 + 0!) + 1, 6) \\475020 &:= C(4 \times 7 + (5 \times 0)!, (2 + 0)!) \\475196 &:= -4 + (7 + 5 - 1)! / C(9, 6) \\475296 &:= C(4!, 7 - 5) + C(29, 6) \\475744 &:= (-C(4!, C(7, 5)) + 7! \times 4!) \times 4 \\475752 &:= (C(4!, 7) + (5 + 7!) \times 5!) / 2 \\475944 &:= 4! \times (7^5 + C(9, 4) \times 4!) \\476883 &:= (C(4!, 7) + 6!) / 8 \times (8 + 3) \\477433 &:= -C(4!, 7) + 7^{4+3} - 3! \\477439 &:= -C(4!, 7) + 7^{4-3!+9} \\477443 &:= 4 + 7^7 - C(4!, 4 + 3) \\477447 &:= 4 + 7^7 + 4 - C(4!, 7) \\478720 &:= (-4^7 + C(8, 7)!) \times 20 \\479976 &:= -4 + C(7 + 9 + 9, 7) - 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}480453 &:= C(4!, 8) + (0! - C(4!, 5)) \times 3! \\480528 &:= -(4 + 8) \times (C((-0! + 5)!, 2) - 8!) \\481320 &:= (4! \times 8! - (1 + 3)!) / 2 + 0 \\481323 &:= (4! \times 8! - (1 + 3)!) / 2 + 3 \\481338 &:= (4 + 8 - 1) \times C(3 \times 3!, 8) \\481537 &:= -4 + (8! + 1) \times 5 + 3!^7 \\482184 &:= 4! \times (8! / 2 + 1 - C(8, 4)) \\482769 &:= (4! \times C(8, 2) + 7) \times (6! - 9) \\482973 &:= 4! \times (8! / 2 - C(9, 7)) - 3 \\482976 &:= 4! \times (8! / 2 - C(9, C(7, 6))) \\483164 &:= 4! \times C(8, 3!) \times (-1 + 6!) - 4 \\483312 &:= (-4! + 8! - C(3!, 3)) \times 12 \\483368 &:= -4! + (-C(8, 3) + 3!) \times (6! + 8) \\483393 &:= -C(4! - 8, 3!) \times 3! + 9^3 \\483483 &:= (-4! + 8! - 3!) \times (4 + 8) + 3 \\483489 &:= (-4! + 8! - 3!) \times (4 + 8) + 9 \\483532 &:= ((-4! + 8!) \times 3! - C(5, 3)) \times 2 \\483543 &:= (4 \times 8! - 3 - 5! + 4!) \times 3 \\483572 &:= 4 \times (8! \times 3 + 5 - 72) \\483594 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - 5! - C(9, 4) \\483628 &:= 4 \times (8 + 3 \times (-C(6, 2) + 8!)) \\483671 &:= 4! \times (C(8, 3!) \times 6! - 7) - 1 \\483696 &:= 4! \times (C(8, 3!) \times 6! - (9 - 6)!) \\483720 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - (7 - 2 + 0)! \\483737 &:= 4 \times (8! \times 3 - (7 - 3)!) - 7 \\483764 &:= ((-4 + 8!) \times 3 - C(7, 6)) \times 4 \\483797 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - 7 - C(9, 7) \\483812 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - C(C(8, 1), 2) \\483821 &:= (4! \times 8! - 38) / C(2, 1) \\483832 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - C(8, 3 - 2) \\483833 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - 8 + C(3, 3) \\483835 &:= (4 + 8) \times (3 \times 8/3)! - 5 \\483843 &:= (4! \times 8! + 3!) / (8 / C(4, 3)) \\483854 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 + C(8, 5) / 4 \\483868 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 + C(8, -6 + 8) \\483871 &:= 4 \times (8! \times 3 + C(8, 7)) - 1 \\483872 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times 3! - C(8, 7)) \times 2 \\483873 &:= (4 \times 8! + 3 + C(8, 7)) \times 3 \\483877 &:= (4 + 8) \times (3 + 8!) + C(7, 7) \\483884 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times 3 - C(8, 8)) \times 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 483888 &:= (4 + 8!) \times (3 + C(8, 8) + 8) \\ 483894 &:= (4 + 8) \times (-3! + 8!) + C(9, 4) \\ 483896 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 + C(8, 9 - 6) \\ 483911 &:= (4! + 8!) \times 3 + 9! - C(1, 1) \\ 483912 &:= ((4! + 8!) \times 3) + C(9, 1^2)! \\ 483924 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 + C(9, 2 + 4) \\ 483951 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - 9 + C(5, 1)! \\ 483958 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 + C(9, 5) - 8 \\ 483977 &:= 4 \times 8! \times 3 - C(9, 7) - 7 \\ 483996 &:= (4! + 8!) \times 3 + 9! + C(9, 6) \\ 484131 &:= ((4! + 8!) \times 4 + 1) \times C(3, 1) \\ 484200 &:= (4! \times 8! + C(4, 2)!)/(0! + 0!) \\ 484272 &:= 4! \times (8!/4 + 2 + 7) \times 2 \\ 484342 &:= -4 - C(8, 4) + (3!! - 4!)^2 \\ 484352 &:= (4! \times 8! + C(4, 3)^5)/2 \\ 484356 &:= (-4 + C((8 - 4)! + 3, 5)) \times 6 \\ 484422 &:= (4!/8)! + (4! - (C(4, 2)))!^2 \\ 484462 &:= -4! + C(8, 4) + (-4! + 6!)^2 \\ 484606 &:= (4! - C(8, 4) + 6!) \times (-0! + 6!) \\ 484852 &:= 4! \times 8! + C(4!, 8 - 5)/2 \\ 484896 &:= (4 + 8) \times (4 + 8! + C(9, 6)) \\ 484919 &:= (C(4!, -8 + 4!) + (9 + 1)!)/9 \\ 485184 &:= 4! \times (C(8, 5) + (-1 + 8)! \times 4) \\ 485240 &:= 4! \times (8! + 5!)/2 - 40 \\ 485273 &:= 4! \times (8! + 5!)/2 - C(7, 3!) \\ 485755 &:= 4!! \times 8 \times 5/C(7, 5)! - 5 \\ 486528 &:= 4! \times C(8, 6)^{5-2} - 8! \\ 486843 &:= (4 \times 8! + C(6 + 8, 4)) \times 3 \\ 487436 &:= -4 + (-8 - C(7, 4) + 3!!) \times 6! \\ 487656 &:= 4! \times C(8 + 7 + 6, 5) - 6! \\ 487692 &:= ((4!/8)!! - 7) \times (6! - C(9, 2)) \\ 488384 &:= (4 + 8) \times (3!! + 8!) - 8^4 \\ 488796 &:= (4 + 8) \times 8! + 7! - C(9, 6) \\ 488896 &:= 4^8 + 8!/8 \times C(9, 6) \\ 489596 &:= -4 + C(8 + 9, 5 + 9) \times 6! \\ 490134 &:= (C(4!, 9 + 0!) - 1 \times 3!!)/4 \\ 490254 &:= (C(4!, 9 + 0!) - 2 \times 5!)/4 \\ 490307 &:= C(4!, 9 + 0!)/(3 + 0!) - 7 \\ 490312 &:= (C(4!, 9 - 0!)/3 - 1) \times 2 \\ 490314 &:= C(4! - (9 \times 0)!/(3 - 1) \times 4) \\ 490318 &:= 4 + C(-9 + 0! + 31, 8) \\ 490338 &:= 4! + C(-9 - 0! + 33, 8) \\ 490408 &:= 4 + 90 + C(4! - 0!, 8) \\ 490434 &:= (-4 + 9)! + C(-0! + 4!, C(3!, 4)) \\ 490734 &:= (C(4!, 9 + 0!) + 7!/3)/4 \\ 491574 &:= (C(4!, 9 + 1^5) + 7!)/4 \\ 491934 &:= (C(4!, 9 + 1) + 9 \times 3!!)/4 \\ 491994 &:= (C(4!, 9) \times 9 + (-1 + 9)!)/4! \\ 492448 &:= C(4!, 9)/2 - 4! - 4 \times 8! \\ 492456 &:= -4! + C(9, 2) \times (4! - 5) \times 6! \\ 493063 &:= 4! + (C(9, 3) + 0! - 6)^3 \\ 494355 &:= 4 + 9! + C(4!, 3!) - 5^5 \\ 495439 &:= 49 \times (5 \times C(4!, 3) - 9) \\ 495495 &:= C(4! - 9, 5) \times (4! + 9) \times 5 \\ 497393 &:= -4! + C(9 + 7 + 3!, 9) - 3 \\ 497420 &:= C(4! - 9 + 7, 4 \times 2 + 0!) \\ 497446 &:= -4! + 9! - (7 - 4)! + C(4!, 6) \\ 497460 &:= -4! + 9! + 7 + C(4!, 6) + 0! \\ 497465 &:= -4 + 9! - 7 + C(4!, C(6, 5)) \\ 497493 &:= 4! + 9! - 7 + C(4!, 9 - 3) \\ 498196 &:= C(4!, 9 + 8 + 1) + 9! + 6! \\ 498636 &:= (-4 \times C(9, 8) + 6!) \times 3^6 \\ 499162 &:= 4 + 99 \times ((1 + 6)! + 2) \\ 500424 &:= ((5 + 0)! - 0!) \times (C(4, 2)! - 4!) \\ 504135 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4! \times 1, 3!) - 5!) \\ 504615 &:= -5! + C(-0! + 4!, 6) \times 1 \times 5 \\ 504625 &:= -5! + (C(-0! + 4!, 6) + 2) \times 5 \\ 504675 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 7 - 5) \\ 504735 &:= C(-5 - (0 - 4) \times 7, 3!) \times 5 \\ 504740 &:= 5 \times (C(-0! + 4!, (7 - 4)!) + 0!) \\ 504855 &:= 5! + C(-0! + 4!, (8 - 5)!) \times 5 \\ 507384 &:= C((5 - 0)!/(C(7, 3!))) + 8! \times 4 \\ 513366 &:= (5! - 1) \times (-C(3, 3) + 6!) \times 6 \\ 514795 &:= C(5 + 1, 4)!/7/9! - 5 \\ 514799 &:= (C(5 + 1, 4)!/7 - 9!)/9! \\ 517320 &:= 5! \times (1 \times 7! - 3^{(2+0)!}) \\ 518232 &:= -(5 + 1) \times C(8, 2) + 3!!^2 \\ 518391 &:= (5 + 1)!^{8-3!} - C(9, 1) \\ 518397 &:= C(5, 1) - 8 + 3!!^{9-7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 518399 &:= (5 + 1)!^{8-3!} - C(9, 9) \\ 519792 &:= (5! - 1) \times C(9 + 7, 9 + 2) \\ 519962 &:= 5! + 1 + (C(9, 9) + 6!)^2 \\ 522693 &:= (-C(5 - 2, 2) + 6!) \times 9^3 \\ 523422 &:= (5 - 2)^{3!} \times (C(4, 2)! - 2) \\ 523436 &:= (C(5, 2) - 3)! - 4 + 3!! \times 6! \\ 523437 &:= C(5, 2)! / (3 + 4) - 3 + 7! \\ 523446 &:= ((5 - 2)! + 3!!) \times (C(4, 4) + 6!) \\ 523844 &:= (C(5, 2) + 3) \times (8! - 4!) - 4 \\ 523848 &:= (C(5, 2) + 3) \times (-(8 - 4)! + 8!) \\ 524040 &:= 5! \times (C(2^4, 0! + 4) - 0!) \\ 524155 &:= 5! \times C(C(2^4, 1), 5) - 5 \\ 524254 &:= -C(5, 2) - 4! + 2^{-5+4!} \\ 524278 &:= 5! - 2 + (C(4, 2) + 7) \times 8! \\ 524396 &:= 5! + 2 \times (C(4, 3)^9 - 6) \\ 524399 &:= 5! + 2 \times C(4, 3)^9 - 9 \\ 524448 &:= 5!^2 + C(4!, 4) \times 48 \\ 524520 &:= 5! \times (C(2^4, 5) + 2 + 0!) \\ 524748 &:= (5 - 2) \times (C(4!, (7 - 4)!) + 8!) \\ 525635 &:= C(5, 2) + (5 + 6!)^{-3+5} \\ 526245 &:= 5 + (2 + 6) \times C(2 + 4!, 5) \\ 526330 &:= (C(5, 2) + 6!) \times ((3 + 3)! + 0!) \\ 526725 &:= 5^2 \times (6! + C(C(7, 2), 5)) \\ 526986 &:= ((5! + 2) \times 6! - C(9, 8)) \times 6 \\ 527356 &:= C(5^2, 7) + 3!^5 \times 6 \\ 529725 &:= (5 + (-2 + 9)!) \times C(7, 2) \times 5 \\ 531303 &:= (C(5^{3-1}, 3!) + 0!) \times 3 \\ 531385 &:= (5 + 3 + 1)^{3!} - C(8, 5) \\ 531420 &:= 5! + 3 \times C(1 + 4!, (2 + 0)!) \\ 531435 &:= 5! + 3 \times (C(1 + 4!, 3!) + 5) \\ 531435 &:= 5! + 3 \times (C(4! + 1, 3!) + 5) \\ 531693 &:= C(C(5, 3), -1 + 6) + 9^{3!} \\ 532166 &:= 5 + C(3^2, 1)^6 + 6! \\ 532344 &:= 5! + C(3! \times 2, 3!) \times 4! \times 4! \\ 533363 &:= 5 + (3!! + 3^3) \times (6! - 3!) \\ 533468 &:= (C(5, 3) + 3) \times (-4 + 6! + 8!) \\ 533525 &:= 5 + 3!! \times (3!! + C(5 + 2, 5)) \\ 533634 &:= (5 \times 3 + 3!!) \times (6! + 3!) + 4! \\ 533660 &:= 5! + (C(3!, 3) + 6!) \times (6! + 0!) \\ 534492 &:= ((5 + 3)! - C(4!, 4)) \times 9 \times 2 \\ 534496 &:= -5 + C(-3! + 4!, 4) + 9^6 \\ 534664 &:= -5! - 3!! + (C(4!, 6) - 6!) \times 4 \\ 535464 &:= (-5 - 3!! - 5 + C(4!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 536250 &:= (-5 + 3!!) \times C(6, 2) \times 50 \\ 537225 &:= (5 + 3!!) \times (C(7, 2) + (-2 + 5)!!) \\ 537595 &:= C(5 + 3, 7)! \times 5! / 9 - 5 \\ 537607 &:= (C(5! / 3!, 7) - 6! + 0!) \times 7 \\ 537835 &:= 5 + 3! + (C(8, 7) + 3!)^5 \\ 538264 &:= (-5 \times 3! + C((8/2)!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 538384 &:= (C(5! / (-3 + 8), 3!)) \times (8 - 4) \\ 538392 &:= 5! + (3!! - 8) \times (3!! + C(9, 2)) \\ 538404 &:= (5 + C(3 \times 8, (4 - 0)!)) \times 4 \\ 538464 &:= C(5, 3) \times 8 + C(4!, 6) \times 4 \\ 538504 &:= 5! + C(3 \times 8, 5 + 0!) \times 4 \\ 538864 &:= (5! + C((3 + C(8, 8))!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 539464 &:= (5 \times 3! \times 9 + C(4!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 541632 &:= (5! + 4) \times C(16, 3 + 2) \\ 542376 &:= (5! + 4) \times 2 \times 3^{C(7, 6)} \\ 543427 &:= 5 - (-C(4!, 3!) \times 4 + 2) + 7! \\ 543429 &:= 5 + C(4!, 3!) \times 4 + (-2 + 9)! \\ 543600 &:= 5 \times (4 + 3)! + 6!^{0!+0!} \\ 543664 &:= (-5! + C(4!, 3!) + 6! + 6!) \times 4 \\ 543694 &:= -5! + (-C(4!, 3) + 6 \times 9!) / 4 \\ 543695 &:= -5^4 + 3! \times 6! \times C(9, 5) \\ 543750 &:= (C(5, 4) + 3!!) \times 750 \\ 543934 &:= 5! + (-C(4!, 3) + 9! \times 3!) / 4 \\ 544344 &:= (C(5, 4) + 4)! \times 3! / 4 + 4! \\ 544356 &:= ((5 + 4)! / 4 + C(3!, 5)) \times 6 \\ 545751 &:= -(5 + 4)^5 + 7! \times C(5, 1)! \\ 546755 &:= C(5, 4)^6 \times 7 \times 5 - 5! \\ 547096 &:= (-5! - C(4!, 7) + (0! + 9)!) / 6 \\ 547547 &:= (C(5, 4)^7 + 5! - 4!) \times 7 \\ 547582 &:= -5! + C(4!, 7) + 5 \times 8! - 2 \\ 547584 &:= -5! + C(4!, 7) + 5! \times 8! / 4! \\ 547675 &:= (C(5 \times 4, 7) + 6!) \times 7 - 5 \\ 548379 &:= (C(5, 4)! - 8 - 3) \times (7! - 9) \\ 552432 &:= -5! + 52 \times C(4!, 3! - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 552959 &:= -C(5,5) + 2^9 \times 5! \times 9 \\ 553630 &:= (5 \times C(5,3) + 6!) \times (3!! - 0!) \\ 553735 &:= (5! - C(5,3)) \times (7! - 3!) - 5 \\ 553740 &:= (5! - C(5,3)) \times (7! - (4 - 0!)!) \\ 553764 &:= (5! - C(5,3)) \times (7! - 6) + 4! \\ 554273 &:= 5 + C(-5 + 4!, 2 + 7) \times 3! \\ 554946 &:= C(5!/5, 4) + 9!/4 \times 6 \\ 554964 &:= 5! + C(-5 + 4!, 9) \times 6 - 4! \\ 556680 &:= 5 \times C(5!/6, 6) + (8 + 0!)! \\ 557525 &:= 5^5 - 7! \times (C(5,2) - 5!) \\ 558665 &:= -55 + 8! + 6! \times C(6,5)! \\ 559764 &:= -5! + (5! - 9) \times (C(7,6)! + 4) \\ 559872 &:= (-C(5, -5 + 9) + 8)!^7 \times 2 \\ 559875 &:= -5! + (5! - C(9,8)) \times (7! + 5) \\ 560281 &:= 5! + (6! + 0!)^2 + C(8,1)! \\ 564363 &:= -5! + (6! + 4^3) \times 6! + 3 \\ 566275 &:= (-5 + 6!) \times C(6 \times 2, 7) - 5 \\ 566280 &:= (-5 + 6!) \times C(6 \times 2, 8 - 0!) \\ 566596 &:= (-5! + 6!) \times 6! + C((-5 + 9)!, 6) \\ 567834 &:= (5! - 6) \times (C(7 + 8, 3!) - 4!) \\ 568568 &:= (5 + 6! + C(8,5)) \times (6! + 8) \\ 570235 &:= -5 + (7 - 0!)! \times C(2 \times 3!, 5) \\ 572032 &:= 5! \times 7! - 2^{C(03!, 2)} \\ 572973 &:= 5! \times 7! - C(2 \times 9, 7) - 3 \\ 572976 &:= 5! \times 7! - C(2 \times 9, C(7,6)) \\ 573470 &:= -5 + C(7,3) \times (4^7 + 0!) \\ 573927 &:= (5! - 7) \times (3 + C(9,2) + 7!) \\ 574735 &:= 5 \times C(7,4) + 7! \times (-3! + 5!) \\ 575232 &:= (5! + C(7 + 5, 2)^3) \times 2 \\ 575664 &:= (-5! + C(7 + 5, 6)) \times (6! - 4) \\ 576265 &:= -5 + (7! + C(6,2)) \times (-6 + 5!) \\ 579853 &:= -5 \times 7 + 9! \times 8/5 - 3!! \\ 587657 &:= (5 \times 8! - 7^{C(6,5)}) \times 7 \\ 588365 &:= 5! + (C(8,8) + 3!)^6 \times 5 \\ 589771 &:= (5 + 8) \times (9 \times 7! + C(7,1)) \\ 592697 &:= (5! - C(9,2))^{-6+9} - 7 \\ 592704 &:= (5! - C(9,2))^{7-04} \\ 593303 &:= -5! + C(9,3)^3 - 0! + 3!! \\ 593304 &:= -5! + C(9,3)^3 + (-0! + 4)!! \\ 593784 &:= 5! \times (-C(9,3) + 7! - 8) + 4! \\ 594175 &:= -C((-5 + 9)!, 4) + 1 + 7! \times 5! \\ 594360 &:= (C((-5 + 9)!, 4) - 3!!) \times 60 \\ 594473 &:= (-5 + C(9,4)) \times (4! - 7)^3 \\ 595053 &:= (5 + 9) \times C((5 - 0!)!, 5) - 3 \\ 595056 &:= C((-5 + 9)!, 5 - 0!) \times 56 \\ 595584 &:= (-C(5 \times (9 - 5), 5) + 8!) \times 4! \\ 595776 &:= C((-5 + 9)!, 5) \times (7 + 7) + 6! \\ 596165 &:= 5 + 9! + C(6,1)^6 \times 5 \\ 596295 &:= 5 \times (9!/6! + C(29,5)) \\ 596757 &:= -C(5 + 9, 6) + 7! \times 5! - 7! \\ 597594 &:= (-59 + 7!) \times 5! - C(9,4) \\ 598320 &:= (5! - C(9,8) + 3!!) \times (2 + 0!)!! \\ 599165 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times ((1 + 6)! - 5) \\ 599522 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times ((5 + 2)! - 2) \\ 599527 &:= 5 + (-C(9,9) + 5!) \times (-2 + 7!) \\ 599697 &:= ((5! - C(9,9)) \times 6! - 9) \times 7 \\ 599730 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! - 30 \\ 599733 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! - 3^3 \\ 599744 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! - 4 \times 4 \\ 599748 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! - 4 - 8 \\ 599773 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! + 7 + 3! \\ 599784 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times 7! + (8 - 4)! \\ 599879 &:= (5! - C(9,9)) \times (-8 + 7! + 9) \\ 603840 &:= (6! \times (0! + 3!) - 8) \times (4 + 0!)! \\ 603875 &:= C(6 + 0!, 3) + (-8 + 7!) \times 5! \\ 604674 &:= 6 \times (C(-0! + 4!, 6) - 7 \times 4!) \\ 604715 &:= C(6 + 0!, 4) + (7! - 1) \times 5! \\ 604791 &:= (6 - 0!) \times 4! \times 7! - C(9,1) \\ 604799 &:= (6 - 0!) \times 4! \times 7! - C(9,9) \\ 604935 &:= C(6, 04) \times (9 + (3 + 5)!) \\ 605394 &:= (6 + 0!)! \times 5! + 3!! - C(9,4) \\ 606403 &:= 6! + 0! + 6 \times C(4! - 0!, 3!) \\ 607543 &:= 6! - 0! + 7! \times 5! + C(4!, 3) \\ 614824 &:= (6 + 1) \times 4! + C(8,2)^4 \\ 615426 &:= (6 + 1)! \times 5! + C(4!, -2 + 6) \\ 617176 &:= (6 - 1)! \times 7! + C(17,6) \\ 619272 &:= 61 \times (C(9,2) + 7!) \times 2 \\ 622083 &:= 6!^2/2 + (0! + 8)! + 3 \\ 622944 &:= (6! + C(2,2)) \times 9 \times 4! \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 624468 &:= 6 \times (2 + C(4!, 4) \times 6 - 8!) \\ 624573 &:= -C(6, 2) + (4 + 5!) \times (7! - 3) \\ 624904 &:= -6 + C(2 + 4!, 9) / (0! + 4) \\ 624916 &:= 6 + C(2 + 4!, 9) / (-1 + 6) \\ 627234 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - 3! - 4! \\ 627253 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - 5 - 3! \\ 627258 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - (-5 + 8!) \\ 627263 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - C(6, 3!) \\ 627270 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 + 7 - 0! \\ 633604 &:= (C(6 + 3!, 3) \times 6! + 0!) \times 4 \\ 634194 &:= (-6! + (3 + 4)! - 1) \times C(9, 4) \\ 634794 &:= (6! + 3) \times (-4 + 7 \times C(9, 4)) \\ 634872 &:= (6 \times (3 + 4)! - 8) \times C(7, 2) \\ 635292 &:= C(6 + 3, 5) \times (2 + (9 - 2)!) \\ 635670 &:= C(6 + 3, 5) \times (6 + 7! - 0!) \\ 635760 &:= C(6 + 3, 5) \times 7! + (6 + 0!) \\ 635775 &:= (6! \times 3! + 5) \times 7 \times C(7, 5) \\ 635795 &:= 6! + 35 + 7! \times C(9, 5) \\ 635796 &:= C(6 + 3, 5) \times (7! + (9 - 6)!) \\ 635976 &:= (6! + 3!) \times (5! + C(9, 7) + 6!) \\ 636475 &:= C(6, 3) \times C(-6 + 4!, 7) - 5 \\ 636480 &:= C(6, 3) \times C(-6 + 4!, 8 - 0!) \\ 637455 &:= (6 - 3) \times (-7 + C(4!, 5)) \times 5 \\ 637545 &:= 6 + 3 \times (-7 + 5 \times C(4!, 5)) \\ 637560 &:= (C(6, 3) + 7!) \times (5! + 6 + 0) \\ 637947 &:= 6! + 3^7 + C(9, 4) \times 7! \\ 639363 &:= 6! \times 3!! + 9! / 3 + 6 - 3 \\ 642096 &:= 6^{C(4, 2) + 0!} + 9! - 6! \\ 643816 &:= 6! - C(4!, 3) + 8! \times 16 \\ 643824 &:= -6^{C(4, 3)} + 8! \times 2^4 \\ 643836 &:= -6 \times (C(4!, 3!) - (8! - 3) \times 6) \\ 643942 &:= -6 \times C(4!, 3!) + 9! \times 4 - 2 \\ 644816 &:= (-C(6, 4) - 4 + 8!) \times 16 \\ 644832 &:= (-6 \times 4! + 4! \times 8! / 3) \times 2 \\ 645873 &:= -C(6, 4) + (5! + 8) \times (7! + 3!) \\ 646284 &:= 6 \times (C(4!, 6) - 2) - 8! \times 4 \\ 647366 &:= 6! + C(4 \times 7 - 3!, 6 + 6) \\ 648350 &:= (-6! + C(4!, 8) - 3!! \times 5! - 0!) \\ 648351 &:= C(6 \times 4, 8) - 3!! \times (5! + 1) \\ 649065 &:= -6 + (C(4!, 9 - 0!) - 6! \times 5!) \\ 653092 &:= -6! + (5! + C((3 + 0!)!, 9)) / 2 \\ 653392 &:= (-6! + C((5 + 3) \times 3, 9)) / 2 \\ 653400 &:= 6 \times C(5 + 3!, 4)^{0! + 0!} \\ 653424 &:= 6 \times (C(5 + 3!, 4)^2 + 4) \\ 653904 &:= 6! + (C(5, 3)! - 9!) / (0! + 4) \\ 654336 &:= 6! / 5 \times C(4!, 3) + (3 + 6)! \\ 654339 &:= 6! / 5 \times C(4!, 3) + 3 + 9! \\ 654352 &:= 6! - 5! + C(4!, 3 \times 5) / 2 \\ 654492 &:= 6! + 5 \times 4 + C(4!, 9) / 2 \\ 654532 &:= 6! + (5! + C(4!, 5 \times 3)) / 2 \\ 654696 &:= (6^5 + 4! - 6) \times C(9, 6) \\ 655206 &:= 6 + (5! + C(5, 2)) \times (0! + 6)! \\ 655207 &:= (6! \times (5! + C(5, 2)) + 0!) \times 7 \\ 655492 &:= (6! \times 5 - 5! + C(4!, 9)) / 2 \\ 656596 &:= (6! + 5) \times 6! + C((-5 + 9)!, 6) \\ 656928 &:= ((-6 + 5!) \times 6! + C(9, 2)) \times 8 \\ 662895 &:= C((6 + 6) \times 2, 8) - 9! / 5 \\ 663126 &:= 6 + 6! \times (-3 + C(12, 6)) \\ 663432 &:= C(6 + 6, 3!) \times (-4 + 3!! + 2) \\ 664632 &:= (6! \times 6 + 4!) \times C(6 \times 3, 2) \\ 664752 &:= (6 + 6)! \times (-4 + 7!) / C(5, 2)! \\ 665196 &:= (6! \times (6 + 5) - 1) \times C(9, 6) \\ 665267 &:= -6 + (C(6, 5) \times 2)! / 6! - 7 \\ 665273 &:= (6 + 6)! / (5 - 2)!! - C(7, 3!) \\ 665279 &:= -C(6, 6) + 5! / 2 \times 7! + 9! \\ 665352 &:= (6! + (6 + 5)! / 3!) / C(5, 2) \\ 665862 &:= 6 + ((6! / 5 - 8) \times 6)^2 \\ 666925 &:= (6! + C(6, 6)) \times 925 \\ 673735 &:= 6! + (7 + C((-3 + 7)!, 3!)) \times 5 \\ 673944 &:= (-6! + 7!) \times 39 \times 4 + 4! \\ 675354 &:= -6 + 7! \times (5^3 + 5 + 4) \\ 675738 &:= 6 \times C(7, 5) \times (7! + 3) + 8! \\ 679344 &:= -6! + (-7 + 9)^{3!} \times C(4!, 4) \\ 679995 &:= (6 + 7! - 9) \times (9 + C(9, 5)) \\ 682248 &:= 68 \times C((2 + 2)!, 4) - 8! \\ 683472 &:= -(6! + 8) \times 3! + C(4!, 7)) \times 2 \\ 684672 &:= -6! - 8! + 4! \times (6 \times 7! - 2) \\ 685389 &:= (6! \times C(8, 5) - 3) \times (8 + 9) \\ 685434 &:= -6 + 8! \times (C(5, 4) + 3 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 685542 &:= (6 + 8!) \times (C(5,5) + 4^2) \\ 686154 &:= (6! \times 8 + 6) \times (-1 + C(5,4)!) \\ 686262 &:= 6! + (8! + 6) \times (2 + C(6,2)) \\ 691472 &:= -6! + (-9 + 1 + C(4!,7)) \times 2 \\ 692784 &:= -6^{9-2} + 7! + 8! \times 4! \\ 695871 &:= 6! + C((9-5)!,8) - (7+1)! \\ 695878 &:= 6! + C((9-5)!,8) + 7 - 8! \\ 699835 &:= 6 \times 9! \times 9 / C(8,3!) - 5 \\ 699864 &:= 6 \times 9! \times 9 / C(8,6) + 4! \\ 703947 &:= -7! + 03 + 9! + C(4!,7) \\ 704492 &:= (-7 - 0! - C(4!,4) + 9!) \times 2 \\ 705432 &:= C(C(7,05),4 + 3!) \times 2 \\ 707274 &:= -7 + (0! + C(7,2) + 7)^4 \\ 715792 &:= (C(7+1,5) - 7! + 9!) \times 2 \\ 715822 &:= (7! + 1) \times (5 \times C(8,2) + 2) \\ 715964 &:= 71 \times (5! \times C(9,6) + 4) \\ 720348 &:= -(7! + (2 \times 0)!) \times 3 + C(4!,8) \\ 720852 &:= (C(7,2) + 0!) \times (8^5 - 2) \\ 723499 &:= -C(C(7,2),3!) / 4! + 9! + 9! \\ 723751 &:= 7 + (-2 + 3!!) \times 7! / C(5,1) \\ 724185 &:= C(C(7,2),4) \times (1^8 + 5!) \\ 724292 &:= (-7 \times 2 - C(4,2)! + 9!) \times 2 \\ 724587 &:= -C(7,2) + (4! + 5!) \times (-8 + 7!) \\ 724759 &:= -C(7 \times 2,4) + (7 - 5) \times 9! \\ 724773 &:= C(7,2) - 4! \times (7 - 7!) \times 3! \\ 725253 &:= (-7! / 2 + C(5,2)!) / 5 - 3 \\ 725274 &:= (-C(7,2) + 5!)^2 \times 74 \\ 725472 &:= (7! - 2) \times (C(5,4) + 7)^2 \\ 725492 &:= (-7 \times 2 - C(5,4)! + 9!) \times 2 \\ 725639 &:= (7 + 2)! - 5! - C(6,3!) + 9! \\ 725734 &:= -C(7,2) - 5 + 7! \times 3! \times 4! \\ 725739 &:= -C(7,2) + (5 + 7 - 3)! + 9! \\ 725770 &:= ((7 + 2)! + 5) \times (C(7,7) + 0!) \\ 725778 &:= (-7 + 25) \times (C(7,7) + 8!) \\ 725781 &:= C(7,2) + (-5 + 7) \times (8 + 1)! \\ 725791 &:= 7 + 2 \times (5 + 7 + C(9,1)!) \\ 725793 &:= C(7,2) + (-5 + 7) \times (9! + 3!) \\ 725812 &:= (C(7,2) + 5 + (8 + 1)!) \times 2 \\ 725886 &:= (C(7,2) + (-5 + 8) \times 8!) \times 6 \\ 725892 &:= (C(7,2) + (5 + 8!) \times 9) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725901 &:= C(7,2) + 5! + 9! \times (0! + 1) \\ 725972 &:= (-C(7,2) + 5! + 9! + 7) \times 2 \\ 725979 &:= -C(7,2) + (5! + 9!) \times (-7 + 9) \\ 725982 &:= (-7 - 2 + 5! + C(9,8)!) \times 2 \\ 725989 &:= 7 + 2 \times (5! - C(9,8) + 9!) \\ 725995 &:= (7 - 2)! - 5 + 9! + 9! + 5! \\ 725998 &:= 7 + 2 \times (5! + 9!) - C(9,8) \\ 726459 &:= -C(7,2) + 6! + (4 + 5)! + 9! \\ 726529 &:= 7^2 + C(6,5)! + 2 \times 9! \\ 726594 &:= C(C(7,2) + 6,5) \times 9 + 4! \\ 726768 &:= C(7,2) \times (6 + 7! - 6!) \times 8 \\ 726894 &:= (-7 + (2 + 6!) \times 8) \times C(9,4) \\ 727272 &:= (7! \times 2 + C(7,2)) \times 72 \\ 728392 &:= 7! / 2 + (C(8,3) + 9!) \times 2 \\ 729342 &:= 7! + 2 \times (9! - 3^{C(4,2)}) \\ 729900 &:= 7! + 2 \times 9! - 900 \\ 730407 &:= -7! - (3 + 0!)! + C(4!,0! + 7) \\ 730424 &:= -7! - 3! - 0! + C(4!,2 \times 4) \\ 730426 &:= -7! - 3! + 0! + C(4!,2 + 6) \\ 730428 &:= -7! - 3 + C(04!,2 \times 8) \\ 730430 &:= -7! + C((3 + 0!)!,4! / 3) - 0! \\ 730431 &:= -7! + C((3 + 0!)!,4 + 3 + 1) \\ 730432 &:= -7! + (3 \times 0)! + C(4!,3! + 2) \\ 730435 &:= -7! + 3 + 0! + C(4!,3 + 5) \\ 730437 &:= -7! + 3! + C(4!,(0 \times 3)! + 7) \\ 730438 &:= -7! + 3! + 0! + C(C(4,3)!,8) \\ 730448 &:= -7! - 3! - 0! + 4! + C(4!,8) \\ 730548 &:= -7! - 3 + 05! + C(4!,8) \\ 732528 &:= C((7 - 3)!,2 + 5) \times 2 + 8! \\ 732953 &:= -C(7,3!) + 2 \times (9! + 5 \times 3!!) \\ 733318 &:= 7 - 3!! \times 3 + C((3 + 1)!,8) \\ 733448 &:= -7 - 3!! - 3!^4 + C(4!,8) \\ 733548 &:= -7! / 3 - 3^5 + C(4!,8) \\ 733748 &:= -C(7 + 3!,3!) - 7 + C(4!,8) \\ 733791 &:= -7! / 3 + C((-3 + 7)!,9 - 1) \\ 734392 &:= 7! - 3!! + (-C(4,3) + 9!) \times 2 \\ 734631 &:= -7! / 3! + C(4!,6 + 3 - 1) \\ 734716 &:= -C(7,3) + C(4!,7 + 1) - 6! \\ 734744 &:= -7 - 3!! + C(4!,7 + C(4,4)) \\ 734748 &:= (-7! + 3 - 4!) / 7 + C(4!,8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 734758 &:= 7 - 3!! + C(4!, (7 - 5) \times 8) \\
 734793 &:= 7 \times 3! + C(4!, 7 + 9) - 3!! \\
 734824 &:= 73 + C(4!, 8) - (2 + 4)! \\
 734826 &:= 73 + C(4!, 8) + 2 - 6! \\
 734848 &:= -7 \times (3^4 + 8) + C(4!, 8) \\
 734854 &:= 7 - 3!! + C(4!, 8) + 5! - 4! \\
 734857 &:= -7 - 3!! + C(4!, 8) + 5! - 7 \\
 735128 &:= -7^3 + C((5 - 1)!, 2 \times 8) \\
 735248 &:= -7^3 + 5! + C(24, 8) \\
 735348 &:= -7! \times 3/5! + 3 + C(4!, 8) \\
 735350 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 5 + 3) - 5! - 0! \\
 735351 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 5 + 3) - C(5, 1)! \\
 735423 &:= -(7! + 3!!)/5! + C(4!, 2^3) \\
 735424 &:= 73 - 5! + C(4!, 2 \times 4) \\
 735435 &:= (-7! + 3!!)/5! + C(4!, 3 + 5) \\
 735442 &:= -(7 - 3)! + 5 + C(4!, 4 \times 2) \\
 735443 &:= 7 - 35 + C(4!, 4!/3) \\
 735448 &:= -7 + 3 - 5 - 4! + C(4!, 8) \\
 735453 &:= -7 - 3! - 5 + C(4!, 5 + 3) \\
 735458 &:= -7 - 3! + C((5 + 4 - 5)!, 8) \\
 735462 &:= -7 + 3 - 5 + C(4!, 6 + 2) \\
 735470 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 5 - 4 + 7) - 0! \\
 735479 &:= -7 + 3 \times 5 + C(4!, 7 + 9) \\
 735480 &:= -7 + 3 \times 5 + C(4!, 8) + 0! \\
 735490 &:= (7 - 3)! - 5 + C(4!, 9 - 0!) \\
 735491 &:= (7 - 3) \times 5 + C(4!, 9 - 1) \\
 735497 &:= 7 \times 3 + 5 + C(4!, 9 + 7) \\
 735508 &:= 7 \times 3! - 5 + C((5 - 0)!, 8) \\
 735518 &:= -73 + 5! + C((5 - 1)!, 8) \\
 735544 &:= 73 + C(5!/5, 4 + 4) \\
 735548 &:= 7 \times (C(3!, 5) + 5) + C(4!, 8) \\
 735598 &:= C(7, 3!) + 5! + C((-5 + 9)!, 8) \\
 735693 &:= -(C(7, 3)/5)^6 + 9! \times 3 \\
 735835 &:= 7! \times (3! + 5 \times C(8, 3!)) - 5 \\
 735838 &:= 7 + 3 \times 5! + C(8 \times 3, 8) \\
 735864 &:= 7! \times (3! + 5 \times C(8, 6)) + 4! \\
 736148 &:= -7 \times 3! + 6! - 1 + C(4!, 8) \\
 736198 &:= 7 + 3!! + C((-6 + 1 + 9)!, 8) \\
 737143 &:= C(7, 3!)^7 - (1 + 4)! \times 3!! \\
 737158 &:= 7!/3 + 7 + C((-1 + 5)!, 8) \\
 737273 &:= -7 + (3!! + 7!) \times 2^{C(7, 3!)} \\
 737394 &:= 7 \times 3! \times (7 + C(3 \times 9, 4)) \\
 737424 &:= 7! + (3! \times 7! + C(4!, 2)) \times 4! \\
 738345 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 8) - 3! + 4! \times 5! \\
 738351 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 8) + 3!! \times (5 - 1) \\
 738354 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 8) + 3 + 5! \times 4! \\
 738495 &:= C((7 - 3)!, 8) + 4! \times C(9, 5) \\
 738773 &:= C(7, 3!) \times 8! + 77^3 \\
 740471 &:= 7! - 40 + C(4!, 7 + 1) \\
 740483 &:= 7! - 4! - 0! + C(4!, 8) - 3 \\
 740484 &:= 7! - 4! + 0! + C(4!, 8) - 4 \\
 740487 &:= 7! - 4! + C(04!, C(8, 7)) \\
 740488 &:= 7! - 4! + 0! + C(4!, 8 + 8) \\
 740507 &:= 7! - 4 + C((-0! + 5)!, 0! + 7) \\
 740508 &:= 7! - 4 + 0! + C((5 - 0)!, 8) \\
 740511 &:= 7! + C(4!, 05 + 11) \\
 740535 &:= 7! + 4! + C((-0! + 5)!, 3 + 5) \\
 744492 &:= (-7!/4 + C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 2 \\
 744855 &:= -7! + 4! + C(4!, 8) + 5! \times 5! \\
 744870 &:= (7 + C(4!, 4) + 8) \times 70 \\
 745440 &:= (C(-7 + 4!, 5) + 4!) \times (4 + 0!)! \\
 745794 &:= (7 \times 4 + 5!) \times 7! - C(9, 4) \\
 746448 &:= 74 \times (6 + C(4!, 4)) + 8! \\
 746847 &:= 7! + C(4!, 8) + 6^4 + 7! \\
 747936 &:= 7 \times 4! \times 7 \times (-C(9, 3) + 6!) \\
 752381 &:= (-C(7, 5) + 2) \times (3!! - 8! + 1) \\
 752435 &:= (7 + C(5, 2)!/4! - 3!!) \times 5 \\
 753375 &:= (7! + C(5 \times 3, 3!)) \times 75 \\
 753473 &:= -7 + (5 - 3) \times C(4 \times 7, 3!) \\
 754443 &:= (75 - 4) \times C(4!, 4) - 3 \\
 754446 &:= (75 - 4) \times C(4!, 4!/6) \\
 756050 &:= (C(7, 5) \times 6! + 0!) \times 50 \\
 756243 &:= (7^5 \times C(6, 2) - 4!) \times 3 \\
 756435 &:= 7^5 \times C(6, 4) \times 3 + 5! \\
 756504 &:= C(7, 5) \times (6! \times 50 + 4!) \\
 757318 &:= 7^5 + 7! + C((3 + 1)!, 8) \\
 759254 &:= (7^5 + 9!) \times 2 - C(5, 4)! \\
 759255 &:= ((C(7, 5) + 9)/2)^5 - 5! \\
 759345 &:= -C(7, 5) - 9 + C(3!, 4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 759354 &:= -C(7,5) + (9+3!)^{C(5,4)} \\ 764345 &:= -7 - 6! + (4! - 3!) \times C(4!,5) \\ 764415 &:= 7! + C(6,4)^4 \times 15 \\ 765135 &:= 7! + 6! + (C(5,1) \times 3)^5 \\ 765144 &:= (7 + 65) \times (1 + C(4!,4)) \\ 765346 &:= (7! + 6) \times 5^3 + C(4!,6) \\ 765748 &:= 7 + 6 \times (5 + 7!) + C(4!,8) \\ 770413 &:= 7^7 - C(0! + 4!, -1 + 3!) \\ 772539 &:= -7! - C(7,2) + 5! \times 3!! \times 9 \\ 772847 &:= -C(7,7) + 2 \times (8! + C(4!,7)) \\ 777336 &:= (-7! + C((C(7,7) + 3)!, 3!)) \times 6 \\ 777595 &:= (7 - C(7,7))! \times 5! \times 9 - 5 \\ 781383 &:= -7! - 8 - 1 + 3 \times 8^{3!} \\ 781584 &:= -7! + (C(8,1)^5 + 8) \times 4! \\ 782376 &:= 7! + (C((8/2)!, 3!) - 7!) \times 6 \\ 786235 &:= (7! \times (C(8,6) - 2)) \times 3! - 5 \\ 786264 &:= 7! \times (C(8,6) - 2) \times 6 + 4! \\ 787536 &:= (-7! + 8!) \times C(7,5) + 3!^6 \\ 796320 &:= 79 \times 6! \times (C(3!,2) - 0!) \\ 799695 &:= (7 + C(9,9))! + (6 + 9)^5 \\ 806340 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - 40 \\ 806348 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - 4 \times 8 \\ 806350 &:= 8! \times C(06,3) - 50 \\ 806355 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - 5 \times 5 \\ 806360 &:= (8! + 0!) \times C(6,3) - 60 \\ 806367 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - 6 - 7 \\ 806373 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - C(7,3!) \\ 806374 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) - (7 - 4)! \\ 806380 &:= (8! - 0!) \times (C(6,3) + 8 \times 0) \\ 806384 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) + 8 - 4 \\ 806386 &:= 8! \times C(06,3) - 8 - 6 \\ 806390 &:= (8! - 0!) \times C(6,3) + 9 + 0! \\ 806391 &:= 8! \times C(06,3) - C(9,1) \\ 806393 &:= (8! + 0!) \times C(6,3) - 9 \times 3 \\ 806399 &:= 8! \times C(06,3) - C(9,9) \\ 806431 &:= 8! \times (-0! + 6) \times 4 + 31 \\ 806520 &:= (8! + C(06,5)) \times 20 \\ 806543 &:= (8! + 0! + 6) \times 5 \times 4 + 3 \\ 806589 &:= -8! + C(0! + 6,5) \times (8! + 9) \\ 807520 &:= (8! + C(0! + 7,5)) \times 20 \\ 807546 &:= (-8 \times 0! + 7) \times (-5 + C(4!,6)) \\ 807576 &:= 8 \times C((-0! + 7) \times 5 - 7,6) \\ 818244 &:= 8! + C(-1 + 8,2)^4 \times 4 \\ 823488 &:= 8^2 \times (-3 + C(4! - 8,8)) \\ 823547 &:= 8/2 + (3! + 5 - 4)^7 \\ 823675 &:= C(8 \times 2,3!) \times 6!/7 - 5 \\ 823680 &:= C(8 \times 2,3!) \times 6!/(8 - 0!) \\ 827298 &:= 82 \times (7! \times 2 + C(9,8)) \\ 827736 &:= C(8,2) \times ((7! + 7) \times 3! - 6!) \\ 827872 &:= 82 \times (7! + C(8,7)) \times 2 \\ 828928 &:= 8^2 \times (9!/C(8,2) - 8) \\ 830775 &:= C(8 + 3,0! + 7) \times (7! - 5) \\ 831600 &:= (8! - 3!!) \times C(1 + 6,0! + 0!) \\ 831624 &:= (8! - 3!!) \times C(1 + 6,2) + 4! \\ 833084 &:= -C(8 \times 3,3!) + 08! \times 4! \\ 833472 &:= (8! + 3!^{3!}) \times (-4 + C(7,2)) \\ 833476 &:= (8 + C(3,3))! + 4 \times 7^6 \\ 834834 &:= C(8 + 3!,4) \times 834 \\ 836640 &:= 83 \times 6! \times (C(6,4) - 0!) \\ 836864 &:= 8! \times 36 - C(8,6)^4 \\ 841344 &:= (8! + C(4!, -1 + 3!) \times 4) \times 4 \\ 843483 &:= 8! \times (4! + 3) - C(4!,8)/3 \\ 843696 &:= (8!/4! - 3!) \times 6 \times C(9,6) \\ 844480 &:= (-C(8,4) + C(4!,4)) \times 80 \\ 844872 &:= (-84 - 4 + 8!) \times C(7,2) \\ 845728 &:= -8 \times (4 + 5!) + C(7,2) \times 8! \\ 845775 &:= (8! - 45) \times C(7,7 - 5) \\ 845952 &:= (8! + C(4!,5) \times 9 + 5!) \times 2 \\ 846216 &:= (8! - 4!) \times (C(C(6,2),1) + 6) \\ 846342 &:= (8! - 4! + 6) \times C(3 + 4,2) \\ 846400 &:= (C(8 + 4,6) - 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 846424 &:= (C(8 + 4,6) - 4)^2 + 4! \\ 846576 &:= (8! - 4!) \times 6 + 5! \times C(7,6)! \\ 846594 &:= ((8! + 4!)/6 - 5) \times C(9,4) \\ 846628 &:= (8! - 4) \times (6 + C(6,2)) - 8 \\ 846672 &:= (8! - 4) \times (6 + 6) + (7 + 2)! \\ 846712 &:= -8 + 4! \times 6! \times C(7,1)^2 \\ 846756 &:= (8! - 4 + 6) \times C(7,5) - 6 \\ 846758 &:= 8 \times 4 + 6 + C(7,5) \times 8! \end{aligned}$$

- 846762** := $(8! - 4 + 6) \times C(C(7,6), 2)$
846776 := $(8 + 4 \times 6 \times 7!) \times C(7,6)$
846864 := $(8! + 4!) \times 6 + 8! \times C(6,4)$
846872 := $8 + 4! \times 6 + 8! \times C(7,2)$
846972 := $(8! + 4 \times (-6 + 9)) \times C(7,2)$
847212 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) - 12$
847217 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) - 1 \times 7$
847221 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) - 2 - 1$
847223 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) + 2 - 3$
847248 := $(8 - 4)! + C(7,2) \times (4! + 8!)$
847254 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) + 5!/4$
847288 := $(8! + 4!) \times C(7,2) + 8 \times 8$
847371 := $(8! + 4! + 7) \times C(3 \times 7, 1)$
847524 := $(8! + 4) \times C(7,5) + (2 + 4)!$
847526 := $(8! + 4) \times C(7,5) + 2 + 6!$
847533 := $(8! + 4) \times C(7,5) + 3^3!$
847872 := $8 \times (-4! + (7! + 8) \times C(7,2))$
847875 := $(8 + 47 + 8!) \times C(7,5)$
847896 := $8! + C(4!, 7 + 8 - 9) \times 6$
848214 := $(C(8,4) + 8!) \times 21 + 4!$
853776 := $C(8,5) \times 3 \times (7! + 7 \times 6)$
854784 := $(8!/C(5,4)! - 7! + 8!) \times 4!$
859435 := $85 \times (-9 + C(4!, 3) \times 5)$
861840 := $(8! + 6!) \times (18 + 4 - 0!)$
862848 := $(-8!/C(6,2) + 8!) \times 4! - 8!$
863379 := $(C(8,6) \times 3! + 3) \times (7! + 9)$
864020 := $(8! + 6! \times 4 - 0!) \times 20$
864864 := $C(8 + 6, 4) \times 864$
865872 := $(8! + (-6 + 5!) \times 8) \times C(7,2)$
866376 := $C(8,6) \times (6! + (-3 + 7!) \times 6)$
874615 := $(8! + 7 + C(4!, 6)) \times 1 \times 5$
874625 := $(8! + 7 + C(4!, 6) + 2) \times 5$
876568 := $(C(8,6) + 5^6) \times 7 \times 8$
876728 := $(-8 + 7! \times 6) \times (C(7,2) + 8)$
878352 := $(8 + 7!) \times (C(8,3) + 5! - 2)$
886320 := $8! \times (C(8,6) - 3!) - (2 + 0!)!!$
886422 := $(8! - C(8,6)) \times (4! - 2) - 2$
886424 := $(8! - C(8,6)) \times (4! + 2 - 4)$
886578 := $(8! - C(7,5)) \times (6 + 8 + 8)$
886862 := $(-8 + 8!) \times (-6 + C(8,6)) - 2$
886864 := $(-8 + 8!) \times (-6 + C(8,6 - 4))$
886986 := $8! \times C(8,6) - (9 + 8!) \times 6$
887208 := $(8 + 8!) \times C(7,2) + 08!$
887213 := $(8 + 8!) \times (C(7,2) + 1) - 3$
887523 := $-8! + (8! + C(7,5)) \times 23$
888384 := $-8! - 8! + (C(8,3) + 8!) \times 4!$
892296 := $8 \times C(9 \times 2, 2) \times (9 + 6!)$
894232 := $-8 + 9 \times C(4!, 2) \times 3!!/2$
894329 := $8 + 9^{C(C(4,3), 2)} + 9!$
896544 := $(8! - C(9,6) - 5! \times 4!) \times 4!$
896896 := $(-8! + 9!) \times C(6 + 8, 9)/6!$
897476 := $89 \times (7! + 4) + C(7,6)!$
901264 := $9! + C((0! + 1 + 2)!, 6) \times 4$
901446 := $(90 + 1) \times (C(4!, 4) - 6!)$
902043 := $-9 \times ((0! + 2)!! - C(-0! + 4!, 3!))$
908523 := $9 \times C(-0! + 8 \times (5 - 2), 3!)$
911493 := $(-9^{C(1,1)+4} + 9!) \times 3$
912673 := $(C(9,1 + 2) + 6 + 7)^3$
913474 := $(9 + 1)^{3!} - C(4!, 7)/4$
917273 := $91 \times 7! \times 2 - C(7,3!)$
924939 := $-9! - 2 + C(4!, 9) - 3^9$
925344 := $C(9 \times 2, 5) \times (3 + 4!) \times 4$
925380 := $C(9,2) \times 5^{3!} + (8 + 0!)!$
933036 := $-C(9,3) + 3!^{0!+3} \times 6!$
933204 := $C(9,3) + 3!! \times (2 + 0!)!^4$
936936 := $9! + (-3! + 6!) \times (C(9,3) + 6!)$
937365 := $C(9 \times 3, (7 - 3)! - 6)/5$
937432 := $(93 \times 7! - C(4,3)) \times 2$
937440 := $93 \times 7! \times (C(4,4) + 0!)$
938853 := $9 \times (-3 + 8! + (8 \times 5)^3)$
941782 := $(9! - C(4! - 1, 7)) \times 8 - 2$
942067 := $(-9 + C(4!, (2 + 0!)!)) - 6) \times 7$
942181 := $9 + C(4!, (2 + 1)!) \times (8 - 1)$
943903 := $-9! + C((C(4,3))!, 9) - 0! - 3!!$
943904 := $-9! + C((C(4,3))!, 9) - (-0! + 4)!!$
944049 := $-9! - 4! \times 4! + 0! + C(4!, 9)$
944504 := $-9! + C(4!, 4 + 5) - (0! + 4)!$
944505 := $-9! + C(4!, 4 + 5) + 0! - 5!$
944562 := $-9! + C(4!, 4 + 5) - 62$

$$\begin{aligned} 944600 &:= -9! - 4! + C(4!, C(6, 0! + 0!)) \\ 944617 &:= -9! + C(4!, 4 + 6 - 1) - 7 \\ 944639 &:= -9 + 4! + C(4!, 6 + 3) - 9! \\ 944644 &:= -9! - 4 + C(4!, C(6, 4)) + 4! \\ 944648 &:= -9! + 4! + C(4!, 6!/48) \\ 944742 &:= (9^4 \times 4! - 7) \times C(4, 2) \\ 945337 &:= -9! + C(4!, 5 \times 3) + 3!! - 7 \\ 945344 &:= -9! + C(4!, 5 \times 3) + (4!/4)! \\ 947520 &:= C(9, 4) \times 7520 \\ 948384 &:= (-C(9, 4) + 8) \times 3! + 8! \times 4! \\ 948393 &:= 9 - 4! \times (-8! + 3!! + C(9, 3)) \\ 949629 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + C(C(6, 2), 9) \\ 949737 &:= -9! + C(4!, 9) + 73 + 7! \\ 952371 &:= C(9, 5)/2 \times 3 \times (7! - 1) \\ 952497 &:= ((-9! + C(5, 2)!)/4! - 9) \times 7 \\ 952560 &:= C(9, 5)^2 \times (5! - 60) \\ 952584 &:= 9! \times C(5 + 2, 5)/8 + 4! \\ 953424 &:= (C(9, 5) - 3!! + (4 \times 2)!) \times 4! \\ 953748 &:= 9 \times (5! - 3 \times (7! - 4 - 8!)) \\ 954954 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 954 \\ 957054 &:= 9! + 5! \times 7! - C((-0! + 5)!, 4) \\ 957600 &:= C(9, 5) \times 7600 \\ 957624 &:= 95 \times C(7, 6)! \times 2 + 4! \\ 959283 &:= (-9 + C((-5 + 9)! - 2, 8)) \times 3 \\ 962675 &:= 9! - C(C(6, 2), 6) + 7! \times 5! \\ 962684 &:= 9 - C(C(6, 2), 6) + 8! \times 4! \\ 962784 &:= (-C(9, 6) - (-2 + 7)! + 8!) \times 4! \\ 963738 &:= (9 + 6!) \times (C(3 \times 7, 3) - 8) \\ 964584 &:= (-C(9, 6) + 45 + 8!) \times 4! \\ 965664 &:= (-C(9, 6) + 56 \times 6!) \times 4! \\ 966672 &:= C(9, 6) \times (6! - 6 + 7!) \times 2 \\ 966884 &:= -C(9, 6) - 6! + 8 + 8! \times 4! \\ 967320 &:= 9! + 6 \times (7! - 3) \times 20 \\ 967548 &:= -C(9, 6)/7 - 5! + 4! \times 8! \\ 967596 &:= 9! + 6! \times 7 \times 5! - C(9, 6) \\ 967644 &:= (-9 + 6! \times 7!/C(6, 4)) \times 4 \\ 967683 &:= (9! - 6 + C(7, 6) - 8!) \times 3 \\ 967696 &:= (9! + 6) \times (C(7, 6) + 9)/6 \\ 967722 &:= (96 \times 7! + C(7, 2)) \times 2 \\ 967728 &:= (9 - 6 + C(7, 7))! \times (2 + 8!) \\ 967764 &:= C(9, 6) + (7 + 7 - 6)! \times 4! \\ 967884 &:= C(9, 6)/7 + (8 + 8!) \times 4! \\ 968316 &:= -C(9, 6) + 8! \times (3 + 1)! + 6! \\ 968493 &:= C(9, 6) + 8! \times 4! + 9^3 \\ 968542 &:= (-C(9, 6) + 8! + 5!) \times 4! - 2 \\ 968544 &:= (-C(9, 6) + 8! + C(5, 4)!) \times 4! \\ 968784 &:= (9 \times 6 - C(8, 7) + 8!) \times 4! \\ 968841 &:= 9 + (6 \times 8 + 8!) \times C(4, 1)! \\ 972414 &:= 9 + C(7, 2)^4 \times (1 + 4) \\ 972435 &:= (9 + (C(7, 2)^4 - 3)) \times 5 \\ 972495 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 + 9) \times 5 \\ 973584 &:= (C(9, 7 - 3) + 5! + 8!) \times 4! \\ 976256 &:= C(9 + 7, 6) \times (2 + 5!) - 6! \\ 976284 &:= -C(9, 7) + (6!/2 + 8!) \times 4! \\ 977443 &:= -9 + 7 \times (7! + C(4!, 4! - 3!)) \\ 977460 &:= 9 + 7 \times (7! + C(4!, 6)) - 0! \\ 977461 &:= 9 + 7 \times (7! + C(4!, 6)) \times 1 \\ 978384 &:= (-9 + C(7 + 8, 3) + 8!) \times 4! \\ 982737 &:= (-9 + C(8, 2) \times 7! - 3!!) \times 7 \\ 983432 &:= (9! - 8 \times 3!! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2 \\ 983682 &:= (C(9, 8)^{3!} + 6! - 8!) \times 2 \\ 984150 &:= C(9, 8)^4 \times 150 \\ 984834 &:= -C(C(9, 8), 4) + (8! + 3!!) \times 4! \\ 984922 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 22 \\ 984928 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 2 \times 8 \\ 984932 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 3! \times 2 \\ 984934 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) - 3! - 4 \\ 984937 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9 + 3!) - 7 \\ 984938 &:= -9 \times 8! + C(4!, 9) - 3! + 8! \\ 984950 &:= -9! + 8! + C(4!, 9) + 5 + 0! \\ 987469 &:= 9!/8 + 7 \times (C(4!, 6) - 9) \\ 987830 &:= -9 + (8! - 7!) \times C(8, 3!) - 0! \\ 987831 &:= -9 + (8! - 7!) \times C(8, 3 - 1) \\ 995328 &:= 9 \times (9 - 5)!^{C(3, 2)} \times 8 \\ 997623 &:= 99 \times C(7, 6)! \times 2 + 3 \\ 997794 &:= 99 \times (7! + 7!) - C(9, 4) \\ 997920 &:= (9 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 2 + 0) \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with square-root**. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.3.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 697680 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 0 \\ 697681 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 1 \\ 697682 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 2 \\ 697683 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 3 \\ 697684 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 4 \\ 697685 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 5 \\ 697686 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 6 \\ 697687 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 7 \\ 697688 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 8 \\ 697689 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6 + 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 629850 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 0 \\ 629851 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 1 \\ 629852 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 2 \\ 629853 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 3 \\ 629854 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 4 \\ 629855 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 5 \\ 629856 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 6 \\ 629857 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 7 \\ 629858 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 8 \\ 629859 &:= C(C(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}), 8) \times 5 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

2.3.2 Non Symmetrical Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 12397 &:= C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 7 \\ 13728 &:= C(13, \sqrt{7^2}) \times 8 \\ 15625 &:= 1 \times 5^{C(6, \sqrt{25})} \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) \\ 20995 &:= C(20, 9) / (\sqrt{9} + 5) \\ 23398 &:= -2 + C(3^3, \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) \\ 43758 &:= C(\sqrt{4} \times 3^{7-5}, 8) \\ 46675 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 6^6 + C(7, 5) \\ 46682 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 6^6 + C(8, 2) \\ 46686 &:= \sqrt{4} + 6^6 + C(8, 6) \\ 48384 &:= (4 + 8)^3 \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69557 &:= -C(6 \times \sqrt{9}, 5) + 5^7 \\ 74431 &:= 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} \times 31 \\ 94864 &:= ((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times C(8, 6))^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 96957 &:= \sqrt{9^6} \times (C(9, 5) + 7) \\ 97242 &:= (\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)^4) / 2 \\ 97979 &:= (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 9) + 7) / \sqrt{9} \\ 98283 &:= \sqrt{9} + C(C(8, 2), 8 - 3) \\ 98285 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 8 + C(28, 5) \\ 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 117976 &:= C(11, 7) - \sqrt{9} + 7^6 \\ 122849 &:= -1 + 2 \times C(28, 4) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 123970 &:= C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$125971 := 1 + C(2 \times C(5, \sqrt{9}), 7 + 1)$$

$$129947 := -1 + C(2 \times 9, \sqrt{9 \times 4}) \times 7$$

$$137280 := C(13, \sqrt{7^2}) \times 80$$

$$139976 := -1 + 3 \times (\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{C(9,7)^6})$$

$$142884 := C(14 \times 2, \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8}})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$147439 := 1 + (4^7 - \sqrt{C(4,3)}) \times 9$$

$$149226 := \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times C((9+2) \times 2, 6)$$

$$159588 := (-1 + 5^{\sqrt{9}}) \times C(5+8, 8)$$

$$159884 := -1 + C(5+9+8, 8) / \sqrt{4}$$

$$159994 := -1 - 5 + C(9 - \sqrt{9}, \sqrt{9})^4$$

$$169344 := 1 \times 6 \times (C(9,3) \times \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$175616 := C(1+7, 5)^{6/\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}}$$

$$185191 := -1 + (C(8,5) + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1$$

$$185192 := 1 + (C(8,5) + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2$$

$$185194 := -1 + (C(8,5) + 1)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4}$$

$$194482 := 1 + C(9 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4})^{8/2}$$

$$196574 := (C(C(-1+9,6), 5) + 7) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$201894 := (20 - 1) \times C(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 4)$$

$$213444 := C(-2 + 13, \sqrt{4} + 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$215998 := -2 + (1 + 59)^{\sqrt{C(9,8)}}$$

$$223839 := C(22, \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8} - 3}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$234373 := -2 + (3 + \sqrt{C(4,3)})^7 \times 3$$

$$235292 := 2 \times (-3 + (5+2)^{\sqrt{C(9,2)}})$$

$$235298 := 2 \times (-3 + 52)^{\sqrt{C(9,8)}}$$

$$259844 := -C(25, \sqrt{9}) + 8^{\sqrt{4}+4}$$

$$259896 := (2+5) \times \sqrt{9} \times C(8+9, 6)$$

$$261649 := -C(2 \times 6, \sqrt{16}) + 4^9$$

$$262154 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} + C(5, \sqrt{4})$$

$$262179 := 2^{6 \times (2+1)} + C(7, \sqrt{9})$$

$$262469 := C(26, 2) + \sqrt{4^{6 \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$264992 := 2 \times C(6 + \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}, \sqrt{9})^2$$

$$269192 := 2 \times C(6 \times (\sqrt{9} + 1), \sqrt{C(9,2)})$$

$$275898 := ((2 \times C(7,5)) \times (8 + (\sqrt{9^8})))$$

$$277986 := C(2 \times 7, 7) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 6}$$

$$277989 := C(2 \times 7, 7) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - \sqrt{9}}$$

$$277992 := C(2 \times 7, 7) \times \sqrt{(9 \times 9)^2}$$

$$277994 := C(2 \times 7, 7) \times 9 \times 9 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$278967 := -C(27 - 8, \sqrt{9}) + 6^7$$

$$279567 := -C(2 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) - 5 + 6^7$$

$$287498 := 2 + (-8 + 74)^{\sqrt{C(9,8)}}$$

$$289444 := (2 + (8 + C(9,4)) \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$293925 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) - \sqrt{25}$$

$$293927 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) - \sqrt{2+7}$$

$$293928 := C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) - \sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}}$$

$$293929 := 2 - \sqrt{9} + C(3 \times (9 - 2), 9)$$

$$295295 := (2 + \sqrt{9}) \times (C(5,2) + 9^5)$$

$$296345 := -2 + C(9,6)^3 / \sqrt{4} - 5$$

$$296347 := 2 + C(9,6)^3 / \sqrt{4} - 7$$

$$296349 := 2 \times C(9,6)^3 / 4 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$296351 := (-2 + C(9,6)^3) / \sqrt{5-1}$$

$$299382 := (C(29, \sqrt{9}) - 3) \times 82$$

$$299617 := -2 + \sqrt{9^9} + C(6,1)^7$$

$$311469 := 3 \times (C(1,1) + 46)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$316969 := (3 + C(16, \sqrt{9}))^{6/\sqrt{9}}$$

$$325584 := C(3 \times (2+5), 5) \times 8 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 342666 &:= C\left(\sqrt{3^{C(4,2)}}, 6\right) + 6^6 \\
 345744 &:= (C(3+4, 5) \times 7 \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 352716 &:= C\left(3 \times (5+2), 7 + \sqrt{16}\right) \\
 352979 &:= 3^{5 \times 2} + C\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 9\right) \\
 354194 &:= \left(-3 + C\left(\sqrt{5^4}, 19\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 379827 &:= \left(-3 + C\left(7 \times \sqrt{9}, 8-2\right)\right) \times 7 \\
 382536 &:= C\left(3 \times 8, \sqrt{25}\right) \times (3+6) \\
 386694 &:= \left(-3 + \sqrt{8^6} \times 6\right) \times C(9, 4) \\
 388949 &:= -3 - 8 + 8 \times C\left(9 \times \sqrt{4}, 9\right) \\
 388969 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} + 8 \times C\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6, 9\right) \\
 393217 &:= C\left(3, \sqrt{9}\right) + 3 \times 2^{17} \\
 393663 &:= 3 + \sqrt{9^{3+6}} \times C(6, 3) \\
 394384 &:= \left(3 + \sqrt{(9 - C(4, 3))^8}\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 397953 &:= 3 \times \left(\sqrt{C(9, 7)} + 9 \times 5\right)^3 \\
 435456 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right)^{C(5,4)} \times 56 \\
 438969 &:= -4 - 3 + (-8 + C(9, 6))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 438976 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times 38\right)^{\sqrt{C(9, 7-6)}} \\
 438977 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times 38\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + C(7, 7) \\
 446464 &:= 4^6 \times \left(4 + C\left(C(6, 4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 447666 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + C(4 \times 7 - 6, 6)\right) \times 6 \\
 447669 &:= C\left(\sqrt{4} \times (4+7), 6\right) \times 6 - 9 \\
 447696 &:= \left(C\left(\sqrt{4} \times (4+7), 6\right) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 6 \\
 451584 &:= (C(4+5, 1+5) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 456976 &:= (4 \times 5 + 6)^{\sqrt{9+C(7,6)}} \\
 458744 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(-4 + 7 \times 8^{C(5,4)}\right) \\
 458752 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + 5\right) \times C(8, 7)^5 \times 2 \\
 459684 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right) \times 68\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 466535 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + 6^6\right) \times C(5, 3) - 5 \\
 466735 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + C(7, 3)\right) \times 5 \\
 473564 &:= C\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 3\right) \times \left(5 + 6^4\right) \\
 474474 &:= C\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4\right) \times 474 \\
 483159 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + C(8+3, 1)^5\right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 492983 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + 9^2\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - C(8, 3) \\
 497419 &:= -4 + \sqrt{9} + C\left(C(7, \sqrt{4}) + 1, 9\right) \\
 497594 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \sqrt{9}\right)^5 - C(7, \sqrt{9})\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 499849 &:= (C(4+9, 9) - 8)^{\sqrt{C(4, \sqrt{9})}} \\
 508725 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{08}}} \times C(C(7, 2), 5) \\
 524278 &:= -C(5, 2) + \sqrt{4^{27-8}} \\
 524286 &:= -\sqrt{5 - C(2, \sqrt{4})} + 2 \times 8^6 \\
 529984 &:= ((C(5, 2) + 9 \times 9) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 531434 &:= -5 + C(3, 1)^{4 \times 3} - \sqrt{4} \\
 531439 &:= -5 + C(3, 1)^{4 \times 3} + \sqrt{9} \\
 531896 &:= C\left(5 \times 3, \sqrt{1+8}\right) + 9^6 \\
 562392 &:= \left(5^{\sqrt{6^2}} - 3\right) \times C(9, 2) \\
 562464 &:= \left(5^6 - C(2, \sqrt{4})\right) \times \sqrt{6^4} \\
 573445 &:= 5 + C(7, 3) \times 4^{\sqrt{4}+5} \\
 592709 &:= \left(5 + C\left(9, \sqrt{2+7}\right)^{\sqrt{09}}\right) \\
 594594 &:= C\left(\sqrt{4} + 9, 5\right) \times C(4+9, 5) \\
 627248 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - \sqrt{4} \times 8 \\
 627254 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - C(5, \sqrt{4}) \\
 627262 &:= C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 - \sqrt{6-2} \\
 629835 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}\right), 8\right) - 3\right) \times 5 \\
 629895 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(\sqrt{6^2}, \sqrt{9}\right), 8\right) + 9\right) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 639744 &:= C(6 \times 3, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{(7 \times 4)^4} \\
 664832 &:= (\sqrt{6^6} - 4) \times C(8, 3)^2 \\
 665494 &:= -6 + C(6 + 5, \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 4 \\
 672986 &:= 6 + (7 - 2) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 8, 6) \\
 697675 &:= 6 \times C(\sqrt{9} \times C(7, 6), 7) - 5 \\
 697704 &:= 6 \times (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 7) + 04) \\
 697716 &:= 6 \times (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 7) \times 1 + 6) \\
 697728 &:= 6 \times (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, \sqrt{7^2}) + 8) \\
 697734 &:= 6 \times (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 7) + \sqrt{3^4}) \\
 697758 &:= 6 \times (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 7) + 5 + 8) \\
 699765 &:= (6 + 9) \times \sqrt{C(9, 7)^6} - 5 \\
 732564 &:= C(7 \times C(3, 2), 5) \times \sqrt{6^4} \\
 735468 &:= \sqrt{7 - 3} - 5 + C(4 \times 6, 8) \\
 744744 &:= C(7 \times \sqrt{4}, 4) \times 744 \\
 753424 &:= (7 \times (5^3 - C(\sqrt{4}, 2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 759595 &:= C(7 + 5, 9) + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^5 \\
 786431 &:= -7 + (8^6 + \sqrt{4}) \times C(3, 1) \\
 786493 &:= 7 + (8^6 + \sqrt{4} \times 9) \times 3 \\
 823488 &:= 8^2 \times (-3 + C(\sqrt{4} \times 8, 8)) \\
 823547 &:= C(8/2, 3) + (5 + \sqrt{4})^7 \\
 871144 &:= 8 \times (-7 + C(11, 4)^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 874874 &:= C(4 \times 7, 8 + \sqrt{4}) / (7 + 8) \\
 884519 &:= 8 + (C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5) - 1) \times 9 \\
 884539 &:= -8 + (C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5) + 3) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 884591 &:= (8 + C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5)) \times 9 - 1 \\
 884592 &:= (8 + C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5)) \times \sqrt{9^2} \\
 884594 &:= (8 + C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5)) \times 9 + \sqrt{4} \\
 892296 &:= 8 \times C(9 \times 2, 2) \times \sqrt{9^6} \\
 918897 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times C(18, 8) - \sqrt{9}) \times 7 \\
 924275 &:= C(9 + 2, \sqrt{4}) \times (-2 + 7^5) \\
 944649 &:= ((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4 - C(6, 4)) \times 9 \\
 945561 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + C(4 \times 5, 5)) \times 61 \\
 963738 &:= \sqrt{9^6} \times (C(3 \times 7, 3) - 8) \\
 972415 &:= (\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)^4 - 1) \times 5 \\
 976752 &:= C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6) \times (-7 + 5^2) \\
 976896 &:= (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 6) + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \times 6 \\
 979734 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7 \times (C(9, 7)^3 - \sqrt{4}) \\
 979764 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (7 \times \sqrt{C(9, 7)^6} - 4) \\
 979768 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7 \times \sqrt{C(9, 7)^6} - 8 \\
 979776 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 7 \times \sqrt{C(9, 7)^7} / 6 \\
 979797 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (7 + C(9, 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7) \\
 986697 &:= -\sqrt{9} + C(-8 + 6 \times 6, 9) / 7 \\
 994834 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (C((3 + 8) \times \sqrt{4}, 9) - \sqrt{9}) \\
 995664 &:= 4 \times ((6 + 6)^5 + C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\
 996625 &:= C(5, 2)^6 - (6 + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 999995 &:= (C(9, 9) + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 \\
 999997 &:= -\sqrt{9} + (C(9, 9) + 9) \sqrt{C(9, 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial and square-root**. The results are in terms of digit's order. Due to high quantity of numbers, the results are only up to 5 digits.

$$\begin{aligned}
 3495 &:= C(3!, \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} + 5! \\
 3597 &:= -3 + 5 \times \left(\sqrt{C(9,7)}\right)! \\
 3978 &:= C(3! \times \sqrt{9}, 7) / 8 \\
 4416 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{4}) \times 16 \\
 4976 &:= -4^{\sqrt{9}} + C(7, 6)! \\
 4999 &:= C(4! - 9, 9) - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 6498 &:= (6! + \sqrt{4}) \times C(9, 8) \\
 7993 &:= -7 + C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, \sqrt{9}\right)^3 \\
 7999 &:= C\left(7 + 9, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - 9 \\
 12544 &:= (-12 + 5! + 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 14169 &:= 1 + \left(C(4!, -1 + 6) / \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 14355 &:= -\sqrt{1 + C(4!, 3)} + 5! \times 5! \\
 14396 &:= -1 \times 4 + C(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times 6! \\
 14945 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 4) - 5 \\
 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) \\
 15456 &:= C\left(\left(-1 + 5\right)!, \sqrt{4}\right) \times 56 \\
 15649 &:= 1 \times 5^6 + C\left(4, \sqrt{9}\right)! \\
 19489 &:= 1 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! - 4!\right) \times C\left(8, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \\
 19792 &:= \left(1 + \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7! - 92) \\
 20989 &:= C(20, 9) / 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 21069 &:= C(21, -0! + 6) + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 22319 &:= -C(2, 2) + 31 \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 24192 &:= (2 \times 4 + 1)! / C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, 2\right) \\
 25932 &:= (-2 + 5)! \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \times 3!! + 2 \\
 29791 &:= \left(\left(-2 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)!\right) + 7)^{\sqrt{C(9,1)}} \\
 30246 &:= \left(\left(3! + 0!\right)!\right) + C\left(2, \sqrt{4}\right) \times 6 \\
 32379 &:= C(3!, 2) \times 3!! - 7 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 32384 &:= C\left(\left(3! - 2\right)!, 3\right) \times 8 \times \sqrt{4} \\
 32445 &:= \left(3!! + C\left(2, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 45 \\
 32490 &:= (3!! + 2) \times \sqrt{C(4!, \sqrt{9})} + 0! \\
 33485 &:= 3!! - C\left(3, \sqrt{4}\right) + 8^5 \\
 34574 &:= (3! \times 4! \times 5! + 7) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 34968 &:= -3 \times C(4!, \sqrt{9}) + 6! + 8! \\
 35568 &:= -C\left(\sqrt{3!!/5}, 5\right) \times 6 + 8! \\
 36434 &:= 3 \times 6 \times C(4!, 3) + \sqrt{4} \\
 37458 &:= -3! - 7! + C\left(4!, \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}}\right) \\
 38293 &:= -3 + 8! - C\left(\left(-2 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)!, 3\right) \\
 38299 &:= 3 + 8! - C\left(\left(-2 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)!, \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 39385 &:= \sqrt{5^8} + C\left(C(3!, \sqrt{9}), 3!\right) \\
 39386 &:= C(3!, \sqrt{9}) + 3^8 \times 6 \\
 39498 &:= -3! - C\left(9 \times \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{9}\right) + 8! \\
 39564 &:= -3! \times C(9, 5) + (\sqrt{64})! \\
 39597 &:= -3 + (\sqrt{9} + 5)! - \left(\sqrt{C(9,7)}\right)! \\
 39655 &:= \left(C(3, \sqrt{9}) + 6!\right) \times 55 \\
 39843 &:= 3^9 + 8! / \sqrt{C(4, 3)} \\
 39985 &:= -C(3! + 9, \sqrt{9}) + 8! + 5! \\
 40044 &:= -C(4!, \sqrt{4}) + ((0! + 0!) \times 4)! \\
 40343 &:= 4! - 0! + \left(3! + \sqrt{C(4, 3)}\right)! \\
 40345 &:= 4! + 0! + \left(C(3, \sqrt{4}) + 5\right)! \\
 40438 &:= (4 + 0)! - \sqrt{C(4, 3)} + 8! \\
 40588 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{-0! + 5}) - 8 + 8! \\
 41492 &:= 41 \times C(4!, \sqrt{9}) / 2 \\
 42338 &:= C\left(\left(\sqrt{4^2}\right)!, 3\right) - 3! + 8! \\
 42344 &:= C\left(\left(\sqrt{4^2}\right)!, 3\right) + (4 + 4)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42348 &:= C\left(\left(\sqrt{4^2}\right)!, 3\right) + 4 + 8! \\
 42454 &:= -4! \times 2 + C(4!, 5) - \sqrt{4} \\
 42459 &:= -4! \times 2 + C(4!, 5) + \sqrt{9} \\
 42492 &:= -4!/2 + C\left(4!, \sqrt{9} + 2\right) \\
 42497 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{2^4 + 9}\right) - 7 \\
 42498 &:= -C(4, 2) + C\left(4!, -\sqrt{9} + 8\right) \\
 42502 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) - 02 \\
 42503 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) - (0 \times 3)! \\
 42504 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}\right) \\
 42505 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) + (0 \times 5)! \\
 42509 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) - 0! + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)! \\
 42515 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) + \sqrt{1 + 5!} \\
 42534 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{25}\right) + 3! + 4! \\
 43638 &:= -\left(\sqrt{4} + 3\right)! + C(6 \times 3, 8) \\
 43944 &:= C(4!, -4 + 9) + 3!! \times \sqrt{4} \\
 44160 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{4}\right) \times 160 \\
 44358 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (C(4!, 3) - 5) + 8! \\
 44368 &:= \sqrt{4} \times C\left(4!, \sqrt{3 + 6}\right) + 8! \\
 44373 &:= C\left(4! - \sqrt{4}, 3!\right) - 7! \times 3! \\
 44836 &:= 6^{3!} - C\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}, 4\right) \\
 45864 &:= C(4!, 5) + 8!/6/\sqrt{4} \\
 45879 &:= C(4!, 5) + (8 + 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 46296 &:= -4! \times C(6, 2) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!^6 \\
 49296 &:= C\left(4!, \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(-2 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)! + 6! \\
 49333 &:= -\sqrt{4} + C(9 \times 3, 3!) / 3! \\
 49335 &:= C\left(4! + \sqrt{9}, 3!\right) / C(3!, 5) \\
 49336 &:= \left(C\left(4! + \sqrt{9}, 3!\right) + 3!\right) / 6 \\
 49339 &:= 4! + C(9 \times 3, 3!) / \left(\sqrt{9}\right)! \\
 49392 &:= \left(C\left(4!, \sqrt{9}\right) + 3!!\right) \times 9 \times 2 \\
 49536 &:= C\left(4, \sqrt{9}\right)! \times 5! + 3!^6 \\
 49984 &:= 4 + \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \times C(8, 4) \\
 53985 &:= -5 \times \left(3 - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! / 8 \times 5!\right) \\
 54259 &:= -5 + C\left(4^2 + 5, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \\
 54384 &:= 5! + C\left(4! - 3, 8 - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 54516 &:= \left(5! - \sqrt{4}\right) \times C\left(\sqrt{5! + 1}, 6\right) \\
 56644 &:= \left(5! - C(6, 6)\right) \times \sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 59029 &:= C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, 2 + 0!\right) + 9^5 \\
 59044 &:= -5 + 9^{0! + \sqrt{4} \times 4} \\
 59280 &:= 5! \times \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, 2, 8\right) - 0!\right) \\
 63744 &:= 6 \times \left(-\sqrt{-3 + 7} + C(4!, 4)\right) \\
 64449 &:= C(6, 4)^4 + 4!^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 64974 &:= C\left(-6 + 4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \times 7 / \sqrt{4} \\
 66564 &:= (6! - C(6 + 5, 6))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 74379 &:= 7 \times C(4!, -3 + 7) - \sqrt{9} \\
 74446 &:= 7 \times C(4!, 4) + \sqrt{4^6} \\
 74459 &:= 7 \times \left(C(4!, 4) + 5 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \\
 75695 &:= -7! + 5 + C\left(\sqrt{6! + 9}, 5\right) \\
 77597 &:= 77 + C\left(5! / \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, 7\right) \\
 79422 &:= 7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + C(4!, 2 + 2)\right) \\
 79443 &:= 7 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + C(4!, 4) + 3!!\right) \\
 79653 &:= 7! + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} - 5, 3!\right) \\
 80584 &:= -C(8, 05) + 8! \times \sqrt{4} \\
 80654 &:= (8! + 0! + C(6, 5)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 81564 &:= \left(8! + C\left(\sqrt{1 + 5!}, 6\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 84736 &:= 8! \times \sqrt{4} + (7 - 3)^6 \\
 84944 &:= 8 \times \left(-4! / \sqrt{9} + C(4!, 4)\right) \\
 84968 &:= 8 + \sqrt{4} \times \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6! + 8!\right) \\
 84992 &:= 8 \times \left(C\left(4!, C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - 2\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84999 &:= 8 \times C(4!, C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9})) - 9 \\
 85944 &:= 8 \times (5! - \sqrt{9} + C(4!, 4)) \\
 86391 &:= -8 + 6! \times 3!! / (\sqrt{9})! - 1 \\
 86592 &:= (8 + 6! \times 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - 2)! \\
 86949 &:= 8! + 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} - 4! - \sqrt{9} \\
 86973 &:= 8! + 6^{\sqrt{C(9,7)}} - 3 \\
 86974 &:= 8! + 6^{\sqrt{C(9,7)}} - \sqrt{4} \\
 86977 &:= 8! + 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} + C(7, 7) \\
 86979 &:= 8! + 6^{\sqrt{C(9,7)}} + \sqrt{9} \\
 86996 &:= 8! + C(6, \sqrt{9}) + (\sqrt{9})!^6 \\
 87379 &:= (C(8, 7)^{3!} - 7) / \sqrt{9} \\
 87696 &:= C(8, 7)! + 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 6! \\
 88648 &:= C(8 + 8, 6) + \sqrt{4} \times 8! \\
 89595 &:= 8! / (\sqrt{9})! \times 5! / 9 - 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 90444 &:= 9! / 04 - C(4!, \sqrt{4}) \\
 92835 &:= C(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2), 8) + 3!! \times 5! \\
 93284 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^{3!} \times 2 - C(8, \sqrt{4}) \\
 93332 &:= C((\sqrt{9})!, 3) + 3!^{3!} \times 2 \\
 93456 &:= C(9, 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! \times 6! \\
 94988 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + C(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) - 8 - 8! \\
 95754 &:= -C((\sqrt{9})!, 5) + 7! \times (-5 + 4!) \\
 97395 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + C(7, 3)) \times (9 + 5!) \\
 97447 &:= (- (\sqrt{9})!! + (7 + 4)^4) \times 7 \\
 98274 &:= - (\sqrt{9})! + C(C(8, 2), 7 - \sqrt{4}) \\
 98464 &:= C(9 + 8, \sqrt{4}) \times (6! + 4) \\
 98984 &:= C(9 + 8, (\sqrt{9})!) \times 8 - 4!
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Binomial-Coefficient Type Patterned Selfie Numbers

3.1 Basic Operations

$$\begin{aligned}
 9576 &:= C(9, 5) \times 76 \\
 95760 &:= C(9, 5) \times 760 \\
 957600 &:= C(9, 5) \times 7600
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 94752 &:= C(9, 4) \times 752 \\
 947520 &:= C(9, 4) \times 7520 \\
 9475200 &:= C(9, 4) \times 75200
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24288 &:= C(24, 2) \times 88 \\
 242880 &:= C(24, 2) \times 880 \\
 2428800 &:= C(24, 2) \times 8800
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98415 &:= C(9, 8)^4 \times 15 \\
 984150 &:= C(9, 8)^4 \times 150 \\
 9841500 &:= C(9, 8)^4 \times 1500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32805 &:= C(3, 2)^8 \times 05 \\
 328050 &:= C(3, 2)^8 \times 050 \\
 3280500 &:= C(3, 2)^8 \times 0500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 114921 &:= (C(11, 4) + 9)^2 \times 1 \\
 1149210 &:= (C(11, 4) + 9)^2 \times 10 \\
 11492100 &:= (C(11, 4) + 9)^2 \times 100
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83755 &:= (-C(8, 3) + 7^5) \times 5 \\
 837550 &:= (-C(8, 3) + 7^5) \times 50 \\
 8375500 &:= (-C(8, 3) + 7^5) \times 500
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 115836 &:= (1 + C(15, 8) \times 3) \times 6 \\
 1158360 &:= (1 + C(15, 8) \times 3) \times 60 \\
 11583600 &:= (1 + C(15, 8) \times 3) \times 600
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}116488 &:= (1 + C(16,4) \times 8) \times 8 \\1164880 &:= (1 + C(16,4) \times 8) \times 80 \\11648800 &:= (1 + C(16,4) \times 8) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}138996 &:= C(13,8) \times (9 + 9) \times 6 \\1389960 &:= C(13,8) \times (9 + 9) \times 60 \\13899600 &:= C(13,8) \times (9 + 9) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}144144 &:= C(14,4) \times 144 \\1441440 &:= C(14,4) \times 1440 \\14414400 &:= C(14,4) \times 14400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}163842 &:= (1 + C(6,3) \times 8^4) \times 2 \\1638420 &:= (1 + C(6,3) \times 8^4) \times 20 \\16384200 &:= (1 + C(6,3) \times 8^4) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}212515 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) - 1) \times 5 \\2125150 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) - 1) \times 50 \\21251500 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) - 1) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}212535 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) + 3) \times 5 \\2125350 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) + 3) \times 50 \\21253500 &:= (C(2 \times 12,5) + 3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}216864 &:= (C(21,6) - 8 \times 6) \times 4 \\2168640 &:= (C(21,6) - 8 \times 6) \times 40 \\21686400 &:= (C(21,6) - 8 \times 6) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}219375 &:= C((2 + 1) \times 9,3) \times 75 \\2193750 &:= C((2 + 1) \times 9,3) \times 750 \\21937500 &:= C((2 + 1) \times 9,3) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}235487 &:= (C(23, C(5,4)) - 8) \times 7 \\2354870 &:= (C(23, C(5,4)) - 8) \times 70 \\23548700 &:= (C(23, C(5,4)) - 8) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}235627 &:= (C(23,5) + 6 \times 2) \times 7 \\2356270 &:= (C(23,5) + 6 \times 2) \times 70 \\23562700 &:= (C(23,5) + 6 \times 2) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}238328 &:= (23 + 8)^{C(3,2)} \times 8 \\2383280 &:= (23 + 8)^{C(3,2)} \times 80 \\23832800 &:= (23 + 8)^{C(3,2)} \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}251975 &:= (2 + 5 + C(19,7)) \times 5 \\2519750 &:= (2 + 5 + C(19,7)) \times 50 \\25197500 &:= (2 + 5 + C(19,7)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}262144 &:= C((2 + 6) \times 2,1)^4 \times 4 \\2621440 &:= C((2 + 6) \times 2,1)^4 \times 40 \\26214400 &:= C((2 + 6) \times 2,1)^4 \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}262688 &:= (2^{C(6,2)} + 68) \times 8 \\2626880 &:= (2^{C(6,2)} + 68) \times 80 \\26268800 &:= (2^{C(6,2)} + 68) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}274274 &:= C(2 \times 7,4) \times 274 \\2742740 &:= C(2 \times 7,4) \times 2740 \\27427400 &:= C(2 \times 7,4) \times 27400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}294753 &:= (-29 + C(4 \times 7,5)) \times 3 \\2947530 &:= (-29 + C(4 \times 7,5)) \times 30 \\29475300 &:= (-29 + C(4 \times 7,5)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}325566 &:= (-3 + C(C(2 + 5,5),6)) \times 6 \\3255660 &:= (-3 + C(C(2 + 5,5),6)) \times 60 \\32556600 &:= (-3 + C(C(2 + 5,5),6)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}326627 &:= (C(3,2) + 6^6 + 2) \times 7 \\3266270 &:= (C(3,2) + 6^6 + 2) \times 70 \\32662700 &:= (C(3,2) + 6^6 + 2) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}327695 &:= (3 + 2^{C(7,6)+9}) \times 5 \\3276950 &:= (3 + 2^{C(7,6)+9}) \times 50 \\32769500 &:= (3 + 2^{C(7,6)+9}) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}329232 &:= 3 \times (2 + C(9,2))^3 \times 2 \\3292320 &:= 3 \times (2 + C(9,2))^3 \times 20\end{aligned}$$

$$32923200 := 3 \times (2 + C(9, 2))^3 \times 200$$

$$354347 := ((3 \times 5)^{C(4,3)} - 4) \times 7$$

$$3543470 := ((3 \times 5)^{C(4,3)} - 4) \times 70$$

$$35434700 := ((3 \times 5)^{C(4,3)} - 4) \times 700$$

$$375168 := 3 \times (7 + C(5, 1)^6) \times 8$$

$$3751680 := 3 \times (7 + C(5, 1)^6) \times 80$$

$$37516800 := 3 \times (7 + C(5, 1)^6) \times 800$$

$$413736 := (41^3 + C(7, 3)) \times 6$$

$$4137360 := (41^3 + C(7, 3)) \times 60$$

$$41373600 := (41^3 + C(7, 3)) \times 600$$

$$433768 := (-43 + C(3 \times 7, 6)) \times 8$$

$$4337680 := (-43 + C(3 \times 7, 6)) \times 80$$

$$43376800 := (-43 + C(3 \times 7, 6)) \times 800$$

$$524288 := (C(5, 2) - 4 - 2)^8 \times 8$$

$$5242880 := (C(5, 2) - 4 - 2)^8 \times 80$$

$$52428800 := (C(5, 2) - 4 - 2)^8 \times 800$$

$$524328 := (5 + 2^{C(4,3)^2}) \times 8$$

$$5243280 := (5 + 2^{C(4,3)^2}) \times 80$$

$$52432800 := (5 + 2^{C(4,3)^2}) \times 800$$

$$524392 := (52 + C(4, 3)^9) \times 2$$

$$5243920 := (52 + C(4, 3)^9) \times 20$$

$$52439200 := (52 + C(4, 3)^9) \times 200$$

$$538364 := (-5 + C(3 \times 8, 3 \times 6)) \times 4$$

$$5383640 := (-5 + C(3 \times 8, 3 \times 6)) \times 40$$

$$53836400 := (-5 + C(3 \times 8, 3 \times 6)) \times 400$$

$$594594 := C(5 + 9, 4) \times 594$$

$$5945940 := C(5 + 9, 4) \times 5940$$

$$59459400 := C(5 + 9, 4) \times 59400$$

$$629946 := (C(6, 2) + (9 + 9)^4) \times 6$$

$$6299460 := (C(6, 2) + (9 + 9)^4) \times 60$$

$$62994600 := (C(6, 2) + (9 + 9)^4) \times 600$$

$$684684 := C(6 + 8, 4) \times 684$$

$$6846840 := C(6 + 8, 4) \times 6840$$

$$68468400 := C(6 + 8, 4) \times 68400$$

$$712956 := (71 + C(29, 5)) \times 6$$

$$7129560 := (71 + C(29, 5)) \times 60$$

$$71295600 := (71 + C(29, 5)) \times 600$$

$$715822 := 71^{C(-5+8,2)} \times 2$$

$$7158220 := 71^{C(-5+8,2)} \times 20$$

$$71582200 := 71^{C(-5+8,2)} \times 200$$

$$724724 := C(7 \times 2, 4) \times 724$$

$$7247240 := C(7 \times 2, 4) \times 7240$$

$$72472400 := C(7 \times 2, 4) \times 72400$$

$$734825 := C(7 \times 3, 4 + 8) / 2 \times 5$$

$$7348250 := C(7 \times 3, 4 + 8) / 2 \times 50$$

$$73482500 := C(7 \times 3, 4 + 8) / 2 \times 500$$

$$741125 := (C(7, 4) \times 11)^2 \times 5$$

$$7411250 := (C(7, 4) \times 11)^2 \times 50$$

$$74112500 := (C(7, 4) \times 11)^2 \times 500$$

$$765667 := (C(7, 6) \times 5^6 + 6) \times 7$$

$$7656670 := (C(7, 6) \times 5^6 + 6) \times 70$$

$$76566700 := (C(7, 6) \times 5^6 + 6) \times 700$$

$$774774 := C(7 + 7, 4) \times 774$$

$$7747740 := C(7 + 7, 4) \times 7740$$

$$77477400 := C(7 + 7, 4) \times 77400$$

$$864864 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 864$$

$$8648640 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 8640$$

$$86486400 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 86400$$

$$\begin{aligned} 954954 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 954 \\ 9549540 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 9540 \\ 95495400 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 95400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972435 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 - 3) \times 5 \\ 9724350 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 - 3) \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Factorial

$$\begin{aligned} 13248 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 2) \times 48 \\ 132480 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 2) \times 480 \\ 1324800 &:= C((1 + 3)!, 2) \times 4800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15939 &:= C(-1 + (-5 + 9)!, 3) \times 9 \\ 159390 &:= C(-1 + (-5 + 9)!, 3) \times 90 \\ 1593900 &:= C(-1 + (-5 + 9)!, 3) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24312 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times 12 \\ 243120 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times 120 \\ 2431200 &:= (2 + C(4!, 3)) \times 1200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24396 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 6 \\ 243960 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 60 \\ 2439600 &:= 2 \times (C(4!, 3) + 9) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25275 &:= (C((-2 + 5)!, 2) + 7!) \times 5 \\ 252750 &:= (C((-2 + 5)!, 2) + 7!) \times 50 \\ 2527500 &:= (C((-2 + 5)!, 2) + 7!) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32175 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 1 \times 7) \times 5 \\ 321750 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 1 \times 7) \times 50 \\ 3217500 &:= C(C(3!, 2), 1 \times 7) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32835 &:= (C(3, 2)^8 + 3!) \times 5 \\ 328350 &:= (C(3, 2)^8 + 3!) \times 50 \\ 3283500 &:= (C(3, 2)^8 + 3!) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34368 &:= 3! \times (-C(4, 3) + 6!) \times 8 \\ 343680 &:= 3! \times (-C(4, 3) + 6!) \times 80 \end{aligned}$$

$$97243500 := (9 + C(7, 2)^4 - 3) \times 500$$

$$\begin{aligned} 972495 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 + 9) \times 5 \\ 9724950 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 + 9) \times 50 \\ 97249500 &:= (9 + C(7, 2)^4 + 9) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$3436800 := 3! \times (-C(4, 3) + 6!) \times 800$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36432 &:= (3 + 6) \times C(4!, 3) \times 2 \\ 364320 &:= (3 + 6) \times C(4!, 3) \times 20 \\ 3643200 &:= (3 + 6) \times C(4!, 3) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42528 &:= (C(4!, 2) + (5 + 2)!) \times 8 \\ 425280 &:= (C(4!, 2) + (5 + 2)!) \times 80 \\ 4252800 &:= (C(4!, 2) + (5 + 2)!) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53625 &:= (-5 + 3!) \times C(6, 2) \times 5 \\ 536250 &:= (-5 + 3!) \times C(6, 2) \times 50 \\ 5362500 &:= (-5 + 3!) \times C(6, 2) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54375 &:= (C(5, 4) + 3!) \times 75 \\ 543750 &:= (C(5, 4) + 3!) \times 750 \\ 5437500 &:= (C(5, 4) + 3!) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59436 &:= (C((-5 + 9)!, 4) - 3!) \times 6 \\ 594360 &:= (C((-5 + 9)!, 4) - 3!) \times 60 \\ 5943600 &:= (C((-5 + 9)!, 4) - 3!) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74256 &:= C(-7 + 4!, (-2 + 5)!) \times 6 \\ 742560 &:= C(-7 + 4!, (-2 + 5)!) \times 60 \\ 7425600 &:= C(-7 + 4!, (-2 + 5)!) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75605 &:= (C(7, 5) \times 6! + 0!) \times 5 \\ 756050 &:= (C(7, 5) \times 6! + 0!) \times 50 \\ 7560500 &:= (C(7, 5) \times 6! + 0!) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$80652 := (8! + C(06, 5)) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 806520 &:= (8! + C(06,5)) \times 20 & 1484450 &:= (-1 - 4 + 8! - C(4!,4)) \times 50 \\
 8065200 &:= (8! + C(06,5)) \times 200 & 14844500 &:= (-1 - 4 + 8! - C(4!,4)) \times 500 \\
 \\
 80752 &:= (8! + C(0! + 7,5)) \times 2 & 152352 &:= C((-1 + 5)!,2)^{-3+5} \times 2 \\
 807520 &:= (8! + C(0! + 7,5)) \times 20 & 1523520 &:= C((-1 + 5)!,2)^{-3+5} \times 20 \\
 8075200 &:= (8! + C(0! + 7,5)) \times 200 & 15235200 &:= C((-1 + 5)!,2)^{-3+5} \times 200 \\
 \\
 84448 &:= (-C(8,4) + C(4!,4)) \times 8 & 153184 &:= (-C((-1 + 5)!,3) \times 1 + 8!) \times 4 \\
 844480 &:= (-C(8,4) + C(4!,4)) \times 80 & 1531840 &:= (-C((-1 + 5)!,3) \times 1 + 8!) \times 40 \\
 8444800 &:= (-C(8,4) + C(4!,4)) \times 800 & 15318400 &:= (-C((-1 + 5)!,3) \times 1 + 8!) \times 400 \\
 \\
 115833 &:= (1 + C(15,8) \times 3!) \times 3 & 154564 &:= (1 - 5! + C(4 \times 5,6)) \times 4 \\
 1158330 &:= (1 + C(15,8) \times 3!) \times 30 & 1545640 &:= (1 - 5! + C(4 \times 5,6)) \times 40 \\
 11583300 &:= (1 + C(15,8) \times 3!) \times 300 & 15456400 &:= (1 - 5! + C(4 \times 5,6)) \times 400 \\
 \\
 124326 &:= (12^4 - C(3!,2)) \times 6 & 161282 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)! + 8!) \times 2 \\
 1243260 &:= (12^4 - C(3!,2)) \times 60 & 1612820 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)! + 8!) \times 20 \\
 12432600 &:= (12^4 - C(3!,2)) \times 600 & 16128200 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)! + 8!) \times 200 \\
 \\
 135665 &:= (1 + C((-3! + 5!)/6,6)) \times 5 & 161284 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)!) \times (8 - 4) \\
 1356650 &:= (1 + C((-3! + 5!)/6,6)) \times 50 & 1612840 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)!) \times (80 - 40) \\
 13566500 &:= (1 + C((-3! + 5!)/6,6)) \times 500 & 16128400 &:= (1 + (C(6,1) + 2)!) \times (800 - 400) \\
 \\
 136269 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times (C(6,2) + 6) \times 9 & 164645 &:= (-1 \times 6! + C(4!,6)/4) \times 5 \\
 1362690 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times (C(6,2) + 6) \times 90 & 1646450 &:= (-1 \times 6! + C(4!,6)/4) \times 50 \\
 13626900 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times (C(6,2) + 6) \times 900 & 16464500 &:= (-1 \times 6! + C(4!,6)/4) \times 500 \\
 \\
 140361 &:= (1 + C(4! + 0!,3)) \times 61 & 168483 &:= (1 + 6! \times (C(8,4) + 8)) \times 3 \\
 1403610 &:= (1 + C(4! + 0!,3)) \times 610 & 1684830 &:= (1 + 6! \times (C(8,4) + 8)) \times 30 \\
 14036100 &:= (1 + C(4! + 0!,3)) \times 6100 & 16848300 &:= (1 + 6! \times (C(8,4) + 8)) \times 300 \\
 \\
 142272 &:= (C(1 \times 4!,2)^2 - 7!) \times 2 & 174384 &:= (C(1 \times 7 \times 4,3) + 8!) \times 4 \\
 1422720 &:= (C(1 \times 4!,2)^2 - 7!) \times 20 & 1743840 &:= (C(1 \times 7 \times 4,3) + 8!) \times 40 \\
 14227200 &:= (C(1 \times 4!,2)^2 - 7!) \times 200 & 17438400 &:= (C(1 \times 7 \times 4,3) + 8!) \times 400 \\
 \\
 144865 &:= (-1 - C(4!,4) + 8! - 6!) \times 5 & 176575 &:= (-1 + 7! + C(6,5)) \times 7 \times 5 \\
 1448650 &:= (-1 - C(4!,4) + 8! - 6!) \times 50 & 1765750 &:= (-1 + 7! + C(6,5)) \times 7 \times 50 \\
 14486500 &:= (-1 - C(4!,4) + 8! - 6!) \times 500 & 17657500 &:= (-1 + 7! + C(6,5)) \times 7 \times 500 \\
 \\
 148445 &:= (-1 - 4 + 8! - C(4!,4)) \times 5 & 179375 &:= (1 + 7! + C(9,3)) \times 7 \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1793750 := (1 + 7! + C(9, 3)) \times 7 \times 50$$
$$17937500 := (1 + 7! + C(9, 3)) \times 7 \times 500$$

$$182439 := (-1 + C(8, 2) \times (4 + 3!)) \times 9$$
$$1824390 := (-1 + C(8, 2) \times (4 + 3!)) \times 90$$
$$18243900 := (-1 + C(8, 2) \times (4 + 3!)) \times 900$$

$$182736 := (C(1 + 8, 2) + 7!) \times 36$$
$$1827360 := (C(1 + 8, 2) + 7!) \times 360$$
$$18273600 := (C(1 + 8, 2) + 7!) \times 3600$$

$$183699 := (-1 + C(8, 3!) \times (6! + 9)) \times 9$$
$$1836990 := (-1 + C(8, 3!) \times (6! + 9)) \times 90$$
$$18369900 := (-1 + C(8, 3!) \times (6! + 9)) \times 900$$

$$184323 := (1 + 8^4 \times C(3!, 2)) \times 3$$
$$1843230 := (1 + 8^4 \times C(3!, 2)) \times 30$$
$$18432300 := (1 + 8^4 \times C(3!, 2)) \times 300$$

$$186585 := (-C(1 + 8 + 6, 5) + 8!) \times 5$$
$$1865850 := (-C(1 + 8 + 6, 5) + 8!) \times 50$$
$$18658500 := (-C(1 + 8 + 6, 5) + 8!) \times 500$$

$$194344 := (1 + 9 + C(4!, 3) \times 4!) \times 4$$
$$1943440 := (1 + 9 + C(4!, 3) \times 4!) \times 40$$
$$19434400 := (1 + 9 + C(4!, 3) \times 4!) \times 400$$

$$201605 := ((C(2, 01) + 6)! + 0!) \times 5$$
$$2016050 := ((C(2, 01) + 6)! + 0!) \times 50$$
$$20160500 := ((C(2, 01) + 6)! + 0!) \times 500$$

$$203332 := (C(23, 3!) + 3!! - 0!) \times 2$$
$$2033320 := (C(23, 3!) + 3!! - 0!) \times 20$$
$$20333200 := (C(23, 3!) + 3!! - 0!) \times 200$$

$$218805 := (2 + C(18, 8) + 0!) \times 5$$
$$2188050 := (2 + C(18, 8) + 0!) \times 50$$
$$21880500 := (2 + C(18, 8) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$223833 := (C(22, 3!) - 8 + 3!) \times 3$$

$$2238330 := (C(22, 3!) - 8 + 3!) \times 30$$
$$22383300 := (C(22, 3!) - 8 + 3!) \times 300$$

$$223863 := (C(22, 3!) + 8) \times (6 - 3)$$
$$2238630 := (C(22, 3!) + 8) \times (60 - 30)$$
$$22386300 := (C(22, 3!) + 8) \times (600 - 300)$$

$$226805 := ((C(2, 2) + 6)! + 8! + 0!) \times 5$$
$$2268050 := ((C(2, 2) + 6)! + 8! + 0!) \times 50$$
$$22680500 := ((C(2, 2) + 6)! + 8! + 0!) \times 500$$

$$227392 := C(22, 7) \times 3!/9 \times 2$$
$$2273920 := C(22, 7) \times 3!/9 \times 20$$
$$22739200 := C(22, 7) \times 3!/9 \times 200$$

$$233376 := 2 \times C(C(3!, 3) - 3, 7) \times 6$$
$$2333760 := 2 \times C(C(3!, 3) - 3, 7) \times 60$$
$$23337600 := 2 \times C(C(3!, 3) - 3, 7) \times 600$$

$$233856 := (-(-2 + 3!)! + 3!) \times C(8, 5) \times 6$$
$$2338560 := (-(-2 + 3!)! + 3!) \times C(8, 5) \times 60$$
$$23385600 := (-(-2 + 3!)! + 3!) \times C(8, 5) \times 600$$

$$234632 := (-(-2 + 3!)! \times 6! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2$$
$$2346320 := (-(-2 + 3!)! \times 6! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 20$$
$$23463200 := (-(-2 + 3!)! \times 6! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 200$$

$$237636 := (C(2^3, 7)! - 6! + 3!) \times 6$$
$$2376360 := (C(2^3, 7)! - 6! + 3!) \times 60$$
$$23763600 := (C(2^3, 7)! - 6! + 3!) \times 600$$

$$238896 := (-C(2 \times 3!, 8) + 8! - 9) \times 6$$
$$2388960 := (-C(2 \times 3!, 8) + 8! - 9) \times 60$$
$$23889600 := (-C(2 \times 3!, 8) + 8! - 9) \times 600$$

$$239976 := ((2^3)! - 9 \times C(9, 7)) \times 6$$
$$2399760 := ((2^3)! - 9 \times C(9, 7)) \times 60$$
$$23997600 := ((2^3)! - 9 \times C(9, 7)) \times 600$$

$$242382 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) + 3 \times 8!) \times 2$$

$$2423820 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) + 3 \times 8!) \times 20$$
$$24238200 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) + 3 \times 8!) \times 200$$

$$242586 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) - 5! + 8!) \times 6$$
$$2425860 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) - 5! + 8!) \times 60$$
$$24258600 := (C(-2 + 4!, 2) - 5! + 8!) \times 600$$

$$247648 := ((2 + 4) \times 7! + 6! - 4) \times 8$$
$$2476480 := ((2 + 4) \times 7! + 6! - 4) \times 80$$
$$24764800 := ((2 + 4) \times 7! + 6! - 4) \times 800$$

$$254306 := 2 + (-5! + C(4!, 3! - 0!)) \times 6$$
$$2543060 := 2 + (-5! + C(4!, 3! - 0!)) \times 60$$
$$25430600 := 2 + (-5! + C(4!, 3! - 0!)) \times 600$$

$$254424 := (-25 + C(4!, 4)) \times 24$$
$$2544240 := (-25 + C(4!, 4)) \times 240$$
$$25442400 := (-25 + C(4!, 4)) \times 2400$$

$$254448 := (-2 + 5) \times (C(4!, 4) - 4!) \times 8$$
$$2544480 := (-2 + 5) \times (C(4!, 4) - 4!) \times 80$$
$$25444800 := (-2 + 5) \times (C(4!, 4) - 4!) \times 800$$

$$255036 := (2 + C(5!/5, -0! + 3!)) \times 6$$
$$2550360 := (2 + C(5!/5, -0! + 3!)) \times 60$$
$$25503600 := (2 + C(5!/5, -0! + 3!)) \times 600$$

$$258975 := (-C(2 \times 5, 8) + 9!/7) \times 5$$
$$2589750 := (-C(2 \times 5, 8) + 9!/7) \times 50$$
$$25897500 := (-C(2 \times 5, 8) + 9!/7) \times 500$$

$$262088 := (2^{C(6,2)} + 0! - 8) \times 8$$
$$2620880 := (2^{C(6,2)} + 0! - 8) \times 80$$
$$26208800 := (2^{C(6,2)} + 0! - 8) \times 800$$

$$265424 := (C(26, 5) + 4!^2) \times 4$$
$$2654240 := (C(26, 5) + 4!^2) \times 40$$
$$26542400 := (C(26, 5) + 4!^2) \times 400$$

$$265964 := (C(26, 5) - 9 + 6!) \times 4$$

$$2659640 := (C(26, 5) - 9 + 6!) \times 40$$
$$26596400 := (C(26, 5) - 9 + 6!) \times 400$$

$$269192 := C((-2 + 6)!, C(9, 1) + 9) \times 2$$
$$2691920 := C((-2 + 6)!, C(9, 1) + 9) \times 20$$
$$26919200 := C((-2 + 6)!, C(9, 1) + 9) \times 200$$

$$269432 := ((2 - 6 + 9)! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2$$
$$2694320 := ((2 - 6 + 9)! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 20$$
$$26943200 := ((2 - 6 + 9)! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 200$$

$$270632 := (C((-2 + 7 - 0)!, 6) + 3!) \times 2$$
$$2706320 := (C((-2 + 7 - 0)!, 6) + 3!) \times 20$$
$$27063200 := (C((-2 + 7 - 0)!, 6) + 3!) \times 200$$

$$282247 := (2 + 8! - C(2, 2)^4) \times 7$$
$$2822470 := (2 + 8! - C(2, 2)^4) \times 70$$
$$28224700 := (2 + 8! - C(2, 2)^4) \times 700$$

$$282261 := (2 + 8! + C(2, 2)) \times (6 + 1)$$
$$2822610 := (2 + 8! + C(2, 2)) \times (60 + 10)$$
$$28226100 := (2 + 8! + C(2, 2)) \times (600 + 100)$$

$$282624 := 2^8 \times C((-2 + 6)!, 2) \times 4$$
$$2826240 := 2^8 \times C((-2 + 6)!, 2) \times 40$$
$$28262400 := 2^8 \times C((-2 + 6)!, 2) \times 400$$

$$295335 := (-2 + 9^5 + C(3!, 3)) \times 5$$
$$2953350 := (-2 + 9^5 + C(3!, 3)) \times 50$$
$$29533500 := (-2 + 9^5 + C(3!, 3)) \times 500$$

$$297577 := (C((2 + 9 - 7)!, 5) + 7) \times 7$$
$$2975770 := (C((2 + 9 - 7)!, 5) + 7) \times 70$$
$$29757700 := (C((2 + 9 - 7)!, 5) + 7) \times 700$$

$$304224 := (-(3! - 0)! + C(4!, 2)^2) \times 4$$
$$3042240 := (-(3! - 0)! + C(4!, 2)^2) \times 40$$
$$30422400 := (-(3! - 0)! + C(4!, 2)^2) \times 400$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322648 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)! - 4) \times 8 \\ 3226480 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)! - 4) \times 80 \\ 32264800 &:= (C(3!, 2) + (2 + 6)! - 4) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322728 &:= ((3 \times 2 + 2)! + C(7, 2)) \times 8 \\ 3227280 &:= ((3 \times 2 + 2)! + C(7, 2)) \times 80 \\ 32272800 &:= ((3 \times 2 + 2)! + C(7, 2)) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 325344 &:= (3!! + 2 \times (5 + 3)! - 4!) \times 4 \\ 3253440 &:= (3!! + 2 \times (5 + 3)! - 4!) \times 40 \\ 32534400 &:= (3!! + 2 \times (5 + 3)! - 4!) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 326487 &:= (-C(3!, 2) + 6^{(4!/8)!}) \times 7 \\ 3264870 &:= (-C(3!, 2) + 6^{(4!/8)!}) \times 70 \\ 32648700 &:= (-C(3!, 2) + 6^{(4!/8)!}) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 327665 &:= (3 - 2 + C(7, 6)!) \times 65 \\ 3276650 &:= (3 - 2 + C(7, 6)!) \times 650 \\ 32766500 &:= (3 - 2 + C(7, 6)!) \times 6500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 328368 &:= (-C(3, 2) + 8! + 3^6) \times 8 \\ 3283680 &:= (-C(3, 2) + 8! + 3^6) \times 80 \\ 32836800 &:= (-C(3, 2) + 8! + 3^6) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 334492 &:= (-3!! + 3! + C(4! - 4, 9)) \times 2 \\ 3344920 &:= (-3!! + 3! + C(4! - 4, 9)) \times 20 \\ 33449200 &:= (-3!! + 3! + C(4! - 4, 9)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 337747 &:= (C(3, 3) + 7!) \times (74 - 7) \\ 3377470 &:= (C(3, 3) + 7!) \times (740 - 70) \\ 33774700 &:= (C(3, 3) + 7!) \times (7400 - 700) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 339507 &:= (C(3 \times 3!, 9) - 5! + 0!) \times 7 \\ 3395070 &:= (C(3 \times 3!, 9) - 5! + 0!) \times 70 \\ 33950700 &:= (C(3 \times 3!, 9) - 5! + 0!) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 341768 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 1 + 7!) \times 68 \\ 3417680 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 1 + 7!) \times 680 \\ 34176800 &:= (-C(3!, 4) + 1 + 7!) \times 6800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 342144 &:= 3!^{C(4,2)-1} \times 44 \\ 3421440 &:= 3!^{C(4,2)-1} \times 440 \\ 34214400 &:= 3!^{C(4,2)-1} \times 4400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 345465 &:= 3 \times (C(4! + 5, 4) - 6!) \times 5 \\ 3454650 &:= 3 \times (C(4! + 5, 4) - 6!) \times 50 \\ 34546500 &:= 3 \times (C(4! + 5, 4) - 6!) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 352716 &:= C(-3! + 5^2, 7) \times (1 + 6) \\ 3527160 &:= C(-3! + 5^2, 7) \times (10 + 60) \\ 35271600 &:= C(-3! + 5^2, 7) \times (100 + 600) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 352737 &:= (-3 + C(5, 2) \times 7! - 3!) \times 7 \\ 3527370 &:= (-3 + C(5, 2) \times 7! - 3!) \times 70 \\ 35273700 &:= (-3 + C(5, 2) \times 7! - 3!) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354264 &:= ((3 + 5!) \times C(4, 2)! + 6) \times 4 \\ 3542640 &:= ((3 + 5!) \times C(4, 2)! + 6) \times 40 \\ 35426400 &:= ((3 + 5!) \times C(4, 2)! + 6) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 354342 &:= (3^{C(5,4)+3!} + 4!) \times 2 \\ 3543420 &:= (3^{C(5,4)+3!} + 4!) \times 20 \\ 35434200 &:= (3^{C(5,4)+3!} + 4!) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 356523 &:= (-3 + C(5!/6, 5)) \times 23 \\ 3565230 &:= (-3 + C(5!/6, 5)) \times 230 \\ 35652300 &:= (-3 + C(5!/6, 5)) \times 2300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362265 &:= (-3 \times 6! + C(22, 6)) \times 5 \\ 3622650 &:= (-3 \times 6! + C(22, 6)) \times 50 \\ 36226500 &:= (-3 \times 6! + C(22, 6)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362790 &:= (-3 + (6 + 2)! - 7) \times (9 + 0) \\ 3627900 &:= (-3 + (6 + 2)! - 7) \times (90 + 0) \\ 36279000 &:= (-3 + (6 + 2)! - 7) \times (900 + 00) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362934 &:= (3! + (6 + 2)!) \times 9 \times (-3 + 4) \\ 3629340 &:= (3! + (6 + 2)!) \times 9 \times (-30 + 40) \\ 36293400 &:= (3! + (6 + 2)!) \times 9 \times (-300 + 400) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 364315 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) - 1) \times 5 \\ 3643150 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) - 1) \times 50 \\ 36431500 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) - 1) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 364335 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) + 3) \times 5 \\ 3643350 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) + 3) \times 50 \\ 36433500 &:= (36 \times C(4!, 3) + 3) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 371432 &:= (3!! \times 71 + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2 \\ 3714320 &:= (3!! \times 71 + C(4!, 3!)) \times 20 \\ 37143200 &:= (3!! \times 71 + C(4!, 3!)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 373065 &:= C(3 \times 7 + (3 \times 0)!, 6) \times 5 \\ 3730650 &:= C(3 \times 7 + (3 \times 0)!, 6) \times 50 \\ 37306500 &:= C(3 \times 7 + (3 \times 0)!, 6) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 374395 &:= (37 \times C(4!, 3) - 9) \times 5 \\ 3743950 &:= (37 \times C(4!, 3) - 9) \times 50 \\ 37439500 &:= (37 \times C(4!, 3) - 9) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 374465 &:= (3!! + 7! + C(4, 4)) \times 65 \\ 3744650 &:= (3!! + 7! + C(4, 4)) \times 650 \\ 37446500 &:= (3!! + 7! + C(4, 4)) \times 6500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 374568 &:= (-3 + 7! + C(4!, 5) - 6!) \times 8 \\ 3745680 &:= (-3 + 7! + C(4!, 5) - 6!) \times 80 \\ 37456800 &:= (-3 + 7! + C(4!, 5) - 6!) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 375375 &:= C(3 + 7 + 5, 3!) \times 75 \\ 3753750 &:= C(3 + 7 + 5, 3!) \times 750 \\ 37537500 &:= C(3 + 7 + 5, 3!) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 378225 &:= (3 + 7!) \times C(8 - 2, 2) \times 5 \\ 3782250 &:= (3 + 7!) \times C(8 - 2, 2) \times 50 \\ 37822500 &:= (3 + 7!) \times C(8 - 2, 2) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 382509 &:= (-3 + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 09 \\ 3825090 &:= (-3 + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 090 \\ 38250900 &:= (-3 + C((8/2)!, 5)) \times 0900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 382536 &:= C(3! \times 8/2, 5) \times (3 + 6) \\ 3825360 &:= C(3! \times 8/2, 5) \times (30 + 60) \\ 38253600 &:= C(3! \times 8/2, 5) \times (300 + 600) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 384384 &:= C(3! + 8, 4) \times 384 \\ 3843840 &:= C(3! + 8, 4) \times 3840 \\ 38438400 &:= C(3! + 8, 4) \times 38400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 399672 &:= 39 \times (C(9, 6) + 7!) \times 2 \\ 3996720 &:= 39 \times (C(9, 6) + 7!) \times 20 \\ 39967200 &:= 39 \times (C(9, 6) + 7!) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 403564 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 56) \times 4 \\ 4035640 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 56) \times 40 \\ 40356400 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 56) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 403744 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 7 - 4) \times 4 \\ 4037440 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 7 - 4) \times 40 \\ 40374400 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) - 7 - 4) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 403784 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) + 7 - 8) \times 4 \\ 4037840 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) + 7 - 8) \times 40 \\ 40378400 &:= (C(4! - 0!, 3!) + 7 - 8) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 403812 &:= (C(4!, 03!) + 8) \times (1 + 2) \\ 4038120 &:= (C(4!, 03!) + 8) \times (10 + 20) \\ 40381200 &:= (C(4!, 03!) + 8) \times (100 + 200) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 404804 &:= (C(4! + 0!, 4) \times 8 + 0!) \times 4 \\ 4048040 &:= (C(4! + 0!, 4) \times 8 + 0!) \times 40 \\ 40480400 &:= (C(4! + 0!, 4) \times 8 + 0!) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 413280 &:= (C(4, 1) + 3)! \times (2 + 80) \\ 4132800 &:= (C(4, 1) + 3)! \times (20 + 800) \\ 41328000 &:= (C(4, 1) + 3)! \times (200 + 8000) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 432432 &:= (4! + 3) \times C(2^4, 3!) \times 2 \\ 4324320 &:= (4! + 3) \times C(2^4, 3!) \times 20 \\ 43243200 &:= (4! + 3) \times C(2^4, 3!) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}433352 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + 3!! \times (-3! + 5!)) \times 2 \\4333520 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + 3!! \times (-3! + 5!)) \times 20 \\43335200 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + 3!! \times (-3! + 5!)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}434128 &:= (C(4! - 3, (4 - 1)!) + 2) \times 8 \\4341280 &:= (C(4! - 3, (4 - 1)!) + 2) \times 80 \\43412800 &:= (C(4! - 3, (4 - 1)!) + 2) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}434352 &:= (4 \times C(-3 + 4!, 3!) - 5!) \times 2 \\4343520 &:= (4 \times C(-3 + 4!, 3!) - 5!) \times 20 \\43435200 &:= (4 \times C(-3 + 4!, 3!) - 5!) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}437584 &:= (C(4!, 3!) - 7! \times 5) \times (8 - 4) \\4375840 &:= (C(4!, 3!) - 7! \times 5) \times (80 - 40) \\43758400 &:= (C(4!, 3!) - 7! \times 5) \times (800 - 400)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}437888 &:= (-4! \times 3 + 7! + 8) \times 88 \\4378880 &:= (-4! \times 3 + 7! + 8) \times 880 \\43788800 &:= (-4! \times 3 + 7! + 8) \times 8800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}439208 &:= C(4!, 3) \times (9 + 208) \\4392080 &:= C(4!, 3) \times (90 + 2080) \\43920800 &:= C(4!, 3) \times (900 + 20800)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}443256 &:= (-4! + (C(4, 3) \times 2)!) \times (5 + 6) \\4432560 &:= (-4! + (C(4, 3) \times 2)!) \times (50 + 60) \\44325600 &:= (-4! + (C(4, 3) \times 2)!) \times (500 + 600)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}444276 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 4! \times 2) \times 7 \times 6 \\4442760 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 4! \times 2) \times 7 \times 60 \\44427600 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 4! \times 2) \times 7 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}445242 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 5^2) \times 42 \\4452420 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 5^2) \times 420 \\44524200 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 5^2) \times 4200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446292 &:= C(4!, 4) \times (6 \times 2 + 9) \times 2 \\4462920 &:= C(4!, 4) \times (6 \times 2 + 9) \times 20 \\44629200 &:= C(4!, 4) \times (6 \times 2 + 9) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446327 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3 + 2) \times 7 \\4463270 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3 + 2) \times 70 \\44632700 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3 + 2) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446334 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3!) \times (3 + 4) \\4463340 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3!) \times (30 + 40) \\44633400 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3!) \times (300 + 400)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446376 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 6/3) \times 7 \times 6 \\4463760 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 6/3) \times 7 \times 60 \\44637600 &:= (C(4!, 4) + 6/3) \times 7 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446397 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3! + 9) \times 7 \\4463970 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3! + 9) \times 70 \\44639700 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 3! + 9) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446535 &:= (4! + (4! + 6!) \times 5! + 3) \times 5 \\4465350 &:= (4! + (4! + 6!) \times 5! + 3) \times 50 \\44653500 &:= (4! + (4! + 6!) \times 5! + 3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}446957 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 95) \times 7 \\4469570 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 95) \times 70 \\44695700 &:= (C(4!, 4) \times 6 + 95) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}450553 &:= (C(4!, 5) + 0!)/5 \times 53 \\4505530 &:= (C(4!, 5) + 0!)/5 \times 530 \\45055300 &:= (C(4!, 5) + 0!)/5 \times 5300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453543 &:= (-4! + (C(5, 3)! + 5!)/4!) \times 3 \\4535430 &:= (-4! + (C(5, 3)! + 5!)/4!) \times 30 \\45354300 &:= (-4! + (C(5, 3)! + 5!)/4!) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453576 &:= (-4 + (C(5, 3) + 5) \times 7!) \times 6 \\4535760 &:= (-4 + (C(5, 3) + 5) \times 7!) \times 60 \\45357600 &:= (-4 + (C(5, 3) + 5) \times 7!) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453585 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)!/5)/8 \times 5 \\4535850 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)!/5)/8 \times 50 \\45358500 &:= (-4! + C(5, 3)!/5)/8 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453888 &:= (C(4!,5)/3! + 8) \times 8 \times 8 \\4538880 &:= (C(4!,5)/3! + 8) \times 8 \times 80 \\45388800 &:= (C(4!,5)/3! + 8) \times 8 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}453945 &:= (C(4!,5 - 3) + 9!)/4 \times 5 \\4539450 &:= (C(4!,5 - 3) + 9!)/4 \times 50 \\45394500 &:= (C(4!,5 - 3) + 9!)/4 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}455409 &:= (4 \times C(5 \times 5,4) + 0!) \times 9 \\4554090 &:= (4 \times C(5 \times 5,4) + 0!) \times 90 \\45540900 &:= (4 \times C(5 \times 5,4) + 0!) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}455736 &:= (-4 + (5! + 5 \times 7!)) \times 3 \times 6 \\4557360 &:= (-4 + (5! + 5 \times 7!)) \times 3 \times 60 \\45573600 &:= (-4 + (5! + 5 \times 7!)) \times 3 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}457432 &:= (4 + (5! - 7) \times C(4!,3)) \times 2 \\4574320 &:= (4 + (5! - 7) \times C(4!,3)) \times 20 \\45743200 &:= (4 + (5! - 7) \times C(4!,3)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}458565 &:= (C(4!,5)/8 + 5! \times 6!) \times 5 \\4585650 &:= (C(4!,5)/8 + 5! \times 6!) \times 50 \\45856500 &:= (C(4!,5)/8 + 5! \times 6!) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}460455 &:= (C(4!,6) - 0! - C(4!,5)) \times 5 \\4604550 &:= (C(4!,6) - 0! - C(4!,5)) \times 50 \\46045500 &:= (C(4!,6) - 0! - C(4!,5)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}463968 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times (-3 + C(9,6)) \times 8 \\4639680 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times (-3 + C(9,6)) \times 80 \\46396800 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times (-3 + C(9,6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}464544 &:= 4! \times (-6 + C(4 \times 5,4)) \times 4 \\4645440 &:= 4! \times (-6 + C(4 \times 5,4)) \times 40 \\46454400 &:= 4! \times (-6 + C(4 \times 5,4)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}464976 &:= (-4! + C(6!/(4 \times 9),7)) \times 6 \\4649760 &:= (-4! + C(6!/(4 \times 9),7)) \times 60 \\46497600 &:= (-4! + C(6!/(4 \times 9),7)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}467544 &:= C(4!,6 - 7 + 5) \times 44 \\4675440 &:= C(4!,6 - 7 + 5) \times 440 \\46754400 &:= C(4!,6 - 7 + 5) \times 4400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}474794 &:= (-4! + C(7,4) + 7!) \times 94 \\4747940 &:= (-4! + C(7,4) + 7!) \times 940 \\47479400 &:= (-4! + C(7,4) + 7!) \times 9400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}475744 &:= (-C(4!,C(7,5)) + 7! \times 4!) \times 4 \\4757440 &:= (-C(4!,C(7,5)) + 7! \times 4!) \times 40 \\47574400 &:= (-C(4!,C(7,5)) + 7! \times 4!) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}476883 &:= (C(4!,7) + 6!)/8 \times (8 + 3) \\4768830 &:= (C(4!,7) + 6!)/8 \times (80 + 30) \\47688300 &:= (C(4!,7) + 6!)/8 \times (800 + 300)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}483312 &:= (-4! + 8! - C(3!,3)) \times 12 \\4833120 &:= (-4! + 8! - C(3!,3)) \times 120 \\48331200 &:= (-4! + 8! - C(3!,3)) \times 1200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}483543 &:= (4 \times 8! - 3 - 5! + 4!) \times 3 \\4835430 &:= (4 \times 8! - 3 - 5! + 4!) \times 30 \\48354300 &:= (4 \times 8! - 3 - 5! + 4!) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}483873 &:= (4 \times 8! + 3 + C(8,7)) \times 3 \\4838730 &:= (4 \times 8! + 3 + C(8,7)) \times 30 \\48387300 &:= (4 \times 8! + 3 + C(8,7)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}483884 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times 3 - C(8,8)) \times 4 \\4838840 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times 3 - C(8,8)) \times 40 \\48388400 &:= ((4 + 8!) \times 3 - C(8,8)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}484272 &:= 4! \times (8!/4 + 2 + 7) \times 2 \\4842720 &:= 4! \times (8!/4 + 2 + 7) \times 20 \\48427200 &:= 4! \times (8!/4 + 2 + 7) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}484356 &:= (-4 + C((8 - 4)! + 3,5)) \times 6 \\4843560 &:= (-4 + C((8 - 4)! + 3,5)) \times 60 \\48435600 &:= (-4 + C((8 - 4)! + 3,5)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 486843 &:= (4 \times 8! + C(6 + 8, 4)) \times 3 \\ 4868430 &:= (4 \times 8! + C(6 + 8, 4)) \times 30 \\ 48684300 &:= (4 \times 8! + C(6 + 8, 4)) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 490312 &:= (C(4!, 9 - 0!) / 3 - 1) \times 2 \\ 4903120 &:= (C(4!, 9 - 0!) / 3 - 1) \times 20 \\ 49031200 &:= (C(4!, 9 - 0!) / 3 - 1) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 495495 &:= C(4! - 9, 5) \times (4! + 9) \times 5 \\ 4954950 &:= C(4! - 9, 5) \times (4! + 9) \times 50 \\ 49549500 &:= C(4! - 9, 5) \times (4! + 9) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 504735 &:= C(-5 - (0 - 4) \times 7, 3!) \times 5 \\ 5047350 &:= C(-5 - (0 - 4) \times 7, 3!) \times 50 \\ 50473500 &:= C(-5 - (0 - 4) \times 7, 3!) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 513366 &:= (5! - 1) \times (-C(3, 3) + 6!) \times 6 \\ 5133660 &:= (5! - 1) \times (-C(3, 3) + 6!) \times 60 \\ 51336600 &:= (5! - 1) \times (-C(3, 3) + 6!) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 526986 &:= ((5! + 2) \times 6! - C(9, 8)) \times 6 \\ 5269860 &:= ((5! + 2) \times 6! - C(9, 8)) \times 60 \\ 52698600 &:= ((5! + 2) \times 6! - C(9, 8)) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 529725 &:= (5 + (-2 + 9)!) \times C(7, 2) \times 5 \\ 5297250 &:= (5 + (-2 + 9)!) \times C(7, 2) \times 50 \\ 52972500 &:= (5 + (-2 + 9)!) \times C(7, 2) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 531303 &:= (C(5^{3-1}, 3!) + 0!) \times 3 \\ 5313030 &:= (C(5^{3-1}, 3!) + 0!) \times 30 \\ 53130300 &:= (C(5^{3-1}, 3!) + 0!) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 534492 &:= ((5 + 3)! - C(4!, 4)) \times 9 \times 2 \\ 5344920 &:= ((5 + 3)! - C(4!, 4)) \times 9 \times 20 \\ 53449200 &:= ((5 + 3)! - C(4!, 4)) \times 9 \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 535464 &:= (-5 - 3!! - 5 + C(4!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 5354640 &:= (-5 - 3!! - 5 + C(4!, 6)) \times 40 \\ 53546400 &:= (-5 - 3!! - 5 + C(4!, 6)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 537607 &:= (C(5!/3!, 7) - 6! + 0!) \times 7 \\ 5376070 &:= (C(5!/3!, 7) - 6! + 0!) \times 70 \\ 53760700 &:= (C(5!/3!, 7) - 6! + 0!) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 538264 &:= (-5 \times 3! + C((8/2)!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 5382640 &:= (-5 \times 3! + C((8/2)!, 6)) \times 40 \\ 53826400 &:= (-5 \times 3! + C((8/2)!, 6)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 538404 &:= (5 + C(3 \times 8, (4 - 0)!)) \times 4 \\ 5384040 &:= (5 + C(3 \times 8, (4 - 0)!)) \times 40 \\ 53840400 &:= (5 + C(3 \times 8, (4 - 0)!)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 538864 &:= (5! + C((3 + C(8, 8))!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 5388640 &:= (5! + C((3 + C(8, 8))!, 6)) \times 40 \\ 53886400 &:= (5! + C((3 + C(8, 8))!, 6)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 539464 &:= (5 \times 3! \times 9 + C(4!, 6)) \times 4 \\ 5394640 &:= (5 \times 3! \times 9 + C(4!, 6)) \times 40 \\ 53946400 &:= (5 \times 3! \times 9 + C(4!, 6)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 543664 &:= (-5! + C(4!, 3!) + 6! + 6!) \times 4 \\ 5436640 &:= (-5! + C(4!, 3!) + 6! + 6!) \times 40 \\ 54366400 &:= (-5! + C(4!, 3!) + 6! + 6!) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 544356 &:= ((5 + 4)! / 4 + C(3!, 5)) \times 6 \\ 5443560 &:= ((5 + 4)! / 4 + C(3!, 5)) \times 60 \\ 54435600 &:= ((5 + 4)! / 4 + C(3!, 5)) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 547547 &:= (C(5, 4)^7 + 5! - 4!) \times 7 \\ 5475470 &:= (C(5, 4)^7 + 5! - 4!) \times 70 \\ 54754700 &:= (C(5, 4)^7 + 5! - 4!) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 575232 &:= (5! + C(7 + 5, 2)^3) \times 2 \\ 5752320 &:= (5! + C(7 + 5, 2)^3) \times 20 \\ 57523200 &:= (5! + C(7 + 5, 2)^3) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 587657 &:= (5 \times 8! - 7^{C(6,5)}) \times 7 \\ 5876570 &:= (5 \times 8! - 7^{C(6,5)}) \times 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$58765700 := (5 \times 8! - 7^{C(6,5)}) \times 700$$

$$66692500 := (6! + C(6,6)) \times 92500$$

$$595056 := C((-5 + 9)!, 5 - 0!) \times 56$$

$$683472 := -(6! + 8) \times 3! + C(4!, 7) \times 2$$

$$5950560 := C((-5 + 9)!, 5 - 0!) \times 560$$

$$6834720 := -(6! + 8) \times 3! + C(4!, 7) \times 20$$

$$59505600 := C((-5 + 9)!, 5 - 0!) \times 5600$$

$$68347200 := -(6! + 8) \times 3! + C(4!, 7) \times 200$$

$$599697 := ((5! - C(9,9)) \times 6! - 9) \times 7$$

$$685389 := (6! \times C(8,5) - 3) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5996970 := ((5! - C(9,9)) \times 6! - 9) \times 70$$

$$6853890 := (6! \times C(8,5) - 3) \times (80 + 90)$$

$$59969700 := ((5! - C(9,9)) \times 6! - 9) \times 700$$

$$68538900 := (6! \times C(8,5) - 3) \times (800 + 900)$$

$$619272 := 61 \times (C(9,2) + 7!) \times 2$$

$$704492 := (-7 - 0! - C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 2$$

$$6192720 := 61 \times (C(9,2) + 7!) \times 20$$

$$7044920 := (-7 - 0! - C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 20$$

$$61927200 := 61 \times (C(9,2) + 7!) \times 200$$

$$70449200 := (-7 - 0! - C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 200$$

$$622944 := (6! + C(2,2)) \times 9 \times 4! \times 4$$

$$705432 := C(C(7,05), 4 + 3!) \times 2$$

$$6229440 := (6! + C(2,2)) \times 9 \times 4! \times 40$$

$$7054320 := C(C(7,05), 4 + 3!) \times 20$$

$$62294400 := (6! + C(2,2)) \times 9 \times 4! \times 400$$

$$70543200 := C(C(7,05), 4 + 3!) \times 200$$

$$633604 := (C(6 + 3!, 3) \times 6! + 0!) \times 4$$

$$715792 := (C(7 + 1, 5) - 7! + 9!) \times 2$$

$$6336040 := (C(6 + 3!, 3) \times 6! + 0!) \times 40$$

$$7157920 := (C(7 + 1, 5) - 7! + 9!) \times 20$$

$$63360400 := (C(6 + 3!, 3) \times 6! + 0!) \times 400$$

$$71579200 := (C(7 + 1, 5) - 7! + 9!) \times 200$$

$$644816 := (-C(6,4) - 4 + 8!) \times 16$$

$$724292 := (-7 \times 2 - C(4,2)! + 9!) \times 2$$

$$6448160 := (-C(6,4) - 4 + 8!) \times 160$$

$$7242920 := (-7 \times 2 - C(4,2)! + 9!) \times 20$$

$$64481600 := (-C(6,4) - 4 + 8!) \times 1600$$

$$72429200 := (-7 \times 2 - C(4,2)! + 9!) \times 200$$

$$644832 := (-6 \times 4! + 4! \times 8! / 3) \times 2$$

$$725274 := (-C(7,2) + 5!)^2 \times 74$$

$$6448320 := (-6 \times 4! + 4! \times 8! / 3) \times 20$$

$$7252740 := (-C(7,2) + 5!)^2 \times 740$$

$$64483200 := (-6 \times 4! + 4! \times 8! / 3) \times 200$$

$$72527400 := (-C(7,2) + 5!)^2 \times 7400$$

$$655207 := (6! \times (5! + C(5,2)) + 0!) \times 7$$

$$725492 := (-7 \times 2 - C(5,4)! + 9!) \times 2$$

$$6552070 := (6! \times (5! + C(5,2)) + 0!) \times 70$$

$$7254920 := (-7 \times 2 - C(5,4)! + 9!) \times 20$$

$$65520700 := (6! \times (5! + C(5,2)) + 0!) \times 700$$

$$72549200 := (-7 \times 2 - C(5,4)! + 9!) \times 200$$

$$656928 := ((-6 + 5!) \times 6! + C(9,2)) \times 8$$

$$725812 := (C(7,2) + 5 + (8 + 1)!) \times 2$$

$$6569280 := ((-6 + 5!) \times 6! + C(9,2)) \times 80$$

$$7258120 := (C(7,2) + 5 + (8 + 1)!) \times 20$$

$$65692800 := ((-6 + 5!) \times 6! + C(9,2)) \times 800$$

$$72581200 := (C(7,2) + 5 + (8 + 1)!) \times 200$$

$$666925 := (6! + C(6,6)) \times 925$$

$$725886 := (C(7,2) + (-5 + 8) \times 8!) \times 6$$

$$6669250 := (6! + C(6,6)) \times 9250$$

$$7258860 := (C(7,2) + (-5 + 8) \times 8!) \times 60$$

$$72588600 := (C(7,2) + (-5 + 8) \times 8!) \times 600$$

$$75624300 := (7^5 \times C(6,2) - 4!) \times 300$$

$$725892 := (C(7,2) + (5 + 8!) \times 9) \times 2$$

$$777336 := (-7! + C((C(7,7) + 3)!, 3!)) \times 6$$

$$7258920 := (C(7,2) + (5 + 8!) \times 9) \times 20$$

$$7773360 := (-7! + C((C(7,7) + 3)!, 3!)) \times 60$$

$$72589200 := (C(7,2) + (5 + 8!) \times 9) \times 200$$

$$77733600 := (-7! + C((C(7,7) + 3)!, 3!)) \times 600$$

$$725972 := (-C(7,2) + 5! + 9! + 7) \times 2$$

$$827872 := 82 \times (7! + C(8,7)) \times 2$$

$$7259720 := (-C(7,2) + 5! + 9! + 7) \times 20$$

$$8278720 := 82 \times (7! + C(8,7)) \times 20$$

$$72597200 := (-C(7,2) + 5! + 9! + 7) \times 200$$

$$82787200 := 82 \times (7! + C(8,7)) \times 200$$

$$725982 := (-7 - 2 + 5! + C(9,8)!) \times 2$$

$$834834 := C(8 + 3!, 4) \times 834$$

$$7259820 := (-7 - 2 + 5! + C(9,8)!) \times 20$$

$$8348340 := C(8 + 3!, 4) \times 8340$$

$$72598200 := (-7 - 2 + 5! + C(9,8)!) \times 200$$

$$83483400 := C(8 + 3!, 4) \times 83400$$

$$726768 := C(7,2) \times (6 + 7! - 6!) \times 8$$

$$841344 := (8! + C(4!, -1 + 3!) \times 4) \times 4$$

$$7267680 := C(7,2) \times (6 + 7! - 6!) \times 80$$

$$8413440 := (8! + C(4!, -1 + 3!) \times 4) \times 40$$

$$72676800 := C(7,2) \times (6 + 7! - 6!) \times 800$$

$$84134400 := (8! + C(4!, -1 + 3!) \times 4) \times 400$$

$$727272 := (7! \times 2 + C(7,2)) \times 72$$

$$845952 := (8! + C(4!, 5) \times 9 + 5!) \times 2$$

$$7272720 := (7! \times 2 + C(7,2)) \times 720$$

$$8459520 := (8! + C(4!, 5) \times 9 + 5!) \times 20$$

$$72727200 := (7! \times 2 + C(7,2)) \times 7200$$

$$84595200 := (8! + C(4!, 5) \times 9 + 5!) \times 200$$

$$735693 := (-(C(7,3)/5)^6 + 9!) \times 3$$

$$864864 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 864$$

$$7356930 := (-(C(7,3)/5)^6 + 9!) \times 30$$

$$8648640 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 8640$$

$$73569300 := (-(C(7,3)/5)^6 + 9!) \times 300$$

$$86486400 := C(8 + 6, 4) \times 86400$$

$$744492 := (-7!/4 + C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 2$$

$$874615 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6)) \times 1 \times 5$$

$$7444920 := (-7!/4 + C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 20$$

$$8746150 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6)) \times 1 \times 50$$

$$74449200 := (-7!/4 + C(4!, 4) + 9!) \times 200$$

$$87461500 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6)) \times 1 \times 500$$

$$752435 := (7 + C(5,2)!/4! - 3!!) \times 5$$

$$874625 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6) + 2) \times 5$$

$$7524350 := (7 + C(5,2)!/4! - 3!!) \times 50$$

$$8746250 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6) + 2) \times 50$$

$$75243500 := (7 + C(5,2)!/4! - 3!!) \times 500$$

$$87462500 := (8! + 7 + C(4!, 6) + 2) \times 500$$

$$753375 := (7! + C(5 \times 3, 3!)) \times 75$$

$$876568 := (C(8,6) + 5^6) \times 7 \times 8$$

$$7533750 := (7! + C(5 \times 3, 3!)) \times 750$$

$$8765680 := (C(8,6) + 5^6) \times 7 \times 80$$

$$75337500 := (7! + C(5 \times 3, 3!)) \times 7500$$

$$87656800 := (C(8,6) + 5^6) \times 7 \times 800$$

$$756243 := (7^5 \times C(6,2) - 4!) \times 3$$

$$911493 := (-9^{C(1,1)+4} + 9!) \times 3$$

$$7562430 := (7^5 \times C(6,2) - 4!) \times 30$$

$$9114930 := (-9^{C(1,1)+4} + 9!) \times 30$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 91149300 &:= (-9^{C(1,1)+4} + 9!) \times 300 \\
 925344 &:= C(9 \times 2, 5) \times (3 + 4!) \times 4 \\
 9253440 &:= C(9 \times 2, 5) \times (3 + 4!) \times 40 \\
 92534400 &:= C(9 \times 2, 5) \times (3 + 4!) \times 400 \\
 937432 &:= (93 \times 7! - C(4, 3)) \times 2 \\
 9374320 &:= (93 \times 7! - C(4, 3)) \times 20 \\
 93743200 &:= (93 \times 7! - C(4, 3)) \times 200 \\
 942067 &:= (-9 + C(4!, (2 + 0!)!) - 6) \times 7 \\
 9420670 &:= (-9 + C(4!, (2 + 0!)!) - 6) \times 70 \\
 94206700 &:= (-9 + C(4!, (2 + 0!)!) - 6) \times 700 \\
 954954 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 954 \\
 9549540 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 9540 \\
 95495400 &:= C(9 + 5, 4) \times 95400 \\
 959283 &:= (-9 + C((-5 + 9)! - 2, 8)) \times 3 \\
 9592830 &:= (-9 + C((-5 + 9)! - 2, 8)) \times 30 \\
 95928300 &:= (-9 + C((-5 + 9)! - 2, 8)) \times 300 \\
 966672 &:= C(9, 6) \times (6! - 6 + 7!) \times 2 \\
 9666720 &:= C(9, 6) \times (6! - 6 + 7!) \times 20 \\
 96667200 &:= C(9, 6) \times (6! - 6 + 7!) \times 200 \\
 967644 &:= (-9 + 6! \times 7! / C(6, 4)) \times 4 \\
 9676440 &:= (-9 + 6! \times 7! / C(6, 4)) \times 40 \\
 96764400 &:= (-9 + 6! \times 7! / C(6, 4)) \times 400
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 967683 &:= (9! - 6 + C(7, 6) - 8!) \times 3 \\
 9676830 &:= (9! - 6 + C(7, 6) - 8!) \times 30 \\
 96768300 &:= (9! - 6 + C(7, 6) - 8!) \times 300 \\
 967722 &:= (96 \times 7! + C(7, 2)) \times 2 \\
 9677220 &:= (96 \times 7! + C(7, 2)) \times 20 \\
 96772200 &:= (96 \times 7! + C(7, 2)) \times 200 \\
 982737 &:= (-9 + C(8, 2) \times 7! - 3!!) \times 7 \\
 9827370 &:= (-9 + C(8, 2) \times 7! - 3!!) \times 70 \\
 98273700 &:= (-9 + C(8, 2) \times 7! - 3!!) \times 700 \\
 983432 &:= (9! - 8 \times 3!! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 2 \\
 9834320 &:= (9! - 8 \times 3!! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 20 \\
 98343200 &:= (9! - 8 \times 3!! + C(4!, 3!)) \times 200 \\
 983682 &:= (C(9, 8)^{3!} + 6! - 8!) \times 2 \\
 9836820 &:= (C(9, 8)^{3!} + 6! - 8!) \times 20 \\
 98368200 &:= (C(9, 8)^{3!} + 6! - 8!) \times 200 \\
 995328 &:= 9 \times (9 - 5)!^{C(3,2)} \times 8 \\
 9953280 &:= 9 \times (9 - 5)!^{C(3,2)} \times 80 \\
 99532800 &:= 9 \times (9 - 5)!^{C(3,2)} \times 800 \\
 997920 &:= (9 + 9) \times 7! \times (9 + 2 + 0) \\
 9979200 &:= (9 + 9) \times 7! \times (90 + 20 + 0) \\
 99792000 &:= (9 + 9) \times 7! \times (90 + 200 + 0)
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3 Square-Root

$$\begin{aligned}
 12397 &:= C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 7 \\
 123970 &:= C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 70 \\
 1239700 &:= C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 700 \\
 13728 &:= C(13, \sqrt{7^2}) \times 8 \\
 137280 &:= C(13, \sqrt{7^2}) \times 80 \\
 1372800 &:= C(13, \sqrt{7^2}) \times 800
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74431 &:= 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} \times 31 \\
 744310 &:= 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} \times 310 \\
 7443100 &:= 7^{\sqrt{4 \times 4}} \times 3100 \\
 299382 &:= (C(29, \sqrt{9}) - 3) \times 82 \\
 2993820 &:= (C(29, \sqrt{9}) - 3) \times 820
 \end{aligned}$$

$$29938200 := (C(29, \sqrt{9}) - 3) \times 8200$$

$$379827 := (-3 + C(7 \times \sqrt{9}, 8 - 2)) \times 7$$

$$3798270 := (-3 + C(7 \times \sqrt{9}, 8 - 2)) \times 70$$

$$37982700 := (-3 + C(7 \times \sqrt{9}, 8 - 2)) \times 700$$

$$435456 := (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{C(5,4)} \times 56$$

$$4354560 := (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{C(5,4)} \times 560$$

$$43545600 := (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{C(5,4)} \times 5600$$

$$447666 := (-\sqrt{4} + C(4 \times 7 - 6, 6)) \times 6$$

$$4476660 := (-\sqrt{4} + C(4 \times 7 - 6, 6)) \times 60$$

$$44766600 := (-\sqrt{4} + C(4 \times 7 - 6, 6)) \times 600$$

$$447696 := (C(\sqrt{4} \times (4 + 7), 6) + \sqrt{9}) \times 6$$

$$4476960 := (C(\sqrt{4} \times (4 + 7), 6) + \sqrt{9}) \times 60$$

$$44769600 := (C(\sqrt{4} \times (4 + 7), 6) + \sqrt{9}) \times 600$$

$$458752 := (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times C(8, 7)^5 \times 2$$

$$4587520 := (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times C(8, 7)^5 \times 20$$

$$45875200 := (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times C(8, 7)^5 \times 200$$

$$466735 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + C(7, 3)) \times 5$$

$$4667350 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + C(7, 3)) \times 50$$

$$46673500 := (\sqrt{4} \times 6^6 + C(7, 3)) \times 500$$

$$474474 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4) \times 474$$

$$4744740 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4) \times 4740$$

$$47447400 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4) \times 47400$$

$$744744 := C(7 \times \sqrt{4}, 4) \times 744$$

$$7447440 := C(7 \times \sqrt{4}, 4) \times 7440$$

$$74474400 := C(7 \times \sqrt{4}, 4) \times 74400$$

$$918897 := (\sqrt{9} \times C(18, 8) - \sqrt{9}) \times 7$$

$$9188970 := (\sqrt{9} \times C(18, 8) - \sqrt{9}) \times 70$$

$$91889700 := (\sqrt{9} \times C(18, 8) - \sqrt{9}) \times 700$$

$$944649 := ((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4 - C(6, 4)) \times 9$$

$$9446490 := ((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4 - C(6, 4)) \times 90$$

$$94464900 := ((9 \times \sqrt{4})^4 - C(6, 4)) \times 900$$

$$945561 := (-\sqrt{9} + C(4 \times 5, 5)) \times 61$$

$$9455610 := (-\sqrt{9} + C(4 \times 5, 5)) \times 610$$

$$94556100 := (-\sqrt{9} + C(4 \times 5, 5)) \times 6100$$

$$972415 := (\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)^4 - 1) \times 5$$

$$9724150 := (\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)^4 - 1) \times 50$$

$$97241500 := (\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)^4 - 1) \times 500$$

4 Revere Order Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients

This section brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** in different situations. Results are in terms of reverse order of digits. First only with **basic operations**. Secondly, with use of **factorial** and then with used of **square-root**. Results based on using together **factorial** and **square-root** are also obtained but only up to 5 digits. All other types are up to 6x digits. In all cases, binomial coefficients are always present.

4.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** just with basic operations and in reverse order of digits. Only basic operations are used The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

4.1.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$00028 := C(8,2) + 000$$

$$00128 := C(8,2) + 100$$

$$00228 := C(8,2) + 200$$

$$00328 := C(8,2) + 300$$

$$00428 := C(8,2) + 400$$

$$00528 := C(8,2) + 500$$

$$00628 := C(8,2) + 600$$

$$00728 := C(8,2) + 700$$

$$00828 := C(8,2) + 800$$

$$00928 := C(8,2) + 900$$

$$38610 := 0 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38611 := 1 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38612 := 2 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38613 := 3 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38614 := 4 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38615 := 5 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38616 := 6 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38617 := 7 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38618 := 8 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$38619 := 9 + C(16,8) \times 3$$

$$001128 := C(8,2) + 1100$$

$$002228 := C(8,2) + 2200$$

$$003328 := C(8,2) + 3300$$

$$004428 := C(8,2) + 4400$$

$$005528 := C(8,2) + 5500$$

$$006628 := C(8,2) + 6600$$

$$007728 := C(8,2) + 7700$$

$$008828 := C(8,2) + 8800$$

$$009928 := C(8,2) + 9900$$

$$011440 := 0 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011441 := 1 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011442 := 2 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011443 := 3 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011444 := 4 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011445 := 5 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011446 := 6 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011447 := 7 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011448 := 8 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$011449 := 9 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10)$$

$$077450 := 0 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077451 := 1 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077452 := 2 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077453 := 3 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077454 := 4 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077455 := 5 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077456 := 6 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077457 := 7 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077458 := 8 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$077459 := 9 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70$$

$$117670 := 0 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117671 := 1 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117672 := 2 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117673 := 3 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117674 := 4 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117675 := 5 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117676 := 6 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117677 := 7 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117678 := 8 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$117679 := 9 + 7^6 + C(7, 1 + 1)$$

$$183680 := 0 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183681 := 1 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183682 := 2 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183683 := 3 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183684 := 4 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183685 := 5 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183686 := 6 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183687 := 7 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183688 := 8 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$183689 := 9 + C(8,6) \times (3^8 - 1)$$

$$497420 := 0 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4)$$

$$497421 := 1 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 497422 &:= 2 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497423 &:= 3 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497424 &:= 4 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497425 &:= 5 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497426 &:= 6 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 497427 &:= 7 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497428 &:= 8 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497429 &:= 9 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \\ 497429 &:= 9 + C(2 \times (4 + 7), 9 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

4.1.2 Non Symmetric Representations

$$28 := C(8, 2)$$

$$2916 := (C(6, 1) \times 9)^2$$

$$3125 := 5^{C(2,1)+3}$$

$$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$$

$$12869 := C(9 + 6, 8) \times 2 - 1$$

$$15504 := C(4 \times 05, 5) \times 1$$

$$19683 := C(3, 8 - 6)^{C(9,1)}$$

$$23398 := 8 \times C(9 \times 3, 3) - 2$$

$$24288 := 88 \times C(24, 2)$$

$$24568 := C(C(8, 6), 5) / 4 - 2$$

$$25088 := 8 \times C(8, 05)^2$$

$$28224 := (C(4, 2) \times 28)^2$$

$$32758 := 8^5 - C(7 - 2, 3)$$

$$37674 := C(4 \times 7, 6) / (7 + 3)$$

$$38472 := (2 \times 7)^4 + C(8, 3)$$

$$44275 := 5 \times C(7 + 2^4, 4)$$

$$46566 := 6 \times (6^5 - C(6, 4))$$

$$46667 := C(7, 6) + 6^6 + 4$$

$$46671 := (-1 + 7)^6 + C(6, 4)$$

$$59511 := C(11, 5) + 9^5$$

$$59973 := -3 + 7 \times C(9 + 9, 5)$$

$$74381 := -1 + C(8 \times 3, 4) \times 7$$

$$77513 := C((3 + 1) \times 5, 7) - 7$$

$$92374 := -4 + C(7 \times 3 - 2, 9)$$

$$004445 := C(5 \times 4, 4) - 400$$

$$012584 := 4 \times (C(8, 5)^2 + 10)$$

$$012882 := C(2 \times 8, 8) + 2 + 10$$

$$015015 := 5 \times C(10 + 5, 10)$$

$$015494 := C(4 \times (9 - 4), 5) - 10$$

$$015554 := C(4 \times 5, 5) + 5 \times 10$$

$$016344 := 4 \times (C(4, 3)^6 - 10)$$

$$017517 := C(7, 1)^5 + 710$$

$$019444 := -4 + C(4 + 4 + 9, 10)$$

$$019448 := C(8 \times 4 / 4 + 9, 10)$$

$$019683 := 3^{(C(8,6)-9-10)}$$

$$021252 := 2 \times C(5^2 - 1, 20)$$

$$042542 := C(24, 5) - 2 + 40$$

$$042546 := C(6 \times 4, 5) + 2 + 40$$

$$046628 := -C(8, 2) + 6^6 + 4 \times 0$$

$$046636 := C(6, 3) + 6^6 - 40$$

$$046655 := -C(5, 5) + 6^6 + 4 \times 0$$

$$046668 := -C(8, 6) + 6^6 + 40$$

$$102912 := C(2, 1)^9 \times 201$$

$$116275 := -5 + C(C(7, 2), C(6, 1) + 1)$$

$$116281 := C(C(-1 + 8, 2), 6 + 1) + 1$$

$$116565 := (-5 + 6^5) \times C(6, 1 + 1)$$

$$117649 := (9 + 4 - 6)^{(C(7,1)-1)}$$

$$117667 := C(7, 6)^6 + 7 + 11$$

$$125845 := C(5 \times 4, 8) - 5^{2+1}$$

$$127294 := 4 \times C(9 \times 2, 7) - C(2, 1)$$

$$131562 := (C(26, 5) + 1) \times (3 - 1)$$

$$132651 := (15 + 6^2)^{C(3,1)}$$

$$134457 := 7^5 \times (4 + C(4, 3)) + 1$$

$$134596 := C(6 \times (9 - 5), 4 + 3 - 1)$$

$$134638 := C(8 \times 3, 6) + 43 - 1$$

$$135284 := (-4 + C(8 \times 2, 5)) \times 31$$

$$135691 := C(19, 6) \times 5 + 31$$

$$136296 := 6 \times C(9, 2) \times 631$$

$$137284 := 4 \times (C(8 \times 2, 7) \times 3 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147348 &:= (8^4 - 3) \times (C(7,4) + 1) & 272916 &:= (6 \times 19)^2 \times C(7,2) \\ 152875 &:= 5 \times (7 \times C(8 \times 2,5) - 1) & 273354 &:= 45^3 \times 3 - C(7,2) \\ 153664 &:= 4 \times (-6 + C(6,3))^{5-1} & 275625 &:= ((C(5,2) + 65) \times 7)^2 \\ 157469 &:= (9 \times 6)^{-4+7} + C(5,1) & 279276 &:= 6^7 - C(2 + 9,7) \times 2 \\ 162786 &:= -6 + 8 \times C(C(7,2),6 - 1) & 279576 &:= 6^7 - 5 \times C(9,7) \times 2 \\ 163288 &:= 8 \times (C(8,2) \times 3^6 - 1) & 279816 &:= 6^{-1+8} - C(9 + 7,2) \\ 164288 &:= 8 \times (C(C(8,2),4) + 61) & 279934 &:= (4 + 3 - C(9,9))^7 - 2 \\ 167954 &:= C(4 \times 5,9) - C(7,6) + 1 & 289737 &:= 73 \times (7 \times C(9,8))^2 \\ 175175 &:= 5 \times 7 \times C(15,7 - 1) & 292681 &:= (1 + C(8,6) + 2^9)^2 \\ 183568 &:= C(8,6) \times (-5 + 3^8 \times 1) & 293912 &:= C(21,9 + 3) - 9 \times 2 \\ 183699 &:= -9 + C(9,6) \times 3^{8-1} & 293924 &:= -4 + C(2 \times 9 + 3,9) - 2 \\ 186624 &:= 4 \times (2 + 6^6) - C(8,1) & 293926 &:= -6 + C(2 \times 9 + 3,9) + 2 \\ 194571 &:= -1 + C(7,5)^4 + 91 & 293927 &:= C(C(7,2),9) + (3 - 9)/2 \\ 221184 &:= 48^{C(1,1)+2} \times 2 & 293928 &:= C((8 \times 2 - 9) \times 3,9) - 2 \\ 230262 &:= C(26,20) + 32 & 293932 &:= C(2 \times (3 + 9) - 3,9) + 2 \\ 233265 &:= 5 \times (6^{2 \times 3} - C(3,2)) & 293937 &:= C(7 \times 3,9 + 3) + 9 - 2 \\ 233295 &:= 5 \times (C(9,2)^3 + C(3,2)) & 295235 &:= 5 \times (3^{C(2 \times 5,9)} - 2) \\ 233928 &:= 8 \times (2 \times C(9,3) + 3)^2 & 297546 &:= C(6 \times 4,5) \times 7 + 9 \times 2 \\ 234253 &:= (-3 + 5^2)^4 - C(3,2) & 297564 &:= C(4 \times 6,5) \times 7 + C(9,2) \\ 234254 &:= (4 \times 5 + 2)^{C(4,3)} - 2 & 329232 &:= 2 \times 3 \times (2 + C(9,2))^3 \\ 235298 &:= (8 + C(9,2) + 5)^3 \times 2 & 336157 &:= (7^5 + 1) \times C(6,3) - 3 \\ 236196 &:= (6 \times (C(C(9,1),6) - 3))^2 & 346104 &:= C(40 - 16,4 + 3) \\ 238328 &:= 8 \times (23 + 8)^{C(3,2)} & 351232 &:= 2 \times C(3^2 - 1,5)^3 \\ 245025 &:= C(5 + 2 + 05,4)^2 & 352708 &:= -8 + C(C(07,2),C(5,3)) \\ 245157 &:= C(7 \times (5 - 1) - 5,4^2) & 352713 &:= C(C(3,1) \times 7,2 \times 5) - 3 \\ 248834 &:= (4 \times 3)^{C(8,8)+4} + 2 & 352716 &:= C(C(6,1) \times 7/2,C(5,3)) \\ 255894 &:= 4^{C(9,8)} - 5^5 \times 2 & 352724 &:= 4 \times 2 + C(C(7,2),C(5,3)) \\ 261868 &:= 8^6 - C(8 + 16,2) & 352736 &:= C(6,3) + C(C(7,2),C(5,3)) \\ 261994 &:= 4^9 - (9 + 1) \times C(6,2) & 352737 &:= 7 \times 3 + C(C(7,2),C(5,3)) \\ 262128 &:= 8 \times (-2 + 1 \times 2^{C(6,2)}) & 352748 &:= 8 \times 4 + C(C(7,2),C(5,3)) \\ 262141 &:= -1 + (C(4,1) \times 2)^6 - 2 & 352779 &:= 9 \times 7 + C(C(7,2),C(5,3)) \\ 262142 &:= (C(2 + 4,1) + 2)^6 - 2 & 356265 &:= C(5 + (6 - 2) \times 6,5) \times 3 \\ 262143 &:= -3 + (C(4,1) \times 2)^6 + 2 & 373248 &:= (C(8,4)/2 + 37)^3 \\ 262146 &:= (C(6 + 4,1) - 2)^6 + 2 & 376742 &:= -2 + C(4 \times 7,6) + 7 - 3 \\ 262328 &:= 8 \times (23 + 2^{C(6,2)}) & 376745 &:= -5 + C(4 \times 7,6) + 7 + 3 \\ 264875 &:= -5^7 + C(8,4)^{6/2} & 376775 &:= C(5 \times 7 - 7,6) + C(7,3) \\ 272484 &:= (C(4 + 8,4) + 27)^2 & 382536 &:= 6^3 \times C(-5 + 28,3) \\ & & 386103 &:= 30 \times C(16,8) + 3 \\ & & 387545 &:= 5 \times (C(4 \times 5,7) - 8 - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 388936 &:= C(6 \times 3, 9) \times 8 - 8 \times 3 \\
 388963 &:= C(3 \times 6, C(9, 8)) \times 8 + 3 \\
 419904 &:= 4 \times C(09 + 9, 1)^4 \\
 442384 &:= (48^{C(3,2)} + 4) \times 4 \\
 455625 &:= (5 - 2)^{C(6,5)} \times 5^4 \\
 458668 &:= (8 + 6) \times (-6 + 8^{C(5,4)}) \\
 458752 &:= (2 + 5 + 7) \times 8^{C(5,4)} \\
 462398 &:= C(8 + 9, 3)^2 - 6 + 4 \\
 466564 &:= (4 + C(6, 5)) \times 6^6 + 4 \\
 468512 &:= 2 \times (-1 - 5 + C(8, 6))^4 \\
 474992 &:= (C(29, 9 - 4) - 7) \times 4 \\
 488376 &:= 6 \times C(7 \times 3, 8 + 8) \times 4 \\
 497416 &:= C(C(C(6, 1), 4) + 7, 9) - 4 \\
 497448 &:= 84 \times 47 \times C(9, 4) \\
 498636 &:= (C(6 + 3, 6) - 8) \times 9^4 \\
 524294 &:= 4^9 \times 2 + C(C(4, 2), 5) \\
 531436 &:= (C(6, 3) \times 4 + 1)^3 - 5 \\
 537572 &:= (2 \times 7)^5 - C(7 + 3, 5) \\
 538384 &:= 4 \times C(8 \times 3, 8 + 3 - 5) \\
 545792 &:= (2^9 + C(7, 5)) \times 4^5 \\
 548859 &:= (C(9, 5) + 8) \times 8^4 - 5 \\
 581375 &:= 5 \times (C(7 \times 3, -1 + 8) - 5) \\
 589784 &:= 4^{C(8,7)} \times 9 - 8 \times 5 \\
 589844 &:= (-4 + 4^8) \times 9 + C(8, 5) \\
 589849 &:= 9 \times (4^8 + 9) - C(8, 5) \\
 593775 &:= 5 \times C(-7 + (7 - 3) \times 9, 5) \\
 614662 &:= C(2 + 6, 6)^4 \times 1 + 6 \\
 627265 &:= -5 + C(6 \times 2, 7)^2 + 6 \\
 646622 &:= C(22, 6 + 6) - 4 \times 6 \\
 646646 &:= C(6 + 4 + 6 + 6, 4 + 6) \\
 646652 &:= C(2 \times (5 + 6), 6 + 4) + 6 \\
 671589 &:= 9 \times (8 + C(5 + 17, 6)) \\
 681388 &:= 88^3 - C(1 + 8, 6) \\
 684936 &:= (C(6 \times 3, 9) + 4^8) \times 6 \\
 688684 &:= -4 + 86 \times C(8 + 8, 6) \\
 697578 &:= (-8 + C(C(7, 5), 7) - 9) \times 6 \\
 697626 &:= (C(C(6, 2) + 6, 7) - 9) \times 6 \\
 697686 &:= C(6 + 8 + 6, 7) \times 9 + 6 \\
 697732 &:= -2 + (C(3 \times 7, 7) + 9) \times 6 \\
 735462 &:= -2 + C(6 \times 4, 5 + 3) - 7 \\
 735464 &:= C(4 \times 6, 4 \times (5 - 3)) - 7 \\
 735469 &:= -9 + C(6 \times 4, 5 + 3) + 7 \\
 735471 &:= C((-1 + 7) \times 4, C(5 + 3, 7)) \\
 735478 &:= C(8 \times (7 - 4), 5 + 3) + 7 \\
 735842 &:= C(24, 8) + 53 \times 7 \\
 739024 &:= 4 \times C(20, 9/3 + 7) \\
 746368 &:= C(8, 6)^3 \times (6 + 4 \times 7) \\
 765625 &:= C(5 + 2, 6) \times 5^6 \times 7 \\
 765667 &:= C(7, 6) \times (6 + 5^6 \times 7) \\
 776887 &:= -(-7 + C(8, 8))^6 + 7^7 \\
 807632 &:= (C(23, 6) + 7) \times 08 \\
 823477 &:= 7^7 - C(4 \times 3, 2 + 8) \\
 823537 &:= 7^{(-3+C(5,3))} + 2 - 8 \\
 834328 &:= (C(8, 2)^3 + 4) \times 38 \\
 852722 &:= (C(22, 7) + 2) \times 5 - 8 \\
 876568 &:= (C(8, 6) + 5^6) \times 7 \times 8 \\
 887936 &:= -6 + C(3 \times 9, 7) - 88 \\
 887966 &:= C(6 \times 6 - 9, 7) - 8 \times 8 \\
 937365 &:= C(5 \times 6 - 3, 7 + 3) / 9 \\
 937528 &:= C(8, 2) + 5^7 \times (3 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial** in reverse order of digits. The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

4.2.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$12960 := 0 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12961 := 1 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12962 := 2 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12963 := 3 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12964 := 4 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12965 := 5 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12966 := 6 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12967 := 7 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12968 := 8 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$12969 := 9 + 6! \times C(9 \times 2, 1)$$

$$13440 := 0 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13441 := 1 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13442 := 2 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13443 := 3 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13444 := 4 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13445 := 5 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13446 := 6 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13447 := 7 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13448 := 8 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13449 := 9 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13680 := 0 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13681 := 1 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13682 := 2 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13683 := 3 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13684 := 4 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13685 := 5 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13686 := 6 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13687 := 7 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13688 := 8 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$13689 := 9 + (8! + 6!) / C(3, 1)$$

$$23760 := 0 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23761 := 1 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23762 := 2 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23763 := 3 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23764 := 4 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23765 := 5 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23766 := 6 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23767 := 7 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23768 := 8 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$23769 := 9 + 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2)$$

$$38880 := 0 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38881 := 1 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38882 := 2 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38883 := 3 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38884 := 4 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38885 := 5 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38886 := 6 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38887 := 7 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38888 := 8 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$38889 := 9 + 8! - 8! / C(8, 3!)$$

$$43380 := 0 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43381 := 1 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43382 := 2 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43383 := 3 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43384 := 4 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43385 := 5 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43386 := 6 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43387 := 7 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43388 := 8 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$43389 := 9 + 8! + C(3 \times 3!, 4)$$

$$47540 := 0 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47541 := 1 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47542 := 2 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47543 := 3 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47544 := 4 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47545 := 5 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47546 := 6 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47547 := 7 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47548 := 8 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$47549 := 9 + C(4!, 5) + 7! - 4$$

$$53130 := 0 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$53131 := 1 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$53132 := 2 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$53133 := 3 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$53134 := 4 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$53135 := 5 + C(31 - 3!, 5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53136 &:= 6 + C(31 - 3!, 5) \\ 53137 &:= 7 + C(31 - 3!, 5) \\ 53138 &:= 8 + C(31 - 3!, 5) \\ 53139 &:= 9 + C(31 - 3!, 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84960 &:= 0 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84961 &:= 1 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84962 &:= 2 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84963 &:= 3 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84964 &:= 4 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84965 &:= 5 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84966 &:= 6 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84967 &:= 7 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84968 &:= 8 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \\ 84969 &:= 9 + 6! \times (C(9, 4) - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 004900 &:= 0 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004901 &:= 1 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004902 &:= 2 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004903 &:= 3 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004904 &:= 4 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004905 &:= 5 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004906 &:= 6 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004907 &:= 7 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004908 &:= 8 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004909 &:= 9 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004900 &:= 0 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \\ 004901 &:= 1 + C(-0! + 9, 4)^{0!+0!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 005680 &:= 0 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005681 &:= 1 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005682 &:= 2 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005683 &:= 3 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005684 &:= 4 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005685 &:= 5 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005686 &:= 6 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005687 &:= 7 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005688 &:= 8 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \\ 005689 &:= 9 + 8 \times (6! - C(5, 0! + 0!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 011440 &:= 0 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011441 &:= 1 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011442 &:= 2 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011443 &:= 3 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011444 &:= 4 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011445 &:= 5 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011446 &:= 6 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011447 &:= 7 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011448 &:= 8 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \\ 011449 &:= 9 + C(4 \times 4, -1 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 042480 &:= 0 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042481 &:= 1 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042482 &:= 2 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042483 &:= 3 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042484 &:= 4 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042485 &:= 5 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042486 &:= 6 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042487 &:= 7 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042488 &:= 8 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \\ 042489 &:= 9 + 8! + C(4, 2)! \times (4 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 049340 &:= 0 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049341 &:= 1 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049342 &:= 2 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049343 &:= 3 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049344 &:= 4 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049345 &:= 5 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049346 &:= 6 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049347 &:= 7 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049348 &:= 8 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \\ 049349 &:= 9 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + (4 - 0!)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 077450 &:= 0 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077451 &:= 1 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077452 &:= 2 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077453 &:= 3 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077454 &:= 4 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077455 &:= 5 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077456 &:= 6 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\ 077457 &:= 7 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}077458 &:= 8 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70 \\077459 &:= 9 + C(5 \times 4, 7) - 70\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}133920 &:= 0 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133921 &:= 1 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133922 &:= 2 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133923 &:= 3 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133924 &:= 4 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133925 &:= 5 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133926 &:= 6 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133927 &:= 7 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133928 &:= 8 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!! \\133929 &:= 9 + 2 \times 93 \times C(3, 1)!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}134340 &:= 0 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134341 &:= 1 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134342 &:= 2 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134343 &:= 3 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134344 &:= 4 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134345 &:= 5 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134346 &:= 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134347 &:= 7 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134348 &:= 8 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1} \\134349 &:= 9 + C(4!, 3!) - 4^{3+1}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}134600 &:= 0 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134601 &:= 1 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134602 &:= 2 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134603 &:= 3 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134604 &:= 4 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134605 &:= 5 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134606 &:= 6 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134607 &:= 7 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134608 &:= 8 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1 \\134609 &:= 9 - 0! + 6 + C(4!, 3!) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}134640 &:= 0 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134641 &:= 1 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134642 &:= 2 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}134643 &:= 3 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134644 &:= 4 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134645 &:= 5 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134646 &:= 6 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134647 &:= 7 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134648 &:= 8 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1 \\134649 &:= 9 + C(4!, 6) + 43 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}136080 &:= 0 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136081 &:= 1 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136082 &:= 2 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136083 &:= 3 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136084 &:= 4 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136085 &:= 5 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136086 &:= 6 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136087 &:= 7 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136088 &:= 8 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1) \\136089 &:= 9 + (8! + (0! + 6)!) \times C(3, 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}138240 &:= 0 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138241 &:= 1 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138242 &:= 2 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138243 &:= 3 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138244 &:= 4 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138245 &:= 5 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138246 &:= 6 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138247 &:= 7 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138248 &:= 8 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)! \\138249 &:= 9 + C(4, 2)! \times 8 \times (3 + 1)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}203760 &:= 0 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203761 &:= 1 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203762 &:= 2 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203763 &:= 3 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203764 &:= 4 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203765 &:= 5 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203766 &:= 6 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203767 &:= 7 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203768 &:= 8 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2)) \\203769 &:= 9 + 6! \times (7 + C((3 + 0)!, 2))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}230230 &:= 0 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\230231 &:= 1 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 230232 &:= 2 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230233 &:= 3 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230234 &:= 4 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230235 &:= 5 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230236 &:= 6 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230237 &:= 7 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230238 &:= 8 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \\ 230239 &:= 9 + C(3! + 20, 3 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241950 &:= 0 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241951 &:= 1 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241952 &:= 2 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241953 &:= 3 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241954 &:= 4 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241955 &:= 5 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241956 &:= 6 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241957 &:= 7 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241958 &:= 8 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241959 &:= 9 + (5 + (9 - 1)!) \times C(4, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241980 &:= 0 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241981 &:= 1 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241982 &:= 2 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241983 &:= 3 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241984 &:= 4 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241985 &:= 5 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241986 &:= 6 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241987 &:= 7 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241988 &:= 8 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \\ 241989 &:= 9 + (8! + 9 + 1) \times C(4, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 244400 &:= 0 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244401 &:= 1 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244402 &:= 2 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244403 &:= 3 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244404 &:= 4 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244405 &:= 5 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244406 &:= 6 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244407 &:= 7 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244408 &:= 8 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \\ 244409 &:= 9 + (-0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 4) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 246240 &:= 0 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246241 &:= 1 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246242 &:= 2 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246243 &:= 3 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246244 &:= 4 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246245 &:= 5 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246246 &:= 6 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246247 &:= 7 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246248 &:= 8 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \\ 246249 &:= 9 + ((4 \times 2)! + 6!) \times C(4, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 247680 &:= 0 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247681 &:= 1 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247682 &:= 2 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247683 &:= 3 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247684 &:= 4 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247685 &:= 5 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247686 &:= 6 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247687 &:= 7 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247688 &:= 8 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \\ 247689 &:= 9 + 8! \times 6 + 7! + C(4, 2)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 252720 &:= 0 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252721 &:= 1 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252722 &:= 2 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252723 &:= 3 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252724 &:= 4 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252725 &:= 5 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252726 &:= 6 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252727 &:= 7 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252728 &:= 8 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \\ 252729 &:= 9 + C(27, 2) \times (5 - 2)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 253640 &:= 0 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253641 &:= 1 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253642 &:= 2 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253643 &:= 3 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253644 &:= 4 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253645 &:= 5 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \\ 253646 &:= 6 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$253647 := 7 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2$$

$$253648 := 8 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2$$

$$253649 := 9 + (C(4!, 6) - 3!^5) \times 2$$

$$268560 := 0 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268561 := 1 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268562 := 2 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268563 := 3 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268564 := 4 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268565 := 5 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268566 := 6 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268567 := 7 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268568 := 8 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$268569 := 9 + 6! \times (-5 + C(C(8, 6), 2))$$

$$272160 := 0 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272161 := 1 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272162 := 2 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272163 := 3 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272164 := 4 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272165 := 5 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272166 := 6 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272167 := 7 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272168 := 8 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$272169 := 9 + 6! \times C(1 + 27, 2)$$

$$276480 := 0 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276481 := 1 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276482 := 2 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276483 := 3 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276484 := 4 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276485 := 5 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276486 := 6 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276487 := 7 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276488 := 8 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$276489 := 9 + 8! \times 4! \times 6/C(7, 2)$$

$$292320 := 0 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292321 := 1 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292322 := 2 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292323 := 3 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292324 := 4 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292325 := 5 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292326 := 6 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292327 := 7 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292328 := 8 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$292329 := 9 + (2 \times 3)! \times C(29, 2)$$

$$308880 := 0 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308881 := 1 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308882 := 2 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308883 := 3 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308884 := 4 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308885 := 5 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308886 := 6 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308887 := 7 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308888 := 8 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$308889 := 9 + C(8 + 8, 8) \times (0! + 3)!$$

$$336960 := 0 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336961 := 1 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336962 := 2 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336963 := 3 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336964 := 4 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336965 := 5 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336966 := 6 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336967 := 7 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336968 := 8 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$336969 := 9 + 6! \times (C(9, 6) - 3!) \times 3!$$

$$343000 := 0 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343001 := 1 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343002 := 2 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343003 := 3 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343004 := 4 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343005 := 5 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343006 := 6 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343007 := 7 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343008 := 8 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$343009 := 9 + C((0! + 0!)^3, 4)^3$$

$$345600 := 0 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345601 := 1 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345602 := 2 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345603 := 3 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345604 := 4 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345605 := 5 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345606 := 6 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345607 := 7 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345608 := 8 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345609 := 9 + 06! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345600 := 00 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345611 := 11 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345622 := 22 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345633 := 33 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345644 := 44 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345655 := 55 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345666 := 66 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345687 := 77 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345698 := 88 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$345699 := 99 + 6! \times 5! \times C(4,3)$$

$$346040 := 0 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346041 := 1 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346042 := 2 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346043 := 3 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346044 := 4 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346045 := 5 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346046 := 6 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346047 := 7 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346048 := 8 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$346049 := 9 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3$$

$$348760 := 0 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348761 := 1 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348762 := 2 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348763 := 3 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348764 := 4 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348765 := 5 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348766 := 6 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348767 := 7 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348768 := 8 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$348769 := 9 + 6! + 7! + C(8,4)^3$$

$$352740 := 0 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352741 := 1 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352742 := 2 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352743 := 3 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352744 := 4 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352745 := 5 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352746 := 6 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352747 := 7 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352748 := 8 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352749 := 9 + 4! + C(C(7,2), C(5,3))$$

$$352780 := 0 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352781 := 1 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352782 := 2 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352783 := 3 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352784 := 4 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352785 := 5 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352786 := 6 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352787 := 7 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352788 := 8 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352789 := 9 + (8! - 7! - 2) \times C(5,3)$$

$$352790 := 0 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352791 := 1 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352792 := 2 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352793 := 3 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352794 := 4 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352795 := 5 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352796 := 6 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352797 := 7 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352798 := 8 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$352799 := 9 + 9! - 7! \times 2 - C(5,3)$$

$$357950 := 0 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5,3)$$

$$357951 := 1 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5,3)$$

$$357952 := 2 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5,3)$$

$$357953 := 3 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5,3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 357954 &:= 4 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \\ 357955 &:= 5 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \\ 357956 &:= 6 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \\ 357957 &:= 7 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \\ 357958 &:= 8 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \\ 357959 &:= 9 + 5! + 9! - 7! - C(5, 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362890 &:= 0 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362891 &:= 1 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362892 &:= 2 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362893 &:= 3 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362894 &:= 4 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362895 &:= 5 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362896 &:= 6 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362897 &:= 7 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362898 &:= 8 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \\ 362899 &:= 9 + 9! + C(8 + 2, 6 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362930 &:= 0 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362931 &:= 1 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362932 &:= 2 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362933 &:= 3 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362934 &:= 4 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362935 &:= 5 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362936 &:= 6 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362937 &:= 7 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362938 &:= 8 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \\ 362939 &:= 9 - 3! + 9! + C(2 + 6, 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 362640 &:= 0 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362641 &:= 1 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362642 &:= 2 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362643 &:= 3 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362644 &:= 4 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362645 &:= 5 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362646 &:= 6 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362647 &:= 7 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362648 &:= 8 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \\ 362649 &:= 9 + (4! - C(6, 2))! - 6!/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363440 &:= 0 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363441 &:= 1 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363442 &:= 2 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363443 &:= 3 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363444 &:= 4 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363445 &:= 5 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363446 &:= 6 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363447 &:= 7 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363448 &:= 8 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \\ 363449 &:= 9 + C(4 \times 4, 3) + (6 + 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363690 &:= 0 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363691 &:= 1 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363692 &:= 2 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363693 &:= 3 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363694 &:= 4 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363695 &:= 5 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363696 &:= 6 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363697 &:= 7 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363698 &:= 8 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \\ 363699 &:= 9 + 9! - 6 + C(3 \times 6, 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 376740 &:= 0 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376741 &:= 1 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376742 &:= 2 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376743 &:= 3 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376744 &:= 4 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376745 &:= 5 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376746 &:= 6 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376747 &:= 7 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376748 &:= 8 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \\ 376749 &:= 9 + C(4 \times (7 - 6) \times 7, 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 413280 &:= 0 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413281 &:= 1 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413282 &:= 2 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413283 &:= 3 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413284 &:= 4 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413285 &:= 5 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413286 &:= 6 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \\ 413287 &:= 7 + 82 \times (C(3, 1) + 4)! \end{aligned}$$

$$413288 := 8 + 82 \times (C(3,1) + 4)!$$

$$413289 := 9 + 82 \times (C(3,1) + 4)!$$

$$425040 := 0 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425041 := 1 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425042 := 2 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425043 := 3 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425044 := 4 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425045 := 5 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425046 := 6 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425047 := 7 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425048 := 8 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$425049 := 9 + C(4! + 0!, 5) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$456250 := 0 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456251 := 1 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456252 := 2 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456253 := 3 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456254 := 4 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456255 := 5 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456256 := 6 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456257 := 7 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456258 := 8 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$456259 := 9 + (C(5,2) + 6!) \times 5^4$$

$$463680 := 0 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463681 := 1 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463682 := 2 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463683 := 3 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463684 := 4 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463685 := 5 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463686 := 6 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463687 := 7 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463688 := 8 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$463689 := 9 + C(8,6) \times (-3!! + 6! \times 4!)$$

$$518330 := 0 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518331 := 1 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518332 := 2 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518333 := 3 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518334 := 4 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518335 := 5 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518336 := 6 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518337 := 7 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518338 := 8 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$518339 := 9 + 3!! \times 3!! - C(8, -1 + 5)$$

$$524160 := 0 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524161 := 1 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524162 := 2 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524163 := 3 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524164 := 4 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524165 := 5 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524166 := 6 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524167 := 7 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524168 := 8 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524169 := 9 + (6 - 1)! \times C(4^2, 5)$$

$$524640 := 0 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524641 := 1 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524642 := 2 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524643 := 3 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524644 := 4 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524645 := 5 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524646 := 6 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524647 := 7 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524648 := 8 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$524649 := 9 + (4^6 + C(4!, 2)) \times 5!$$

$$537830 := 0 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537831 := 1 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537832 := 2 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537833 := 3 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537834 := 4 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537835 := 5 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537836 := 6 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537837 := 7 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537838 := 8 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$537839 := 9 + 3! + (C(8,7) + 3!)^5$$

$$597480 := 0 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597481 := 1 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597482 := 2 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597483 := 3 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597484 := 4 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597485 := 5 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597486 := 6 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597487 := 7 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597488 := 8 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$597489 := 9 + (-C(8,4) + 7! + 9) \times 5!$$

$$599760 := 0 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599761 := 1 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599762 := 2 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599763 := 3 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599764 := 4 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599765 := 5 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599766 := 6 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599767 := 7 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599768 := 8 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$599769 := 9 + 6! \times 7 \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)$$

$$604680 := 0 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604681 := 1 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604682 := 2 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604683 := 3 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604684 := 4 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604685 := 5 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604686 := 6 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604687 := 7 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604688 := 8 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$604689 := 9 + 8! \times C(6,4) - (-0! + 6)!$$

$$679590 := 0 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679591 := 1 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679592 := 2 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679593 := 3 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679594 := 4 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679595 := 5 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679596 := 6 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679597 := 7 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679598 := 8 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$679599 := 9 + (C(9,5) + 9) \times (7! - 6)$$

$$685440 := 0 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685441 := 1 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685442 := 2 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685443 := 3 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685444 := 4 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685445 := 5 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685446 := 6 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685447 := 7 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685448 := 8 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$685449 := 9 + (-C(4,4) + 5!) \times 8 \times 6!$$

$$735440 := 0 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735441 := 1 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735442 := 2 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735443 := 3 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735444 := 4 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735445 := 5 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735446 := 6 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735447 := 7 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735448 := 8 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$735449 := 9 - 4! + C(4!, 5 + 3) - 7$$

$$737280 := 0 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737281 := 1 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737282 := 2 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737283 := 3 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737284 := 4 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737285 := 5 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737286 := 6 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737287 := 7 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737288 := 8 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737289 := 9 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$737289 := 9 + 8! \times 2^{C(7,3!)} / 7$$

$$745920 := 0 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 745921 &:= 1 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745922 &:= 2 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745923 &:= 3 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745924 &:= 4 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745925 &:= 5 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745926 &:= 6 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745927 &:= 7 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745928 &:= 8 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \\ 745929 &:= 9 + (-2 + C(9,5) + 4!) \times 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 930242 &:= 2 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930243 &:= 3 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930244 &:= 4 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930245 &:= 5 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930246 &:= 6 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930247 &:= 7 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930248 &:= 8 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930249 &:= 9 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 846720 &:= 0 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846721 &:= 1 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846722 &:= 2 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846723 &:= 3 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846724 &:= 4 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846725 &:= 5 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846726 &:= 6 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846727 &:= 7 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846728 &:= 8 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \\ 846729 &:= 9 + C(2 + 7, 6) / 4 \times 8! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 949670 &:= 0 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949671 &:= 1 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949672 &:= 2 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949673 &:= 3 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949674 &:= 4 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949675 &:= 5 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949676 &:= 6 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949677 &:= 7 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949678 &:= 8 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \\ 949679 &:= 9 + 7! + 6 - 9! + C(4!, 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 930240 &:= 0 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930241 &:= 1 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930242 &:= 2 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930243 &:= 3 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930244 &:= 4 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930245 &:= 5 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930246 &:= 6 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930247 &:= 7 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930248 &:= 8 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930249 &:= 9 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 984940 &:= 0 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984941 &:= 1 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984942 &:= 2 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984943 &:= 3 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984944 &:= 4 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984945 &:= 5 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984946 &:= 6 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984947 &:= 7 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984948 &:= 8 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \\ 984949 &:= 9 + C(4!, 9) - 4 + 8! - 9! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 930240 &:= 0 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \\ 930241 &:= 1 + 4! \times C(20, -3 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

4.2.2 Non Symmetric Representations

From the number 039419 onwards the extra bracket are not removed. This can be easily done.

$$\begin{aligned} 0593 &:= 3!! - C(9,5) + 0! \\ 0793 &:= C(3 + 9, 7) + 0! \\ 1345 &:= 5^4 + C(3, 1)!! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1432 &:= 2 \times (3!! - C(4, 1)) \\ 1436 &:= 6! + 3!! - C(4, 1) \\ 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2436 &:= 6! \times 3 + C(4!, 2) \\ 2684 &:= -4 + 8!/C(6, 2) \\ 3456 &:= 6!/5 \times C(4, 3)! \\ 3528 &:= C(8, 2) \times (5! + 3!) \\ 3599 &:= -C(9, 9) + 5 \times 3!! \\ 3654 &:= C(4! + 5, 6 - 3) \\ 3723 &:= 3!! + C(2 \times 7, 3!) \\ 4324 &:= C(4, 2)! \times 3! + 4 \\ 7248 &:= 8 \times C(4!, 2) + 7! \\ \\ 00165 &:= C(5 + 6, 1 + 0! + 0!) \\ 00169 &:= C(9, 6) \times (1 + 0!) + 0! \\ 00175 &:= 5 \times C(7, 1 + 0! + 0!) \\ 00189 &:= 9 \times C(8 - 1, 0! + 0!) \\ 00231 &:= C((1 + 3)! - 2, 0! + 0!) \\ 00256 &:= (6 + C(5, 2))^{0!+0!} \\ 00268 &:= -8 + C((6 - 2)!, 0! + 0!) \\ 00324 &:= (C(4, 2) \times 3)^{0!+0!} \\ 00351 &:= C((-1 + 5)! + 3, 0! + 0!) \\ 00396 &:= 6 \times C(9 + 3, 0! + 0!) \\ 00437 &:= -7 + 3!! - C(4!, 0! + 0!) \\ 00493 &:= C(3 + 9, 4) - 0! - 0! \\ 00512 &:= 2^{-1+C(5, 0!+0!)} \\ 00596 &:= 6! - C(9, 5) + 0! + 0! \\ 00648 &:= -C(8, 4) + 6! - 0! - 0! \\ 00672 &:= 2 \times 7!/C(6, 0! + 0!) \\ 00741 &:= (-1 + 4)!! + C(7, 0! + 0!) \\ 00972 &:= 27 \times C(9, 0! + 0!) \\ 01293 &:= -3 + C(9, 2)^{1+0!} \\ 01584 &:= 4! \times (C(8, 5) + 10) \\ 01625 &:= 5 \times C(26, 1 + 0!) \\ 01876 &:= 67 \times C(8, 1 + 0!) \\ 01934 &:= C(4!, 3) - 9 \times 10 \\ 02044 &:= C(4!, 4 - 0!) + 20 \\ 02145 &:= 5! + C(4!, 1 + 2) + 0! \\ 02268 &:= C(C(8, 6), 2) \times (2 + 0!)! \\ 02408 &:= 8 \times (C(0! + 4!, 2) + 0!) \\ 02439 &:= 9 \times (-3! + C(4!, 2) + 0!) \\ 02449 &:= 9 \times (-4 + C(4!, 2)) + 0! \\ 02573 &:= C(3! + 7, 5) \times 2 - 0! \\ \\ 02683 &:= -3! + 8!/C(6, 2) + 0! \\ 02687 &:= 7! \times 8/C(6, 2) - 0! \\ 02743 &:= 3!! + C(4!, C(7, 2)) - 0! \\ 02964 &:= 4 \times 6! + C(9, 2 + 0!) \\ 03277 &:= C((7 + 7) \times 2, 3) + 0! \\ 03283 &:= 3! + C(C(8, 2), 3) + 0! \\ 03324 &:= -C(4!, 2) + 3!! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03361 &:= C(16, 3) \times 3! + 0! \\ 03376 &:= C(6, 7 - 3)^3 + 0! \\ 03463 &:= 3!! + 6! + C(4!, 3) - 0! \\ 03542 &:= 2 \times C(4!, 5)/(3 + 0!)! \\ 03599 &:= -C(9, 9) + 5! \times 30 \\ 03628 &:= C(8, 2) + 6! \times (3! - 0!) \\ 03648 &:= 8 \times (4! \times C(6, 3) + 0!) \\ 03653 &:= C(35 - 6, 3) - 0! \\ 03984 &:= 48 \times (C(9, 3) - 0!) \\ 04295 &:= 5! \times C(9, 2) - 4! - 0! \\ 04336 &:= 6! \times 3! + C(3!, 4) + 0! \\ 04375 &:= 5 \times C(7, 3) \times (4! + 0!) \\ 04524 &:= -C(4!, 2) + 5! \times 40 \\ 04724 &:= -C(4!, 2) + 7! - 40 \\ 04913 &:= (3! + 1)! - C(9, 4) - 0! \\ 05068 &:= C(8, 6) + (0! + 5 + 0!)! \\ 05097 &:= 7! + C(9 - 0!, 5) + 0! \\ 05738 &:= 8 \times 3!! - C(7, 5) - 0! \\ 06188 &:= C(8 + 8 + 1, 6 - 0!) \\ 06189 &:= C(9 + 8, -1 + 6) + 0! \\ 06435 &:= C(5 + 3! + 4, 6 + 0!) \\ 06479 &:= C(9, 7)/4 \times 6! - 0! \\ 07341 &:= C(1 + 4!, 3) + 7! + 0! \\ 08443 &:= -3 \times C(4!, 4) + 8! + 0! \\ 10624 &:= C(4!, -2 + 6) - 0! - 1 \\ 10626 &:= C((6 - 2)!, 6 - 0! - 1) \\ 11344 &:= C(4!, 4) + 3!! - 1 - 1 \\ 11346 &:= 6! + C(4!, C(3, 1) + 1) \\ 11544 &:= 4! \times (4 \times 5! + C(1, 1)) \\ 12143 &:= 3! \times C(4!, 1 + 2) - 1 \\ 12144 &:= C(4!, 4 - 1) \times (2 + 1)! \\ 12374 &:= C(4! - 7, 3!) - C(2, 1) \\ 12544 &:= (-4 - 4 + 5!)^{C(2, 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13248 &:= 8 \times C(4!, 2) \times C(3, 1)! \\13368 &:= (8! - 6^3)/C(3, 1) \\13432 &:= ((2^3)! - 4!)/C(3, 1) \\13458 &:= (8! + 54)/C(3, 1) \\13488 &:= 8 \times (8!/4! + C(3, 1)!) \\13557 &:= (-7 + 5!) \times 5! - C(3, 1) \\14352 &:= (-2 - 5! + 3!!) \times C(4, 1)! \\15119 &:= 9!/(-C(1, 1) + 5)! - 1 \\15503 &:= C((3 + 0!) \times 5, 5) - 1 \\15505 &:= C((5 - 0!) \times 5, 5) + 1 \\16345 &:= C(5, 4)^{3!} + C(6, 1)! \\16464 &:= (-4 + 6!) \times 4! - C(6, 1)! \\18234 &:= (C(4!, 3) + 2) \times (8 + 1) \\18368 &:= -C(8, 6)^3 + C(8, 1)! \\18563 &:= C(3 \times 6, (-5 + 8)!) - 1 \\18564 &:= C(4! - 6, 5 + 8 - 1) \\18729 &:= 9^{-2+7} - C(8, 1)! \\19368 &:= (-8 + 6! \times 3) \times C(9, 1) \\20328 &:= C(8, 2) \times (3!! + (0! + 2)!) \\20474 &:= C(4 \times 7, 4) - (0 \times 2)! \\21254 &:= C(4!, 5)/2 + 1 \times 2 \\22679 &:= (9 \times C(7, 6)! - 2)/2 \\23343 &:= C(3!, 4) + 3!^{3!}/2 \\23952 &:= -2 \times 5! + 9!/C(3!, 2) \\24564 &:= (4! + 65) \times C(4!, 2) \\24675 &:= 5 \times (7! - C(C(6, 4), 2)) \\24756 &:= -6! + 5 \times 7! + C(4!, 2) \\24835 &:= -5 + 3!!/8 \times C(4!, 2) \\24864 &:= 4! + 6!/8 \times C(4!, 2) \\25275 &:= 5 \times (7! + C((-2 + 5)!, 2)) \\25375 &:= 5 \times (C(7, 3) + (5 + 2)!) \\25377 &:= (7! + C(7, 3)) \times 5 + 2 \\28334 &:= C(4!, 3) \times (3! + 8) - 2 \\29196 &:= (6! + 91) \times C(9, 2) \\29561 &:= (1 + 6!) \times (5 + C(9, 2)) \\30247 &:= 7! \times C(4, 2) + 0! + 3! \\30345 &:= 5 \times (C(4!, 3) - 0!) \times 3 \\31817 &:= -7 + C(18, 1 + 3!) \\31824 &:= C(4! + 2 - 8, 1 + 3!) \\32384 &:= (4! - 8) \times C((3! - 2)!, 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}32558 &:= 8^5 - C(C(5, 2), 3!) \\33649 &:= 9 \times C(4!, 6)/(3! \times 3!) \\33839 &:= -9 \times 3!! + 8! - C(3, 3) \\34368 &:= 8 \times (6! \times 3! - C(4, 3)!) \\34392 &:= 2 \times (-C(9, 3) + 4! \times 3!!) \\34408 &:= (-8 + 0! + 4!) \times C(4!, 3) \\34497 &:= -7 \times 9 + (4! + 4!) \times 3!! \\35415 &:= 5 \times (-1 + C(4!, 5)/3!) \\35424 &:= 4!/2 \times 4! \times (5! + 3) \\35435 &:= 5 \times (3 + C(4!, 5)/3!) \\36289 &:= 9!/(8 + 2) + C(6, 3!) \\36573 &:= -3^7 + C(5!/6, 3!) \\36792 &:= 2 \times (9! + 7!)/C(6, 3) \\37344 &:= 4! \times (-4 + 3!! + 7!/3!) \\37447 &:= 7 + (4! + 4 \times 7) \times 3!! \\37454 &:= C(4!, 5) - 4 - 7! - 3! \\38497 &:= -C(7 + 9, 4) + 8! - 3 \\38523 &:= -C(3!, 2) \times 5! + 8! + 3 \\38528 &:= 8! - 2^5 \times C(8, 3) \\38755 &:= -5 + C(5 + 7 + 8, 3!) \\38936 &:= 6! \times 3! \times 9 + C(8, 3) \\38948 &:= 8! - 49 \times C(8, 3!) \\39388 &:= -8 + 8! - C(3 + 9, 3!) \\39682 &:= -2 + 8! - 6! + C(9, 3) \\39732 &:= (2^3)! - 7 \times C(9, 3) \\39738 &:= 8! + 3! - 7 \times C(9, 3) \\39744 &:= 4! \times C(4!, -7 + 9) \times 3! \\39784 &:= 4! + 8! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\39836 &:= C(6, 3) + 8! - 9!/3!! \\39892 &:= -2^9 + 8! + C(9, 3) \\39948 &:= 8! - 4 \times (9 + C(9, 3)) \\40048 &:= 8! - C(4!, 0! + 0!) + 4 \\40288 &:= 8! - C(8, 2) - 04 \\40335 &:= (5 + 3)! + C(3!, 04) \\40344 &:= 4! + (C(4, 3) + 04)! \\40345 &:= (C(5, 4) + 3)! + 0! + 4! \\40378 &:= 8! + C(7, 3) - 0! + 4! \\42342 &:= -2 + C(4!, 3) + (2 \times 4)! \\42344 &:= C(4!, 4! - 3) + (2 \times 4)! \\42348 &:= 8! + C(4!, C(3, 2)) + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}42454 &:= C(4!, 5) - 4! - 2 - 4! \\42504 &:= C(4!, -05 + 24) \\42526 &:= C((6 - 2)!, 5) - 2 + 4! \\42528 &:= C((8/2)!, 5) + 24 \\42544 &:= (C(4!, 4) + C(5, 2)) \times 4 \\42546 &:= -6 + C(4!, 5) + 2 \times 4! \\43734 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 + 3) - 4! \\44155 &:= -5! + 5 \times C(-1 + 4!, 4) \\44284 &:= 4^8 - 2 \times C(4!, 4) \\44836 &:= 6^3! - C(-8 + 4!, 4) \\45384 &:= C(4!, 8 - 3) + 5! \times 4! \\46641 &:= (-1 + 4!)^6 - C(6, 4) \\46689 &:= C(9, 8) + 6^6 + 4! \\47754 &:= C(4!, 5) + 7! + 7!/4! \\48324 &:= C(4^2, 3!) + 8! - 4 \\49336 &:= 6! + C(3 \times 3!, 9) - 4 \\50395 &:= (5! \times C(9, 3) - 0!) \times 5 \\53125 &:= C(5^2, -1 + 3!) - 5 \\53154 &:= 4! + C(5^{-1+3}, 5) \\54154 &:= 4^5 + C(1 + 4!, 5) \\56448 &:= 8! \times (C(4, 4) + 6)/5 \\57456 &:= (-6 + 5!) \times 4! \times C(7, 5) \\58935 &:= -5! + 3! + C(9, 8)^5 \\59027 &:= -C(7, 2) - 0! + 9^5 \\59436 &:= -6 \times (3!! - C(4!, 9 - 5)) \\60393 &:= 3 + C(9, 3) \times (-0! + 6!) \\63748 &:= -8 + C(4!, 7 - 3) \times 6 \\64468 &:= -8 + 6! + C(4!, 4) \times 6 \\67536 &:= (6 + 3)!/5 - C(7, 6)! \\69024 &:= (C(4, 2)! - 0!) \times 96 \\72338 &:= C(8 \times 3, 3!)/2 + 7! \\72559 &:= 9!/5 + C(5, 2) - 7 \\72576 &:= (7 + 2)!/C(5, 7 - 6) \\72577 &:= (7 + 2)!/5 + C(7, 7) \\72864 &:= 4!! \times 6/(C(8, 2) - 7)! \\73998 &:= 7! \times 3! + C(9 + 9, 8) \\74256 &:= C(-7 + 4!, (-2 + 5)!) \times 6 \\74319 &:= (-9 + C((1 + 3)!, 4)) \times 7 \\74319 &:= 7 \times (C(4!, 3 + 1) - 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74354 &:= (C(4!, 5!/3!) - 4) \times 7 \\74376 &:= -6 + C((7 - 3)!, 4) \times 7 \\74382 &:= C((2 + 8 - 3)!, 4) \times 7 \\74402 &:= 20 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74403 &:= 30 + C(04!, 4) \times 7 \\74413 &:= 31 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74424 &:= 42 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74431 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (C(4!, 4) + 7) \\74435 &:= 53 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74438 &:= C(8, 3) + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74445 &:= (5 + C(4!, 4) + 4) \times 7 \\74446 &:= 64 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74452 &:= (2 \times 5 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7 \\74457 &:= 75 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74466 &:= (6 + 6 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7 \\74468 &:= 86 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74473 &:= (3! + 7 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7 \\74479 &:= 97 + C(4!, 4) \times 7 \\74487 &:= (7 + 8 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7 \\74613 &:= C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!) \\74624 &:= C(4! - 2, 6) + 4 + 7 \\75324 &:= -C(4!, 2) + 3 \times 5 \times 7! \\75473 &:= (3 \times 7! - 4!) \times 5 - 7 \\75525 &:= (C(5, 2) + 5) \times (-5 + 7!) \\75585 &:= 5!/8 \times (-C(5, 5) + 7!) \\75675 &:= (5 + 7!) \times C(6, -5 + 7) \\79956 &:= 6! \times (5! - 9) + C(9, 7) \\80664 &:= 4! + (C(6, 6) + 0!) \times 8! \\82824 &:= C(4!, (2 + 8)/2) + 8! \\83542 &:= -2 + C(4!, 5) + 3!! + 8! \\83544 &:= C(4!, 4! - 5) + 3!! + 8! \\84078 &:= 8! + C(-7 + 0! + 4!, 8) \\84448 &:= (-C(8, 4) + C(4!, 4)) \times 8 \\84764 &:= C(4!, 6)/7 + 4^8 \\86565 &:= 5! \times 6! + C(5 + 6, 8) \\88648 &:= C(-8 + 4!, 6) + 8! + 8! \\89234 &:= C(4!, 3!) - 2 - 9!/8 \\92354 &:= -4! + C(-5 + (3! - 2)!, 9) \\92378 &:= C(8 + 7 + 3! - 2, 9) \\95544 &:= (C(4!, 4) - 5 - 5) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95634 &:= C(4!, 3 + 6 - 5) \times 9 \\ 97144 &:= 4 \times (-4! + C(17, 9)) \\ 97263 &:= (3!! \times C(6, 2) + 7) \times 9 \\ \\ 000137 &:= C(-7 + (3 + 1)!, 0! + 0!) + 0! \\ 000179 &:= 9 \times (C(7, 1 + 0!) - 0!) - 0! \\ 000249 &:= C(9, 4) \times 2 - 0! - 0! - 0! \\ 000269 &:= 9 \times C(6, 2) \times (0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000271 &:= C(17, 2) \times (0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000275 &:= C((5 + 7) \times 2, 0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000278 &:= 8 \times C(7, 2 + 0!) - 0! - 0! \\ 000283 &:= 3! + C((8/2)!, 0! + 0!) + 0! \\ 000284 &:= 4 \times (C(8, 2 + 0! + 0!) + 0!) \\ 000298 &:= 8 \times (C(9, 2) + 0!) + 0! + 0! \\ 000342 &:= 2 \times C(4! - 3! + 0!, 0! + 0!) \\ 000364 &:= C(-4 + 6 \times 3, 0! + 0! + 0!) \\ 000387 &:= 7 \times (C(8, 3) - 0!) + 0! + 0! \\ 000419 &:= C(9 + 1, 4) \times (0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000462 &:= C(2 \times 6, (4 - 0!)!)/(0! + 0!) \\ 000487 &:= 7 \times (C(8, 4) - 0!) - 0! - 0! \\ 000561 &:= C(16, 5 - 0! - 0!) + 0! \\ 000567 &:= C(7 + 6, 5) - (0! + 0! + 0!)!! \\ 000614 &:= 41 \times C(6, 0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000639 &:= -C(9, 3) + 6! + 0! + 0! + 0! \\ 000645 &:= 5^4 + C(6, 0! + 0! + 0!) \\ 000724 &:= C(4, 2)! + 7 - 0! - 0! - 0! \\ 000742 &:= (2 + 4)! + C(7, 0! + 0!) + 0! \\ 000782 &:= -2 + C(8, 7 - 0!)^{0!+0!} \\ 000813 &:= -3 + C(18, 0! + 0! + 0!) \\ 000816 &:= 6 \times C(18 - 0!, 0! + 0!) \\ 000835 &:= 5 \times (3! \times C(8, 0! + 0!) - 0!) \\ 000867 &:= 7!/6 + C(8, 0! + 0!) - 0! \\ 000924 &:= C(4!/2, 9 - 0! - 0!) - 0! \\ 000962 &:= 26 \times C(9, 0! + 0!) + 0! \\ 000973 &:= 3!! + 7 \times C(9, 0! + 0!) + 0! \\ 001026 &:= 6 \times C(20 - 1, 0! + 0!) \\ 001225 &:= C(5 + 2, 2 + 1)^{0!+0!} \\ 001304 &:= C(4!, 03) - (1 + 0! + 0!)!! \\ 001327 &:= C(C(7, 2), 3) - 1 - 0! - 0! \\ 001355 &:= -5 \times (5 - C((3 + 1)!, 0! + 0!)) \\ 001363 &:= -3! + (6 + 31)^{0!+0!} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 001365 &:= C(5 \times (6 - 3), 10 + 0!) \\ 001369 &:= (C(9, 6/3) + 1)^{0!+0!} \\ 001383 &:= (3!! - C(8, 3!)) \times (1 + 0!) - 0! \\ 001385 &:= 5 \times (C(8 \times 3, 1 + 0!) + 0!) \\ 001437 &:= C(7, 3) \times 41 + 0! + 0! \\ 001632 &:= 2 \times C(3 \times 6, 1 + 0! + 0!) \\ 001656 &:= 6 \times C(5!/(6 - 1), 0! + 0!) \\ 001682 &:= 2 \times (C(8, 6) + 1)^{0!+0!} \\ 001686 &:= 6 \times C(8, 6) \times 10 + 0! \\ 001795 &:= 5 \times (C(9, 7) \times 10 - 0!) \\ 001932 &:= 23 \times C(9, 1 + 0! + 0!) \\ 001937 &:= (C(7, 3) + 9)^{1+0!} + 0! \\ 001945 &:= 54 \times C(9, 1 + 0!) + 0! \\ 002144 &:= C(4!, 4 - 1) + ((2 + 0!)! - 0!)! \\ 002156 &:= (C(6, 5)! - 1) \times (2 + 0!) - 0! \\ 002184 &:= 4! \times C((8 - 1) \times 2, 0! + 0!) \\ 002301 &:= C(1 + (0! + 3)!, 2 + 0!) + 0! \\ 002304 &:= C(4! + 0!, 3) + 2 + 0! + 0! \\ 002399 &:= (-C(9, 9) + 3!)! \times 20 - 0! \\ 002439 &:= 9 \times (-3 + C(4!, 2) - 0! - 0!) \\ 002475 &:= C(5 + 7, 4) \times ((2 + 0!)! - 0!) \\ 002484 &:= (4!/8)!! + 42^{0!+0!} \\ 002487 &:= (7! - C(8, 4))/2 + 0! + 0! \\ 002491 &:= -1 + 9 \times (C(4!, 2) + 0!) - 0! \\ 002492 &:= -2 + 9 \times (C(4!, 2) + 0!) + 0! \\ 002519 &:= C(C(9, 1), 5) \times 20 - 0! \\ 002592 &:= 2 \times C(9, 5 + 2)^{0!+0!} \\ 002638 &:= (8! - 3!!)/C(6, 2) - 0! - 0! \\ 002685 &:= -5 + 8!/C(6, 2) + 0! + 0! \\ 002746 &:= 6! + C(4!, C(7, 2)) + 0! + 0! \\ 002755 &:= -5 + 5! \times (C(7, 2) + 0! + 0!) \\ 002795 &:= 5 \times (C(9 + 7, 2 + 0!) - 0!) \\ 002808 &:= 8 \times C(-0! + C(8, 2), 0! + 0!) \\ 002854 &:= 4! \times 5! - C(8, 2) + 0! + 0! \\ 002918 &:= 81 \times C(9, 2) + 0! + 0! \\ 002939 &:= C(9, 3) \times (C(9, 2) - 0!) - 0! \\ 002975 &:= 5 \times 7 \times (C(9, 2 + 0!) + 0!) \\ 003049 &:= (C(9, 4) + 0!) \times (3 + 0!)! + 0! \\ 003124 &:= (C(4, 2) - 1)^{3! - 0!} - 0! \\ 003149 &:= C(9, 4) \times ((1 + 3)! + 0!) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

- 003248** := $8 \times C(4! + 2 + 3, 0! + 0!)$
003278 := $C(C(C(8, 7), 2), 3) + 0! + 0!$
003324 := $(C(4!, 2) \times 3! + 3!) \times (0! + 0!)$
003346 := $C(6, 4)^3 - 30 + 0!$
003354 := $C(4! + 5, 3) - 300$
003373 := $C(3!, 7 - 3)^3 - 0! - 0!$
003384 := $4! \times (C(8, 3!) \times (3! - 0!) + 0!)$
003385 := $5! \times C(8, 3!) + (3 + 0!)! + 0!$
003462 := $2 \times 6! + C(4!, 3) - 0! - 0!$
003466 := $6! + 6! + C(4!, 3) + 0! + 0!$
003525 := $(5! \times 2 - 5) \times C(3!, 0! + 0!)$
003541 := $-1 + C(4!, 5) / (3! \times (0! + 0!))$
003542 := $C(24, 5) / 3! / (0! + 0!)$
003544 := $C(4!, 4 \times 5) / 3 + 0! + 0!$
003589 := $-C(9, 8) + 5 \times 3!! - 0! - 0!$
003712 := $C(2, 1)^7 \times (30 - 0!)$
003765 := $5 \times (6! + C(7, 3) - 0! - 0!)$
003924 := $C(4!, 2) \times 9 + 3!! \times (0! + 0!)$
003945 := $5! \times (4! + 9) - C(3!, 0! + 0!)$
003983 := $3! \times 8 \times (C(9, 3) - 0!) - 0!$
004356 := $(6! + 5) \times 3! + 4 + 0! + 0!$
004415 := $-C(5, 1)^4 + ((4 - 0!)! + 0!)!$
004593 := $-3!! + C((9 - 5)!, 4) / (0! + 0!)$
004621 := $C(12, 6) \times (4 + 0!) + 0!$
004625 := $5 \times (C(2 \times 6, (4 - 0!)!) + 0!)$
004692 := $(2 + 9 + 6) \times C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004753 := $3! \times C(5 + 7, 4 + 0!) + 0!$
004758 := $-(8 - 5)! + 7! - C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004759 := $(C(9, 5) - 7) \times 40 - 0!$
004762 := $-2 + 6! \times 7 - C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004765 := $-5 + 6 + 7! - C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004771 := $1 \times 7 + 7! - C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004787 := $7! - C(-8 + 7 + 4!, 0! + 0!)$
004885 := $-5! / 8 + C(8, 4)^{0!+0!}$
004886 := $-6 - 8 + C(8, 4)^{0!+0!}$
004891 := $-1 \times 9 + C(8, 4)^{0!+0!}$
004899 := $-C(9, 9) + C(8, 4)^{0!+0!}$
004916 := $(6 + 1)! - C(9, 4) + 0! + 0!$
004917 := $7! + 1 - C(9, 4) + 0! + 0!$
004935 := $5 \times (3!! - 9 + C(4!, 0! + 0!))$
004953 := $(-3!! + C((-5 + 9)!, 4)) / (0! + 0!)$
004968 := $(8 - 6) \times 9 \times C(4!, 0! + 0!)$
004993 := $C(3! + 9, 9) - 4! / (0! + 0!)$
005006 := $C(C(6, 0! + 0!), 5 + 0!) + 0!$
005025 := $(5 + 2)! - C(0! + 5, 0! + 0!)$
005031 := $(1 + 3!)! + 0! - C(5, 0! + 0!)$
005074 := $4! + 7! + C(05, 0! + 0!)$
005249 := $C(-9 + 4!, 2) \times 50 - 0!$
005464 := $4 \times (C(C(6, 4), 5 - 0!) + 0!)$
005537 := $(-C(7, 3!) + 5!) \times (50 - 0!)$
005625 := $(C(5, 2) + 65)^{0!+0!}$
005648 := $8 \times (-4 + 6! - C(5, 0! + 0!))$
005698 := $8 \times (-9 + 6!) + C(5, 0! + 0!)$
005737 := $7! + 3!! - C(7, 5) - 0! - 0!$
005745 := $C(5, 4)! + 75^{0!+0!}$
005783 := $3!! \times 8 + C(7, 5) + 0! + 0!$
005797 := $7! + C(9, 7) + (5 + 0!)! + 0!$
005838 := $8 \times 3!! + C(8 + 5, 0! + 0!)$
006328 := $8 \times (C(2 \times 3!, 6 - 0!) - 0!)$
006345 := $(5 + 4) \times (3!! - C(6, 0! + 0!))$
006432 := $-2 + C(C(3!, 4), 6 + 0!) - 0!$
006433 := $-3 + C(C(3!, 4), 6 + 0!) + 0!$
006435 := $C(5 \times 3, 4 + 6 - 0! - 0!)$
006624 := $C(4!, 2) \times 6 \times (6 - 0! - 0!)$
006685 := $(-5! + 8!) / 6 - C(6, 0! + 0!)$
006722 := $(C(2, 2) + 7)! / 6 + 0! + 0!$
006726 := $6! + C(2 \times 7, 6) \times (0! + 0!)$
006936 := $-6! / 3! + C(9, 6)^{0!+0!}$
007247 := $7! + C(4!, 2) \times (7 + 0!) - 0!$
007393 := $C(3 + 9, 3!) \times (7 + 0!) + 0!$
007393 := $C(3 + 9, 3!) \times (7 + 0!) + 0!$
007497 := $7! + (-C(9, 4) + 7!) / (0! + 0!)$
007524 := $C(4! - 2, 5) / 7 \times (0! + 0!)$
007539 := $9 \times (3!! + 5!) - C(7, 0! + 0!)$
007828 := $C(8 \times 2, 8) - 7! - 0! - 0!$
008464 := $(4 \times (C(6, 4) + 8))^{0!+0!}$
008564 := $C(4! - 6, 5) - 8 / (0! + 0!)$
008592 := $C((2 \times 9), 5) + (8 / (0! + 0!))!$
008624 := $(C(4, 2) \times 6! - 8) \times (0! + 0!)$
008656 := $(C(6, 5) \times 6! + 8) \times (0! + 0!)$

- 009516** := $61 \times (5! + C(9, 0! + 0!))$
009544 := $C(4!, 4) - 5! \times 9 - 0! - 0!$
009614 := $C(4!, 1 + 6) / C(9, 0! + 0!)$
009927 := $7! \times 2 - C(9 + 9, 0! + 0!)$
010379 := $9! / C(7, 3) + 0! + 10$
010626 := $C((6 - 2)!, -6 + 0!0)$
010644 := $C(4!, 4) + 6 \times (0! + 1 + 0!)$
012134 := $C(4!, 3) \times (1 + 2)! - 10$
012145 := $(C(5, 4) - 1)!! / (21)! + 0!$
012146 := $6 \times C(4!, 1 + 2) + 1 + 0!$
012223 := $(C(3!, 2) + 2) \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$
012257 := $(7 + C(5, 2)) \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$
012371 := $C(17, 3!) - (2 + 1)! + 0!$
012377 := $C(7 + 7 + 3, (2 + 1)!) + 0!$
012398 := $C(8 + 9, 3!) + 21 + 0!$
012575 := $5 \times (7! - C(5, 2)) / (1 + 0!)$
012652 := $C(25, 6 - 2) + 1 + 0!$
012848 := $C(-8 + 4!, 8) - 21 - 0!$
013225 := $(5! + C(2, 2) - 3!)^{1+0!}$
013462 := $((-2 + 6)! + C(4!, 3!)) / 10$
013468 := $C(8, 6) \times (4 \times (3! - 1)! + 0!)$
013575 := $(5! - 7) \times 5! + C(3!, 1 + 0!)$
013634 := $4!^3 - C(C(6, 3), 1 + 0!)$
013678 := $(C(8, 7)! + 6!) / 3 - 1 - 0!$
013724 := $4 \times (C(2 \times 7, 3! + 1) - 0!)$
013727 := $C(7 \times 2, 7) \times (3 + 1) - 0!$
013738 := $8 \times C(3! + 7, 3!) + 10$
014124 := $-C(4!, 2) + (1 + 4!)^{1+0!}$
014125 := $5!^2 + 1 - C(4!, 1 + 0!)$
014168 := $8! / 6! \times C(-1 + 4!, 1 + 0!)$
014234 := $4!^{C(3, 2)} + 410$
014366 := $6! \times C(6, 3) - 4! - 10$
014374 := $4! + C(7, 3) \times 410$
014399 := $(-C(9, 9) + 3!)! \times (4 + 1)! - 0!$
014489 := $9 \times C(8, 4) \times (4! - 1) - 0!$
014495 := $5 \times (C(9, 4) \times (4! - 1) + 0!)$
014523 := $C(3, 2) + 5! \times ((4 + 1)! + 0!)$
014625 := $5!^2 + C(6, 4)^{1+0!}$
014904 := $(4 - 0!)! \times 9 \times C(4!, 1 + 0!)$
014952 := $C(2 + (-5 + 9)!, 4) + 1 + 0!$
015245 := $(5! + C(4, 2)) \times (5! + 1) - 0!$
015295 := $5 \times (C(9 \times 2, 5 - 1) - 0!)$
015324 := $C(4! / 2, 3!) + 5!^{1+0!}$
015532 := $2 \times (C(3!, 5)^5 - 10)$
015552 := $(2 + C(5, 5))!^5 \times (1 + 0!)$
015553 := $3!^5 \times (C(5, 5) + 1) + 0!$
015568 := $(8 + C(6, 5)^5) \times (1 + 0!)$
015623 := $(3 + 2)^{C(6, 5)} - 1 - 0!$
015627 := $(7 - 2)^{C(6, 5)} + 1 + 0!$
015674 := $4^7 - C(6, 5)! + 10$
015924 := $4! \times 2 + C(9, 5)^{1+0!}$
016016 := $C(6 + 10, 6) \times (1 + 0!)$
016469 := $C(9, 6) + 4^{6+1} + 0!$
016574 := $4^7 + C(5! / 6, 1 + 0!)$
017199 := $9 \times 9! \times C(7, 1 + 0!)$
017256 := $(C(6, 5) - 2)! \times ((7 - 1)! - 0!)$
017275 := $-5 + (7 + 2)! / C(7, 1 + 0!)$
017279 := $9! / C(7, 2) - (7! \times 0!)$
017343 := $3!! \times 4! + 3 \times C(7, 1 + 0!)$
017535 := $(5! + 3!! - 5) \times C(7, 1 + 0!)$
017738 := $(C(8, 3!) + 7!) \times 7 / (1 + 0!)$
018226 := $C(6, 2)^2 \times 81 + 0!$
018256 := $652 \times C(8, 1 + 0!)$
018563 := $C(3 \times 6, 5 + 8 - 1) - 0!$
018564 := $C(4! - 6, (5 + 8 - 10)!)!$
018646 := $C(-6 + 4!, 6) + 81 + 0!$
018873 := $-C(3! + 7, 8) + 8! / (1 + 0!)$
019424 := $-4! + C(2 \times 4 + 9, 10)$
019448 := $C(8 \times 4 / 4 + 9, 10)$
019449 := $C(9 + 4 + 4, 9 + 1) + 0!$
019476 := $-6! + 7! \times 4 + C(9, 1 + 0!)$
019628 := $C(8, 2) \times (6! - 9 - 10)$
020245 := $5 \times (C(4!, 2 + 0!) \times 2 - 0!)$
020343 := $C(-3 + 4!, 3! - 0!) - (2 + 0!)!$
020349 := $C(9 + 4 \times 3, -0! + (2 + 0!)!)$
020468 := $C(C(8, 6), 4) - 0! - (2 + 0!)!$
020474 := $C(4 \times 7, 4) - (0 \times 20)!$
020482 := $C(28, 4) + 0! + (2 + 0!)!$
020544 := $C(4! - 4, 5) + (0! + (2 + 0!)!)!$

$$020764 := (-4 + 6!) \times (C(7 + 0!, 2) + 0!)$$

$$021923 := 3! \times C(29, 1 + 2) - 0!$$

$$022413 := 31 \times (C(4, 2)! + 2 + 0!)$$

$$022434 := (C(4!, 3!) + 4 \times 2) / (2 + 0!)!$$

$$022494 := (4! + C(9, 4))^2 - (2 + 0!)!$$

$$022637 := 7^3 \times C(6 \times 2, 2) - 0!$$

$$022848 := 8 \times 4! \times (C(8 \times 2, 2) - 0!)$$

$$023184 := 4!! / ((C(8, 1) + 3) \times 20!)$$

$$023369 := (C(9, 6) + 3!^{3!}) / 2 - 0!$$

$$023469 := 9! / C(6, 4) - 3!! - 2 - 0!$$

$$023697 := -7 \times 9 + 6! \times (32 + 0!)$$

$$023715 := (5! - 1 + C(7, 3))^2 - 0!$$

$$023738 := 83 \times C(7 + 3!, 2 + 0!)$$

$$023745 := C(5 + 4!, 7 - 3) - (2 + 0!)!$$

$$023754 := C(4! + 5, 7 - 3) + 2 + 0!$$

$$023761 := 1 \times 6! \times (C(7, 3) - 2) + 0!$$

$$023793 := (-3 + C(9, 7)) \times ((3 \times 2)! + 0!)$$

$$023953 := (-3!! \times 5 + 9!) / C(3!, 2) + 0!$$

$$023975 := (5! - 7! + 9!) / C(3!, 2) + 0!$$

$$024024 := C(4^2, (-0! + 4)!) \times (2 + 0!)$$

$$024186 := 6 \times (8! / C(1 + 4, 2) - 0!)$$

$$024239 := 9! / C(3!, 2) + 4! \times 2 - 0!$$

$$024244 := 44 \times (2 \times C(4!, 2) - 0!)$$

$$024264 := -4! + 6 \times 2 \times C(4!, 2 + 0!)$$

$$024311 := C(11 + 3!, 4 \times 2) + 0!$$

$$024324 := 4! / 2 \times (3 + C(4!, 2 + 0!))$$

$$024375 := 5 \times 7! - 3 \times C(4!, 2) + 0!$$

$$024438 := -8 + 34 \times (C(4, 2)! - 0!)$$

$$024445 := -5 + C(4!, 4) + 4!^{2+0!}$$

$$024446 := (6 + 4 + 4!) \times (C(4, 2)! - 0!)$$

$$024457 := 7! \times 5 - 4! - C(4, 2)! + 0!$$

$$024469 := 9! / C(6, 4) + C(4!, 2) + 0!$$

$$024471 := C(1 + 7 \times 4, 4) + (2 + 0!)!!$$

$$024475 := 5 \times 7! - 4 - C(4, 2)! - 0!$$

$$024476 := 6! \times C(7, 4) - 4 - (2 + 0!)!!$$

$$024481 := C(18, 4) \times 4 \times 2 + 0!$$

$$024696 := 6 \times C(9, 6) \times (4! \times 2 + 0!)$$

$$024697 := 7 \times C(9, 6) \times 42 + 0!$$

$$024723 := 3^{2+7} + (C(4, 2) + 0!)!$$

$$024833 := -3! + 3!! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) - 0!$$

$$024839 := (9 - 3)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) - 0!$$

$$024841 := (-1 + 4)!! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) + 0!$$

$$024875 := 5 \times (7! - C(8 + 4, 2) + 0!)$$

$$024925 := 5 \times (-2 + 9)! - C(4!, 2) + 0!$$

$$024949 := C(9, 4) \times 9 \times (4! - 2) + 0!$$

$$024985 := 5 \times (-8 + C(-9 + 4!, (2 + 0!)!))$$

$$025025 := 5 \times C(20 - 5, (2 + 0!)!)$$

$$025145 := 5 \times (4! + C(15, (2 + 0!)!))$$

$$025255 := 5 \times ((C(5, 2) + (5 + 2)!) + 0!)$$

$$025487 := 7 \times (C(8, 4) \times 52 + 0!)$$

$$025619 := C(9 + 1, 6) \times (5! + 2) - 0!$$

$$025667 := (-7 + 6!) \times C(6, 5)^2 - 0!$$

$$025679 := C(9, 7) \times 6! - 5! \times 2 - 0!$$

$$025704 := C(4! + 0! - 7, 5) \times (2 + 0!)$$

$$025735 := -5 + C(3! + 7, 5) \times 20$$

$$025764 := 4! + C(6 + 7, 5) \times 20$$

$$025964 := 4 \times (6! \times 9 + C(5, 2) + 0!)$$

$$026029 := C(9, 2) \times (0! + 6! + 2) + 0!$$

$$026243 := 3^{C(4, 2)} \times 6^2 - 0!$$

$$026334 := C(4! - 3! / 3, 6 - (2 \times 0)!)!$$

$$026496 := 69 \times 4! \times (C(6, 2) + 0!)$$

$$026645 := C(5, 4) + 6! \times (6^2 + 0!)$$

$$026668 := C(8, 6) + 6! \times (6^2 + 0!)$$

$$026677 := (C(7, 7) + 6!) \times (6^2 + 0!)$$

$$026775 := 5 \times (7! + 7! / (C(6, 2) + 0!))$$

$$026878 := (C(8, 7)! + 8! - 6) / (2 + 0!)$$

$$026885 := 5 \times ((8! + 8!) / C(6, 2) + 0!)$$

$$027126 := -6 + C(2 + 17, (2 + 0!)!)$$

$$027132 := C(-2 + C(3, 1) \times 7, (2 + 0!)!)$$

$$027237 := 7! \times 3! - C(2 \times 7, (2 + 0!)!)$$

$$027324 := C(4!, 2) \times ((3 + 7)^2 - 0!)$$

$$027343 := (3!^4 + 3!) \times C(7, 2) + 0!$$

$$027384 := C(4!, 8 - 3) - 7! \times (2 + 0!)$$

$$028225 := (C(5 + 2, 2) \times 8)^2 + 0!$$

$$028344 := (C(4!, 4) + 3) \times 8 / (2 + 0!)$$

$$028524 := -C(4!, 2) + 5 \times 8 \times (2 + 0!)!!$$

$$028567 := 7 \times (6! + 5! \times C(8, 2) + 0!)$$

$$028568 := 8 \times (6! \times 5 - C(8, 2) - 0!)$$

$$028856 := 6! \times 5 \times 8 + C(8, 2 + 0!)$$

$$028895 := (5! + 9) \times 8 \times C(8, 2) - 0!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 029232 &:= 2^3 \times C(29, 2 + 0!) \\
 029394 &:= C(4!, 9 + 3)/92 + 0! \\
 029519 &:= (C(9, 1)^5 - 9)/2 - 0! \\
 029575 &:= (5! \times 7 + 5) \times (C(9, 2) - 0!) \\
 029733 &:= -3 + 3! \times (7! - C(9, 2 + 0!)) \\
 029753 &:= C(3!, 5) \times (7! - 9^2) - 0! \\
 029763 &:= 3 + 6 \times (7! - 9^2 + 0!) \\
 029799 &:= 9 \times (C(9, 7) \times 92 - 0!) \\
 029948 &:= 8! - 4 - 9!/(C(9, 2) - 0!) \\
 029976 &:= 6 \times (7! - 9 - C(9, 2) + 0!) \\
 030245 &:= ((C(5, 4) + 2)! + 0!) \times 3! - 0! \\
 030268 &:= (C(8, 6) + (2 + 0!)! \times (3! + 0!))! \\
 030367 &:= (7! + C(6, 3) + 0!) \times 3! + 0! \\
 030492 &:= 2 \times C(9, 4) \times (0! + (3! - 0!))! \\
 030739 &:= (C(9, 3) + 7! - 0!) \times 3! + 0! \\
 031344 &:= 4! \times (C(4!, 3) + 1 - 3!! + 0!) \\
 031465 &:= (5! - 6) \times C(4!, -1 + 3) + 0! \\
 031799 &:= C(9 + 9, 7) - (1 + 3)! + 0! \\
 031822 &:= -2 + C(2 \times (8 + 1), 3! + 0!) \\
 031823 &:= C(3 \times (-2 + 8), 1 + 3!) - 0! \\
 031825 &:= C(C(5, 2) + 8, 1 + 3!) + 0! \\
 031829 &:= C(9 \times 2, 8 - 1) + 3! - 0! \\
 032175 &:= 5 \times C(C(7 - 1, 2), 3! + 0!) \\
 032343 &:= 3 \times (-4 + C(3!, 2) \times (3!! - 0!)) \\
 032346 &:= 6 \times (C(4! + 3, 2) + (3! + 0!))! \\
 032347 &:= (7! + C(4! + 3, 2)) \times 3! + 0! \\
 032375 &:= 5 \times (7 \times C(3! \times 2, 3!) + 0!) \\
 032376 &:= 6! \times C(7 + 3, 2) - (3 + 0!)! \\
 032384 &:= C((-4 + 8)!, 3) \times 2^{3+0!} \\
 032401 &:= C(10, 4 \times 2) \times 3!! + 0! \\
 032424 &:= (C(4, 2)!/4)^2 + (3 + 0!)! \\
 032624 &:= -4! + 2^{C(6, 2)} - (3! - 0!)! \\
 032748 &:= (-8 + 4^7) \times 2 - 3 - 0! \\
 033241 &:= (1 + C(4!, 2)) \times 3!!/3! + 0! \\
 033263 &:= 3! \times C(6 \times 2, 3!) \times 3! - 0! \\
 033434 &:= C(4!, 3!)/4 - 3!^3 + 0! \\
 033463 &:= -3! + 6! + C(4!, 3!)/(3 + 0!) \\
 033469 &:= (9 - 6)!! + C(4!, 3!)/(3 + 0!) \\
 033518 &:= C(8, 1)^5 + 3!! + 30 \\
 033532 &:= C(23, 5) + 3 - (3! - 0!)! \\
 033586 &:= (6 + 8) \times (5! \times C(3!, 3) - 0!) \\
 033625 &:= 5 \times ((2 + 6)!/3! + 3! - 0!) \\
 033643 &:= -3! + C(4!, 6)/(3 + (3 \times 0!)) \\
 033646 &:= (-6 + C(4!, 6) - 3!)/(3 + 0!) \\
 033649 &:= 9 \times C(4!, 6)/(3! + 30) \\
 033775 &:= 5 \times (7! + C(7 + 3!, 3!)) - 0! \\
 033832 &:= -(2 \times 3)! + 8 \times (3!! \times 3! - 0!) \\
 033885 &:= -C(5!/8, 8) + (3 \times 3 - 0!)! \\
 033893 &:= 3! + (-9 + C(8, 3)) \times (3!! + 0!) \\
 033896 &:= -6! \times 9 + C(8, 3) \times (3!! + 0!) \\
 033915 &:= 5 \times C(19, 3!)/(3 + 0!) \\
 034248 &:= 8! - C(4!, 2) \times (4! - 3 + 0!) \\
 034286 &:= -6 - 8! + C(-2 + 4!, 3!) - 0! \\
 034287 &:= -7 - 8! + C(-2 + 4!, 3!) + 0! \\
 034293 &:= 3 \times (-9 + C(2^4, 3! + 0!)) \\
 034312 &:= -2^{13} + C(4!, 3! - 0!) \\
 034335 &:= (5 + 3)! - C(-3 + 4!, 3 + 0!) \\
 034338 &:= 8! + 3 - C(-3 + 4!, 3 + 0!) \\
 034344 &:= -4! + C(4!, 3!)/4 + 3!! - 0! \\
 034357 &:= 7^5 + C(3 + 4!, 3 + 0!) \\
 034374 &:= (4! - 7) \times (-3 + C(4!, 3) + 0!) \\
 034407 &:= (-7 + 04!) \times C(4!, 3) - 0! \\
 034425 &:= (-5 - 2 + 4!) \times (C(4!, 3) + 0!) \\
 034562 &:= 2 \times C(6, 5)! \times 4! + 3 - 0! \\
 034665 &:= C(5!/6, 6) - 4^{3!} + 0! \\
 034732 &:= (2 \times 3!! + 7) \times 4! + 3 + 0! \\
 034734 &:= (4!/3)! + 7! - C(4!, 3 + 0!) \\
 034776 &:= 6 \times (7! + C(7, 4) + 3!! + 0!) \\
 034836 &:= 6! \times 3! \times 8 + C(4!, 3 - 0!) \\
 034848 &:= 8 \times (-4 + C(8, 4))^{3-0!} \\
 035035 &:= C(5 \times 3, 0! + 5) \times (3! + 0!) \\
 035345 &:= 5 \times (C(4!, 3) + 5 + (3! + 0!))! \\
 035415 &:= 5 \times (C(1 \times 4!, 5)/3! - 0!) \\
 035425 &:= 5 \times (C(24, 5)/3! + 0!) \\
 035445 &:= 5 \times (4 + C(4!, 5)/3! + 0!) \\
 035616 &:= (6! + C(16, 5)) \times (3! + 0!) \\
 035617 &:= 7 \times (C(16, 5) + 3!!) + 0! \\
 035635 &:= C(5!/3!, 6) - 5^{3!-0!} \\
 035649 &:= 9 \times (4! \times C(6 + 5, 3) + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 035777 &:= 7 \times (7! + 7 \times C(5,3)) + 0! \\
 035795 &:= (5! + 9! - 7!)/C(5,3) - 0! \\
 035938 &:= (C(8, -3 + 9) + 5)^3 + 0! \\
 035999 &:= (C(9,9) + 9) \times 5 \times 3!! - 0! \\
 036284 &:= -4 + C(8,2) \times 6^{3+0!} \\
 036293 &:= 3! + 9! \times 2/C(6,3) - 0! \\
 036295 &:= (5! + 9! \times 2)/C(6,3) + 0! \\
 036431 &:= -1 + 3 \times 4!!/(C(6,3) + 0!)! \\
 036433 &:= 3! \times 3 \times C(4 \times 6,3) + 0! \\
 036434 &:= C(4!,3) \times (4! - 6) + 3 - 0! \\
 036445 &:= 5 \times (C(4 \times 4,6) - 3!! + 0!) \\
 036488 &:= 8! - 8 \times (4! \times C(6,3) - 0!) \\
 036598 &:= 8! - C(9 + 5,6) - 3!! + 0! \\
 036884 &:= -4 + 8! - C(8 + 6,3! + 0!) \\
 037123 &:= 3 \times (-2 + C(17,3!)) + 0! \\
 037125 &:= (5 - 2) \times (C(17,3!) - 0!) \\
 037128 &:= (8 - 2) \times C(17,3! - 0!) \\
 037131 &:= 1 \times 3 \times (C(17,3!) + 0!) \\
 037133 &:= 3! + 3 \times C(17,3!) - 0! \\
 037143 &:= 3 \times (4 + C(17,3!) + 0!) \\
 037247 &:= 7 \times (C(4!,2) + 7! + 3! - 0!) \\
 037304 &:= C(4!,03) + 7! \times (3! + 0!) \\
 037318 &:= 8! - C((-1 + 3) \times 7,3!) + 0! \\
 037455 &:= 55 \times (C(4! - 7,3) + 0!) \\
 037464 &:= 4! \times (6! + 4! \times C(7,3) + 0!) \\
 037494 &:= C(4!,9 - 4) - 7! + 30 \\
 037554 &:= C(4!,5) + 5! - 7! - 30
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 037799 &:= (9 + C(9,7)) \times 7!/3! - 0! \\
 037801 &:= C(10,8) \times 7!/3! + 0! \\
 037845 &:= C(5,4) \times 87^{3-0!} \\
 038213 &:= (3!! + 1) \times (-2 + C(8,3) - 0!) \\
 038318 &:= 8! - C(1 \times 3! + 8,3! - 0!) \\
 038326 &:= -C((6 - 2)!,3) + 8! - 30 \\
 038344 &:= 4! - C(4!,3) + 8! + (3 + 0!)! \\
 038347 &:= C(7 + 4,3!) \times 83 + 0! \\
 038399 &:= (-9 + C(9,3)) \times 8^3 - 0! \\
 038466 &:= 6 \times (C(C(6,4),8) - (3 + 0!)!) \\
 038486 &:= (6 + 8)^4 + C(8,3 + 0!) \\
 038548 &:= 8! - C(4!,5)/(8 \times 3) - 0! \\
 038578 &:= 8! - C(7,5) \times 83 + 0! \\
 038609 &:= C(9 + 06,8) \times 3! - 0! \\
 038675 &:= -C(5 + 7,6) + 8! - 3!! - 0! \\
 038748 &:= 8! - 4 \times (7 \times C(8,3) + 0!) \\
 038753 &:= -3! + C(5 + 7 + 8,3!) - 0! \\
 038759 &:= C((9 - 5) \times 7 - 8,3!) - 0! \\
 038761 &:= C(-1 + 6 + 7 + 8,3!) + 0! \\
 038823 &:= -3!! \times 2 + 8! - C(8,3) - 0! \\
 038879 &:= 9 \times (7 - C(8,8))! \times 3! - 0! \\
 038881 &:= 1 \times 8! - 8!/C(8,3!) + 0! \\
 038932 &:= -2 + 3! \times C(9,8) \times (3!! + 0!) \\
 038937 &:= (7! - 3!!) \times 9 + C(8,3) + 0! \\
 039273 &:= (3!! + C(7,2)) \times (9 \times 3! - 0!) \\
 039392 &:= 2 \times (9 + 3^9 + 3 + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

From now onwards the results are with unnecessary extra brackets. These can be removed easily.

$$\begin{aligned}
 039419 &:= (((C(9,1)^4) + 9) \times 3!) - 0! \\
 039528 &:= (8! - C(-((2 - 5) - 9)), (3! - 0!)) \\
 039535 &:= (-5!) + (C((3! + 5),9) \times (3!! + 0!)) \\
 039678 &:= (((8! - 7!) - 6!) + (C(9,3))) + 0! \\
 039825 &:= ((C(5,2) + 8!) + ((-9!)/3!!) - 0!) \\
 039838 &:= ((8! - 3) - ((8!/C(9,3)) - 0!)) \\
 039848 &:= (8! - (-4) \times (8 - C(9, (3 + 0!)))) \\
 039959 &:= ((9 \times (5! + (9!/C(9,3)))) - 0!) \\
 039977 &:= (-7) \times (-((7 \times C((9 + 9),3))) + 0!) \\
 040108 &:= (((8! - 0!) - (C(10,4))) - 0!) \\
 040109 &:= (((9 - 0!)! - (C(10,4) + 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 040238 &:= ((8! - (C(3,2)^04)) - 0!) \\
 040334 &:= (((4!/3)!) + (C(3!,04) - 0!)) \\
 040388 &:= (8! + (C(8,3!) + 040)) \\
 040398 &:= (((8! + (C(9,3))) - 0!) - (4)) - 0! \\
 040698 &:= (8! + (C(9, (6 - 0!)) \times (4 - 0!))) \\
 040754 &:= (C(4!,5) + (-70) \times (4! + 0!)) \\
 040768 &:= ((8 + 6!) \times C((7 + 0!), (4 - 0!)) \\
 040888 &:= (8! + (8 \times (C(8,04) + 0!))) \\
 041617 &:= (((7 + 1)!) + (C(6,1)^4)) + 0! \\
 041618 &:= ((8! + ((1 + (C(6,1)^4)))) + 0! \\
 042338 &:= ((8! - 3!) + C(((3! - 2)!)!, (4 - 0!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 042343 := ((C((3! × 4), 3) + ((2 × 4)!) - 0!)
042354 := (C(4!, 5) - (3! × (24 + 0!)))
042362 := ((-2 + 6!) × ((C(3!, 2) × 4) - 0!))
042375 := (((5! - 7)) × C(3!, 2)) × (4! + 0!)
042384 := (C(4!, (8 - 3)) - (((2 + 4) - 0!)!))
042444 := (4 × ((C(4!, 4) - ((2⁴))) + 0!))
042459 := (-((9 × 5)) + C(4!, ((2 + 4) - 0!)))
042464 := (C(4!, ((6 + 4)/2)) - 40)
042494 := (C(4!, (9 - 4)) - (2 × (4 + 0!)))
042495 := (((C((-((5 - 9))!), 4) - 2) × 4) - 0!)
042502 := (-2 + C(((0! + (5 - 2))!), (4 + 0!)))
042503 := (C(((3 + 0!)!), 5) - ((24 × 0)!)
042504 := C(4!, (05 + (24 × 0)))
042505 := (C(((5 - 0!)!), 5) + ((24 × 0)!)
042513 := ((C(((3 + 1)!), 5) + (2 × 4)) + 0!)
042514 := (C(4!, (1 × 5)) + (2 × (4 + 0!)))
042531 := (((C(((1 + 3)!), 5) + 2) + 4!) + 0!)
042541 := (-1 + (C(4!, 5) - ((2 - 40))))
042543 := (-3 + (C(4!, 5) + (2 + 40)))
042545 := ((-5 + C(4!, 5)) + (2 × (4! - 0!)))
042547 := ((-7) + C(4!, 5)) + (2 × (4! + 0!))
042551 := (C((-((1 - 5))!), 5) + ((2 × 4!) - 0!))
042554 := (C(4!, 5) + (C(5, 2) + 40))
042584 := (C((-((4 - 8))!), 5) + (2 × 40))
042654 := (C(4!, 5) + (-6 × (-24) - 0!))
042954 := (C(4!, 5) + ((9 × 2) × (4! + 0!)))
043224 := ((C(4, 2))! + C((-2 + 3)!)!, (4 + 0!))
043226 := ((6! + 2) + C((-2 + 3)!)!, (4 + 0!))
043233 := ((3^{3!}) + C((-2 + 3)!)!, (4 + 0!))
043324 := (-4 × (((-2 - 3!)) × C(3!, 4)) - 0!))
043381 := (((1 × 8)!) + (C((3 × 3!), 4) + 0!))
043475 := (-((5! - ((C(7, 4)³)))) + (((4 - 0!)!)!))
043556 := -((6! - ((C((5 × 5), 3!)/4) + 0!)))
043559 := (((9!/5!) - 5!) × C(3!, 4)) - 0!
043593 := (-3 + (9 × (C((5!/3!), 4) - 0!)))
043597 := (-7) - ((-9) × C((5!/3!), 4)) + 0!)
043598 := (-8) + ((9 × C((5!/3!), 4)) + 0!)
043659 := (9 × ((5 + C(C(6, 3), 4)) + 0!))
043681 := (1 + (C((8 + 6), 3) × ((4 + 0!)!))
043684 := (-4 × (((-8 - 6!) × C(3!, 4)) - 0!))
043685 := (((5! × C((8 + 6), 3)) + (4)) + 0!)
043687 := (7 + (C((8 + 6), 3) × ((4 + 0!)!))
043689 := (9 + (C((8 + 6), 3) × ((4 + 0!)!))
043694 := (((4⁹) + C(6, 3))/((4 - 0!)!))
043733 := ((C((3 × 3!), (7 + 3)) - 4!) - 0!)
043759 := (C((C(9, 5)/7), (3! + (4))) + 0!)
043763 := ((C((3 × 6), (7 + 3)) + 4) + 0!)
043764 := (C((4! - 6), (7 + 3)) + ((4 - 0!)!))
043781 := ((C(18, (7 + 3)) + 4!) - 0!)
043829 := (C((9 × 2), 8) + ((3 × 4!) - 0!))
043833 := (C((3 × 3!), 8) + (3 × (4! + 0!)))
043881 := ((C(18, 8) + 3) + ((4 + 0!)!))
043944 := ((C(4!, -(4 - 9)) + 3!) + (((4 - 0!)!)!))
044353 := (((C((3! + 5), 3!) × 4) × 4!) + 0!)
044368 := (8! - (-((6/3)) × C(4!, (4 - 0!))))
044388 := ((8! - C(8, 3!)) + (4^{(4-0!)!}))
044575 := (5 × (7! + (C((-5) + 4!), 4) - 0!))
044631 := ((-1 + (3!⁶)) - C(4!, (4 - 0!)))
044632 := (((2 × 3)⁶) - C(4!, (4 - 0!)))
044638 := (8! + (((3! × 6!) - C(4, 4)) - 0!))
044864 := ((C(4!, 6) - (8 - 4))/(4 - 0!))
045355 := (-5 + ((C(5, 3))!/(5! - 40)))
045487 := (((7! + 8!) + (C((4 + 5), 4))) + 0!)
045504 := (C(4!, 05) + (5! × (4! + 0!)))
045689 := (((9!/8) + (C((6 + 5), 4))) - 0!)
045779 := (((C((9 + 7), 7) + 5) × 4) - 0!)
045839 := ((-9) + C((3! + 8), 5)) × (4! - 0!))
046414 := ((C(4!, -(1 - 4)) - 6) × (4! - 0!))
046446 := (-C((6 + 4), 4) + (6^{(4-0!)!}))
046512 := ((2 + 1) × C((5!/6), (4 + 0!)))
046535 := -((5! - ((C(3!, 5)⁶) - ((4 × 0)!)!))
046557 := ((C(7, 5) - 5!) + (6^{(4-0!)!}))
046665 := (-((5 - (6⁶)) - C(6, 4)) - 0!)
046668 := -((C(8, 6) - ((6⁶) + 40)))
046676 := (((6⁷)/6) + C(6, (4 - 0!)))
046682 := (-((2 - C(8, 6))) + (6^{(4-0!)!}))
046944 := (4! × (4! + (C(9, 6) × (4! - 0!))))
046979 := ((C(9, 7) × (9 + (6⁴))) - 0!)
047025 := (C((5²), (0! + 7))/(4! - 0!))
047068 := (C(8, 6) × (0! + (7!/(4 - 0!))))
047504 := ((C(4!, 05) + 7!) - 40)
047541 := (((C(((1 × 4)!)!, 5) + 7!) - 4) + 0!)
047543 := ((C((3! × 4), 5) + 7!) - ((4 × 0)!)!

047554 := (((C(4!, 5) + 5) + 7!) + 4) + 0!
047584 := (C(-(4 - 8))!, 5) + ((7! + 40))
047879 := ((9 × (7! + (8 × C(7, 4)))) - 0!)
048024 := ((-4!) + (((2 + 0!)!)!) × (C(8, 4) - 0!))
048168 := ((8! - 6!) + C(18, (4 + 0!)))
048235 := (-5 + (3!! × (-(2 - C(8, 4)) - 0!)))
048264 := (4! + (6! × (-(2 - C(8, 4)) - 0!)))
048306 := (((6! + 0!) × ((-3 + C(8, 4)))) - 0!)
048328 := (C((8 × 2), 3!) + ((8 + (4 × 0)))!)
048378 := (((C(8, 7))! - 3!) - (8!/(-4 - 0!)))
048644 := (4! + C((4! - 6), (8 + ((4 × 0)!)))
049064 := (C(4!, (6 - 0!)) - (-(9⁴) + 0!))
049152 := ((2^{C(5,1)+9}) × (4 - 0!))
049363 := (3!! - ((-C((6 × 3), 9) - 4!) + 0!))
049364 := ((4! + (C((6 × 3), 9))) + (((4 - 0!)!)!))
049775 := (5 × (((7! + 7!) - (C(9, 4))) + 0!))
049995 := (-5) × (-(C(9, 9) + 9⁴) + 0!))
050388 := C(((8 + 8) + 3), ((0! + (5)) + 0!))
050457 := ((7⁵) + (C((4! - 0!), 5) + 0!))
050626 := C(6, 2)^{-(6×0)!+5} + 0!
051667 := ((C(7, 6) × 61) × (5! + 0!))
051789 := (((C(9, 8))!/7) - (1 + 50))
051843 := (3 × ((4! × ((C(8, 1) - 5))!)! + 0!))
051864 := (4! × ((6! × (C(8, 1) - 5)) + 0!))
053129 := (C((9 + (2¹⁺³)), 5) - 0!)
053131 := (C((1 + (C((3 + 1), 3))!), 5) + 0!)
053144 := (((C(4!, 4) + (1 × 3)) × 5) - 0!)
053155 := (-5 × (-5 - C(((1 + 3))!, (5 - 0!))))
053244 := (((C(4!, 4) + (23)) × 5) - 0!)
053519 := ((-((9 - C(15, 3))) × 5!) - 0!)
053544 := (C(((4 × 4) + 5), 3!) - ((5 + 0!)!))
053592 := (-C((2 + 9), 5) × ((3 - 5!) + 0!))
053784 := (4 × (((C(8, 7))!/3) + 5) + 0!)
053881 := (((1 + (8 × C(8, 3))) × 5!) + 0!)
053995 := (-5) + (-(9 - C(9, 3)) × ((5 + 0!)!))
053996 := (((6! × ((-9 + C(9, 3)))) - (5)) + 0!)
054143 := (C((-3 + 4!), (-(1 - 4))!) - ((5! + 0!)))
054257 := (-7) + C(((5²) - 4), (5 + 0!))
054262 := (-2 + C(-(6/2) + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054264 := C((4! - ((6 × 2)/4)), (5 + 0!))
054304 := (40 + C((-3 + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054312 := ((C(21, 3!) + 4!) + ((5 - 0!)!))

054315 := (51 + C((-3 + 4!), (5 + 0!)))
054326 := (62 + C((-3) + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054328 := ((8²) + C((-3) + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054337 := (73 + C((-3) + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054348 := (84 + C((-3) + 4!), (5 + 0!))
054488 := (8! + ((-8) × C(4!, 4))/(-5 - 0!))
054535 := (-5 × (3!! - ((C((-5 + 4!), 5) - 0!)))
055439 := ((C((9 + 3!) - (4)), 5) × 5!) - 0!
055561 := (((1 + C((6 + 5), 5)) × 5!) + 0!)
055902 := (C((2 + 09), 5) × (5! + 0!))
056475 := (-(5⁷) + ((C(4!, 6) + (5)) - 0!))
057144 := (4! + (4! × C(17, (5 - 0!))))
057474 := (((C(4!, 7) × 4) - 7!)/(5 - 0!)!))
057604 := (4 × (0! + (6! × (C(7, 5) - 0!)))
057684 := (C(4!, (8 + 6))/(7 × 5) - 0!)
057795 := (-5) × (-(C((9 + 7), 7) - 5!) + 0!))
057879 := (9 × ((C((7 + 8), 7) - 5) + 0!))
057939 := ((9 × C((3! + 9), 7)) + ((5 - 0!)!))
057969 := (9 × ((C((6 + 9), 7) + 5) + 0!))
057983 := ((3 × (C((8 + 9), 7) - 5!)) - 0!)
058254 := (-(4⁵) - 2) × (-(C(8, 5) - 0!))
058338 := (8! + (3! × C((3! + 8), (5 + 0!)))
058439 := (((C((9 + 3), 4) - 8) × 5!) - 0!)
058674 := (-C((4 + 7), 6) × ((-8 - 5!) + 0!))
058905 := (((5! - 0!) × 9) × (C(8, 5) - 0!))
058954 := (((4! - 5!) + (C(9, 8)⁵)) + 0!)
058996 := (-(6 × 9 - (C(9, 8)⁵)) + 0!)
059078 := (C(8, (7 - 0!)) + (9⁵) + 0!)
059386 := (((6 × C(8, 3)) + (9⁵)) + 0!)
059723 := ((3! × ((2 × 7!) - (C(9, 5)))) - 0!)
059796 := -(((6! - C(9, 7)) - (9!/(5 + 0!)))
059947 := (-(7 × (4 - C((9 + 9), 5))) - 0!)
059977 := ((7 × C(-(7 - 9) × 9), 5) + 0!)
060368 := (C(8, 6) × ((-3) × (0! - 6!)) - 0!)
060628 := (-8!) + (C(((2 - 6))! - 0!), 6) + 0!)
061435 := (-5 × (-(3 × (C(4, 1)⁶))) + 0!)
061439 := (((9 + 3!) × (C(4, 1)⁶)) - 0!)
061885 := (-5) × (-(C(((8 + 8) + 1), 6)) - 0!)
062378 := ((-87) × (C(3, 2) - 6!)) - 0!
062639 := (((C(9, 3) + (6/2)) × 6!) - 0!)
062865 := ((C((5!/6), 8)/2) - ((6 - 0!)!))
062929 := ((-92) × (C(9, 2) - 6!)) + 0!

- 063272 := ((C((2 × 7), 2) - 3) × (6! - 0!))
063499 := (((9! × C(9, 4))/(3!))! - (6 - 0!))
063648 := ((8/4) × C((6 × 3), (6 + 0!)))
063755 := ((C((5!/5), (7 - 3)) × 6) - 0!)
064169 := (((C(9, 6) + 1) + 4) × (6! + 0!))
064248 := (8 × ((4! + (C((2⁴), 6))) - 0!))
064477 := ((7!/7) + ((C(4!, 4) × 6) + 0!))
064483 := (3!! - (-8 - ((C(4!, 4) × 6) - 0!)))
065259 := (9 × ((C(5, 2) × (5 + 6!)) + 0!))
065987 := ((-78) × (-C(9, 5) - 6!)) - 0!
066239 := (((C(9, 3) + 2) + 6) × 6!) - 0!
066242 := (2 × (((C(4!, 2)/6) × 6!) + 0!))
066292 := ((2⁹) + C(26, (6 - 0!)))
066867 := ((C(7, 6) + 86) × (6! - 0!))
067199 := (((9! + (C((9 - 1), 7))!)/6) - 0!)
067344 := (-((4! × (C(4!, 3) - 7!))) - ((6 + 0!))!)
068543 := ((C(-((3! - 4!)), 5) × 8) - ((6 × 0!))!)
069637 := (((7! - 3!)/(6)) × ((C(9, 6) - 0!))
070561 := (((-1 + C(6, (5 - 0!))) × 7!) + 0!)
071266 := (6! - (-((C(6, 2) - 1)) × (7! - 0!)))
071824 := ((C(4!, 2) - 8)^{1+(7×0)!})
072334 := (((C(4!, 3!) - 3!)/2) + 7!) - 0!
072337 := (((C(((7 - 3)!), 3!)/2) + 7!) - 0!)
072343 := (3! + (((C(4!, 3!)/2) + 7!) - 0!))
072589 := (((C(9, 8))!/5) + ((2 × 7))) - 0!
072934 := ((C(4!, 3) × C(9, 2)) + 70)
073457 := (-((C(7, 5) - 4) × (3!! - (7! + 0!)))
073464 := (4! × (C((-6 + 4!), -(3 - 7))) + 0!))
073728 := ((8! × (2<sup>C(7, 3!)))/70)
074253 := ((-3 × 5!) + C((-2 + 4!), (7 - 0!)))
074256 := (6 × C((-((5 + 2) + 4!), (7 - 0!)))
074383 := ((C(((3 × 8)/3!))!, 4) × 7) + 0!)
074404 := ((4! - 0!) + ((C(4!, 4) × 7) - 0!))
074405 := (((5 - 0!))! + ((C(4!, 4) × 7) - 0!))
074414 := (4! + (((1 + C(4!, 4)) × 7) + 0!))
074416 := (((6 - 1) + C(4!, 4)) × 7) - 0!
074417 := (-7) × (1 - ((C(4!, 4) + (7) - 0!)))
074423 := (((3! + C(24, 4)) × 7) - 0!)
074425 := (((((5 - 2))! + C(4!, 4)) × 7) + 0!)
074452 := ((2 + 5) × C(4!, 4)) + 70)
074613 := C((3! + (16)), ((4! - 7) - 0!))
074642 := ((C((-2 + 4!), 6) + ((4 × 7))) + 0!)
075226 := ((C(6, 2) × (-25 + 7!)) + 0!)
075244 := (((-4 × (C(4, 2))!) + (5⁷)) - 0!)
075333 := (3!! + C(((3³) - 5), (7 - 0!)))
075347 := ((C((7 × 4), 3!)/5) - ((7 × 0)!))
075438 := -(((8!/C(3!, 4)) + (-((5⁷)) - 0!)))
075456 := (((-6) - 5!) + C((4! - (5)), (7 + 0!)))
075582 := C((2 + (85/5)), (7 + 0!))
075683 := ((3 × (C(8, 6) - (-5 × 7!))) - 0!)
075726 := (((C(6, 2) × 7!) + 5!) + (7) - 0!)
075924 := ((C(4!, 2) × (9 + 5!)) + ((7 + 0!))!)
076224 := ((C(4!, 2)²) - (-6 × (7 + 0!)))
077405 := ((C(5, 04)⁷) - ((7 - 0!))!)
077445 := (-5 + (C((4! - 4), 7) - 70))
077514 := ((C((C(4, 1) × 5), 7) - 7) + 0!)
077519 := (C((((9 - 1) + 5) + 7), 7) - 0!)
077521 := (C(-((1 + ((2 - 5) × 7))), 7) + 0!)
077526 := ((C(((6 - 2) × 5), 7) + 7) - 0!)
077528 := ((C(((8/2) × 5), 7) + 7) + 0!)
077544 := (4! + (C((4 × 5), 7) + (7 × 0)))
077854 := (((C(4!, 5) + 8!) - 7!) + 70)
078846 := ((6! + (((4 + C(8, 8))⁷))) + 0!)
079345 := (((5! - 4) × (3!! - C(9, 7))) + 0!)
079365 := (((-5 + 6!) × 3) × (C(9, 7) + 0!))
079855 := ((C((5 × 5), 8)/9) - ((7 + 0!))!)
079883 := -((3!! - (((8! + 8!) - C(9, 7)) - 0!)))
082358 := (C((8 + 5), 3!) + (2 × (8! + 0!)))
082461 := (C(16, 4) - ((-2 × 8!) - 0!))
083424 := (C(4, 2) × ((4!³) + (80)))
083546 := (6! + (((C(4!, 5) + 3) + 8!) - 0!))
083592 := ((C((2 × 9), 5) + 3!!) × (8 + 0!))
084282 := (2 × ((C((8 × 2), 4) + 8!) + 0!))
084462 := (((2 × 6!) + C(4!, 4)) × (8 - 0!))
084961 := (((1 × 6!) × ((C(9, 4) - 8))) + 0!)
085325 := ((C(5, 2) × 3!!) + ((5^{8-0!})))
085567 := ((((-7) + (C(6, 5))!) × 5!) + 8) - 0!)
085687 := (((7! + 8!) + C(6, 5)) + 8!) + 0!)
085689 := (C(9, 8) + (6! × (5! - ((8 × 0!))!))
085932 := (((2 + 3!!) × (C(9, 5))) - ((8 - 0!))!)
086391 := (((C((1 + 9), 3) × 6!) - 8) - 0!)
086415 := (C((5 + 1), 4) × ((6! × 8) + 0!))
086445 := (C(5, 4) × (((4! × 6!) + 8) + 0!))
086523 := (C(3, 2) + (5! × (6! + ((8 × 0!))!)))</sup>

- 086632** := $(-C((23-6),6)) \times (-8+0!)$
086674 := $((C((4!-7),6)+6) \times (8-0!))$
086759 := $((9 \times (5! + (C(7,6))!)) + (8! - 0!))$
088439 := $((9!/3!) + C(4!,8))/(8+0!)$
088933 := $((C((3 \times 3!),9) + 8!) - 8) + 0!$
089424 := $((C(4!,2) \times (4 \times 9)) \times (8+0!))$
091429 := $((-9! \times (2)) + (C((4!-1),9) - 0!))$
091528 := $(8 \times (C((2^{5-1}),9) + 0!))$
092354 := $(-4!) + (C((-5 + ((3!-2))!),9) \times (0!))$
092373 := $-(((3! - C((7 \times 3) - 2),9)) - 0!)$
092377 := $(C(((7+7)+3)+2),9) - 0!$
092379 := $(C(((9 \times 7)/3) - 2),9) + 0!$
093023 := $((3! \times C(20, (3!+9))) - 0!)$
093024 := $((4! \times C(20,3!))/(9+0!))$
093292 := $(2 \times (((C(9,2)^3) - 9) - 0!))$
093556 := $(-((6! - C((5!/5),3!))) - ((9-0!)!))$
094555 := $((-5! + C((5!/5),4)) \times 9) + 0!$
095644 := $((C(4!,4) + (6-5)) \times 9) + 0!$
096144 := $(4! \times ((C(4,1)^6) - 90))$
096436 := $((6! \times 3) + C(4!,6)) - ((9-0!)!)$
096526 := $((C(6,2) \times ((-5+6!) \times (9))) + 0!)$
097195 := $(-5) \times (9 - C(17, (9+0!)))$
097242 := $(2 \times (C((4 + (2 \times 7)),9) + 0!))$
103674 := $((4! \times (7! - 6!)) - (C(3,01))!)$
103704 := $(4! \times ((0! + 7!) - ((C(3,01))!)!))$
104976 := $((6^7 \times 9)/(C(4,01))!)$
105757 := $((C(7,5) \times ((7! - 5) + 0!)) + 1)$
113344 := $((C(4!,4)/3) \times ((31+1)))$
115248 := $(8 \times (C(4,2) + (5!^{1+1})))$
115374 := $((C(4!,7)/3) + (C(5,1) + 1))$
116273 := $-((3! - ((C(C(7,2), (6+1)) - 1)))$
116639 := $((((9 \times 3) \times 6!) \times (6)) - C(1,1))$
116649 := $(9 \times (((4! - 6) \times 6!) + C(1,1)))$
116937 := $((7^{3!} + 9) - 6!) - C(1,1)$
117537 := $((7^{3!} - 5!) + C((7+1),1))$
117637 := $((7^{3!} - C(((6+7) - 1),1))$
117649 := $((9+4) - 6)^{C(7,1)-1}$
117678 := $((8 + (7^6)) + C(7, (1+1)))$
117679 := $((9 + (7^6)) + C(7, (1+1)))$
117745 := $((5! - 4!) + ((7^{C(7,1)-1}))$
120864 := $(4! \times ((-6 + ((8-0!)!) + C(2,1)))$
120945 := $((-C(5,4) + ((9-0!)!) \times ((2+1)))$
120967 := $(C(7,6) - (9!/((0-2) - 1)))$
122396 := $((6! + ((9!/3!) - 2)) \times C(2,1))$
123291 := $(C(19,2) \times (((3 \times 2)!) + 1))$
123498 := $((8! + (C(9,4))) + (3!)! \times (2+1))$
123648 := $((8! \times 46)/C(3!,C(2,1)))$
123668 := $(-86) \times ((-6!) - (3!)! + C(2,1))$
123744 := $(4! \times ((-4+7!) + (C((3+2),1))!))$
123848 := $(-8!) + (-4) \times ((-8!) - (3!)! - C(2,1))$
124389 := $(C(9,8) \times (-3) + (4!^{2+1}))$
124494 := $((-4! + 9!) + C(4!,4))/(2+1))$
124496 := $(-6) + ((9! + C(4!,4))/(2+1))$
124499 := $((-9+9!) + C(4!,4))/(2+1))$
125125 := $((5^2) \times C(15, ((2+1))!))$
125316 := $((-6) - (-((1 \times 3) \times 5!))^{C(2,1)})$
125328 := $(8! + (C(((2+3!)!,5) \times (C(2,1))))$
125426 := $(62 \times (C(4!, (5-2)) - 1))$
125724 := $((-C(4!,2) + (7! \times (5^2))) \times 1)$
125725 := $((5^2) \times (7! - (C(5,2) + 1)))$
125744 := $(-((4^4) + (7! \times (C((5^2),1))))$
125844 := $((C((4! - 4),8) - 5!) - ((2+1))!)$
125865 := $(C((5!/6),8) - ((5 \times 21)))$
125957 := $((7! \times 5) - 9) \times 5 + C(2,1)$
125997 := $(7! - ((9-9!)/C((5-2),1)))$
126358 := $(8! - ((5! \times (3-6!)) + C(2,1)))$
126722 := $((22 \times (7! + 6!)) + C(2,1))$
127443 := $(-3 \times (4! - (C(4!, (7-2)) + 1)))$
127513 := $((3 \times C(((1-5))!), (7-2))) + 1)$
129235 := $(5 \times (((3! - 2) \times (C(9,2))) - 1))$
129456 := $((6! \times 5) - 4) \times (C(9,2) \times 1)$
129555 := $((5! \times 5!) - 5) \times C(9, (2-1))$
129557 := $((7! - (C((5!/5), (9 \times 2)) + 1)))$
129602 := $((20 \times 6!) \times 9) + C(2,1)$
129605 := $(-5 \times (((0-6!) \times C(9,2)) - 1))$
129635 := $(5 \times (3! + ((6! \times (C(9,2))) - 1)))$
129647 := $((7! - (C(4!,6) + ((92-1))))$
131027 := $((7! \times (2)) - 0!) \times (C(13,1))$
131792 := $((2^{9+7+1}) + ((C(3,1))!)!)$
132301 := $((C(10,3!)^2) \times 3) + 1)$
132436 := $((-6! \times (3)) + (C(4!, (2 \times 3)) \times (1)))$
132456 := $((-6) + (5! \times C(4!,2))) \times (3+1)$
132547 := $(7! + (((C(4!,5) - 2) \times (3)) + 1))$

- 132649** := $(9! - (C(((4 \times 6) + 2), 3!) + 1))$
132848 := $((8 \times 4!) - 8) \times (2 + ((C(3, 1))!))$
133056 := $((6! \times 5!) + ((03)!^{C(3,1)!}))$
133156 := $(-((6! - C(((5 - 1)!, 3!))) - ((C(3, 1))!))$
133248 := $((8^4) + ((2^3)!) \times (C(3, 1)))$
133371 := $((17 \times 3)^3 + ((C(3, 1))!))$
133734 := $((C(4, 3))! + 7) \times 3! \times (3!! - 1)$
133756 := $((6! + 5!) + C(((7 - 3)!, 3!)) \times (1))$
133757 := $((-7) \times 5!) + (C(((7 - 3)!, 3!) + 1))$
133765 := $((-5 + 6!) + (C(7, 3)!) \times (31))$
133864 := $((C(4!, 6) - 8) - 3!!) - (3 + 1)$
133868 := $((-8) - 6!) + (C((8 \times 3), 3!) \times (1))$
133875 := $((C(((5 + 7) - 8)!, 3!) - 3!!) - 1)$
133876 := $(-6!) + C(-((7 - 8) - 3)!, (C(3, 1))!))$
133877 := $((-7! / 7) + (C((8 \times 3), 3!) + 1))$
133883 := $(-3!! - (8 + (C((8 \times 3), 3!) - 1)))$
133893 := $(3 \times ((9! / 8) - (3^{C(3,1)!})))$
133932 := $(2 \times ((3!! \times 93) + (C(3, 1))!))$
134044 := $((4! \times (-4! + 0!)) + C(4!, 3!)) \times 1$
134064 := $(-4!) \times (((6 + 0)!) - (C(4!, (3 + 1))))$
134164 := $(C(4!, 6) - ((1 + 431)))$
134233 := $((-3! - 3!!) / 2) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1)$
134234 := $((-4 - 3!!) / 2) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1)$
134235 := $((-5! \times 3) + (C(24, 3!) - 1))$
134236 := $((-6 - 3)!! / (2)) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1))$
134258 := $((-8! / 5!) - 2) + C(4!, 3!) \times (1)$
134324 := $(-((C(4!, 2) - 3) - (C(4!, 3!) + 1)))$
134334 := $((C(4!, 3!) - 3!) - (4^{3+1}))$
134352 := $((-2 \times 5!) - 3) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134353 := $(-3^5 + (C((3! \times 4), 3!) \times 1))$
134355 := $((-5! \times ((5 - 3))) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134356 := $((-6 \times 5!) / 3) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1))$
134363 := $((3! - (6! / 3)) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134364 := $((4! - 6!) / 3) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1)$
134367 := $(-((76 \times 3)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134373 := $((-37) \times 3!) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134375 := $(-C((5 + 7), 3)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134379 := $((-9) \times ((7 - 3)!) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134385 := $((5) \times (((8! / 3!) \times (4)) - C(3, 1)))$
134387 := $((-7! / ((8 \times 3))) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134415 := $((-5 + 1)! / 4) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134416 := $((6! / ((1 \times 4))) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1)))$
134417 := $((-((7 - 1))! / (4)) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134427 := $(-((7 \times 24)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134429 := $((-((9 - 2)) \times 4!) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134433 := $((3! \times (-3 - 4!)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134435 := $((-5! / 3) \times 4) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134445 := $(-((5! - (C(4!, (4! / 4)) - (31))))$
134451 := $(((-1 - 5!) - 4!) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134452 := $((-(-2 + 5)! \times (4!)) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134453 := $(-((C(3!, 5) \times 4!) - (C(4!, 3!) + 1)))$
134455 := $(-((5! + ((5 \times 4))) - (C(4!, 3!) - 1)))$
134456 := $((-6! / (5)) + (4)) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1))$
134464 := $(C(4!, 6) - ((44 \times 3) \times 1))$
134465 := $(-((5! + (6 + 4)) - (C(4!, 3!) - 1)))$
134469 := $((-9! / 6!) / (4)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134472 := $(-((2^7) - 4) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134475 := $(-((5! - (C((7 \times 4) - 4), 3!) - 1)))$
134476 := $((-6! / (7 - 4)!) + C(4!, 3!)) \times (1)$
134477 := $(((-7) \times (-7 + 4!)) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1)))$
134483 := $((-3!! / 8) - ((4! - (C(4!, 3!) + 1))))$
134489 := $(-((9 \times (8 + 4))) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134493 := $((-3!! / 9) - ((4! - (C(4!, 3!) + 1))))$
134494 := $((4! - (C(9, 4))) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134496 := $((6 + 94) + (C(4!, 3!) \times (1)))$
134523 := $((-3!! / ((2 \times 5))) + ((C(4!, 3!) - 1)))$
134524 := $((4! \times (-2 + 5)) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134527 := $(-((7 \times 2) \times 5) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134528 := $(-((8^2) + 5) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134531 := $((-13 \times 5) + (C(4!, 3!) \times 1))$
134532 := $((-2^{C(3!, 5)}) + C(4!, 3!)) \times 1$
134534 := $(C(4!, 3!) - ((5! + 4) / (3 - 1)))$
134535 := $((5! / (3 - 5)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134536 := $((6 + 3!) \times (-5) - (C(4!, 3!) \times (-1)))$
134542 := $((-2 \times 4!) - 5) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134543 := $((3! \times (-4 + 5)) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134544 := $(-(((4! + 4!) + 5) - (C(4!, 3!) + 1)))$
134545 := $(-((5 + 45)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1))$
134546 := $(-((6 + 45)) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134547 := $(((-7) \times 4!) + 5!) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)$
134557 := $(-((7 \times 5) + 5) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1))$
134561 := $(-(((1 + 6) \times 5) - (C(4!, 3!) \times (-1))))$
134563 := $(-((3 \times (6 + 5))) - (C(4!, 3!) \times (-1)))$
134564 := $(C(4!, 6) - ((5 - 4) + 31))$

$$\begin{aligned} 134565 &:= (-((5 \times C(6,5))) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134566 &:= (-(((6 \times 6) - 5)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134568 &:= (- (C(8,C(6,5))) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134571 &:= -((((1^7) - 5)))! - ((C(4!,3!) - 1))) \\ 134572 &:= (((2 - 7) \times 5) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134573 &:= (-((3 + C(7,5))) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134574 &:= (-(((4 \times 7) - 5)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134577 &:= (-(((7 + 7) + 5)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134579 &:= (-((9 \times (7 - 5))) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134581 &:= (-(((1 + 8) + 5)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134582 &:= (-(((2 + 8) + 5)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134583 &:= -(((3! + ((8 - 5))!) - (C(4!,3!) - 1))) \\ 134584 &:= (C(4!, ((8 - 5))!) - C((4 \times 3), 1)) \\ 134585 &:= ((-5) - ((8 - 5))!) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1)) \\ 134586 &:= (((6 - 8) \times 5) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134587 &:= (-(((7 + 8) - 5)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134588 &:= (-8) + C((((8 - 5))! \times 4), (C(3,1))!) \\ 134589 &:= (-(((9 - 8) + 5)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134591 &:= (-(((1^9) + 5)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134593 &:= (-3 + C(((9 - 5))!), ((4 + 3) - 1)) \\ 134594 &:= (C(4!, ((9 + 5) + 4)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 134595 &:= (C(((5 \times (9 - 5)) + 4), 3!) - 1) \\ 134597 &:= (C(((7 \times (9 - 5)) - 4), 3!) + 1) \\ 134598 &:= ((8/(9 - 5)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134599 &:= (-((C(9,9) - 5)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134606 &:= ((60/6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134611 &:= (-((1 - 16)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134612 &:= ((21 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134613 &:= (((C(((3 + 1))!), 6) + 4!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 134614 &:= ((C(4!, (1 \times 6)) + 4!) - (C(3,1))!) \\ 134615 &:= (((C(((5 - 1))!), 6) + 4!) - 3!) + 1) \\ 134616 &:= (((((6 - 1))!/6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134617 &:= (C(7, -((1 - 6))) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134619 &:= (((((9 + 1) - 6))! + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134621 &:= (-((1 - 26)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134622 &:= ((C(((2 + 2))!), 6) + 4!) + (3 - 1)) \\ 134623 &:= ((32 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134624 &:= (C((4 \times 2), 6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134625 &:= ((5!/(-2 - 6))) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134626 &:= ((C(((6 - 2))!), 6) + 4!) + (C(3,1))! \\ 134627 &:= (((7 - 2) \times 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134628 &:= (-((8 \times (2 - 6))) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 134629 &:= ((9 + (-((2 - 6))))!) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1)) \\ 134631 &:= (C(((1 + 3))!), 6) + (4 + 31)) \\ 134632 &:= (((2 \times 3) \times 6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134633 &:= ((3! \times 3!) + (C((6 \times 4), 3!) + 1)) \\ 134634 &:= (C(4!,3!) - (((6 - 43) - 1))) \\ 134635 &:= ((5!/3) + (C((6 \times 4), 3!) - 1)) \\ 134636 &:= (((6!/(3 \times 6)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134637 &:= ((7 \times 3!) + (C((6 \times 4), 3!) - 1)) \\ 134651 &:= (-((1 - 56)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134653 &:= (((((3 + 5))!/6!) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134655 &:= (((5 + 5) \times 6) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134656 &:= ((65 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134658 &:= ((C(8,5) + 6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134659 &:= (C(((9 - 5))!), 6) + (((4^3) - 1)) \\ 134661 &:= (-((1 - 66)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134664 &:= (C(4!,6) + ((64 + 3) + 1)) \\ 134667 &:= ((76 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134671 &:= (-((1 - 76)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134673 &:= ((3! \times (7 + 6)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134675 &:= ((5! - (7 \times 6)) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134678 &:= ((87 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134679 &:= ((9!/(7! - 6!)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134681 &:= (C((1 + 8), 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134685 &:= (((5!/8) \times 6) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134686 &:= (((6!/8) - (C((6 \times 4), 3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134687 &:= (((7 + 8) \times 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134689 &:= ((98 - 6) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134691 &:= (-((1 - 96)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134698 &:= (((8 + 9) \times 6) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134715 &:= (5! + (C((((1 + 7) - 4))!), 3!) - 1) \\ 134716 &:= (((6 - (1^7))!) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134722 &:= (-((2 - (2^7))) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134723 &:= (((((3 + 2))! + 7) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134724 &:= (((4 - 2)^7) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134725 &:= ((5! + (2 + 7)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134734 &:= (((4! \times 3!) - 7) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134735 &:= (((5!/3!) \times 7) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134736 &:= ((C(6,3) \times 7) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134743 &:= (((-3 + 4!) \times 7) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \\ 134745 &:= ((5! + ((4 \times 7))) + (C(4!,3!) + 1)) \\ 134746 &:= (((6 \times 4!) + (7)) + (C(4!,3!) - 1)) \\ 134749 &:= ((9 \times (4! - 7)) - (C(4!,3!) \times (-1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 134764 &:= (C(4!, 6) + (7 \times (C(C(4, 3), 1))!)) \\
 134783 &:= ((3 \times (C(8, 7))!) + ((4!^3) - 1)) \\
 134835 &:= (((5 \times 3!) \times 8) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)) \\
 134836 &:= ((6!/3) - (C(((8 - 4))!, 3!) \times (-1))) \\
 134844 &:= (((4^4) - 8) - (C(4!, 3!) \times (-1))) \\
 134852 &:= (((2^5) \times 8) - (C(4!, 3!) \times (-1))) \\
 134853 &:= (((-((3 - 5))^8) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1)) \\
 134864 &:= ((C(4!, 6) - 8) + C(4!, (3 - 1))) \\
 134875 &:= (((5 \times 7) \times 8) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)) \\
 134956 &:= (((6! - (5! \times 9)) - C(4!, 3!)) \times (-1)) \\
 134957 &:= ((7!/(5 + 9)) + (C(4!, 3!) + 1)) \\
 134973 &:= ((3! \times (7 \times 9)) + (C(4!, 3!) - 1)) \\
 135134 &:= (((4! + 3) \times C(15, 3!)) - 1) \\
 135315 &:= (C(((5 - 1))!, 3!) + ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\
 135316 &:= (6! + C(((1 + 3))!, ((5 - 3) + 1)!)) \\
 135322 &:= (((C(((2 + 2))!, 3!) + 5) + 3!!) + 1) \\
 135334 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + ((3 + 5!) \times (C(3, 1))!)) \\
 135344 &:= (((4! + (C(4!, 3!) + 5)) + 3!!) - 1) \\
 135346 &:= ((6! + C(4!, 3!)) + (5!/(3 + 1))) \\
 135408 &:= (C((-8) + (04)!), 5) \times 31) \\
 135464 &:= (C(4!, 6) + ((4 + 5!) \times (3! + 1))) \\
 135654 &:= ((C((4! - 5), 6) \times 5) - (C(3, 1))!) \\
 135738 &:= (((8! + 3!) + 7!) - 5!) \times C(3, 1)) \\
 135879 &:= (((9 \times (7! - 8)) + (5)) \times C(3, 1)) \\
 136034 &:= (C(4!, 3!) - ((0! - 6!) \times (3 - 1))) \\
 136036 &:= (6! + (C(((3 + 0!))!, 6) + ((C(3, 1))!))) \\
 136095 &:= ((5 + (9 \times ((0! + (6))))!) \times C(3, 1)) \\
 136269 &:= ((9 \times (C(6, 2) + 6)) \times ((3!)! + 1)) \\
 136734 &:= (C(4!, 3!) + (((7 - 6!) \times (-3)) - 1)) \\
 136764 &:= ((C(4!, 6) + 7) + ((6! \times 3) + 1)) \\
 137282 &:= (2 \times ((C((8 \times 2), 7) \times 3!) + 1)) \\
 137544 &:= (4! \times (-((4! + 5) - 7!)) + ((C(3, 1))!)) \\
 137754 &:= ((-4 \times ((5! - 7!) \times 7)) - (C(3, 1))!) \\
 137952 &:= ((2^5) \times ((-9 + 7!) - ((C(3, 1))!))) \\
 138216 &:= (((C(6, 1) - 2))! \times ((8 \times 3!!) - 1)) \\
 138234 &:= (((4!^3) \times (2 + 8)) - (C(3, 1))!) \\
 138354 &:= ((4! \times (5 + (3!! \times 8))) - (C(3, 1))!) \\
 138433 &:= (C(3, 3) + ((4! \times 8) \times (3!! + 1))) \\
 138564 &:= (C(4!, 6) + ((5! + 8) \times 31)) \\
 138768 &:= (C(8, 6) \times (7! - ((83 + 1)))) \\
 138769 &:= (((-C(9, 6) + 7!) \times C(8, 3!)) + 1) \\
 139104 &:= ((C(4!, (0! + 1)) \times 9!)/((C(3, 1))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 139533 &:= ((C(C(3!, 3), 5) \times 9) - C(3, 1)) \\
 139536 &:= ((6^3!) + ((5! + 9) \times ((C(3, 1))!))) \\
 139635 &:= ((5! - ((3!^6) + 9)) \times (-C(3, 1))) \\
 139637 &:= (7! + (C(((36/9))!, 3!) + 1)) \\
 139647 &:= (7! + (C(4!, 6) + ((9 + 3) - 1))) \\
 142848 &:= (8 \times ((4! + ((8 - 2))!) \times (C(4, 1))!)) \\
 143568 &:= -(((8! - 6!) - (C(5, 3))!)/(4! + 1)) \\
 143724 &:= (-C(4!, 2) - ((7! + 3!!) \times (-4! + 1))) \\
 143837 &:= -((7! - (-((3 - C(8, 3)))^{4-1}))) \\
 144143 &:= (((3! \times 4!) \times C(14, 4)) - 1) \\
 144144 &:= ((4! + 4!) \times C(14, ((4 - 1))!)) \\
 144145 &:= (((5! + 4!) \times C(14, 4)) + 1) \\
 144342 &:= ((2 - 4!) \times (-3^{C(4+4, 1)})) \\
 144865 &:= (-5 \times ((6! - 8!) + (C(4!, 4) + 1))) \\
 144888 &:= (-8 - ((8! - (8^4)) \times (-C(4, 1)))) \\
 145145 &:= ((5 + 4!) \times C(15, ((4 - 1))!)) \\
 145151 &:= (-1 + (((C(5, 1) + 5))!/(4! + 1))) \\
 145296 &:= ((6! + (9! \times 2))/C(C(5, 4), 1)) \\
 145392 &:= (2 \times (((9! + 3!!)/5) - (C(4, 1))!)) \\
 145726 &:= (((C(6, 2) - 7!) \times (-5 - 4!)) + 1) \\
 145928 &:= (((-8) + (-((2 - 9))!)) \times (5 + (C(4, 1))!)) \\
 146592 &:= (2 \times ((9!/5) + (C(6, (4 + 1))!))) \\
 146856 &:= (((6! \times (-5)) + 8!) - (6)) \times C(4, 1)) \\
 147348 &:= (((8^4) - 3) \times (C(7, 4) + 1)) \\
 148392 &:= ((C((2 \times 9), 3!) \times 8) - ((4 + 1))!) \\
 148445 &:= (-5 \times ((C(4!, 4) - 8!) + (4 + 1))) \\
 148644 &:= ((C(4!, 4) \times (6 + 8)) - ((4 + 1))!) \\
 149568 &:= (8 \times ((6! + (59)) \times (C(4, 1))!)) \\
 150359 &:= (9! + ((-5) \times C(((3 + 0!))!, 5)) - 1)) \\
 150924 &:= (-C(4!, 2) - (((9 + 0!))!)/(-((5 - 1))!)) \\
 151275 &:= (((-5) + (7! \times (-2))) \times (-C(15, 1))) \\
 152639 &:= ((((-C(9, 3) + 6!) \times 2) \times 5!) - 1) \\
 153153 &:= (C(((3 \times 5) - 1), 3!) \times 51) \\
 153696 &:= (((6! - 9) \times (6^3)) + (C(5, 1))!) \\
 153867 &:= ((C((7 + 6), 8) + 3!) \times (5! - 1)) \\
 154377 &:= ((C((7 + 7), 3!) + 4!) \times 51) \\
 154675 &:= ((5! \times (-7 - (6^4))) - C(5, 1)) \\
 154725 &:= ((5^2) \times (C((-7 + 4!), 5) + 1)) \\
 154748 &:= (((-8) - (-4 \times 7!)) + C(4!, (5 + 1))) \\
 155488 &:= (8! - (8 \times (4 - (5! \times (C(5, 1))!)))) \\
 155733 &:= (3! + (C((3! + 7), 5) \times (5! + 1))) \\
 156834 &:= (C((4! - 3), 8) - (6^{5+1}))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 157469** := $((9 \times 6)^{-4+7} + C(5,1))$
157584 := $(4 \times (8! - (C((5+7), (5+1))))))$
157978 := $((C(8,7))! + ((9 + (7^{5+1}))))$
158399 := $(-C(9,9) + (((3!)! - 8!) \times (-5 - 1)))$
158428 := $(C(8,2) + (4 \times (8! - ((5+1)!)))$
158976 := $((6^7) - (9!/C((8-5),1)))$
159344 := $((((C(4!,4) \times (-3)) + 9) \times (-5)) - 1)$
159344 := $(-1 + (-5 \times (9 + (-3 \times C(4!,4))))))$
160337 := $((-7 - (3!^3)) \times (0! - (C(6,1)!)))$
160584 := $((4 \times ((8! + 5) + 0!)) - (C(6,1)!))$
161051 := $((1 + C(5, (0! + 1)))^{6-1})$
161184 := $((4! - 8!) \times ((C(1,1) - 6) + 1))$
161274 := $((4 \times (((7+2) - 1)!)) - C(6,1))$
161281 := $((((1 \times 8)! \times (-C(2,1) - 6)) + 1)$
161754 := $((4 \times (5! + ((7+1)!)) - C(6,1))$
162225 := $((C(((5-2)!, 2)^2) \times (6! + 1))$
162438 := $(-(8! - ((3! + C(4!,2)) \times (6! - 1))))$
162764 := $(-(C(4!,6) - (7! \times (-2 - 61))))$
162793 := $((3! - 9) \times (-C(C(7,2),6))) + 1)$
163288 := $(8 \times ((C(8,2) \times (3^6)) - 1))$
163667 := $((7 + C((6+6),3)) \times (6! + 1))$
164288 := $(8 \times (C(C(8,2),4) + 61))$
164388 := $((8 \times C(8,3!)) + (4)) \times (6! + 1))$
164439 := $(9 \times ((C((3+4!),4) + 6!) + 1))$
164645 := $(-5 \times ((C(4!,6)/(-4)) + (C(6,1)!)))$
164837 := $((7! \times 3!) + (C(((8-4)!,6) + 1))$
164864 := $((((-4+6!) + 8!) \times 4) + (C(6,1)!))$
165324 := $(C(4!,2) \times (((3!! \times 5)/6) - 1))$
166808 := $((8 \times (0! + (C(8,6)))) \times (6! - 1))$
167555 := $((5! + 5!) - 5) \times (-7 + (C(6,1)!))$
168336 := $((6^3!) + ((3 \times 8!) + (C(6,1)!))$
168483 := $(3 \times (((C(8,4) + 8) \times 6!) + 1))$
169343 := $((-((3!^4)) - 3!!) \times (-C(9,6))) - 1)$
169344 := $((C((4+4),3) \times 9!)/((6-1)!))$
170425 := $(-(5! - (C((-2+4!),07) + 1)))$
170543 := $(C(((3+4!) - 5),07) - 1)$
170544 := $C(((-4 - 4!) + (50)),C(7,1))$
171275 := $((5 + (7! \times (-2))) \times (-C(17,1)))$
171292 := $(-((2 - C(9,2))) \times ((-1 + 7!) - 1))$
172524 := $(-(C(4!,2) + ((5! \times (-2)) \times ((7-1)!))))$
172553 := $((((3!! \times 5!) - 5!) \times 2) - C(7,1))$
172801 := $((10!/(C(8,2) - 7)) + 1)$
173033 := $((3!!/(-3)) \times (-0! - 3!!)) - C(7,1))$
173844 := $((C(4!,4) - 8!) + 3!!) \times (-7 - 1))$
174196 := $(-(((6! - ((9-1)!)) - C(4!, (7-1))))))$
174455 := $((5 - 5!) \times ((C(4!,4)/(-7)) + 1))$
174743 := $((-34) \times 7!) + (C(4!,7) - 1))$
174748 := $((8! - (4! \times 7)) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174858 := $((8! - (58)) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174868 := $((8! - ((6 \times 8))) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174884 := $((-(4 \times 8) + 8!) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174907 := $((7 + 0!)! + (-9) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174908 := $((8! + 0!) - 9) + C(4!, (7-1))$
174913 := $((-3 + (-((1-9)!)) + (C(4!, (7-1))))))$
174988 := $((8! + (8 \times 9)) + C(4!, (7-1)))$
174996 := $((6! + 9!)/9) + C(4!, (7-1))$
175435 := $(-5 + (34 \times (5! + (C(7,1)!))))$
175567 := $(-C(7,6) \times (5! - ((5 \times 7!) + 1)))$
176395 := $(-5) + (((9! \times 3)/6) - (C(7,1)!))$
176399 := $((-((C(9,9) - 36)) \times 7!) - 1)$
176401 := $((C(10,4)/6) \times 7!) + 1)$
176404 := $(4! + (C((0! + 4!),6) - ((7-1)!)))$
176477 := $((7! \times C(7,4)) + ((6+71)))$
177345 := $(-5 \times (((4! + 3) + 7!) \times (-C(7,1))))$
177385 := $(-5) \times (((C(8,3!) + 7!) \times (-7)) - 1))$
178464 := $(-4 \times (((6! + 4!) - 8!) - (C(7,1)!)))$
178529 := $((C(9,2) - 5) \times ((8!/7) - 1))$
178553 := $((3!! \times ((5! + 5!) + 8)) - C(7,1))$
178564 := $(-4 \times (((C(6,5)! - 8!) - 7!) - 1))$
179677 := $((-7) \times ((7-6!) \times C(9,7))) + 1)$
179747 := $((7! - 47) \times C(9,7)) - 1)$
179964 := $((C(4!,6) + 9) - ((-9 \times 7!) + 1))$
181344 := $(-4 \times ((4! - ((3! + 1)!)) - (C(8,1)!)))$
181429 := $((9!/2) - C(((4-1) + 8),1))$
181449 := $((9!/(C(4,4) + 1)) + (8 + 1))$
181729 := $((C(9,2) \times (7! + (1 \times 8))) + 1)$
183557 := $((-((7^5)) + 5!) \times (-C((3+8),1)))$
183568 := $(-(C(8,6) \times (5 - ((3^8) \times 1))))$
183688 := $(8 + (C(8,6) \times ((3^8) - 1)))$
183689 := $(9 + (C(8,6) \times ((3^8) - 1)))$
183699 := $(-(9 - (C(9,6) \times (3^{8-1}))))$
183708 := $(C(8, -((0! - 7))) \times ((3^8) \times 1))$
184352 := $((-((2^5)) \times 3!!) - 4) \times (-C(8,1))$
184368 := $((-((8! + 6))) + ((3!)! \times 4!)) \times (-C(8,1))$

- 185592** := ((((-2 × 9!)/(-5)) + 5!) + (C(8, 1)!))
185664 := ((4 × (6⁶)) + (5! × (-C(8, 1))))
186479 := (((9 × C(7, 4)) × 6!) - 8!) - 1)
186534 := ((4! × (3!⁵)) - (6!/C(8, 1)))
186632 := (((-2 + 3!) × (6⁶)) + C(8, 1))
187964 := (((C(4!, 6) - 9!) + (7! × 8)) × (-1))
191482 := ((2 - (8!/4)) × (-C(19, 1)))
193344 := -(((4! × C(4!, 3)) - (3! × ((9 - 1)!)))
193444 := (4 × ((4! × (C(4!, 3) - 9)) + 1))
193548 := (((8! × 4!)/5) + C((3 + 9), 1))
194337 := ((7 + (3!! × (-3! + 4!))) × (-C(9, 1)))
194344 := (4 × ((C(4!, 3) × 4!) + (9 + 1)))
194355 := ((5 + ((5! × 3!)/(-4))) × (-C(9, 1)))
194364 := ((4 - (6! × (3! + 4!))) × (-C(9, 1)))
194436 := (((6! × (3! + 4!)) + (4)) × C(9, 1))
194457 := ((C(7, 5)⁴) - (-(((4 - 9) + 1)!))
194944 := (((C((4! - 4), 9) - 4!) - 9!) × (-1))
194945 := (((-C((5 × 4), 9) + 4!) + 9!) + 1)
196237 := ((C(((7 - 3)!), 2) × (6! - 9)) + 1)
196243 := (3! + ((C(4!, 2) × (6! - 9)) + 1))
196328 := (C(((8/2)!), 3) × (6 + 91))
197342 := (2 × ((C((4! + 3), 7)/9) + 1))
198555 := (-5 × (((5! × 5) - 8!) + C(9, 1)))
199439 := ((9! - 3) + (C(4!, 9)/(-9 - 1)))
201585 := ((5 × 8!) - C((5 + 1), 02))
201685 := (5 × (8! + (C(6, (1 + 0!)) + 2)))
201845 := (-5 × ((-4 - 8!) - C(10, 2)))
202614 := ((C((4! - 1), 6) × 2) + (((0! + 2)!))
203324 := (((C(4!, 2) + 3!) × (3!! + 0!)) + 2)
204568 := (((-8) - 6!) × (-5) - C(4!, 02)))
204624 := ((C(4!, 2) × (6! + 4!)) - (((0! + 2)!))
205634 := ((4! × C((3 × 6), 5)) + 02)
207636 := ((6! + 3!) × C((6 + 7), (0! + 2)))
211677 := ((7! × (7 × 6)) - (C(1, 1) + 2))
212544 := (4! + (C(4!, 5) × ((2 + 1) + 2)))
212545 := (5 × (C(4!, 5) + ((2 + 1) + 2)))
213444 := (C((44/4), 3!)^{1×2})
214369 := (((C(9, 6) × 3!) - 41)²)
217418 := (8! + (C((1 + 4!), (7 - 1)) - 2))
217554 := (((C(4!, 5) × 5) + 7!) - ((1 + 2)!))
221748 := (8! - ((4! - ((C(7, 1) + 2)!)/2))
221784 := ((4! + 8!) - (((C(7, 1) + 2)!)/(-2)))
223144 := ((C(4!, 4) × C((1 + 3!), 2)) - 2)
223944 := (C(4!, -((4 - 9))) + (((3²)!)/2))
224384 := (((-((4⁸)) - (3!^{C(4,2)})) × (-2))
224672 := ((2 × (7⁶)) - C(4!, (2 + 2)))
225744 := (4! - ((4! - 7!) × C(C(5, 2), 2)))
226397 := (((7! - 9) × (3 × C(6, 2))) + 2)
226432 := -(((2^{C(3!,4)}) - ((6!²)/2)))
226573 := ((3 × ((7! - 5) × C(6, 2))) - 2)
226773 := (3 × (-7 + ((7! × C(6, 2)) - 2)))
226785 := (5 × ((8! + 7!) - C((6/2), 2)))
226805 := (5 × ((0! + 8!) + ((6 + C(2, 2))!))
226875 := (5 × ((7! + 8!) + C(6, (2 + 2))))
228284 := -((C(4!, (8 - 2)) - ((8 + C(2, 2))!))
228864 := ((C(4!, 6) - ((-8 - 8!)/(-2))) × 2)
230224 := (C((4! + 2), 20) - (3 × 2))
230228 := (C((C(8, 2) - 2), (03)!) - 2)
230242 := (C((2 + 4!), 20) + (3! × 2))
230254 := (4! + C(((5²) + 0!), (3 × 2)))
230398 := (((8!/C(9, 3))^{-0!+3}) - 2)
230428 := (C(8, 2) + ((4 × (-((0! - 3!)))!))²)
230744 := (4 × ((C(4!, 7)/(03)!) + 2))
230945 := ((C((-5 + 4!), 9) × (0! - 3!))/(-2))
231361 := ((1 + (C(6, 3) × ((1 + 3)!))!))²
233205 := (5 × (((0! + 2)!^{3!}) - C(3!, 2)))
233475 := ((57 × (4^{3!})) + C(3, 2))
233535 := (((-5!) - 3!) + (((5^{3!}) × C(3!, 2))))
233854 := ((((-4 + 5!) × 8!)/C(3!, 3)) - 2)
233985 := (-5) × (-8!) + ((-9) × 3!) + C(3, 2)))
234165 := (((5⁶) - 14) × C(3!, 2))
234236 := (-C(6, 3) + ((-2) + 4!)^{3!-2})
234241 := (((((1 × 4)! - 2)⁴) - C(3!, 2))
234249 := (-9) + (((4! - 2)^{C(4,3)}) + 2))
234259 := (((((9 - 5)! - 2)⁴) + C(3, 2))
234271 := (((1 + C(7, 2))⁴) + C(3!, 2))
234315 := (((5^(1×3!)) - 4) × C(3!, 2))
234324 := (C((4! + 2), 3!) + ((4^{3!}) - 2))
234465 := (((5⁶) + (4!/4)) × C(3!, 2))
234546 := (-6) + ((-4) + 5!) × (C(4!, 3) - 2)))
234648 := (((-8) + (4! × 6!)) - C(4!, 3!)) × (-2))
234984 := -((4! + (-((8 + 9) × (4!^{C(3,2)}))))))

$$\begin{aligned} 235289 &:= (-C(9,8) - ((2+5)^{3!}) \times (-2)) \\ 235298 &:= (((8 + C(9,2) + 5)^3) \times 2) \\ 235299 &:= (C(9,9) - (((2+5)^{3!}) \times (-2))) \\ 235302 &:= (2 \times (((0! + C(3!,5))^{3!}) + 2)) \\ 235318 &:= (((8-1)^{3!}) + C(5,3)) \times 2) \\ 236535 &:= (((5^{3!}) \times (-5)) - 6!) \times (-C(3,2)) \\ 236544 &:= ((4^4) \times (C((5+6),3!) \times 2)) \\ 236723 &:= (-C(3!,2) - ((-(7^6)) - 3!!) \times 2)) \\ 236736 &:= (((C(6,3!) - (7^6)) - 3!!) \times (-2)) \\ 236865 &:= (((5! + 6!) - 8!) \times (-6) - C(3!,2)) \\ 237322 &:= (C(((2+2)!,3) - (7^{3!}) \times (-2))) \\ 237334 &:= (C(4!,3) - ((3! + 7^{3!}) \times (-2))) \\ 237534 &:= (4! - (C(-(3! - (5 \times 7)),3!)/(-2))) \\ 238313 &:= (((31^3) \times 8) - C(3!,2)) \\ 238335 &:= ((-5 \times 3!!) + ((3! \times 8!) + C(3!,2))) \\ 238446 &:= (-6) \times (((4! \times 4!) - 8!) + C(3,2)) \\ 238698 &:= (-89) \times (6 - (8!/C(3!,2))) \\ 238784 &:= ((48 \times 7!) - (C(8,3^2))) \\ 238896 &:= (((6! - 9) \times 8!)/(8 - C(3,2)))! \\ 239121 &:= ((C(12, -(1-9)) - 3!)^2) \\ 239445 &:= (((-5 \times (C(4!,4) \times 9)) - 3!)/(-2)) \\ 239814 &:= (((4-1)! \times (8! - (C(9 \times 3),2))) \\ 239826 &:= (-6) \times ((-2) - 8!) + (C(9 \times 3),2))) \\ 239904 &:= (((4! + 0!) + 9) \times (C(9,3^2))) \\ 240352 &:= ((C(25, (3! + 0!)) + 4)/2) \\ 240846 &:= (((6!/4) - 8!) - 0!) \times (-C(4,2)) \\ 240959 &:= (((((9+5)!/9!) - 0!) + (C(4,2))! \\ 241428 &:= ((8! - ((2 \times 41))) \times C(4,2)) \\ 241582 &:= (-2 + ((8!/5!) \times (-1 + (C(4,2))!))) \\ 241638 &:= (((8! + 3) \times 6) - C((1+4!),2)) \\ 241644 &:= (((4+4)! \times 6) - C(((1 \times 4)!,2)) \\ 241668 &:= ((8! \times 6) - (C(6,1) \times 42)) \\ 241698 &:= (((8! + 9) \times 6) - C(((1 \times 4)!)!,2)) \\ 241805 &:= -(((5! + 0!) - ((8! + 1) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241818 &:= ((8! - (18 - 1)) \times C(4,2)) \\ 241824 &:= (((4^2) + 8!) \times C((1 \times 4),2)) \\ 241858 &:= (-C(8,5) + ((8! - 1) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241862 &:= (-((2^6) + ((8! + 1) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241871 &:= (-1 - (((7 - 8!) + 1) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241872 &:= (((2+7) - 8!) - 1) \times (-C(4,2)) \\ 241877 &:= (-7) + (((7 - 8!) - 1) \times (-C(4,2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241883 &:= ((3! \times 8!) - (C((8-1),4) + 2)) \\ 241884 &:= (((4!/8)!) \times (8! - C((1 \times 4),2))) \\ 241886 &:= ((6 \times 8!) - ((C(8,1) \times 4) + 2)) \\ 241896 &:= (((-(6-9) - 8!) + 1) \times (-C(4,2))) \\ 241902 &:= (((2+0!) - ((9-1)!) \times (-C(4,2))) \\ 241907 &:= (-7) - ((0! - ((9-1)!) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241908 &:= (((8! - ((0 \times 9)!) - 1) \times C(4,2)) \\ 241913 &:= -(((3! + 1) - (((9-1)!) \times C(4,2)))) \\ 241914 &:= (((4-1)!) \times ((9-1)!) - C(4,2)) \\ 241924 &:= (((-C(4,2) - 9!)/(-1-4)) \times (-2)) \\ 241926 &:= (((6/2)!) \times ((9-1)!) + C(4,2)) \\ 241935 &:= ((5 \times 3) + (((9-1)!) \times C(4,2))) \\ 241938 &:= ((8! + 3) \times C(((9-1) - 4),2)) \\ 241968 &:= ((8! \times 6) + ((9-1) \times C(4,2))) \\ 242028 &:= ((8! + (20 - 2)) \times C(4,2)) \\ 242064 &:= ((4! + ((6+02)!) \times C(4,2)) \\ 242088 &:= ((8! + C(8,02)) \times C(4,2)) \\ 242145 &:= -(((5! \times 4!) - (C(12,4^2)))) \\ 242188 &:= (((-8) + (8! \times ((1+2)!) + C(4!,2)) \\ 242196 &:= ((6 \times ((9-1)!) + (C(24,2))) \\ 242382 &:= (2 \times ((8! \times 3) + C((-2+4!),2))) \\ 242448 &:= ((8! + (44 \times 2)) \times C(4,2)) \\ 242468 &:= (((8! \times 6) - 4) + (2 \times C(4!,2))) \\ 242472 &:= (2 \times ((7! \times 4!) + (C(24,2)))) \\ 242488 &:= (((-8) - (8! \times (-C(4,2)))) + (4!^2)) \\ 242496 &:= ((6! - (C(9,4^2))) \times (-4^2)) \\ 242598 &:= (((8! - 9) + 5!) + 2) \times C(4,2) \\ 242635 &:= (-5 + ((3! \times ((6+2)!) + (C(4,2))!)) \\ 242652 &:= (((-2-5!) - ((6+2)!) \times (-C(4,2))) \\ 242664 &:= (4! + ((6 \times ((6+2)!) + (C(4,2))!)) \\ 242668 &:= (((8! \times 6) + 6!) + C((2 \times 4),2)) \\ 242766 &:= (6! + (-6) \times (-C(7,2) - ((4 \times 2)!)!)) \\ 242784 &:= (((4! + 8!) + ((7-2)!) \times C(4,2)) \\ 242856 &:= (-6) \times ((5! - 8!) - (C(24,2))) \\ 242988 &:= ((8! + (89 \times 2)) \times C(4,2)) \\ 243186 &:= (6 \times ((8! + 1) + C((-3) + 4!),2))) \\ 243316 &:= -(((6! - ((-1) + C((3! + 3!),4^2)))) \\ 243453 &:= (-3 + ((5! \times C(4!,3)) + (4!^2))) \\ 243454 &:= ((4! \times ((5 \times C(4!,3)) + 4!)) - 2) \\ 243468 &:= ((8! + ((6 \times 43))) \times C(4,2)) \\ 243568 &:= (-8) - ((-6) \times (((5+3)!) + C(4!,2))) \\ 243576 &:= (-6) \times ((7! \times (-5+3)) - C(4!,2)) \end{aligned}$$

- 243786** := $(6 \times ((8! + C(7,3)) + C(4!,2)))$
243938 := $((8! \times 3!) + ((C(9,3) \times 4!) + 2))$
243978 := $((8! + ((7^{9/3}))) \times C(4,2))$
244305 := $-(((5+0!)! - ((C((3 \times 4),4^2))))$
244306 := $-(((6! - 0!) - ((C((3 \times 4),4^2))))$
244396 := $((69/3) \times C(4!,4) - 2)$
244398 := $((-8) + (9 \times 3!)) \times (C(4!,4)/2)$
244414 := $((4! - 1) \times C(4!,4) + ((4^2)))$
244444 := $((4! - C(4,4)) \times (C(4!,4) + 2))$
244806 := $((6 \times (0! + 8!)) - (-4) \times (C(4,2)!))$
244836 := $((6 \times (3! + 8!)) - (-4) \times (C(4,2)!))$
244905 := $(-5!) + (C(-((0! - (9 + 4))),4^2))$
245088 := $((8 \times ((-8) - 0!) + 5!) \times C(4!,2))$
245229 := $(9! - (2 + ((2 + 5)^{C(4,2)}))$
245538 := $((8! + 3) - (5! \times (-5))) \times C(4,2)$
245952 := $((-2 - 5!) \times (-C(9,5) \times (4^2)))$
246235 := $(-5 + (3! \times (((2 + 6)! + (C(4,2)!))))$
246258 := $((8! + (5 - 2)) + 6!) \times C(4,2)$
246264 := $((4 + 6!) + ((2 + 6)!)) \times C(4,2)$
246318 := $((8! + 13) + 6!) \times C(4,2)$
246348 := $((8! + 4!) - 3!) + 6!) \times C(4,2)$
246384 := $((4! + 8!) \times 3!) + (6! \times C(4,2))$
246947 := $((7! \times 49) - (C(6,4) - 2))$
247236 := $((6 \times ((3! + 2)!)) + (7! + C(4!,2)))$
247238 := $((8! \times 3!) + 2) + 7!) + C(4!,2)$
248064 := $((4^{6-0!}) + 8!) \times C(4,2)$
248344 := $(4! - ((4!^3) - (8^{C(4,2)})))$
248395 := $(-5) - ((-9) \times 3!) + (8! \times (-C(4,2)))$
248481 := $((1 + 8)^4) - (8! \times (-C(4,2)))$
248548 := $((8 + 4)^5) - 8) - C(4!,2)$
248616 := $((6 + 1)! - (-6) \times (8! + C(4!,2)))$
248617 := $((7! + 1) - (-6) \times (8! + C(4!,2)))$
248628 := $((8! - 2) \times 6) + (8!/C(4,2))$
248688 := $((-8) - 8!) \times (-6) + (8!/C(4,2))$
248973 := $(37 \times (9 + (8!/C(4,2))))$
249336 := $((63^3) + 9) - (C(4,2)!)$
249543 := $((3 \times 4)^5) - 9) + (C(4,2)!)$
249696 := $(6 \times ((C(9,6) + ((9 - 4)!^2)))$
251648 := $((-C(8,4)) \times ((6! - 1) \times (-5))) - 2)$
253123 := $((C(3!,2)^{1+3}) \times 5) - 2)$
253296 := $((6! - ((9 \times C((2^3),5)^2)))$
253994 := $-((4! + (((9! \times (-C(9,3)))/5!) - 2)))$
254302 := $-((((2 + 0!)!)! - (((3! \times C(4!,5)) - 2))))$
254303 := $-((3! + (0! - (3 \times (C(4!,5) \times 2))))$
254304 := $((C(4!,(0! + 3)) \times 4!) - ((5 - 2)!))$
254306 := $-((6! + (((0 - 3!) \times C(4!,5)) - 2)))$
254316 := $((6! \times (-1)) + (3! \times (C(4!,5) + 2)))$
254424 := $(4! \times (C(24,4) - (5^2)))$
254436 := $-((6! - (3! \times (4! + (C(4!,5) - 2))))$
254446 := $((-6) \times ((4! \times 4) - C(4!,5))) - 2)$
254546 := $((6 \times C(4!,5)) + ((-4) \times 5!) + 2)$
254576 := $((-6) \times (75 - C(4!,5))) + 2)$
254686 := $((-6) \times ((8!/6!) - C(4!,5))) - 2)$
254796 := $(-6) \times (C(9,7) - (C(4!,5) - 2))$
254836 := $-(((6! + (-3) \times 8!) - C(4!,((5 - 2)!)))$
254934 := $-((4! + (3! \times (9 - (C(4!,5) - 2))))$
254936 := $((-6) \times ((3! + 9) - C(4!,5))) + 2)$
254946 := $(-6) \times ((4! - 9) - (C(4!,5) + 2))$
254958 := $((8 - 5)! \times (-9) + (C(4!,5) - 2))$
254964 := $(-4 - ((-6 \times (-9 + C(4!,5))) + 2))$
254966 := $(-6) - ((-6) \times (-9 + C(4!,5))) - 2)$
254982 := $((2 - 8) \times (-9 + (C(4!,5) + 2)))$
255006 := $(-6) \times (0! - (C(-((0! - (5))))!,5) - 2))$
255012 := $((2 + 1)! \times (C(-((0! - (5))))!,5) - 2))$
255016 := $((-6) \times (1 - C(-((0! - (5))))!,5))) - 2)$
255026 := $((6 \times C((20/5)!),5)) + 2)$
255033 := $(3 \times (3 - (C(-((0! - (5))))!,5) \times (-2)))$
255034 := $((4!)! / ((3 + 0!) \times 5!) + C(5,2))$
255036 := $(6 \times (C((3 + ((0 \times 5)!),5) + 2))$
255046 := $((-6) \times (-4) - C(-((0! - (5))))!,5))) - 2)$
255054 := $((C(4!,5) - (0 - 5)) \times ((5 - 2)!))$
255056 := $((6 \times (C(((5 - 0!)!,5) + (5))) + 2))$
255146 := $((6 \times C(4!,(1 \times 5))) + (5! + 2))$
255788 := $((C(8,8) - 7!) + 5!) \times (-52)$
256326 := $((6! - 2) \times ((3! - (C(6,5)!)/(-2)))$
256498 := $(-89) \times ((-4) \times (C(6,5)! - 2))$
256675 := $(-5) - (((7 - 6!) \times (C(6,5)!)/2))$
257094 := $((4^9) - (07!) - C(5,2))$
257398 := $((8 \times (C((9 + 3!),7) \times 5)) - 2)$
259195 := $(-5) - (-((C(9,1) + 9)) \times (5!^2))$
259228 := $(C(8,2) + ((2 \times 9) \times (5!^2)))$
259262 := $((2 - ((6!^2) + (C(9,5))))/(-2))$
259266 := $((-6) - ((6!^2) + (C(9,5))))/(-2))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 259375 &:= (-5) \times (-C(7,3) + (9!/(-5+2))) \\
 259623 &:= (((3!!^2) + (6! + (C(9,5))))/2) \\
 259774 &:= -((C(4!,7) - (((7! + 9) \times 5!) - 2)) \\
 259776 &:= ((6! + 7!) + ((-7) \times 9!/(-C(5,2)))) \\
 261424 &:= -(((C(4,2))! - (4^{1+6+2})) \\
 261494 &:= (((C(4!,9) - 4!)/(-1-6)) - 2) \\
 261868 &:= ((8^6) - C((8+16),2)) \\
 262078 &:= ((8^{7-0!}) - C((2 \times 6),2)) \\
 262088 &:= (8 \times ((-8) + 0!) + (2^{C(6,2)})) \\
 262435 &:= (-5 + (((3^{C(4,2)}) \times 6!)/2)) \\
 262504 &:= ((4^{-0!+C(5,2)}) - (6!/(-2))) \\
 262546 &:= ((C((-6) + 4!), C(5,2)) \times 6) - 2) \\
 262838 &:= (((8^3!) - (C(8,2))) + 6!) + 2) \\
 262894 &:= (((4^9) + C(8,2)) + 6!) + 2) \\
 263594 &:= (((4^9) + C(5,3)) + (6! \times 2)) \\
 263678 &:= ((8! \times 7) - (C((6 \times 3),6) - 2)) \\
 263886 &:= ((6! + C(8,8)) \times (3! - (6!/(-2)))) \\
 264147 &:= -(((7! + (4+1)) + (C(4!,6) \times (-2)))) \\
 264152 &:= (((2+5)! \times (-1)) - (C(4!,6) \times (-2))) \\
 264157 &:= (((7! - 5) \times (-1)) - (C(4!,6) \times (-2))) \\
 264168 &:= ((8^6) + C(((1 \times 4))!, (6/2))) \\
 264174 &:= ((4! - 7!) + ((1 - C(4!,6)) \times (-2))) \\
 264384 &:= (((4+8)^3) \times C((4! - 6),2)) \\
 264606 &:= (6 \times (0! + ((C((6+4),6)^2))) \\
 264636 &:= (6 \times (3! + ((C((6+4),6)^2))) \\
 264735 &:= (53 \times (7! - C((4+6),2))) \\
 265248 &:= (8 \times ((C(4!,2) \times 5!) + ((6^2))) \\
 266256 &:= ((6! - (C(C(5,2),6) - 6))^2) \\
 266312 &:= (2 \times (C(((1+3))!,6) - (6! \times 2))) \\
 266475 &:= (-5) \times ((-74) \times 6!) - (C(6,2))) \\
 267135 &:= ((53 \times ((1 \times 7))!) + (C(6,2))) \\
 267168 &:= (((8^6) - 1) + 7!) - (C(6,2)) \\
 267184 &:= ((4^{8+1}) + (C(7, ((6/2))!))! \\
 267464 &:= (((C(4!,6) - 4!) + (7!/(-6))) \times 2) \\
 267764 &:= ((C(4!,6) - ((7!/7) - 6)) \times 2) \\
 267825 &:= -(((5!^2) - ((8! \times 7) - (C(6,2)))) \\
 267855 &:= -(((5! \times 5!) - ((8! \times 7) + (C(6,2)))) \\
 268264 &:= (((C(4!,6) + (2^8)) - 6!) \times 2) \\
 268463 &:= (-((3^6) - (C((-((4-8)))!,6) \times (-2))) \\
 268466 &:= ((-6) - 6!) - (C((-((4-8)))!,6) \times (-2)) \\
 268964 &:= -(((C(4!,6) - 9!) - 8!) + (6!/(-2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 269024 &:= ((C(4!, ((2+0!))!) - (C(9,6))) \times 2) \\
 269144 &:= ((4! - C(4!, ((1^9) \times 6))) \times (-2)) \\
 269164 &:= ((C(4!,6) + (((1-9) - 6))) \times 2) \\
 269204 &:= ((C(4!, (02 \times 9)) + 6) \times 2) \\
 269234 &:= ((C(4!,3!) \times 2) + (C(9,6)/2)) \\
 269264 &:= ((C(4!,6) \times 2) + (9 \times (6+2))) \\
 269364 &:= ((-C(4!,6) - ((3!/9) + 6)) \times (-2)) \\
 269384 &:= ((C((-((4-8)))!,3!) + (96)) \times 2) \\
 269432 &:= (((2+3))! + C(4!, ((9-6))!)) \times 2) \\
 269642 &:= (2 \times (C(4!,6) + ((9+6)^2))) \\
 270632 &:= ((C((-2+3!))!,6) + (-((0! - 7)))! \times 2) \\
 270634 &:= (((C(4!,3!) + 6!) + ((0 \times 7))!) \times 2) \\
 270646 &:= ((6! + (C(4!,6) - (0-7))) \times 2) \\
 270648 &:= (((8 + C(4!,6)) + (-((0! - 7))))! \times 2) \\
 272496 &:= (-6) \times ((9 \times (-C(4,2) - 7!)) - 2) \\
 274234 &:= (((C(4!,3!) \times (-2-4)) + 7!) + 2) \\
 274288 &:= ((8^{8-2}) - ((4!)!/(-C(7,2))!)) \\
 274464 &:= (4! \times (-6 - (C((4 \times 4),7) + 2))) \\
 274806 &:= (((6! - 0!) + 8) \times C((4 \times 7),2)) \\
 275384 &:= -((4! - (-C(8,3) \times ((5! - 7!) + 2))) \\
 275518 &:= ((-C(C(8,1),5)) \times (5! - 7!)) - 2) \\
 275724 &:= (C(4!,2) \times ((7!/5) - (7+2))) \\
 275745 &:= ((C(5,4))! + (((75 \times 7)^2))) \\
 276459 &:= (9! + (((-5) \times 4!) \times 6!) - (C(7,2))) \\
 276648 &:= (8 \times ((4! \times (6! + 6!)) + C(7,2))) \\
 277178 &:= (((8! \times 7) - 1) - 7!) - (C(7,2)) \\
 277179 &:= (9! + ((7! \times (-17)) - (C(7,2)))) \\
 277338 &:= (((8! + C(3!,3)) \times 7) - (7! + 2)) \\
 277837 &:= (-7) \times (3!! - ((8! + (C((7+7),2)))))) \\
 278736 &:= ((6! + (3!^7)) + (8!/(-C(7,2)))) \\
 279254 &:= (((C(4!, ((5-2))!) - 9) + 7!) \times 2) \\
 279747 &:= (((7-4))!^7) - ((9 \times C(7,2))) \\
 279927 &:= (-7) + (((2 + C(9,9))!^7) - 2) \\
 279929 &:= (-9) + (((2 + C(9,9))!^7) + 2) \\
 281738 &:= ((C(8,3) \times (7! - (1+8))) + 2) \\
 281792 &:= (2 \times (((9-7!) - 1) \times (-C(8,2)))) \\
 282158 &:= ((8! \times (C(5,1) + 2)) - (82)) \\
 282228 &:= (((8! - 2) \times (-C(2,2) - 8)) + 2) \\
 282231 &:= (((1+3!) \times (-C(2,2) + 8!)) - 2) \\
 282239 &:= ((9! - 3) - ((C(2,2) - 8!) \times (-2))) \\
 282242 &:= (((2 \times 4))! \times (-C(2,2) - 8)) + 2) \\
 282247 &:= (-7) \times ((-((C(4,2)/2)) - 8!) + 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 282254 &:= ((4 + C(5, 2)) \times ((2 + 8!)/2)) \\ 282261 &:= ((1 + 6) \times ((C(2, 2) + 8!) + 2)) \\ 282268 &:= ((8! \times (6 + C(2, 2))) + (C(8, 2))) \\ 282287 &:= ((7 \times 8!) + (2 + C((2 + 8), 2))) \\ 282331 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((C(3!, 2) + 8!) - 2)) \\ 282343 &:= (((3 + 4) \times (C(3!, 2) + 8!)) - 2) \\ 282368 &:= (((8^6) - (C(3, 2) \times 8!)) \times 2) \\ 282487 &:= ((-7) \times (-((C(8, 4)/2) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282557 &:= ((-7) \times (-C((5 + 5), 2) - 8!)) + 2) \\ 282618 &:= ((8! \times (1 + 6)) + (C(28, 2))) \\ 282624 &:= (C(4!, 2) \times (((6 - 2) \times 8)^2)) \\ 282956 &:= (((C(6, 5))! + 9!) + ((2 + 8!) \times (-2))) \\ 283024 &:= (C(4!, 2) + (-0! + 3)^8)^2 \\ 283505 &:= (5 \times (0! - ((C(5, 3))! / (-8^2)))) \\ 284755 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (-((7^4) - C(8, 2)))))) \\ 284759 &:= (((9! - (5^7)) - 4!) + (C(8, 2))) \\ 285115 &:= (-5 - ((11)! / (-5 \times C(8, 2)))) \\ 285747 &:= (((-7) + 4!) \times (7^5)) + (C(8, 2)) \\ 286554 &:= (((C(4!, (5 + 5))/6) - 8!) - 2) \\ 287238 &:= (((8! + 3!) - 2) \times 7) - C(8, 2) \\ 287267 &:= ((7! - (C(6, 2))) + ((7 \times 8!) + 2)) \\ 287275 &:= ((-5) + 7!) - ((-2) \times 7!) \times C(8, 2)) \\ 287278 &:= (((8! \times 7) - 2) + (C(7, (8 - 2)))) \\ 287308 &:= ((8! \times (0! + 3!)) + (7! + (C(8, 2)))) \\ 287337 &:= ((7! + C(3, 3)) \times (-7 - (8^2))) \\ 288764 &:= -((C(4!, 6) - (7 \times (8! + (8!/2)))))) \\ 291456 &:= ((6!/5) \times C(4!, ((1^9) + 2))) \\ 292313 &:= (-((3! + 1)) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292314 &:= (-(((4 - 1)!)) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292315 &:= (-5 - ((-1 \times 3!) \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292332 &:= ((2 \times 3!) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292335 &:= ((5 \times 3) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292342 &:= ((-2 + 4!) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292352 &:= ((2^5) + (3! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 292368 &:= ((8 \times 6) + ((3!)! \times C(29, 2))) \\ 293385 &:= ((5^8) + (C((3 \times 3!), 9) \times (-2))) \\ 293931 &:= (-1 + (C(((3! + 9) + 3!), 9) + 2)) \\ 293934 &:= (C((4! - 3), 9) - ((3 - 9) + 2)) \\ 293943 &:= ((C((-3 + 4!), 9) + 3!) + (9 - 2)) \\ 293957 &:= (C(C(7, 5), 9) + ((3! \times 9)/2)) \\ 295568 &:= ((8 + 6!) \times C((5 + (-((5 - 9)))!), 2)) \\ 296028 &:= (C((C(8, 2) - 0!), 6) + ((9 \times 2))) \\ 296639 &:= ((9! - C(3!, 6)) - (6! \times 92)) \\ 296688 &:= ((8 \times (8! + (6))) + (6! \times (-C(9, 2)))) \\ 296723 &:= (3!! + ((C(27, 6) - 9) + 2)) \\ 297388 &:= (8! + (((8^3) - 7!) - C(9, 2))) \\ 297543 &:= (-3 + ((C(4!, 5) \times 7) + ((9 \times 2)))) \\ 297545 &:= (((5 + C(4!, 5)) \times 7) - ((9 \times 2))) \\ 297548 &:= (((8 + C(4!, 5)) \times 7) - C(9, 2)) \\ 297727 &:= ((C(C(7, 2), 7) + 7) - (9! / (-2))) \\ 297865 &:= ((5^6) + ((C(8, 7))! \times (9 - 2))) \\ 302376 &:= ((-6) + (7! \times C(3!, 2))) \times (0! + 3) \\ 302428 &:= (C(8, 2) + (420 \times 3!)) \\ 302488 &:= ((8! + ((8^{C(4, 2)}))) + ((0! + 3)!)) \\ 302841 &:= (C((-1 + 4!), (8 - 2)) \times 03) \\ 303264 &:= ((4! + (C(6, 2))) \times (3!^{-0!+3!})) \\ 304644 &:= ((4!^4) - C(((6 + 4!) + 0!), 3!)) \\ 305748 &:= -(((8! - C(4!, 7)) + ((5 + 0!) \times 3!)) \\ 305784 &:= (C((-((4 - 8)))!, 7) - (((5 + 03)!)) \\ 307328 &:= (-((C(8, 2)^3)) \times ((-7) - 0!) - 3!) \\ 307648 &:= ((8 \times (C(4!, 6) / (-7))) \times (0! - 3)) \\ 309337 &:= (-(((C((7 \times 3), 3!) - 9!) - 0!)) + 3!) \\ 312936 &:= (((6! \times 3!) + 9!) - C(21, 3!)) \\ 314752 &:= (((2 + 5!) - 7!) \times (-C(4, 1^3))) \\ 316239 &:= ((9! + C(3!, 2)) - (6^{(1 \times 3)!})) \\ 316808 &:= (8 \times ((0! + 8!) - (C(6, (1^3))))!) \\ 317457 &:= (C(7, C(5, 4)) \times ((7! - 1) \times 3)) \\ 317517 &:= (((-C(C(7, 1), 5)) \times 7!) + 1) \times (-3)) \\ 319344 &:= (-(((4! \times C(4!, 3)) - 9!)) + ((1 + 3)!)) \\ 319654 &:= -((((C(4!, 5) + 6!) - 9!) - ((1 - 3)))) \\ 319824 &:= (C((4! - 2), 8) + (9 \times ((1 \times 3)!)) \\ 319842 &:= (C((-2 + 4!), 8) + (9! / ((1 + 3)!))!) \\ 319843 &:= -(((C(-((3! - 4!)), 8) - (9! + 1)) - 3!)) \\ 320488 &:= (8 \times (8! - (C((4! - 0!), 2) + 3!)) \\ 320768 &:= ((-C(8, 6) + 7!) \times (02^3!)) \\ 321648 &:= (((8! - 4!) \times (C(6, 1) + 2)) - (3!)!) \\ 321888 &:= (8 \times (8! - C(((8 - 1) + 2), 3))) \\ 322287 &:= (((7!/8)^2) - C(22, 3!)) \\ 322558 &:= (((8 + C(5, 5))! - 2) - ((2^3)!)) \\ 322559 &:= ((9! - C(5, 5)) - ((2 + (2 \times 3)))!) \\ 322579 &:= ((9! + (C(7, 5) - 2)) - ((2^3)!)) \\ 322582 &:= (((2 + 8!) \times (C(5, 2) - 2)) + 3!) \\ 322584 &:= ((4! - 8!) + ((C((5 - 2), 2) \times 3)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 322588 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + C((C(5,2) - 2), 3!)) \\ 322594 &:= (((4! + 9!) + C(5,2)) - ((2^3)!) \\ 322679 &:= (-9) + (((C(7,6))! + 2) \times (2^{3!})) \\ 322695 &:= (((5! + 9!) + C(6,2)) - ((2^3)!) \\ 323064 &:= (C(4!, (6 + 0!)) + (-32) \times 3!)) \\ 323184 &:= (4! \times ((8! + (C(13,2))))/3) \\ 323788 &:= ((8 \times 8!) + (((C(7,3)^2) + 3))) \\ 324396 &:= (((6! + 9) \times (3!! - C(4!, 2))) + 3!!) \\ 324744 &:= (((4 + 4)! \times 7) + C(4!, (2 + 3))) \\ 324786 &:= (((6 + 8!) \times 7) + C(4!, (2 + 3))) \\ 324808 &:= (-8) \times ((0! - 8!) - (C(4!, 2) + 3!)) \\ 324848 &:= (8 \times ((4 + 8!) + (C(4!, 2) + 3!)) \\ 324885 &:= (5! + ((8 \times (8! + C(4!, 2))) - 3)) \\ 325374 &:= (C(4!, 7) - (((3!!/5)^2) - (3!)) \\ 325436 &:= ((-6!) - 3!!) + ((C(4!, C(5,2))/3!)) \\ 325445 &:= (C(5, 4) - (-452) \times 3!)) \\ 325468 &:= (C(8, 6) - (-452) \times (3!)) \\ 325572 &:= ((-2 + C(C(7,5), ((5 - 2)!)) \times 3!) \\ 325577 &:= (-7) + (C(C(7,5), ((5 - 2)!)) \times 3!) \\ 325578 &:= ((8 \times (C(C(7,5), 5) \times 2)) - 3!) \\ 325584 &:= (C((4! - (8 - 5)), ((5 - 2)!)) \times 3!) \\ 325734 &:= ((-4 \times ((3!! - C(7,5))^2))/(-3!)) \\ 326235 &:= (((-5 + 3!!) + 2) \times C(C(6,2), 3)) \\ 326637 &:= ((7 \times (3!^6)) + (C(6,2) \times 3)) \\ 326744 &:= (((4!^4) - (C(7,6))!) + (2^3)) \\ 326864 &:= ((C(4!, (6 + 8))/6) - (2 \times 3!)) \\ 326894 &:= (((C(4!, 9)/(-8)) - 6) \times (-2)) + 3! \\ 327275 &:= ((-5) + 7!) \times (2 + (C(7,2) \times 3)) \\ 327405 &:= (((5^{(-0!+4)!}) \times C(7,2)) - (3!)) \\ 327579 &:= (((9! - (C(7,5))) + 7!) - ((2^3)!) \\ 327596 &:= (6! + (C(((9 - 5)!), (7 \times 2))/3!)) \\ 327735 &:= (5 \times (3!! + ((7 \times (C(7,2)^3)))) \\ 328088 &:= (8 \times (((8! - 0!) - (C(8,2))) + (3!)) \\ 328376 &:= ((6! + (C(7,3!) + 8!)) \times (2^3)) \\ 329088 &:= (8 \times (8! - (0 - C((9 \times 2), 3)))) \\ 329193 &:= ((3!! - 9) \times (1 + C((9 + 2), 3!)) \\ 329231 &:= (-1 + (3! \times ((2 + C(9,2))^3)) \\ 329544 &:= (((C(4!, 4) + 5!) \times 92)/3) \\ 330984 &:= (C(4!, (8 + 9)) + (((0! + 3!))! \times (-3))) \\ 331584 &:= (4! \times (-8 + ((C((5 - 1), 3))!^3))) \\ 331744 &:= ((4!^4) - (C(C(7,1), 3) - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 331824 &:= (4! \times (2 + ((C(8,1) \times 3)^3))) \\ 331944 &:= ((4!^4) + (C((9 - 1), 3) \times 3)) \\ 331964 &:= -((C(4!, 6) - ((9 + 1) \times (3!^{3!}))) \\ 332274 &:= (C(4!, 7) - (((2 + 2)!^3) + 3!)) \\ 332468 &:= ((-C(8, 6) + (4!^{-2+3!})) + (3!)) \\ 332635 &:= (-5 + (3!! \times C(((6 + 2) + 3), 3!)) \\ 332639 &:= (((((9 + 3))! / 6!) / 2) - C(3, 3)) \\ 332655 &:= ((-5 - (5! \times C((6 \times 2), 3!))) \times (-3)) \\ 332667 &:= ((7! \times C((6 + 6), 2)) + ((3^3))) \\ 332772 &:= ((2 + 7!) \times ((C(7, 2) \times 3) + 3)) \\ 332928 &:= -((8! - ((2 \times C(9, 2))^{-3+3!})) \\ 333089 &:= (9! - ((C(8, (03!)) + 3^3)) \\ 333234 &:= (C((4! - 3!), 2) \times ((-3!) - 3!!) \times (-3)) \\ 333453 &:= -((((3! - 5!) \times C((4! + 3), 3)) - 3) \\ 333456 &:= (((-6) + 5!) \times C((4! + 3), 3) + 3! \\ 334134 &:= ((4! - 3!) \times (-1 + C((4! - 3!), 3!)) \\ 334667 &:= ((7! \times 66) + (C(4!, 3) + 3)) \\ 334698 &:= -((((8! - 9!) + (6)) - (C(4!, 3) \times 3!)) \\ 334784 &:= -((((4! \times 8!) + 7!) - C(4!, (3 \times 3))) \\ 335185 &:= ((5^8) + (-(((1 + C(5, 3))!)/3!)) \\ 335304 &:= (C(4!, (0! + 3!)) - ((5 \times 3) \times 3!)) \\ 335556 &:= ((6! - (C((5 + 5), 5))) \times (3!! - 3)) \\ 335838 &:= (((C(8, 3!) + 8!) + (5^{3!})) \times 3! \\ 335838 &:= (((C(8, 3!) + 8!) + (5^{3!})) \times 3! \\ 335985 &:= ((((-5) \times 8!) + 9) \times (-C(5, 3)))/3! \\ 336137 &:= (((7^{3! - 1}) \times C(6, 3)) - 3) \\ 336328 &:= ((8! - 2) + C(((3 + 6) \times 3), 3!)) \\ 336348 &:= ((8! + C((4! + 3), 6)) + (3 \times 3!)) \\ 336487 &:= (((7 + 8) \times C(4!, 6))/3!) - 3) \\ 336493 &:= (((3! + 9) \times C(4!, 6))/3!) + 3) \\ 336496 &:= (((6 + 9) \times C(4!, 6))/3!) + 3! \\ 336747 &:= -(((7! - C(4!, 7)) + ((6! \times 3!) - 3))) \\ 336966 &:= (((6! \times (-6 - C(9, 6))) \times 3!) + 3! \\ 337464 &:= (((4 \times 6!) + (C(4!, 7)/(-3))) \times (-3)) \\ 337559 &:= ((9! - 5!) - ((5 \times 7!) + C(3, 3))) \\ 337575 &:= ((-5) \times (C(7, 5) + 7!)) + ((3 \times 3!)) \\ 337673 &:= -((3! - ((7! \times 67) - C(3, 3))) \\ 337679 &:= ((-((9 - 76) \times 7!) - C(3, 3)) \\ 337681 &:= (((-((1 - 8))! \times 67) + C(3, 3)) \\ 337683 &:= (((C((3 + 8), 6) + 7) \times 3!!) + 3) \\ 337747 &:= ((74 - 7) \times (7! + C(3, 3))) \\ 338184 &:= (C(4!, (8 - 1)) + (-((8 + 3) \times 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 338395 &:= ((-5) + 9!) + (3!! \times (-C(8,3!) + 3!)) \\
 338694 &:= (((4! \times 9!)/6!) \times C(8,3!) + 3!) \\
 339264 &:= ((4! + 6!) \times (C((2+9),3!) - 3!)) \\
 339279 &:= ((9! - 7!) - (C((2 \times 9),3!) - 3)) \\
 339768 &:= (-C((8+6),7)) \times (-93 - 3!) \\
 340038 &:= ((8 \times C((3+0)!), (0! + (4)))) + (3!) \\
 340928 &:= (C(8,2) \times (9 + (-((0! - 4!))^3))) \\
 340944 &:= -(((4! + (C(4!,9)/(0! - 4!))) \times 3!)) \\
 340974 &:= ((C(4!,7) - (90)) - ((4+3)!)) \\
 341064 &:= (C(4!, (6+0!)) - ((4+3)!)) \\
 341784 &:= (C((-((4-8))!),7) - ((-((1-4))!) \times 3!)) \\
 342249 &:= (((9 + (4!^2))^2) + (C(4,3)!)) \\
 342424 &:= -(((4!^2) - (C((4 \times 2),4)^3))) \\
 342666 &:= ((6^6) + C(((6/2) + 4!),3!)) \\
 342724 &:= ((C((4! + 2),7)/2) + (4!^3)) \\
 342728 &:= (((8! \times (-2)) - 7!) - 2) \times (-C(4,3)) \\
 343024 &:= (4! + (C((2^0 3),4)^3)) \\
 343224 &:= (C(4!, ((2+2) + 3)) + (-4 \times 3!)) \\
 343245 &:= ((-((5^{C(4,2)})) - 3!)) \times (-4! - 3)) \\
 343299 &:= (9! + ((-C((9 \times 2),3)) \times 4!) + 3) \\
 343308 &:= (((8+0!))! / (-3!)) + (3 \times C(4!,3!)) \\
 343374 &:= (C(4!,7) - (3! \times C(C(3!,4),3))) \\
 343389 &:= (9! - ((C(8,3!) \times ((3!)! - 4!)) + 3)) \\
 343564 &:= ((4 \times ((6! \times 5!) - 3)) - C(4!,3)) \\
 343649 &:= (9! + ((C(4!,6)/(-3+4)) - 3)) \\
 343728 &:= (C(((8/2) + 7),3!) \times (4! + 3!)) \\
 343896 &:= (-69) \times (C(8,3) - ((4+3)!)) \\
 344074 &:= ((C(4!,7) - (-((0! - 4)!))!) - (C(4!,3))) \\
 344084 &:= ((C(4!, (8-0!)) + 4) - C(4!,3)) \\
 344342 &:= (-2 - (-43) \times C((4 \times 4),3!)) \\
 344344 &:= (C((4 \times 4), (3! + 4)) \times 43) \\
 344395 &:= (-5) - (-C(9,3)) \times (4 + (4^3!)) \\
 344424 &:= -((((4 \times 2)!/4!) - C(4!, (4+3))) \\
 344448 &:= -((((8!/4!) - 4!) - C(4!, (4+3))) \\
 344599 &:= ((9! - (C((9+5),4))) - (4! \times (3)!)) \\
 344662 &:= (((-2 - 6!) - 6!) + C(4!, (4+3))) \\
 344664 &:= (((4-6) \times 6!) + C(4!, (4+3))) \\
 344725 &:= (-((5^2)) \times (C(7,4) - (4!^3))) \\
 344774 &:= (C(4!,7) - C(((7+4!) + 4),3)) \\
 345324 &:= (-C(4!,2) + (3!! \times (5! \times C(4,3)))) \\
 345345 &:= ((-C(5,4) + 3!!) \times ((5! \times 4) + 3)) \\
 345374 &:= (C(4!,7) - (((3! \times 5!) + 4) + 3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 345384 &:= (C(4!, -((8 - (3 \times C(5,4)))))) - 3!!) \\
 345456 &:= (((6! \times 5!) \times 4) - 5!) - (C(4,3)!)) \\
 345465 &:= (((5 \times 6!) - C((4! + 5),4!)) \times (-3)) \\
 345498 &:= (89 \times (C((4! - 5),4) + 3!)) \\
 345504 &:= (4! \times (((05)! \times 5!) - C(4,3))) \\
 345528 &:= (((8/2)! \times ((5! \times (C(5,4)!)) - 3)) \\
 345538 &:= (-C(8,3) + (((5! \times 5!) \times 4!) - 3!)) \\
 345544 &:= (-C((4+4),5) - ((5! \times (-4)) \times 3!)) \\
 345564 &:= (4 \times ((6! \times 5!) - (5 + C(4,3)))) \\
 345579 &:= ((9! - (C(7,5))) - ((5! \times 4!) \times 3!)) \\
 345585 &:= (((5! \times (-8)) \times 5!) + C(5,4)) \times (-3)) \\
 345592 &:= (-((2^9) + C((5!/5), (4+3))) \\
 345596 &:= (((6! \times (9-5)) \times 5!) - C(4,3)) \\
 345599 &:= (((9!/C(9,5)) \times 5!) - (4-3)) \\
 345625 &:= ((5^2) + ((6! \times 5!) \times C(4,3))) \\
 345627 &:= (C(7,2) + (((6! \times 5!) \times 4) + 3!)) \\
 345632 &:= ((-((2^3)) - (6! \times 5!)) \times (-C(4,3))) \\
 345636 &:= ((6 \times 3!) + ((6! \times 5!) \times C(4,3))) \\
 345732 &:= (C(((2+3)!),7) - ((5! + 4) \times 3)) \\
 345742 &:= ((-2 + C(4!,7)) + ((-5 \times 4!) \times 3)) \\
 345744 &:= (C(4!, (4! - 7)) + ((-5 \times 4!) \times 3)) \\
 345748 &:= ((-8) + C(4!,7) - ((5! - 4) \times 3)) \\
 345768 &:= -((8! + ((6! - 7^5)) \times (C(4,3)!)) \\
 345774 &:= ((C(4!,7) - ((7! \times 5)/4!)) + 3!)) \\
 345784 &:= (C((-((4-8))!),7) - (5 \times (4^3))) \\
 345789 &:= ((9 \times (8! + (C(7,5)))) - (4! \times (3)!)) \\
 345874 &:= ((C(4!,7) - ((C(8,5) \times 4))) - 3!) \\
 345924 &:= (C(4!, -((2-9))) - ((5!/4) \times 3!)) \\
 345957 &:= (((-((7^5)) + 9!) - 5!) + C(4,3)) \\
 345974 &:= (C(4!,7) - (C(9,5) + C(4,3))) \\
 345984 &:= (C(4!, (8+9)) - (C(5, (4-3)))!) \\
 346032 &:= (C(((2+3)!), (0! + 6)) + (4! \times (-3))) \\
 346034 &:= (C(4!, (3! + 0!)) - (6 + (4^3))) \\
 346043 &:= 3 + C(4!, 0! + 6) - 4^3 \\
 346056 &:= ((-6) + (5! \times (0! + 6!))) \times C(4,3)) \\
 346074 &:= (C(4!,7) - ((06+4) \times 3)) \\
 346083 &:= (C((3 \times 8), (0! + 6)) - (4! - 3)) \\
 346094 &:= (C(4!, (((9 \times 0)! + 6)) - (4 + 3!)) \\
 346097 &:= (-7) + C(((9+0!) - (6)))!, (4+3)) \\
 346102 &:= (-2 + C((-((0! + (1-6))))!), (4+3)) \\
 346103 &:= (C(((3+0)!), (1+6)) - (4-3)) \\
 346105 &:= (C(((5-0)!), (1+6)) + (4-3))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 346114** := ((C(4!, (C(1, 1) + 6)) + 4) + 3!)
346122 := ((C(((2 + 2))!), (1 + 6)) + 4!) - 3!)
346128 := (C(((8/2))!), (1 + 6)) + (C(4, 3))!
346131 := ((C(((1 + 3))!), (1 + 6)) + 4!) + 3)
346134 := ((C((C(4, 3))!), (1 + 6)) + 4!) + 3!)
346144 := -((4! - (C(4!, (1 + 6)) + (4³))))
346164 := (C(4!, (6 + 1)) + (6! / (4 × 3)))
346174 := (C(4!, 7) + ((1 × 6) + (4³)))
346254 := (C(4!, (5 + 2)) - ((-6 × 4!) - 3!))
346274 := ((C(4!, 7) + (26)) + (4! × 3!))
346276 := ((6! × ((7²) × 6)) + C(4!, 3!))
346314 := (C(4!, (1 + 3!)) + C((6 + 4), 3!))
346374 := (C(4!, 7) + (3! × (C(6, 4) × 3)))
346539 := ((9! - (3!))! - ((5⁶) - C(4, 3)))
346544 := ((4 - (-4 × 5!)) × (6! - C(4, 3)))
346674 := (((C(4!, 7) - 6!) + (6⁴)) - 3!)
346746 := ((6! + (C(4!, 7) - (6))) + (4! × (-3)))
346774 := (((C(4!, 7) - 7) + 6!) - 43)
346814 := (((C(4!, -((1 - 8))) + 6!) - 4) - 3!)
346824 := (C(4!, ((2 × (8 + 6)) / 4)) + 3!))
347034 := ((C(4!, (3! + 0!)) + (7! / 4!)) + 3!))
347238 := ((8! + ((3 + C(27, 4)))) × 3!)
347424 := (((4!²) + (C(4!, 7) + 4!)) + 3!))
347445 := (((5⁴) + (C(4!, 7) - 4)) + 3!))
347481 := ((-((1 - C(8, 4))) × (7! - 4)) - 3)
347745 := (((C(5, 4) + 7!) - (7! × 4!)) × (-3))
347748 := (((C(8, 4) × 7!) - 7!) - (4 × 3))
347754 := (((C(4!, -((5 - 7))) × 7!) / 4) - 3!)
347775 := ((-5) + (7! × (C(7, 7) - 4!))) × (-3))
347935 := -((((5^{3!}) - 9!) - C((-7 + 4!), 3))
348035 := ((-5 + ((3! + 0!))!) + (C(8, 4)³))
348037 := (7! - ((3 - (C(08, 4)³))))
348064 := ((4! + ((6 + 0!))!) + (C(8, 4)³))
348128 := (C(((8/2))!), -((1 - 8))) + C(4!, 3))
348156 := ((6 - 5!) × (-C(18, 4) + 3!))
348239 := (9! - (((C(3, 2) + 8)^{C(4, 3)})))
348288 := -((8! - (((8/2))! × 8) × C(4!, 3)))
348344 := (C(4!, (4 + 3)) + (8! / (4! - 3!)))
348359 := ((9! + 5!) - ((3 + 8)^{C(4, 3)}))
348392 := (-2 × (((9 - 3))! - 8!) - C(4!, 3!))
348624 := (((-((C(4, 2)⁶)) - 8!) × (-4)) + 3!))
348752 := (2 × ((-5 × (7! - 8!)) - C(4!, 3)))
348784 := (4! - ((8! / (-7)) - ((C(8, 4)³))))
348877 := (((7! - ((7 × 8))) × C(8, 4)) - 3)
348935 := -((((5^{3!}) - 9!) - (8! / (C(4, 3))!))
348984 := (C(4!, (8 + 9)) + ((8 - 4) × 3!))
349028 := ((-C(8, 2)) + (09!)) - (4!³)
349036 := ((-C(6, 3)) + (09!)) - (4!³)
349055 := ((-C(5, 5)) + (09!)) - (4!³)
349139 := (((C(9, 3) - 1) + 9!) - (4!³))
349244 := -((C(4!, C(4, 2)) + ((9! × 4) / (-3)))
349374 := (-((C(4!, (7 - 3)) - 9!)) + (-4 × 3!))
349398 := ((8! + ((9! × (-3)) + (C(9, 4)))) / (-3))
349704 := (C(4!, 07) - (-((9 - 4) × 3!))
349784 := (((4! / (-8)) × 7!) + 9!) + C(4!, 3))
349812 := (2 × (((-1 + 8!) - 9) + C(4!, 3!))
349842 := (2 × (((-4 + 8!) + 9) + C(4!, 3!))
349862 := (2 × (((6 + 8!) + 9) + C(4!, 3!))
349993 := -((3! - (9! - ((-C(9, 9)) + 4!)³)))
351147 := (7! + (C(4!, ((1 + 1) + 5)) + 3))
351351 := (C(15, (3! - 1)) × (5! - 3))
351649 := (((-C(9, 4)) + 6!) - 1)⁵⁻³
352254 := (((4 + 5))! - C(((2 + 2))!, (5! / 3!))
352259 := ((9! + (5)) - C(((2 + 2))!, (5! / 3!))
352734 := ((4! - 3!) + C(C(7, 2), C(5, 3)))
352775 := (-5) - (((7! × (-7)) + 2) × C(5, 3))
352779 := ((9 × 7) + C(C(7, 2), C(5, 3)))
353304 := (C(4!, (0! + 3!)) - (3! × (-C(5, 3))))
353367 := (((7⁶) - (C(3!, 3) + 5!)) × (-3))
353433 := (3! - (3 - C((4! - 3), C(5, 3))))
353436 := (6! + C(((3 + 4) × 3), C(5, 3)))
353457 := (((7! + (5)) - C(4!, 3)) × (5! - 3))
353567 := (-7) - (6 × (5! - (3^{C(5, 3)})))
353574 := ((-4 + 7)^{C(5, 3)} - 5!) × 3!
353579 := ((9! - (C(7, 5)³)) - (5! / 3))
353667 := (((C(7, 6)⁶) × 3) + (5! × 3!))
354049 := ((9! + 4!) - (C((0! + 4!), 5) / 3!))
354292 := (-2 - (-(((C(9, 2) / 4)⁵)) × 3!))
354309 := (9! - (C(((0 - 3!) + 4!), 5) + 3))
354318 := (((8 + 1))! - (C(-((3! - 4!)), 5) - (3!)))
354319 := ((9! + 1) - (C(-((3! - 4!)), 5) - (3!)))
354341 := -((C((1 + 4!), 3!) - ((4 + 5)^{3!})))

- 354363** := $((C(3!, 6) - (3!! \times (-4))) \times (5! + 3))$
354742 := $((-2 + C(4!, 7)) - ((4! \times 5!) \times (-3)))$
354744 := $(C(4!, (4! - 7)) - ((4! \times 5!) \times (-3)))$
354895 := $((-5) + 9!) + (-C(8, 4) \times (5! - 3!))$
354956 := $-(((6! + 5!) - 9!) + (C(4!, 5)/3!))$
355545 := $((C((5 + 4!), 5) - 5!) - 5!) \times 3$
355584 := $(4! \times (C(8, 5) + (5! \times (5! + 3))))$
355599 := $((9! - (9^{5-C(5,5)})) - (3!))$
355923 := $((3! + (C(29, 5))) - 5!) \times 3$
356145 := $-((5! + (C((4! - (1 - 6)), 5) \times (-3))))$
356379 := $(9! - ((7 + (3 \times (C(6, 5)!)) \times 3))$
356382 := $(((-2 + 8!) - 3!!) \times (C(6, 5) + 3))$
356395 := $((-5) + 9!) + ((3 \times (C(6, 5)!)) \times (-3))$
356748 := $(-(((8! - C(4!, 7)) \times (6! + 5!)))/(3!))$
356859 := $(9! - (((5 + C((8 + 6), 5)) \times 3)))$
356874 := $((4! \times 7!) - C((8 + 6), 5)) \times 3$
357125 := $(((((C(5, 2) - 1)! - 7!) + 5) - 3!))$
357336 := $((6 + 3)! - (3! \times C((7 + 5), 3!))$
357339 := $((9! + 3) - (3! \times C((7 + 5), 3!))$
357487 := $(7! - ((-C(8, 4) \times (7! - 5))) + 3))$
357689 := $((9! - (C(8, 6))) - 7!) - 5! - 3$
357794 := $((4! + 9!) - 7!) - (7 \times C(5, 3))$
357839 := $((9! - (3 + 8)) - 7!) + C(5, 3)$
357855 := $((C(5, 5) + 8)! - 7!) + (5 \times 3)$
357879 := $((9! - 7!) + ((C(8, 7) + 5) \times 3))$
357888 := $((8 \times 8) \times 8) \times (-C(7, 5) + (3!))$
357894 := $((4! + (C(9, 8))) - 7!) + (5 \times 3!)$
357903 := $-(((3! + 0!)! - (9! + (C(7, 5) \times 3))))$
357939 := $((C(9, 3) + 9!) - 7!) + (5 \times 3)$
357945 := $((C(5, 4)! + 9!) - 7!) - (5 \times 3)$
357966 := $((C(6, 6) + 9!) - 7!) + (5^3)$
358494 := $-(((4! - 9!) + (C((4! - 8), 5) - 3!))$
358498 := $((-8) + 9!) - (C((4! - 8), 5) + 3!)$
358509 := $(9! - (C((0! + (5!/8)), 5) + 3))$
358559 := $((9! - C(5, 5)) - (((8 - 5)! \times (3!))$
358755 := $(-5!) - (-C((5 + 7), 8) \times (5 + 3!))$
358824 := $-((4! + (((2 + 8)! - 8!)/(-C(5, 3))))$
358839 := $(9! - (((3!)/(-8)) - 8!)/(-C(5, 3))$
358848 := $((((8/4) + 8)! - 8!)/C(5, 3))$
358929 := $((9^2) + 9!) - (8!/C(5, 3))$
358937 := $((-(7^3) + (C(9, 8)!)) - (5 \times 3!))$
358944 := $((4! \times 4) + 9!) - (8!/C(5, 3))$
358959 := $(((-9) + 5!) + 9!) - (8!/C(5, 3))$
358975 := $((5! + (7) + 9!) - (8!/C(5, 3))$
359004 := $(-((C(4!, (0! + 0!)) - 9!)) - (5 \times 3!))$
359199 := $((9! - ((C(9, 1) \times 9))) - (5 \times (3!))$
359247 := $((-((C(7, 4) - 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!))$
359257 := $((-((C(7, 5) + 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!))$
359277 := $((-((C(7, 7) + 2)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!))$
359279 := $((9! - C((7 + 2), 9)) - (5 \times (3!))$
359308 := $((C(8, (03)!)) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!))$
359434 := $((4^3)/(-4) + 9!) + C(5, 3)$
359523 := $((C(3, 2)^5) + 9!) - (5 \times 3!))$
359528 := $((-C(8, 2) \times 5!) + 9!) + (5 + 3)$
359639 := $((9! - C(3!, 6)) - ((9 \times 5!) \times 3))$
359664 := $((4! - 6!) + (((6 + 9)!)/(C(5, 3)!))$
359839 := $((9! - 38) - C((9 + 5), 3!))$
359877 := $(-C((7 + 7), 8) + (C(9, (5 + 3)!))$
359964 := $((-4 \times 6!) + 9!) - C(9, (5 - 3))$
359989 := $((9! - 8) - ((9!/C(9, 5)) + 3))$
359992 := $((-2 + 9!) - ((9!/C(9, 5)) + 3!))$
359998 := $((-8) + 9!) - ((9!/C(9, 5)) - 3!))$
359999 := $((9! - C(9, 9)) - (9!/(5! + 3!))$
360689 := $((9! - (C(8, 6))) - ((0! + 6!) \times 3))$
360859 := $((9! - 5) + (8!/(0 - C(6, 3))))$
360924 := $(-((C(4!, 2) - 9!)) - (((0! + 6)!)/3))$
361109 := $(9! - C((-0!) + (-((1 + 1) - 6)!), 3))$
361195 := $((-5) + 9!) + (((C(1, 1) + 6)!)/(-3))$
361224 := $-(((C(4!, 2) \times ((2 + 1)!)) - ((6 + 3)!))$
361594 := $(-((C((4 + 9), 5) - 1)) + ((6 + 3)!))$
361796 := $-(((6! - 9!) + (C((7 + 1) + 6), 3)))$
361879 := $(9! - (C(((7 + 8) - 1), 6)/3))$
361959 := $(9! - (C((5!/(9 + 1)), 6) - 3))$
362059 := $((9! - 5) - C(((0! + 2) \times 6), 3))$
362064 := $-((C((4! - 6), (0! + 2)) - ((6 + 3)!))$
362157 := $((C(7, 5) - 12)! - 6!) - 3$
362199 := $((9! + C(C(9, 1), 2)) - 6!) + 3$
362239 := $((9! + (C(3!, 2) + (2^6))) - (3!))$
362324 := $-(((4!^2) - ((3^2)!)) - (C(6, 3)))$
362355 := $-((5 \times C((5 \times 3), 2)) + ((6 + 3)!))$
362398 := $((8!/(C(9, 3))) - 2) + ((6 + 3)!)$
362413 := $-((3! - (C((-1 + 4!), 2) + ((6 + 3)!))$
362418 := $((8 + 1)! - ((4! - 2)!)/(C(6, 3)!))$
362419 := $(9! + (C((-1 + 4!), 2) - 6!) + 3!)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 362433 &:= (((3 \times 3)!) + ((C(4!, 2) - 6!) - 3)) \\
 362439 &:= (9! - (C((3 + 4), 2)^{6/3})) \\
 362449 &:= (9! + ((C(4, 4) - (2 \times (6^3)))))) \\
 362496 &:= ((-6) + 9!) - (C(4, 2) \times 63) \\
 362499 &:= (9! - (((C(9, 4)/2) \times 6) + 3)) \\
 362529 &:= (9! - C((25 + 2), (6/3))) \\
 362544 &:= ((4! \times (-4 + C(5, 2)))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362592 &:= ((-2 + 9!) - C(((5 + 2) + 6), 3)) \\
 362594 &:= (-C((4 + 9), C(5, 2))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362595 &:= ((-5) + 9!) - (5 \times C((2 + 6), 3)) \\
 362597 &:= (-7) - (C(((9 - 5)!)!, 2) - ((6 + 3)!)!) \\
 362604 &:= (-C((4 \times 06), 2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362609 &:= ((9! - 0!) - ((C(6, 2) \times 6) \times 3)) \\
 362625 &:= (((5! \times (-2)) - (C(6, 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)!) \\
 362628 &:= ((C(8, 2) - ((6 + 2)!) \times (-6 + 3)) \\
 362646 &:= ((-6) \times (4! + (C(6, 2)))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362654 &:= (((4 + 5)!) - (6 + C((2 \times 6), 3))) \\
 362685 &:= (-(((5 + 8) \times C(6, 2))) + ((6 + 3)!)!) \\
 362735 &:= (((-5^3) + ((7 + 2)!) - (C(6, 3))) \\
 362742 &:= (-2 - (C((4! - 7), 2) - ((6 + 3)!)!) \\
 362753 &:= -(((3! + 5!) - ((7 + 2)!) + C(6, 3)!) \\
 362756 &:= (((6! / (-5)) + ((7 + 2)!) + (C(6, 3))) \\
 362767 &:= ((C(7, 6) - ((7 - 2)!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362772 &:= (((-2^7) + ((7 + 2)!) + (C(6, 3))) \\
 362775 &:= (-((5 \times C(7, (7 - 2)))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362784 &:= ((4! \times (-C(8, 7)/2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362788 &:= (((8 - 8!) \times (-7 + 2)) - (C(6, 3))) \\
 362789 &:= (9! - (C(C(8, 7), 2) + 63)) \\
 362817 &:= (((-7) + ((1 + 8)!) - C((2 + 6), 3)) \\
 362825 &:= (-C(((5 - 2) + 8), 2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362828 &:= (((-C(8, 2)) - ((8/2)!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362835 &:= (-C(C(5, 3), 8)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!) \\
 362837 &:= (-((C(7, 3) + 8)) + (((2 \times 6) - 3)!) \\
 362844 &:= (((C(4, 4) + 8)!) - ((2 \times 6) \times 3)) \\
 362845 &:= (((5 + 4)!) + ((C(8, 2) - 63))) \\
 362854 &:= (((4 + 5)!) - ((8 - 2) + C(6, 3))) \\
 362866 &:= (((C(6, 6) - 8) \times 2) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362873 &:= (((3 \times 7) - C(8, 2)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 362882 &:= (3 + 6)! + C(2, C(8, 8)^2) \\
 362885 &:= (3 + 6)! + (2 - C(8, 8)) \times 5 \\
 362887 &:= (3 + 6)! + (2 - C(8, 8)) \times 7 \\
 362888 &:= (3 + 6)! + (2 - C(8, 8)) \times 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 362921 &:= (((1^2) + 9!) + (2 \times C(6, 3))) \\
 362923 &:= ((C(3, 2) + 9!) + (2 \times C(6, 3))) \\
 362927 &:= (((7 + 2)!) - ((9 - C((2 + 6), 3)))) \\
 362937 &:= (((7 - 3!) + 9!) + C((2 + 6), 3)) \\
 362945 &:= (((5 + 4)!) + (9 + C((2 + 6), 3))) \\
 362953 &:= ((C(3!, 5) + 9!) + ((2^6) + 3)) \\
 362956 &:= (((6! / (-5)) + 9!) + (C((2 \times 6), 3))) \\
 362968 &:= (((8 \times 6) + 9!) + (2 \times C(6, 3))) \\
 362972 &:= (((-2^7) + 9!) + (C((2 \times 6), 3))) \\
 362973 &:= ((37 + 9!) + C((2 + 6), 3)) \\
 362984 &:= ((48 + 9!) + C((2 + 6), 3)) \\
 362999 &:= (9! + ((9 \times (9 + 2)) + C(6, 3))) \\
 363019 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((0! + 3!) \times C(6, 3))) \\
 363028 &:= ((C(8, 2) + (-((0! - 3)!)!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363033 &:= (C((3 \times 3)!, -((0! - 3)!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363035 &:= (5! + (C((3! + 0!), 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363049 &:= (9! + ((4! \times (0! + 3!)) + C(6, 3)!) \\
 363059 &:= (((9! + 5!) - 0!) + (3 \times C(6, 3))) \\
 363148 &:= (-8) + (C(4!, -((1 - 3))) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363166 &:= (C(((6 + 6) + 1), 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363234 &:= ((C((4! + 3), 2) + 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363244 &:= (C(((4 \times 4) - 2), 3) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363249 &:= (9! + (C(4, 2) + 363)) \\
 363324 &:= -(((C(4!, 2) - ((3 + 3)!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363328 &:= ((8 \times C((2^3), 3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363335 &:= (C((5 \times 3), 3) + ((3^{6/3})!) \\
 363339 &:= (9! + (C((33/3), 6) - 3)) \\
 363342 &:= (C(((2 \times 4) + 3), 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363399 &:= (9! + (((C(9, 3) + 3) \times 6) - 3)) \\
 363409 &:= (9! + ((0! - 4!) \times (-3 + C(6, 3)))) \\
 363419 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((4! + 3) \times C(6, 3))) \\
 363465 &:= (((-5! + C(6, 4)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363468 &:= ((C(8, 6) \times (4! - 3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363488 &:= ((8 \times (C(8, 4) + 3!)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363495 &:= ((5 \times (C(9, 4) - 3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363509 &:= ((9! - 0!) + (C(5, 3) \times 63)) \\
 363544 &:= (((-C((4 + 4), 5)) + 3!) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363569 &:= ((9! + 6!) - (C((5 + 3), 6) + 3)) \\
 363572 &:= (((2 + 7)!) - C((5 + 3), 6)) + 3! \\
 363573 &:= (3! - ((C(7, 5) + 3!) - ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363576 &:= ((6! - (C(7, 5) + 3)) + ((6 + 3)!) \\
 363579 &:= ((9! - (C(7, 5))) + (((3 + 6) - 3)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363589 &:= (((C(9,8))! - (5 + 3)) + 6!) - 3) \\
 363592 &:= (((-2 + (C(9, (5 + 3))))!) + 6!) - 3!) \\
 363593 &:= ((((-3 + 9!) - C(5,3)) + 6!) + 3!) \\
 363596 &:= ((6! + 9!) - C((C(5,3) - 6), 3)) \\
 363598 &:= (((-8) + (C(9, (5 + 3))))!) + 6!) + 3!) \\
 363623 &:= (((3^2))! + 6!) + (3 + C(6,3)) \\
 363628 &:= ((C(8,2) + 6!) + ((3^{6/3}))!) \\
 363744 &:= (4! - ((4! \times (-C(7,3))) - ((6 + 3))!)) \\
 363759 &:= (((C(9,5) \times 7) - 3) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 363802 &:= ((-2 + ((0! + 8))!) + (C((3! + 6), 3!))) \\
 363804 &:= (C((4 + 08), 3!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 363849 &:= (9! + C((4! - (8 - 3)), (6 - 3))) \\
 363881 &:= (((1 + 8))! + (C((8 + 3!), 6)/3)) \\
 363889 &:= ((9! + 8) + (C((8 + 3!), 6)/3)) \\
 363936 &:= (((6!/3) + 9!) + C((3 \times 6), 3)) \\
 364019 &:= ((9! - 1) + C((((0! + 4))!/6), 3)) \\
 364139 &:= (9! + (((3! + 1))!/4) - C(6,3!)) \\
 364167 &:= (C((7 + 6), (1 + 4)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364168 &:= (-((8 - (C(6,1)^4))) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364197 &:= (((7! + 9!) - C(14, 6)) - 3!) \\
 364245 &:= (C((5!/(4 \times 2)), 4) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364314 &:= (((C(4!, (1 \times 3)))/4) \times 6!) - 3!) \\
 364319 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((-3) \times 4!) \times (-C(6,3))) \\
 364326 &:= (((C(((6 - 2))!, 3)/4) \times 6!) + 3!) \\
 364344 &:= (4! + (C(4!, 3) \times ((4! + 6) \times 3!))) \\
 364364 &:= (-C(4!, 6) + (3!! \times (-((4! - 6!) + 3)))) \\
 364389 &:= (((C(9,8))! - 3) - (4! \times (-63))) \\
 364569 &:= ((9! + 6!) + C((-5 + 4!), (6 - 3))) \\
 364593 &:= ((-3 + 9!) + C(((5 + 4!) - 6), 3!)) \\
 364635 &:= (((5! - 3) \times C(6,4)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364674 &:= (C(4!, 7) + (C((-6 + 4!), 6) + 3!)) \\
 364689 &:= (9 \times (8! - ((C(6,4) - (6^3)))))) \\
 364735 &:= ((53 \times C(7,4)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364834 &:= ((C(4!, 3) - C(8,4)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 364839 &:= (9! + (((3 - C(8,4)) + 6!) \times 3)) \\
 364859 &:= ((9 \times (-5 + 8!)) + (C((4 \times 6), 3))) \\
 364893 &:= ((-3 + 9!) - (8 - C((4 \times 6), 3))) \\
 364897 &:= ((-7) + 9!) + (C(((8 - 4) \times 6), 3)) \\
 364902 &:= ((-2 + (09)!) + (C((4 \times 6), 3))) \\
 364903 &:= -((((3 \times 0))! - 9!) - (C((4 \times 6), 3))) \\
 364904 &:= (((4 \times 0) + 9))! + (C((4 \times 6), 3)) \\
 364905 &:= (((5 \times 0))! + 9!) + (C((4 \times 6), 3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 364928 &:= (((8/2))! + 9!) + (C((4 \times 6), 3)) \\
 364934 &:= ((C(4!, 3) + 9!) + ((4 + 6) \times 3)) \\
 365024 &:= (C(4!, (2 + 0!)) + (5! + ((6 + 3))!)) \\
 365025 &:= (((C(5,2) - 0!))! + ((5 - 6!) \times (-3))) \\
 365159 &:= (((9! - 5!) - 1) - (5! \times (-C(6,3)))) \\
 365424 &:= (C(4!, 2) \times ((4 - 5!) + 6!) + 3!) \\
 365574 &:= ((C(4!, 7) + ((5^5) \times 6)) + 3!) \\
 365599 &:= (((9! + (C((9 + 5), 5))) + 6!) - 3) \\
 365764 &:= (-4 \times ((6! \times (-7 - 5!)) - C(6,3!))) \\
 365883 &:= (C((3! + 8), ((8 - 5))!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 365889 &:= (9! + (C((8 + ((8 - 5))!), 6) + 3!)) \\
 365904 &:= ((4! \times C(09, 5)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 366312 &:= ((2 \times C(13, 6)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 366455 &:= ((-5 \times (C(5,4) - 6!)) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 366528 &:= ((C((8 \times 2), 5) - 6!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 366696 &:= (((6! - (C(9,6))) \times 6) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 366699 &:= (9! + (((-C(9,6)) + 6!) \times 6) + 3) \\
 366924 &:= (((C(4!, 2) - 9!)/(-6)) + 6!) \times 3! \\
 367228 &:= ((C(8,2) + ((2 + 7))!) + (6! \times 3!)) \\
 367248 &:= (C((-8) + 4!), -((2 - 7))) + ((6 + 3))! \\
 367524 &:= -((((C(4!, 2) + 5!) - 7!) - ((6 + 3))!)) \\
 367629 &:= (9! + (((C((2 \times 6), 7) \times 6) - 3))) \\
 367644 &:= -((((C(4!, -((4 - 6))) - 7!) - ((6 + 3))!)) \\
 367891 &:= ((((-1 + 9!) - 8) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367893 &:= ((-((3 \times C(9,8))) + 7!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 367895 &:= (((-5) + (C(9,8))!) + 7!) - (C(6,3)) \\
 367899 &:= (((9! - (9 - 8)) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367904 &:= ((4 + (09)!) + 7!) - (C(6,3)) \\
 367907 &:= ((7! + (09)!) + ((7 - C(6,3)))) \\
 367924 &:= (((-((4^2)) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3))) \\
 367926 &:= (((C(6,2) - 9) + 7!) + ((6 + 3))!) \\
 367933 &:= (((33 + 9!) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367938 &:= ((((-8) + 3!) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3)) \\
 367939 &:= (((9! + 39) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367941 &:= (((1^4) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3)) \\
 367942 &:= (((-((2 - 4)) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3))) \\
 367944 &:= (((44 + 9!) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367945 &:= (((C(5,4) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3))) \\
 367949 &:= (((9! + (49)) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367955 &:= (((55 + 9!) + 7!) - (C(6,3))) \\
 367958 &:= (((C(8,5) + 9!) + 7!) - ((6 \times 3))) \\
 367964 &:= (((4 \times 6) + 9!) + 7!) + (C(6,3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 367966 &:= (((66 + 9!) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 367968 &:= (((C(8, 6) + 9!) + 7!) + C(6, 3)) \\ 367969 &:= (((9! + 69) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 367975 &:= (((5 \times 7) + 9!) + 7!) + C(6, 3)) \\ 367977 &:= (((77 + 9!) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 367979 &:= (((9! + 79) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 367985 &:= (((5 + 8!) \times 9) + 7!) + C(6, 3)) \\ 367988 &:= (((88 + 9!) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 367997 &:= ((7! + 9!) + (97 - C(6, 3))) \\ 367999 &:= (((9! + 99) + 7!) - C(6, 3)) \\ 368079 &:= (((9! + 7!) - 0!) + (8 \times C(6, 3))) \\ 368379 &:= ((9! + 7!) + (C((3 + 8), 6) - 3)) \\ 368453 &:= (3!! - ((5 - C(4!, 8))/(6/3))) \\ 368548 &:= (-((8 \times 4^5)) + C(C(8, 6), 3!)) \\ 368619 &:= ((9! - 1) + ((6! \times 8) - C(6, 3))) \\ 368645 &:= (C(5, 4) + (6! \times (8^{6-3}))) \\ 368668 &:= (C(8, 6) + (6! \times (8^{6-3}))) \\ 368859 &:= ((9! - 5) + (8 \times (C(8, 6) + (3!)!))) \\ 368996 &:= (((6! \times 9) + 9!) - C((8 + 6), 3)) \\ 369216 &:= -((((C(6, 1) + 2))! - 9!) - (6^3)) \\ 369357 &:= (((7!/C(5, 3)) + 9) \times 6!) - 3 \\ 369385 &:= (((5 + 8!) + 3!) \times 9) - C(6, 3) \\ 369386 &:= (((6! + 8!) + 3) \times 9) - C(6, 3!) \\ 369388 &:= (8 + (((-8!) - (3!)!) \times (-9)) + C(6, 3)) \\ 372024 &:= (4! \times (C(20, -(2 - 7)) - 3)) \\ 372775 &:= (((5 - 7!) - 7!) \times (-2 + C(7, 3))) \\ 372927 &:= (((7! \times 2) + 9!) + ((2 - C(7, 3))) \\ 372937 &:= ((-C(7, 3) + 9!) + (2 \times (7! + 3!))) \\ 372938 &:= -(((C(8, 3!) - 9!) + ((-2) \times 7!) - 3!)) \\ 373035 &:= (-5 \times (3! - C((0! + ((3 \times 7))), 3!)) \\ 373045 &:= (-5 \times (4 - C((0! + ((3 \times 7))), 3!)) \\ 373065 &:= (5 \times C((((6 \times 0)!) + ((3 \times 7))), 3!)) \\ 373213 &:= (((3! \times 12)^3) - C(7, 3)) \\ 373248 &:= (((C(8, 4)/2) + 37)^3) \\ 373268 &:= ((8 \times (C(6, 2) + (3!^7)))/3!) \\ 373283 &:= (((3 \times ((8/2)!)^3) + C(7, 3)) \\ 373298 &:= ((8 \times ((C(9, 2)^3) + 7)) - 3!) \\ 373459 &:= (9! + (((C(5, 4)^3) - 7!) - 3!)) \\ 373488 &:= (((-((8 \times 8)) \times C(4!, 3)) + 7!) \times (-3)) \\ 373495 &:= (((-5) + 9!) + (C(4!, -((3 - 7))) - 3!)) \\ 373498 &:= (((-8) + 9!) + C((C(4, 3))!, (7 - 3))) \\ 373509 &:= (9! + (C((-((0! - 5))))!, -((3 - 7))) + 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 373528 &:= (8 \times (((-(2 - 5))!)^3) + C(7, 3)) \\ 373545 &:= (((-C((5 + 4!), 5) - 3!) - 7!) \times (-3)) \\ 373679 &:= (((9! + 7!) - (C(6, 3!) - 7!)) + (3!)!) \\ 373896 &:= ((6! + 9!) + (C((8 + 3!), 7) \times 3)) \\ 373944 &:= ((C(4!, 4) + 9!) - (3! \times (-73))) \\ 374368 &:= (8 \times ((6^3!) + (4 \times C(7, 3))) \\ 374555 &:= ((5! \times ((5^5) - 4)) + C(7, 3)) \\ 374796 &:= (-6) \times ((9!/(-7)) - C(4!, (7 - 3))) \\ 374965 &:= (((5^{(-6+9)!}) \times 4!) - C(7, 3)) \\ 375035 &:= ((5! \times ((3! - 0!)^5)) + C(7, 3)) \\ 375155 &:= (((5^5) + 1) \times 5!) + C(7, 3)) \\ 375624 &:= ((C(4!, 2) - 6!) \times ((5! \times (-7)) - 3!)) \\ 376319 &:= ((9! - 1) + (((C(3!, 6) + (7)))! / 3)) \\ 376338 &:= (C(C(8, 3!), 3!) - (67 \times 3!)) \\ 376344 &:= (((C(4!, (4 + 3))/6) + 7!) \times 3!) \\ 376374 &:= ((C(4!, 7) - 3!) + ((6 + 7!) \times 3!)) \\ 376668 &:= (C(C(8, 6), 6) - (6! / (7 + 3))) \\ 376689 &:= (-((9 - C(C(8, 6), 6))) + (-7) \times 3!)) \\ 376698 &:= (C(C(8, ((9 - 6)!)!, 6) + (-7) \times 3!)) \\ 376705 &:= (C(((5 - 0!) \times 7), 6) - C(7, 3)) \\ 376727 &:= ((C((C(7, 2) + 7), 6) - 7) - 3!) \\ 376735 &:= (-5 + C(((3 + 7) - 6) \times 7), 3!)) \\ 376739 &:= ((C(-((9 - 37)), 6) - (7)) + 3!) \\ 376753 &:= ((C((35 - 7), 6) + 7) + 3!) \\ 376764 &:= (C(((4!/6) \times 7), 6) + ((7 - 3)!) \\ 376825 &:= (5! + ((C(28, 6) - C(7, 3))) \\ 377825 &:= (-5 \times (((-2 \times 8!) + 7!) + C(7, 3)) \\ 377959 &:= ((9! - ((5 + C(9, 7)))) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 377965 &:= (((5 \times (6 + 9)) \times 7!) - C(7, 3)) \\ 377993 &:= -((((3! - ((9 \times 9))) \times 7!) + C(7, 3!)) \\ 377999 &:= ((9! - (C(9, 9)^7)) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378028 &:= ((C(8, 2) + ((0! + 8)!) - (7! \times (-3))) \\ 378075 &:= ((5 \times (7! + 0!)) \times (8 + C(7, 3!))) \\ 378336 &:= (((6^3!) + 3!) \times 8) + (C(7, 3!)!) \\ 379345 &:= (((C(5, 4)^3) + 9!) + (7! / 3!)) \\ 379449 &:= (9 \times (C(4!, -((4 - 9))) - ((7^3)))) \\ 379545 &:= (((C((-5 + 4!), 5) + 9!) + 7!) - 3) \\ 379554 &:= (((C((4! - 5), 5) + 9!) + 7!) + 3!) \\ 379579 &:= (9! + ((7^5) - (C(9, 7) \times 3))) \\ 380226 &:= (C((6 \times 2), 2) \times (0! + (8 \times 3!))) \\ 380433 &:= ((C((3^3), 4) + ((0! + 8)!) + 3) \\ 381419 &:= (((9! - 1) - 4!) + C(18, 3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 381479 &:= ((9! + C(7,4)) + C(18,3!)) \\
 381559 &:= (((9! + 5!) - (5)) + C(18,3!)) \\
 382468 &:= ((8 \times (6! - (4))) + C(28,3!)) \\
 382476 &:= (((6! + 7!) - 4!) + C(28,3!)) \\
 382549 &:= ((9 \times C(4!,5)) + ((2 \times 8) - 3)) \\
 382928 &:= (((8!/2) + 9!) - ((2 \times C(8,3)))) \\
 383068 &:= (C(8,6) \times (0! - (((3!)! + 8!)/(-3)))) \\
 383187 &:= ((7 \times 8!) + C(-((1 - (3 \times 8))), 3!)) \\
 383229 &:= (9! + C(-(2 - 23), (8 - 3))) \\
 383724 &:= (((C((4! - 2), 7) \times 3!)/(-8)) \times (-3)) \\
 383785 &:= ((5^{C(8,7)}) - ((3!! + 8!)/3!)) \\
 383824 &:= (((C(4,2))! + (8^{3!}) - (8! \times (-3))) \\
 384382 &:= (-2 - ((-8 \times 3!) \times C((4! - 8), 3!)) \\
 384384 &:= (48 \times C(((3! - 4) \times 8), 3!)) \\
 385623 &:= -((C(C(3!,2),6) - (((5^8) + 3)))) \\
 385626 &:= (-((C(C(6,2),6) - (5^8))) + 3!) \\
 385674 &:= (((C(4!,7) - ((6 \times 5))) + 8!) - 3!!) \\
 385728 &:= (C(8,2) \times (((7!/5) + 8!)/3)) \\
 385944 &:= (4! + ((4 \times (C(9,5) + 8)) \times 3!!)) \\
 386105 &:= (5 \times (0! - (-C(16,8)) \times 3!)) \\
 386364 &:= ((C(4!,6) - ((3! + 6!) \times 8)) \times 3) \\
 386424 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + C(4!, ((6 + 8) + 3))) \\
 386618 &:= (((8! + (C(16,6))) \times 8) - 3!) \\
 386675 &:= (-5) \times (((-((C(7,6)^6)) + 8!) - 3!)) \\
 386785 &:= (-5) \times ((8! - ((7^6))) - C(8,3!)) \\
 386897 &:= (((-7) + 9!) - (-8) \times C((6 + 8), 3!)) \\
 386944 &:= ((C(4!,4) + 9!) + ((6 - 8!)/(-3))) \\
 387137 &:= (((-7) + (C(((3 + 1)!)!, 7) + 8!)) + 3!!) \\
 387142 &:= (((-2 + (C(4!, (1 \times 7)) + 8!)) + 3!!) \\
 387144 &:= ((C((C(4, (4 - 1)))!, 7) + 8!) + 3!!) \\
 387193 &:= ((3! + 9!) + (C(17,8) - 3)) \\
 387454 &:= ((4^5) + ((C(4!,7) + 8!) + 3!)) \\
 387655 &:= (5 \times (C((5!/6), 7) + (8 + 3))) \\
 388644 &:= -((4! + ((C(4!,6) - (8!/8)) \times (-3))) \\
 388647 &:= (((7 - C(4!,6)) + (8!/8)) \times (-3)) \\
 388946 &:= (((C((-6) + 4!), 9) \times 8) - 8) - 3! \\
 389185 &:= ((5^8) - (((-((1 - 9)))!)/C(8,3!))) \\
 389225 &:= (((3 + 8) + 9!) + (C(22,5))) \\
 389238 &:= ((C(8,3) + 2) \times (-9) + (8!/3!)) \\
 389348 &:= ((8! - ((4!^3) - 9!)) - C(8,3!)) \\
 389785 &:= ((5^8) - (7!/(C(9,8) - 3))) \\
 389788 &:= (((8! \times 87)/9) + C(8,3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 389905 &:= ((5^{-0!+9}) - ((C(9,8) - 3)!)) \\
 390348 &:= ((8! - (C(4!,3!) \times 09))/(-3)) \\
 390541 &:= (((1 + 4!)^{5-0!}) - (C(9,3))) \\
 390622 &:= (((-((C(2,2) - 6))^{-0!+9}) - 3) \\
 391464 &:= (4! \times ((6! \times 4!) - (C(19,3)))) \\
 392448 &:= (((8^4) + (4!^2)) \times C(9,3)) \\
 393174 &:= -((4! + ((7! + 1) \times (3! - (C(9,3)))))) \\
 393216 &:= (((C(6,1) + 2)^{3!}) \times 9)/3! \\
 393273 &:= (-3 - ((7! + 2) \times (3! - (C(9,3)))) \\
 393624 &:= (426 \times C((3 + 9), 3!)) \\
 393744 &:= (((-((4 + 4) - 7!) \times (3! - (C(9,3)))) \\
 393745 &:= ((5^4) - (7! \times (3! - (C(9,3)))) \\
 393837 &:= (((C(7,3) + 8) \times 3!!) + ((9! - 3))) \\
 393846 &:= (((C((-6) + 4!), 8) + 3) \times 9) - 3) \\
 394734 &:= (((C((4! - 3!), 7) + 4!) + 9!) + 3!) \\
 394858 &:= (((8^5) - C(8,4) + 9!) - (3!)!) \\
 395585 &:= ((5 + C(8,5)) \times (5 - (-9 \times 3!))) \\
 395643 &:= (((C(3!,4)!)/((6 + 5)!)) + (9! + 3)) \\
 395646 &:= (((C(6,4)!)/((6 + 5)!)) + 9!) + 3! \\
 395832 &:= (2 \times (((3!! - 8!) \times (-5)) - (C(9,3)))) \\
 396532 &:= (((C(23,5) + 6) + 9!) - 3) \\
 396541 &:= (((C((-1 + 4!), 5) + 6) + 9!) + 3!) \\
 397524 &:= (((C(4!,2) \times 5!) + 7) \times (9 + 3)) \\
 398544 &:= (((C((4 \times 4), 5) \times 8) + 9!) + 3!!) \\
 398723 &:= (((((C(3,2) + 7)! - 8!)/9) + 3) \\
 398796 &:= (((6! + 9!) - 7!) + 8!) - (C(9,3)) \\
 399924 &:= (C(4!,2) \times ((9 \times 9) \times 9) + 3!)) \\
 402528 &:= (C(8,2) \times ((5!^2) - (04)!)) \\
 402924 &:= -(((C(4!,2) - 9!) - ((2 \times 04)!)) \\
 403225 &:= (((C(5,2) \times ((2^3)!) + 0!) + 4!) \\
 403368 &:= ((C(8,6) \times 3!) \times ((3! + 0!)^4)) \\
 403453 &:= ((-3 \times (5! - C(4!,3!))) + (0! + 4!)) \\
 403644 &:= -((4! + (C(4!,6) \times (-3))) - ((0! + 4)!)) \\
 403645 &:= -((5! + (((C(4!,6) \times (-3)) - 0!) + 4!)) \\
 403647 &:= (((7 - C(4!,6)) \times (-3)) - ((0! + (4)!)) \\
 403676 &:= (((6 + 7!) \times C(6,3)) - 0!) \times 4) \\
 403764 &:= (((C(4!,6) - 7) \times 3) + 0!) - 4) \\
 403784 &:= ((C((4! - (8 - 7)), 3!) - 0!) \times 4) \\
 403788 &:= (C(((8 + 8) + 7), 3!) \times 04) \\
 403825 &:= ((C(5,2) \times 8!) + ((3! - 0!)^4)) \\
 403925 &:= (((C(5,2)!)/9) + 3!!) + (0! + 4) \\
 404364 &:= ((C(4!,6) \times 3) + (4! \times (04)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 404436 &:= (6! + (3 \times (C(4!, ((4 - 0!)!) - 4!))) \\
 404659 &:= (((9! - (5)) - 6!) + C(4!, (0! + (4)))) \\
 405379 &:= (9! + ((C(((7 - 3)!)!, 5) - 0!) - (4))) \\
 405384 &:= (C(4!, (8 - 3)) + ((5 + 04)!)) \\
 405389 &:= (((9! + C((8 \times 3), 5)) + 0!) + (4)) \\
 405408 &:= (((8 + 0!)!) + ((C(4!, 5) + (04)!)) \\
 405409 &:= (9! + ((C((04)!, 5) + 0!) + 4!)) \\
 405497 &:= (((-7) + 9!) + C(4!, 5)) + ((0! + (4)))! \\
 409533 &:= ((3!^{C(3,5)}) + ((9! + 0!) - 4)) \\
 413424 &:= (-((C(4, 2)!) - (4! \times ((3!! - 1) \times (-4!)))) \\
 413568 &:= (8! + ((6!/C(5, 3))^{-1+4})) \\
 414464 &:= (((4! \times 6!) \times 4!) - (C(4, 1)^4)) \\
 414668 &:= (-C(8, 6)) + (((6! \times 4!) - 1) \times 4!) \\
 414724 &:= (((((C(4, 2)!) - 7!) \times 4!) - 1) \times (-4)) \\
 416744 &:= ((C(4!, (4 + 7))/6) + ((-(1 - 4)))!) \\
 422476 &:= (((6! - ((C(7, 4) \times 2)))^2) - 4!) \\
 422496 &:= ((6! \times C(9, 4)) + (((2 + 2)!)^4)) \\
 423339 &:= (((9!/3!) - 3) \times (C(3, 2) + 4)) \\
 423384 &:= (4! + ((C(8, 3!) \times ((3^2)!) / 4!)) \\
 423395 &:= ((5 + (9!/3!)) \times (C(3, 2) + 4)) \\
 423399 &:= ((9! + (9!/3!)) + (C(3!, 2) + 4!)) \\
 425054 &:= (((C(4!, 5) + 0!) \times C(5, 2)) + 4) \\
 425064 &:= ((C(4!, (6 - 0!)) \times C(5, 2)) + 4!) \\
 426496 &:= (((6! - (C(9, 4))) \times (6! - 2)) + (4)) \\
 426636 &:= (((6 + 3)!) - (-6 \times C(((6 - 2)!)!, 4))) \\
 426639 &:= ((9! + 3) - (-6 \times C(((6 - 2)!)!, 4))) \\
 426748 &:= (8! + ((C(4!, 7) + ((6 + 2)!) + (4))) \\
 427391 &:= (-1 - (-C(9, 3) \times (7! + (2 \times 4!)))) \\
 427392 &:= ((2 \times C(9, 3)) \times ((7!/2) + 4!)) \\
 427536 &:= (-6) \times ((3!! \times (-5! - (C(7, 2)))) + 4!) \\
 434112 &:= ((C(21, (-((1 - 4)))!) / 3) \times 4!) \\
 434352 &:= (2 \times (5! - (C((-3 + 4)!, 3!) \times (-4)))) \\
 434596 &:= (((6! - 9!) / (-C(5, 4))) \times 3!) + (4)) \\
 434688 &:= (8 \times ((8 \times 6!) + (C(4!, 3) \times 4!))) \\
 435124 &:= (((C(4, 2)!) + 1) - 5!) \times (3!! + 4)) \\
 435408 &:= (8 \times (C((0! + 4!), 5) + (3!^4))) \\
 435546 &:= (-6) \times (((4 + 5)!) / (-5)) - C(3!, 4)) \\
 435615 &:= (((5! + 1) \times 6!) \times 5) + C(3!, 4)) \\
 435936 &:= ((C(6, 3) + ((9!/5!) \times 3!)) \times 4!) \\
 436335 &:= (((-5!) + 3!!) + (3!)) \times 6! + C(3!, 4)) \\
 436344 &:= (((4 - C(4!, 3)) \times (-6^3)) + 4!) \\
 437469 &:= (9! + (C((C(6, 4) + 7), 3!) - 4!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 439263 &:= (C((3 \times 6), 2) \times (-9 - (3!! \times (-4)))) \\
 443508 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times (5 + 3!)) - C(4, 4)) \\
 443515 &:= (-5 - (-((1 + C(5, 3))) \times ((4 + 4)!)!) \\
 443523 &:= (C(3, 2) - ((-5 - 3!) \times ((4 + 4)!)!) \\
 443528 &:= (((8! - 2) - ((C(5, 3)!) / 4!)) \times (-4)) \\
 443553 &:= ((C(3!, 5) + 5) \times (3 + ((4 + 4)!)!) \\
 443586 &:= ((6 + 8!) \times (C(5, 3) + C(4, 4))) \\
 443755 &:= (-5 \times (-((5^7)) - C((3! \times 4), 4))) \\
 443828 &:= ((-C(8, 2) - 8!) \times (-((3 + 4) + 4))) \\
 444276 &:= ((6 \times 7) \times ((-2) \times 4!) + C(4!, 4)) \\
 444693 &:= ((-3 - 9!) + (6 \times C(4!, (4!/4)))) \\
 444696 &:= (-6) \times ((9!/6) - C(4!, (4!/4))) \\
 444816 &:= -((6! - (C(18, (4!/4)) \times 4!)) \\
 444936 &:= ((6! \times (3!! - (C(9, 4) - 4!))) - 4!) \\
 445392 &:= (((C((2 \times 9), 3!) - 5) \times 4!) - 4!) \\
 445625 &:= ((-((5 + 2)) + 6!) \times (C(5, 4)^4)) \\
 446274 &:= (-4 + (-7 \times (2 - (6 \times C(4!, 4)))) \\
 446291 &:= (-1 + ((C(9, 2) + 6) \times C(4!, 4))) \\
 446292 &:= (((2 \times 9) \times 2) + 6) \times C(4!, 4)) \\
 446313 &:= ((3! + 1) \times (3 + (6 \times C(4!, 4)))) \\
 446327 &:= (-7) \times (-((2 + 3)) - (6 \times C(4!, 4))) \\
 446334 &:= ((4 + 3) \times (3! + (6 \times C(4!, 4)))) \\
 446397 &:= (-7) \times ((-9) - 3!) - (6 \times C(4!, 4))) \\
 446537 &:= (-7) \times (-35) - (6 \times C(4!, 4))) \\
 447552 &:= ((C((2 \times 5), 5) \times 74) \times 4!) \\
 447884 &:= (-4 - (-8 \times ((8! + 7!) + C(4!, 4)))) \\
 447888 &:= (8! + (8 \times ((C(8, 7)!) + C(4!, 4)))) \\
 448608 &:= (((8 + 0!)!) + ((6! - (-8) \times C(4!, 4)))) \\
 448609 &:= (((9! + 0!) + 6!) - (-8) \times C(4!, 4)) \\
 449376 &:= (((6! \times (C(7, 3) - 9)) + (4)) \times 4!) \\
 450635 &:= (C(5, 3) + ((6! + 0!) \times (5^4))) \\
 451577 &:= (-((7^7)) - (-5!) \times C(-((1 - 5)!)!, 4)) \\
 451588 &:= (((8! \times (-C(8, 5))) / (-1 \times 5)) + (4)) \\
 453125 &:= ((5 + ((C(2, 1) \times 3)!) \times (5^4)) \\
 453324 &:= -((C(4!, 2) - (((3 \times 3)!) \times 5) / 4)) \\
 453543 &:= (-3 \times (4! - (((C(5, 3)!) + 5!) / 4!)) \\
 453576 &:= (((6 \times 7!) \times (C(5, 3) + 5)) - 4!) \\
 453585 &:= (-((5 - 8)) \times (((C(5, 3)!) - 5!) / 4!)) \\
 453628 &:= (C(8, 2) + (((6 + 3)!) \times 5) / 4)) \\
 453675 &:= ((5 + (7! \times 6)) \times (3 \times C(5, 4))) \\
 453695 &:= (5! - (((9! - (C(6, 3))) \times 5) / (-4))) \\
 453793 &:= (((3 \times 9) \times (C(7, 3!)^5)) + 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 453825 := ((C(5,2) × 8!) + (((3 × 5)⁴)))
 453843 := (((3! + 4)!/8) + (3^{C(5,4)}))
 454225 := (((C(5,2))!/(2 × 4)) + ((5⁴)))
 454356 := (((6! × 5) + 3!) × C((4 + 5),4))
 454896 := ((6 × 9) × ((C(8,4) × 5!) + 4!))
 455409 := (9 × (0! + ((4 × C((5 × 5),4))))))
 456384 := (4! × (8 + (C((3! + 6),5) × 4!)))
 456464 := ((C(4!,6) - ((4⁶) × 5)) × 4)
 457344 := -(((C(4!, (-4 + 3!)) - 7!) × (5! - 4!)))
 458514 := ((C(4!, -((1 - 5))) + 8!) × (5 + 4))
 458668 := -(((8 + 6) × (6 - (8^{C(5,4)}))))
 458784 := (((4⁸) × 7) + C(8,5)) - 4!
 459277 := ((7! + (7)) × (-29 + (C(5,4)!))
 459351 := (((1 + 5))! × 3!!) - (9^{C(5,4)}))
 459369 := ((9⁶) - (C((3! + 9),5) × 4!))
 459648 := (((8 × 4!) + 6!) × (C(9,5) × 4))
 459798 := ((89 × (7! + (C(9,5)))) + 4!)
 460412 := (2 × (C(((1 + 4!) + 0!),6) - 4!))
 462385 := (((-((5 × 8)) + 3!!)²) - C(6,4))
 462398 := (((C((8 + 9),3)²) - 6) + 4)
 462816 := ((6! + C(((1 + 8) × 2),6)) × 4!)
 464396 := ((6! × (C((9 + 3!),4) - 6!)) - (4))
 464544 := (4! × ((C((4 × 5),4) - 6) × 4))
 466559 := ((9! - C(5,5)) + ((6! × 6) × 4!))
 467064 := C(4!,6 + 0!) + 7! × 6 × 4
 467542 := (-2 + (C(4!,5) × (C(7,6) + 4)))
 467544 := (C(4!,4) × (-5 - (7⁶⁻⁴)))
 467593 := -((C((3! + 9),5) - ((7⁶) × 4)))
 467636 := (((C(6,3) + 6!) - ((7⁶))) × (-4))
 468723 := (C(3,2) + ((7!/8) × (6! + 4!)))
 469728 := (((8!/2) - ((7 × C(9,6)))) × 4!)
 470564 := -((C(4!,6) + (5! × ((0! - 7!) - 4))))
 472346 := (((6! - (C(4!,3!) × (-2))) × 7)/4)
 474196 := ((6! × (-9)) + (C((1 + 4!),7) - 4!))
 475044 := (4! + C((4! - (0 - 5)), ((7 - 4)!))
 475224 := (((((C(4,2) × 2))! × 5)/7!) + 4!)
 475462 := (-2 - ((6! + C(4!,5)) × (-7 + 4)))
 475464 := (((4 + 6) × (C(4!,5) + 7!)) + 4!)
 475744 := (-4 × (C(4!,C(7,5)) - (7! × 4!)))
 476064 := ((4! - 6!) × ((0! - 6!) + (C(7,4))))
 478235 := (5! + ((3!)²) - ((8! - (C(7,4))))))
 479976 := -((6! - ((C(((7 + 9) + 9),7) - 4))))
 480234 := ((C(4!, (C(3!,2) - 0!)) - 8!)/4)
 480704 := (C((4! + 0!),7) + (08 - 4))
 480725 := ((C((5²),7) + 0!) + ((8 - 4)!))
 481416 := (6! + (C((1 + 4!), -((1 - 8))) - (4)))
 482664 := (C((4! - 6),6) × (2 + ((8 - 4)!))
 483124 := -(((C(4,2))! - ((-1 + (-3 × 8!)) × (-4))))
 483164 := -((C(4!,6) + (((13)!/8!) × (-4))))
 483385 := -((C((5!/8),3) + ((-3) × 8!) × 4))
 483551 := (-1 - ((5!/(-C(5,3))) × (8! - 4!)))
 483603 := (3 × (0! - ((C(6,3) - 8!) × 4))
 483696 := (((6! × C(9,6)) - 3!) - 8!) × 4!
 483712 := (-((C(2,1)⁷)) - ((-3 × 8!) × 4))
 483728 := (((8! × 2) - (7)) × 3!) - C(8,4))
 483739 := (9! - ((3 × (C(7,3) - 8!)) - (4)))
 483744 := ((C(4,4) - 7!) × (-((3 × 8) × 4)))
 483797 := (-((7 + C(9,7))) - ((-3) × 8!) × 4))
 483823 := (C(3!,2) + (((8! × 3) - 8) × 4))
 483841 := (1 + ((4 × 8!) × C(3, (8/4))))
 483843 := (((3 × 4) × 8!) + (C(3, (8/4))))
 483845 := (5 + ((4 × 8!) × C(3, (8/4))))
 483849 := (9 + ((4 × 8!) × C(3, (8/4))))
 483877 := (C(7,7) + ((8! + 3) × (8 + 4)))
 483909 := ((9! - 0!) - ((9!/(-3)) - C(8,4)))
 483914 := ((-4 × (-1 + (9!/(-3)))) + (C(8,4)))
 483918 := ((8 × (1 + (9!/3!))) + (C(8,4)))
 483934 := ((4 × (3! - (9!/(-3)))) + (C(8,4)))
 483947 := ((C(7,4) + 9!) + (3 × (8! + 4!)))
 483968 := (8 × (((6! × C(9,3)) - 8) + 4!))
 484288 := (((8! + (C(8,2))) × 4) - 8!) × 4)
 484346 := (((6! - 4!)^{3!-4}) - (C(8,4)))
 484368 := (((8! + (C(6,3))) + 4!) × (8 + 4))
 484606 := ((6! - 0!) × ((6! + 4!) - C(8,4)))
 485256 := (((C(6,5) × 2) × (5! + 8!)) - 4!)
 485348 := ((8 × (C((4! - 3),5) + 8!)) - (4))
 486843 := (3 × ((4 × 8!) + (C((6 + 8),4))))
 487296 := (((-6) × (C(9,2) + 7!)) × (8 - 4!))
 487305 := ((5! - 0!) × (3 × C((7 + 8),4)))
 488373 := (-3 - (-C((7 × 3), (8 + 8))) × 4!))
 488634 := (C((4! - C(3!,6)),8) - (8!/4!))
 488779 := ((97 × (7! - C(8,8))) - (4))
 490307 := (-7 - (C(((0! + 3)!), (0! + 9)))/(-4)))

$$\begin{aligned} 490312 &:= (-2 - (C(((1+3)!)!, (0!+9)))/(-4))) \\ 490314 &:= C((4!-1), ((3+09)-4)) \\ 490329 &:= (-9) + (C(23, -((0!-9))) + 4!) \\ 490359 &:= ((9 \times (-5!) - C(((3+0!)!)!, 9)))/(-4!) \\ 491523 &:= C(3,2) + 5! \times (-1+9)^4 \\ 491645 &:= ((5! \times 4^6) - (1 - C(9,4))) \\ 492075 &:= (-5) \times (C((7-0!), 2) \times (-9^4))) \\ 494436 &:= (((-6!) \times 3!) + (C(4!, (4+9))))/4 \\ 495495 &:= ((5 \times C((-9+4!), 5)) \times (9+4!)) \\ 497345 &:= -((5! - (((C(4!, 3!) - 7) + 9!) - 4))) \\ 497349 &:= (9! + ((C(4!, 3!) - 7) - ((9-4)!)) \\ 497393 &:= (-3 + (C(((9+3!) + 7), 9) - 4!)) \\ 497396 &:= (C(-(((6+9) - 37)), 9) - 4!) \\ 497429 &:= (9 + C((2 \times (4+7)), (9+4))) \\ 497437 &:= (-7) + (C((C(3!, 4) + 7), 9) + 4!) \\ 497444 &:= (C(((4!)/(-4) + ((4 \times 7))), 9) + 4!) \\ 497446 &:= (-6) + (C(4!, (-((4-7)!)) + ((9! - 4!)))) \\ 497448 &:= ((84 \times 47) \times C(9,4)) \\ 497574 &:= (C(4!, 7) + ((5! \times (7! + 9))/4)) \\ 498967 &:= (C(7,6) - (-9) \times (8! + (9!/4!))) \\ 499676 &:= (6! + (((C(7,6))! \times 99) - 4)) \\ 499677 &:= (((-7) - (C(7,6))!) \times (-99)) + 4! \\ 500424 &:= (((C(4,2))! - 4!) \times (-0!) + ((0! + 5)!)) \\ 502389 &:= (9 \times (8! - ((3 - C(20,5)))) \\ 503275 &:= (-5) + ((-C(7,2) + 3!) \times ((0! + (5)!))) \\ 503276 &:= (((6! - (C(7,2))) \times 3!) + ((0! - (5)))) \\ 503879 &:= (9! + ((7! \times C(8,3!)) - (0! + 5!))) \\ 504735 &:= (((5+3) + 7) \times C((4! - 0!), 5)) \\ 504855 &:= (5! + ((5!/8) \times C((4! - 0!), 5)) \\ 507324 &:= (-C(4!, 2) - (3! \times (-705))) \\ 507628 &:= (C(8,2) - (6! \times (-705))) \\ 510474 &:= ((4 \times 7!) + C((4! - 0!), 15)) \\ 511345 &:= (((-C(5,4) + 3!)^{1+1}) + 5!) \\ 512638 &:= (((-8) + 3!) \times 6!) - C(2, (1^5)) \\ 513246 &:= (((6! - C(4,2)) \times 3!) - 1) - 5! \\ 513247 &:= ((7 - ((C(4,2))! \times 3!)) \times (1 - 5!)) \\ 516235 &:= (-5 - ((C(3,2) - 6!) \times ((1+5)!)) \\ 516236 &:= (((6! - C(3,2)) \times 6!) + ((1-5))) \\ 516242 &:= ((-2 + (C(4,2))!) \times (6! - (1^5))) \\ 518267 &:= (-7) + ((6!^2) - (C((8+1), 5))) \\ 518274 &:= ((((-((4-7)!))!)^2) - C((8+1), 5)) \\ 518324 &:= (((C(4,2))! \times 3!) - (81 - 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 518344 &:= ((4 \times (C(4!, 3!) - ((8-1)!)) + 5!) \\ 518362 &:= (2 - (((-6!) \times 3!) + (C(8,1) \times 5))) \\ 518367 &:= (7 - (((-6!) \times 3!) + (C(8,1) \times 5))) \\ 518368 &:= (8 - (((-6!) \times 3!) + (C(8,1) \times 5))) \\ 518369 &:= (9 - (((-6!) \times 3!) + (C(8,1) \times 5))) \\ 518399 &:= (-C(9,9) + ((3!)^{8-1-5})) \\ 518413 &:= ((3! \times ((-((1-4)!))!) + (C(8,1) + 5)) \\ 518428 &:= (C(8,2) + (((4!/8)!))! \times ((1+5)!)) \\ 518466 &:= (((6! \times 6!) - 4) + C(8, -((1-5))) \\ 518526 &:= (((6!^2) + 5!) + ((C(8,1) - 5)!)) \\ 518533 &:= ((3! \times 3!) + (5! + (C(8,1) + 5))) \\ 519036 &:= ((6! \times (3! + 0!)) - C(9, (1+5))) \\ 519961 &:= (((1+6!)^{C(9,9)+1}) + 5!) \\ 522734 &:= (((4! + 3!) - C(7,2))^2 + 5) \\ 523368 &:= (((8+6!) \times 3!) - (C((3! \times 2), 5))) \\ 523436 &:= ((6! \times 3!) - (C(4,3) - ((2+5)!)) \\ 524155 &:= (-5 - (5! \times (-C(((1 \times 4)^2), 5)))) \\ 524748 &:= ((8! + C(4!, ((7-4)!)) \times (-2-5))) \\ 524885 &:= (((5+8) \times 8!) + (C(4,2)!)) + 5) \\ 525605 &:= (((5+0!)! \times (6! + C(5,2))) + 5) \\ 525606 &:= (6 \times (0! + ((6! + C(5,2)) \times 5!)) \\ 525623 &:= (C(3,2) + (((6! + 5)^2) - 5)) \\ 525624 &:= (-C(4,2) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525634 &:= (C(4,3) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525637 &:= (C(7,3!) + (((6! + 5)^2) + 5)) \\ 525654 &:= (4! + (((5 + (C(6,5))!)^2) + 5)) \\ 526844 &:= (-4 + (4! \times (C(8,6)^{-2+5})) \\ 526848 &:= (((8-4)! \times (C(8,6)^{-2+5})) \\ 526956 &:= (((C(6,5))! + ((9-6)!^2) - 5!) \\ 528504 &:= -((4! + ((0! + 5!) \times (-C((8 \times 2), 5)))) \\ 528519 &:= (-9) + (((-1) - 5!) \times (-C((8 \times 2), 5))) \\ 528675 &:= (((-5) + 7!) \times (-C(6, (8/2))) + 5!) \\ 529439 &:= ((9^3!) - C(-((4 - (9 \times 2))), 5)) \\ 531446 &:= (((-C(6,4) + 4!)^{(1 \times 3)!}) + 5)) \\ 532233 &:= (((3^3!)^2) + C((2 \times 3!), 5)) \\ 532344 &:= (((4! \times 4!) \times C((3! \times 2), 3!)) + 5!) \\ 532368 &:= (((-((8! \times C((6+3!), 2))) - (3!)!)/(-5)) \\ 532644 &:= (-4 \times (-C(4!, 6) - ((-2 \times 3!) + 5))) \\ 532775 &:= (((5 + (7! \times (-C(7,2)))) - 3!) \times (-5)) \\ 532906 &:= (((6! + 0!) + 9)^2 + C(3!, 5)) \\ 533344 &:= ((4 \times C(4!, 3!)) - ((3!/3) + 5)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 533364 &:= (C((4! - 6), 3!) + (3!! \times (3!! - 5))) \\
 533525 &:= (((C((5 + 2), 5) + 3!!) \times 3!!) + 5) \\
 534249 &:= ((9^{C(4,2)}) - (4! \times (3 - 5!))) \\
 534456 &:= (((6 + 5) \times 4!) \times C(4!, 3) + 5!) \\
 534492 &:= (-((2 \times 9)) \times (C(4!, 4) - ((3 + 5)!))) \\
 534664 &:= (((C(4!, 6) - 6!) \times 4) - 3!!) - 5! \\
 535599 &:= (9 \times (9^5) + C((5 + 3!), 5)) \\
 535644 &:= ((-4 \times (-((C(4!, 6) + 5)) + 3!!)) + 5!) \\
 535848 &:= (8 \times ((C(4!, 8) / (5 + 3!)) + 5!)) \\
 536344 &:= ((4 \times C(4!, 3!)) + ((6! \times (-3)) + 5!)) \\
 536944 &:= (4 \times (C(4!, ((9 - 6)!)) + (-3 \times 5!))) \\
 537821 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 537823 &:= (-((3 - 2)) + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 537828 &:= ((8/2) + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 537844 &:= ((4! - 4) + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 537848 &:= (((8 - 4)! + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 537888 &:= ((8 \times 8) + ((C(8, 7) + 3!)^5)) \\
 538244 &:= (4 \times (C(4!, -((2 - 8))) - 35)) \\
 538264 &:= ((4 \times C(((6/2) \times 8), 3!)) - 5!) \\
 538344 &:= (4 \times (C(4!, 3!) - ((8 - 3) + 5))) \\
 538364 &:= (4 \times (C(((6 - 3) \times 8), 3!) - 5)) \\
 538404 &:= (4 \times (C((((0 - 4) + 8)!, 3!) + 5)) \\
 538444 &:= (4 \times (C(4!, ((4!/8)!) + (3 \times 5))) \\
 538504 &:= ((4 \times C(((0! - ((5 - 8)))!, 3!)) + 5!) \\
 538544 &:= (((C(4, 4) + 5)!) + ((8 + 3!)^5)) \\
 539644 &:= (4 \times (C(4!, 6) + (9 \times 35))) \\
 540276 &:= (6 \times (7! - (2 \times (0! - C(4!, 5)))))) \\
 543069 &:= ((9^6) + C(((0! - 3!) + 4!), 5)) \\
 543427 &:= ((7! - 2) - ((C(4!, 3!) \times (-4)) - (5))) \\
 543429 &:= (((9 - 2)!) - ((C(4!, 3!) \times (-4)) - (5))) \\
 543476 &:= (((6! + (C(7, 4))) \times 3!!) + (-4 - 5!)) \\
 543924 &:= -((C(4!, 2) - ((9! \times 3!) / 4) - 5!)) \\
 543934 &:= (((C(4!, 3) - (9! \times 3!)) / (-4)) + 5!) \\
 544368 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times ((3!)! + ((C(4!, 4) - (5)))))) \\
 544439 &:= (((9! \times 3!) / 4) - C(4, 4) + 5!) \\
 544984 &:= ((4! + (8! / 9)) \times (C(4, 4) + 5!)) \\
 547349 &:= ((-C(9, 4)) \times ((3!)! - ((7! + 4!))) + (5)) \\
 548344 &:= ((4 \times C(4!, 3!)) - ((8! / (-4)) + 5!)) \\
 548464 &:= ((C(4!, 6) \times 4) + (84 \times 5!)) \\
 548859 &:= (((C(9, 5) + 8) \times (8^4)) - 5) \\
 554112 &:= ((2 + 11) \times (C(4!, 5) + 5!)) \\
 558719 &:= (((((9 + 1)!) / 7) + 8!) - C(5, 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 558726 &:= (((6!^2) + (7)) + 8!) - C(5, 5) \\
 559671 &:= (((-1 - (C(7, 6)!) \times (9 - 5!)) + 5!) \\
 562464 &:= (((4! + 6!) \times (-C(4, 2))) \times (-6 - 5!)) \\
 563688 &:= ((8! \times (8 + 6)) - C((3! + (6)), 5)) \\
 564474 &:= (((-4 \times 7!) \times (-4 - 4!)) - C(6, 5)) \\
 564485 &:= (((5! - 8) \times ((C(4, 4) + 6)!) + (5)) \\
 564486 &:= (((6 + 8) \times ((4 + 4)!) + C(6, 5)) \\
 564768 &:= ((C(8, 6) \times ((7! \times 4) + (6))) + 5!) \\
 569407 &:= ((7! - 0!) \times (4! + ((C(9, 6) + 5)))) \\
 570235 &:= (-5 - (3!! \times (-C((-2 \times (0! - 7)), 5)))) \\
 571438 &:= ((C(8, 3!) + ((4 - 1)!) \times (7^5)) \\
 572736 &:= (-C((6 \times 3), 7) - ((2 - 7!) \times 5!)) \\
 573954 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (9 + (3^{7+5}))) \\
 575784 &:= (((((4!/8)!)! + 7) \times C((5 + 7), 5)) \\
 576699 &:= (((9 \times 9) + 6!) \times 6! - (C(7, 5))) \\
 579349 &:= -((9! + (((C(4!, 3!) - 9) \times (-7)) - 5!))) \\
 579488 &:= (((8 \times (-C(8, 4) + 9!)) - 7!) / 5) \\
 579498 &:= (-((8 - C(9, 4))) \times ((-9) + 7!) - 5!)) \\
 583443 &:= (((-3 + 4!)^{C(4,3)}) \times (8 - 5)) \\
 583674 &:= (C(4!, 7) + (-6 \times (3!! - ((8! - 5)))))) \\
 584577 &:= (-7) + ((7! \times (5! - 4)) - C(8, 5)) \\
 584645 &:= (((5! - 4) \times ((C(6, 4) - 8)!) + 5) \\
 588672 &:= (((((2 + C(7, 6))!) \times (-8)) - 8!) / (-5)) \\
 589675 &:= (-5) - ((C(7, 6)!) \times (-9 \times (8 + 5)))) \\
 589849 &:= ((9 \times ((4^8) + 9)) - C(8, 5)) \\
 591164 &:= ((C(4!, 6) \times (-1)) + (((1 + 9)!) / 5)) \\
 593655 &:= -((5! - (5 \times C((C(6, 3) + 9), 5)))) \\
 594175 &:= (((5! \times 7!) + 1) - C(4!, (9 - 5))) \\
 595048 &:= (-8) - (C(4!, 05) \times (-9 + 5))) \\
 595053 &:= (-3 - (C(((5 - 0)!)!, 5) \times (-9 + 5))) \\
 595056 &:= (C((-6) \times (-5) + 0!), 5) \times (9 + 5) \\
 595434 &:= (((4! + 3) + C(4!, 5)) \times (9 + 5)) \\
 595584 &:= (4! \times (8! - C(-(5 \times (5 - 9)), 5))) \\
 595776 &:= (6! + ((7 + 7) \times C((-((5 - 9)!)!, 5))) \\
 596165 &:= (((5 \times (C(6, 1)^6) + 9!) + 5) \\
 596757 &:= (((7! \times 5!) - 7!) - (C((6 + 9), 5))) \\
 597368 &:= ((-8) + 6!) \times ((3!)! - ((7 - C(9, 5)))) \\
 599165 &:= ((5 - ((6 + 1)!) \times (C(9, 9) - 5!)) \\
 599515 &:= ((5! \times (C(15, 9) - 9)) - 5) \\
 599522 &:= ((2 - ((2 + 5)!) \times (C(9, 9) - 5!)) \\
 599527 &:= (((7! - 2) \times (5! - C(9, 9))) + (5)) \\
 599675 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - C((6 + 9), 9)) - 5!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 599697 := $(-7) \times (9 + (6! \times (C(9,9) - 5!)))$
599733 := $(-(3^3) + (7! \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)))$
599744 := $(-(4 \times 4) + (7! \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)))$
599748 := $(-(8 + 4) + (7! \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)))$
599773 := $((3! + 7) + (7! \times (-C(9,9) + 5!)))$
599879 := $((-9) - 7!) + 8 \times (C(9,9) - 5!)$
604524 := $(-C(4!,2) - (-5!) \times (((4 \times 0)! + 6)!))$
604738 := $(-C(8,3) - ((-7!) \times ((4 + 0)!)) + (6))$
604823 := $((C(3!,2) \times 8!) + 4!) - ((0 \times 6)!)$
604828 := $(C(8,2) + (840 \times 6!))$
604846 := $((C(6,4) \times 8!) + (40 + 6))$
604875 := $((5! \times 7!) + C(8,4) - 0!) + (6)$
605645 := $(C(5,4) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)))$
605668 := $(C(8,6) + ((6! + 5!) \times (0! + 6!)))$
606403 := $((3! \times C(-(0! - 4!),6) + (0! + 6!))$
615426 := $(C(((6 - 2)! , 4) + (5! \times ((1 + 6)!))$
617822 := $(C(((2 + 2)! , 8) - (C(7,1)^6))$
618624 := $((C(4!,2) \times 6) - 8!) \times (-16)$
622944 := $((4! \times (-4 \times 9)) \times (-C(2,2) - 6!))$
624468 := $((8! - ((-6) \times C(4!,4) - 2)) \times 6)$
627234 := $(-((4! - ((C((3! \times 2),7)^2) - 6)))$
627249 := $(-9) + ((C((4!/2),7)^2) - (6))$
627258 := $((C(((8 - 5)! \times 2),7)^2) - (6))$
627845 := $(C(5,4) - (-872) \times 6!)$
627868 := $(C(8,6) - (-872) \times 6!)$
627977 := $(-(7^7) + (C(9,7) \times ((2 + 6)!))$
631344 := $(4! \times ((C(4!,3) \times 13) - 6))$
633597 := $((7! \times C(9,5) - 3!) + (-3 - 6!))$
633604 := $(4 \times (0! + (C((6 + 3!),3) \times 6!))$
633744 := $(-((4! + (C(4!,7)/(-3)))) - (3! \times (-6!))$
634524 := $(C(4!,2) \times (-5 + ((4!^3)/6))$
634572 := $((2 + 7!) \times ((C(5,4)! + 3!) - 6!)$
634917 := $((7! - 1) \times C(9,4) - (3 - 6))$
634974 := $(-((4! + (-7 \times ((9!/C(4,3) - 6))))$
635755 := $(5! + ((5! + 7) \times C((5 \times 3),6))$
635759 := $((C(9,5) \times 7!) + (5) - 3!) + 6!$
635772 := $((2 + (7! \times C(7,5))) \times 3!) + 6!$
635976 := $(-((6 - (7 \times C(9,5)))) \times (3! + 6!))$
637545 := $(((-5 \times C(4!,5)) + 7) \times (-3) + 6)$
637554 := $((C(4!,5) \times ((5 + 7) + 3)) - 6)$
639359 := $(9! + ((-5!) \times (3!) + (9! - C(3!,6))))$
639369 := $((C(9,6)^3 + 9) + (3!^6))$
643104 := $(-((C((4!/(0! + 1)),3!) \times (4! - 6!)))$
643328 := $(-((C(8,2)^3) + (((3 \times 4)!/6!))$
643836 := $(-6) \times (((3 - 8!) \times 3!) + C(4!,6))$
643942 := $((-2 + (4 \times 9!)) - (3! \times C(4!,6))$
644784 := $((4! + (C(8,7)!)) \times (4 \times 4) - 6!)$
644844 := $((4 \times 4) \times 8!) - C(4!, -((4 - 6)))$
645354 := $(C((4! - 5),3) \times (-54 + 6!))$
645926 := $(-((6! - C((-2) + ((9 - 5)!), (4 + 6))))$
646642 := $(C((-2 + 4!), (6 + 6)) - (4!/6))$
647236 := $(-6!) + ((3!^2) - ((7! - C(4!,6))))$
647342 := $((C((-2 + 4!), (3 + 7)) - 4!) + 6!$
647745 := $(C(5,4) \times ((-7 - 7!) + C(4!,6))$
647775 := $(-5) \times ((7! + C(7,7)) - C(4!,6))$
647785 := $(-5) \times (((-8) + 7!) + (7) - C(4!,6))$
647815 := $(-5 \times (((1 - 8) + 7!) - C(4!,6))$
647835 := $(-5 \times ((-((3 + 8)) + 7!) - C(4!,6))$
647855 := $(-5 \times (((5!/(-8)) + 7!) - C(4!,6))$
647925 := $(-5 \times ((-29) + 7!) - C(4!,6))$
647945 := $(5 \times ((4! + 9) - 7!) + C(4!,6))$
649368 := $((C((8 + 6),3!) \times 9) \times 4!) + 6!$
656496 := $((6! + (C(9,4))) \times (6! + (56)))$
657324 := $((C(4,2)! + 3!) + 7!) \times (5! - 6)$
657864 := $(-((4! - ((6! - 8) \times C((7 + 5),6))))$
658432 := $(-((2^{C(3!,4)} - ((8 \times 5!) \times 6!)))$
659736 := $((6! - 3!) \times (7 \times (C(9,5) + 6))$
660960 := $((6^{6-0!}) \times (C(9,6) + 0!))$
663426 := $((6! - 2) \times C((4 \times 3),6) - (6))$
663432 := $((2 - 3!) \times (-C(-(4 \times (3 - 6)),6))$
663624 := $((C(4!,2) \times (-6)) + (((3! + 6)!/6!))$
665304 := $(4! + (C(((0! + 3!) + 5),6) \times 6!))$
665724 := $(-((C(4!,2) - (((7 + 5)!/6! + 6!)))$
666567 := $(C((7 + 6),5) + (((6 + 6)!/6!))$
670321 := $((12! / 3!) + ((0! + (C(7,6)!))$
671589 := $(9 \times (8 + C((5 + 17),6))$
671748 := $(C((8 + 4), (7 - 1)) \times (7 + 6!))$
672945 := $(5 \times (C(4!, (9 \times 2)) - C(7,6))$
672955 := $(-5 \times (5 - C(((9 + 2) - 7)! , 6))$
673045 := $(5 \times (C(4!, (03!)) + (7 + 6))$
673135 := $(-5 \times (-31 - C((-((3 - 7)! , 6))$
673345 := $(5 \times (C(4!,3!) - (3 - 76))$
673555 := $(-5 \times ((5 - 5!) - C((-((3 - 7)! , 6))$
673596 := $((6! + 9) \times C((5!/(3 + 7)),6))$

$$\begin{aligned} 673735 &:= ((5 \times (C(-(3-7))!, 3!) + 7)) + 6!) \\ 673919 &:= ((9! - 1) - ((9! \times 3!) / (-C(7, 6)))) \\ 674645 &:= (C(5, 4) \times ((6! \times 4!) + ((7^6)))) \\ 675366 &:= (((-((6 - C(6, 3))) + 5!) \times 7!) + (6)) \\ 675384 &:= (4! - (((-8 - 3!) - 5!) \times (C(7, 6)!))) \\ 676645 &:= (5 \times ((C(4!, 6) + 6!) + (7 + 6))) \\ 679239 &:= (9 \times ((C(3!, 2) \times (-9 + 7!)) + (6))) \\ 679536 &:= ((6! + 3!) \times ((5! + C(9, 7)) \times 6)) \\ 681388 &:= ((88^3) - C((1 + 8), 6)) \\ 683254 &:= -(((C(4!, 5) + 2) - ((-3 \times 8!) \times (-6)))) \\ 684723 &:= (C(3, 2) - (((7 - 4!) \times 8!) + 6!)) \\ 685457 &:= ((C(7, 5) - 4) \times ((-5) + 8!) + (6)) \\ 685468 &:= -((8! + (((6 + 4)! / (-5)) - (C(8, 6)))))) \\ 686262 &:= (((2 + C(6, 2)) \times (6 + 8!)) + 6!) \\ 691484 &:= ((-4 + 8!) - (4! \times (-C(19, 6)))) \\ 691488 &:= (8! - (((8 - 4)! \times (-C(19, 6)))) \\ 692274 &:= ((C(4!, 7) \times 2) + ((2 + 9) \times 6)) \\ 692304 &:= ((C(4!, (0! + 3!)) \times 2) + (96)) \\ 697578 &:= -(((8 - (C(C(7, 5), 7) - 9)) \times 6)) \\ 697734 &:= ((C((4! - 3), (7 + 7)) + 9) \times 6) \\ 703125 &:= ((C(5, 2) - 1) \times ((3! - 0!)^7)) \\ 703974 &:= (((C(4!, 7) + 9!) + (30)) - 7!) \\ 704492 &:= (2 \times (9! - ((C(4!, 4) + 0!) + 7))) \\ 705426 &:= (-6) + C((-2 + 4!), ((5 - 0!) + (7))) \\ 705432 &:= C((-2 + (3! \times 4)), ((5 - 0!) + 7)) \\ 705628 &:= (C(8, 2) \times (6 + (-5) \times (0! - 7!))) \\ 705768 &:= (C(8, 6) \times (((7! \times 5) - 0!) + (7))) \\ 708984 &:= (C(4!, (8 + 9)) + ((8 + ((0 \times 7)!))!)) \\ 709704 &:= ((C(4!, 07) + 9!) + (-((0! - 7)!))! \\ 715692 &:= (2 \times ((9! + C(6, 5)) - ((1 \times 7)!)) \\ 722488 &:= (8! - ((8 - (4 \times C(22, 7)))) \\ 722544 &:= -((4! - (C(4!, 5) \times (((2 + 2)! - 7)))) \\ 723573 &:= (((3 + 7)! / 5) - (C(3, 2)^7)) \\ 724893 &:= -((3! + ((9! - C(8, 4)) \times (-2)) + 7)) \\ 724939 &:= -((9! - ((3 \times (9! - C(4!, 2))) + (7)))) \\ 724968 &:= (((8 - 6) \times 9!) - C((4! / 2), 7)) \\ 725026 &:= (-6!) - (-2) \times (((0! - C(5, 2)))! - (7))) \\ 725437 &:= (-C(7, 3)) - ((4! + 5!) \times (2 - 7!)) \\ 725472 &:= (((-2 + 7!) \times 4!) \times ((C(5, 2) - 7)!)) \\ 725532 &:= (2 \times ((C(3!, 5) - 5!) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 725539 &:= (((9! + (C(3!, 5) - 5!)) \times 2) + (7)) \\ 725625 &:= (((C(5, 2))! - 6!) / 5) + (2 + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 725632 &:= ((2 \times ((3 + C(6, 5)))! - (2^7)) \\ 725634 &:= ((4! - 3!) \times (((C(6, 5) + 2)! - 7)) \\ 725709 &:= (((9! - 0!) - (C(7, 5))) \times 2) - (7)) \\ 725739 &:= (((9! \times 3) - (C(7, 5))) - ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 725743 &:= (((3! \times 4!) \times 7!) - (C(5, 2) + 7)) \\ 725754 &:= (((4! + 5!) \times 7!) - ((C(5, 2) - 7)!)) \\ 725755 &:= (-5 + ((C(5, (7 - 5)))! / (-2 - 7))) \\ 725759 &:= ((9! \times (-5 - 7)) - C((5 + 2), 7)) \\ 725778 &:= ((8! + C(7, 7)) \times ((5^2) - 7)) \\ 725781 &:= (((1 + 8)! + (C(7, 5))) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 725789 &:= ((9! + (8 + C(7, 5))) + ((2 + 7)!)) \\ 725895 &:= (((5! + 9!) - (C(8, 5))) \times 2) + (7)) \\ 725902 &:= (2 \times ((0! + 9!) + (C(5, 2) \times 7))) \\ 725924 &:= (4! + (2 \times (9! + (C(5, 2) \times 7)))) \\ 725937 &:= (((-C(7, 3)) + 9!) + 5!) \times 2) + (7)) \\ 725989 &:= (((9! - (8 - C(9, 5))) \times 2) - (7)) \\ 725993 &:= (((3! - 9!) - (C(9, 5))) \times (-2)) - 7) \\ 726552 &:= (((2 \times 5)! / 5) + C((6 \times 2), 7)) \\ 727484 &:= ((-4 + 8!) - ((C(4!, 7) \times (-2)) + 7!)) \\ 727488 &:= (8! - ((C(((8 - 4)!), 7) \times (-2)) + 7!)) \\ 728984 &:= (C(4!, 8) + ((-9 \times ((8 - 2)!)) - 7)) \\ 729435 &:= (-C((5 \times 3), 4) + ((9! \times 2) + 7!)) \\ 730112 &:= ((C(2, 1)^{10}) \times (3! - 7)) \\ 730424 &:= (((C(4!, (2 \times 4)) - 0!) - 3!) - 7!) \\ 730431 &:= (C(((1 + 3)!), (4! / 03)) - 7!) \\ 730434 &:= (C(4!, ((3 + 4) + 0!)) - (-3 + 7!)) \\ 732384 &:= (4! \times (C((8 \times 3), 2) + (3! \times 7!)) \\ 732528 &:= (8! - (-2) \times C(((5 + 2) - 3)!), 7)) \\ 732584 &:= (C(4!, 8) - ((5! \times ((-2 + 3)!)) + 7)) \\ 733284 &:= (C(4!, 8) - ((2 \times 3) - 3)^7) \\ 733484 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (C(4!, 3) - 37)) \\ 733784 &:= (C(4!, 8) - ((7! / (-3 + 3!)) + 7)) \\ 733992 &:= (2 \times (9! - (C((9 + 3), 3!) - 7!)) \\ 734356 &:= (((6! + 5!) \times 3!) + (C(4!, 3!) - 7!)) \\ 734384 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (((3! / 4) \times 3!) + 7)) \\ 734392 &:= (2 \times ((9! - 3!)) + (-C(4, 3) + 7!)) \\ 734454 &:= (-((4^5)) + (C(4!, (4! / 3)) + 7)) \\ 734744 &:= ((C(4!, (4! / (7 - 4))) - 3!) - 7) \\ 734784 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (C((-7 + 4!), 3) + 7)) \\ 734895 &:= (C((-((5 - 9)))! , 8) - (4! \times (-((3 - 7)!))!)) \\ 735184 &:= (C(4!, 8) - ((1 + (5! / 3)) \times 7)) \\ 735284 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (2 + (5 \times 37))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 735384 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (3 \times (5 + (-((3 - 7)))))) \\
 735424 &:= (C(4!, (2 \times 4)) - ((5!/3) + 7)) \\
 735434 &:= (C(4!, ((-3 + 4!) - 5)) - 37) \\
 735453 &:= -(((3! + 5) - (C(4!, (5 + 3)) - 7))) \\
 735457 &:= (-C(7, 5) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) + (7))) \\
 735458 &:= (-((8 + 5) + C(4!, C((5 + 3), 7))) \\
 735463 &:= ((3!/(-6)) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) - 7)) \\
 735465 &:= (-((5 - 6) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) - 7)) \\
 735466 &:= (-((6 + 6) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) + (7))) \\
 735469 &:= -((9 - (C((6 \times 4), (5 + 3)) + 7))) \\
 735471 &:= C(((1 + 7) - 4)!, C((5 + 3), 7)) \\
 735474 &:= (-((4 - 7) + C(4!, C((5 + 3), 7))) \\
 735477 &:= (-C(7, 7) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) + (7))) \\
 735478 &:= (C((8 \times (7 - 4)), (5 + 3)) + 7) \\
 735483 &:= (-((3 - 8) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) + 7)) \\
 735484 &:= (C(4!, 8) + (((4 + 5) - 3) + 7)) \\
 735493 &:= ((3! + 9) + (C(4!, (5 + 3)) + 7)) \\
 735495 &:= (((-((5 - 9)))! + (C(4!, C((5 + 3), 7)))) \\
 735584 &:= (C(4!, 8) + (C((5 + 5), 3) - 7)) \\
 735792 &:= (2 \times ((9! - (C(7, 5) + 3)) + 7!)) \\
 735824 &:= (C(4!, (2 \times 8)) + ((5! \times 3) - 7)) \\
 735838 &:= (C((8 \times 3), 8) - ((5! \times (-3)) - (7))) \\
 735838 &:= (C((8 \times 3), 8) - ((5! \times (-3)) - (7))) \\
 735884 &:= (C(4!, 8) + ((C(8, 5) + 3) \times 7)) \\
 735984 &:= (C(4!, 8) + ((9 - (5 \times 3!)) / (-7))) \\
 736184 &:= ((C(4!, 8) + (((1^6) \times 3)!)!) - 7) \\
 736904 &:= (((C(4!, -(0! - 9)) + 6!) + 3!) - 7) \\
 737143 &:= ((3!! \times (-((4 + 1)!)!) + (C(7, 3!)^7)) \\
 737273 &:= (((3!! + 7!) \times (2^{C(7, 3!)})) - 7) \\
 737384 &:= (C(4!, 8) - (((3!! + 7!) / (-3)) + 7)) \\
 737493 &:= ((3 \times 9!) - ((C(4!, 7) + 3) + 7!)) \\
 739644 &:= ((C((4! + 4), 6) + 9!) + (-((3 - 7)))!) \\
 739784 &:= (((C(4!, 8) + 7!) - ((9 - 3)!) - 7) \\
 740484 &:= (((C(4!, 8) - 4) + 0!) - 4!) + 7! \\
 740534 &:= (((C(4!, (3 + 5)) - 0!) + 4!) + 7! \\
 741312 &:= (((2 + 1)!)^3 \times C(14, 7)) \\
 742368 &:= ((-C(8, 6) - ((3 + 2)!) \times (4! - 7!)) \\
 742536 &:= (((6 + 3)!) \times (5 - 2)) - C(4!, 7) \\
 742539 &:= (((9! \times 3) + (5 - 2)) - C(4!, 7)) \\
 742596 &:= ((((-6) \times 9!) - 5!) / (-2)) - C(4!, 7) \\
 745328 &:= ((C(8, (2 \times 3)) + 5!) \times (-4) + 7!)) \\
 746368 &:= ((C(8, 6)^3) \times (6 + (4 \times 7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 746455 &:= (-5 - ((5! - 4) \times (-C(C(6, 4), 7)))) \\
 746489 &:= (((9! / C(8, 4)) \times 6) \times 4!) - (7) \\
 749185 &:= -((((5! - 8!) - 1) - 9!) - C(4!, 7)) \\
 749268 &:= (((8! - ((6^2))) + 9!) + C(4!, 7)) \\
 749288 &:= (((8! - ((8 \times 2))) + 9!) + C(4!, 7)) \\
 749304 &:= (((4! / 03)!) + (9! + C(4!, 7))) \\
 749307 &:= (((7 + 0!)!) - ((-3) - 9!) - C(4!, 7)) \\
 749308 &:= (((8! + 0!) + 3) + 9!) + C(4!, 7) \\
 749328 &:= ((8! + ((-2) + 3)!) + (9! + C(4!, 7))) \\
 750584 &:= (C(4!, 8) + ((5! - 0!) \times (5! + 7))) \\
 751855 &:= (C((5! / 5), 8) + (-((1 - 5))^7)) \\
 753475 &:= (-5 - (C((7 \times 4), 3!) \times (5 - 7))) \\
 754323 &:= ((3! \times (-2)) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754325 &:= (-C(5, 2) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754331 &:= (-((1 + 3)) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754333 &:= ((3! / (-3)) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754334 &:= (-((4 - 3)) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754335 &:= ((C(((5 - 3) \times 3), 4)^5) - 7!) \\
 754336 &:= (C(6, 3!) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754341 &:= (((-((1 - 4)))! + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754354 &:= ((4! - 5) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754359 &:= (((9 - 5)!) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754365 &:= ((5 \times 6) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 754383 &:= ((3! \times 8) + ((C(3!, 4)^5) - 7!)) \\
 756025 &:= ((5^2) \times (0! + (C(6, 5) \times 7!))) \\
 758535 &:= (((C(5, 3))! / 5) + ((8^5) + 7)) \\
 758543 &:= (((C(3!, 4)^5) + 8) + (5! \times (-7))) \\
 759344 &:= -((4! - (((C(4, 3))! - 9^5) - 7))) \\
 759347 &:= (-C(7, 4) + (((3! + 9)^5) + (7))) \\
 759438 &:= (C(8, 3) + (((4! - 9)^5) + (7))) \\
 759543 &:= ((C(3!, 4)^5) + (((9 - 5)!) \times 7)) \\
 760854 &:= (((-C((4 \times 5), 8)) + 0!) \times (-6) + 7!) \\
 763056 &:= (-6!) - (((5 - 0)!) \times (-C((3 \times 6), 7))) \\
 763344 &:= -((4! \times ((4! - 3!) - (C((3 \times 6), 7)))) \\
 763632 &:= (((-2 + 3)!) \times (-6 - C((3 \times 6), 7))) \\
 763824 &:= (4! \times (2 + C(((8 \times 3) - 6), 7))) \\
 764496 &:= (((-((6 - 9)))!) + ((4! \times C((4! - (6)), 7)))) \\
 765054 &:= ((C(4!, 5) - 0!) \times ((5 + 6) + 7)) \\
 765135 &:= (((C((5 \times 3), 1)^5) + 6!) + 7!) \\
 765144 &:= ((C(4!, 4) + 1) \times (5 + 67)) \\
 765453 &:= (3 \times (5! + ((C(4!, 5) \times 6) + 7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 765745 &:= ((C(5,4)! + ((7 \times ((5^6) \times 7)))) \\ 765831 &:= ((C(((1+3)!),8) + 5!) + (6 \times 7!)) \\ 766944 &:= (4! \times (C((4+9),6) + (6 \times 7!))) \\ 770751 &:= (C((-((1-5)!), (7+0!)) - (7! \times (-7))) \\ 771584 &:= (C(4!,8) - (((5! - 1) + 7!) \times (-7))) \\ 772191 &:= (C((19-1),2) \times (7! + 7)) \\ 778515 &:= -((5! + ((-1-5!) \times C((8+7),7))) \\ 778635 &:= ((5! + C(3!,6)) \times C((8+7),7)) \\ 780831 &:= ((C(((1+3)!),8) + (08!)) + 7!) \\ 780832 &:= (C((-(-2+3)!),8) + (((0! + 8!) + 7!)) \\ 786432 &:= ((2 \times 3!) \times ((4!/6)^{C(8,7)})) \\ 786584 &:= ((4! \times ((8^5) + 6)) + C(8,7)) \\ 793795 &:= (-5) + ((9! \times (-C(7,3)))/(-9+7))) \\ 794688 &:= ((8 \times (8^6)) - (C(4!,9) - 7!)) \\ 807584 &:= ((C(4!, ((8-5)!)) \times (7-0!)) + 8) \\ 813564 &:= (((4!/6) + 5!) \times (C(3,1)^8)) \\ 816489 &:= (9 \times (((C(8,4) \times 6!) + 1) + 8!)) \\ 829426 &:= -(((6!^2) - ((C(4!,9) + 2) + 8!)) \\ 829435 &:= (-5 + (3!! \times (4 \times (C(9,2) \times 8)))) \\ 829464 &:= (4! + (6! \times (4 \times (C(9,2) \times 8)))) \\ 829577 &:= (-((7^7)) + ((5 + C(9,2)) \times 8!)) \\ 830775 &:= ((-5) + 7!) \times C(((7+0!) + 3),8)) \\ 831327 &:= (-C(7,2)) \times (3!! + (13 - 8!)) \\ 831573 &:= (-3!) + (C(7,5) \times ((-1 - 3!!) + 8!)) \\ 832328 &:= (((C(8,2) + 3!)^2) \times 3!! + 8) \\ 832364 &:= ((-C(4!,6) - 3!!) + (((-2+3)! \times 8!)) \\ 834768 &:= ((8! + (-((6^7)) \times (C(4,3)!)))/(-8)) \\ 834839 &:= ((-9) - (3! \times 8!)) + (C(4!,3!) \times 8) \\ 834848 &:= (((8!/(-4)) + 8!) - C(4!,3!)) \times (-8) \\ 835725 &:= (((5^2) + 7!) \times C((5+3!),8)) \\ 836577 &:= (7! + (-C(7,5)) \times ((6! + 3) - 8!)) \\ 836676 &:= (((6+7!) \times 6) + (C(6,3) \times 8!)) \\ 837824 &:= (((C(4!, -((2-8))) + 7!) \times 3!) + 8) \\ 838656 &:= (((6+5)!)/(-6-C(8,3))) + 8! \\ 840446 &:= ((((-6) + 4!)^4) - 0!) + C(4!,8) \\ 841344 &:= (-4 \times ((C(4!, (3! - 1)) \times (-4)) - 8!)) \\ 845117 &:= (-7) \times (-((11^{C(5,4)})) + 8!)) \\ 845578 &:= (-8) + (C(7,5) \times (-54) + 8!)) \\ 846216 &:= (C((6+1),2) \times (-((6 \times 4) + 8!)) \\ 846657 &:= (C(7,5) \times ((C(6,6) - 4) + 8!)) \\ 846678 &:= (((8! - 7)) \times 6) + (C(6,4) \times 8!)) \\ 846693 &:= (-((3 \times 9)) + ((6 + C(6,4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846712 &:= ((21 \times (-((7 - C(6,4))))!) - 8) \\ 846713 &:= -(((3! + 1) - (C(7, (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846715 &:= (-5 + (C((1 \times 7), (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846732 &:= ((2 \times 3!) + (C(7, (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846735 &:= ((5 \times 3) + (C(7, (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846742 &:= ((-2 + 4!) + (C(7, (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846752 &:= ((2^5) + (C(7, (6 - 4)) \times 8!)) \\ 846768 &:= (((C(8,6) \times 7!) \times 6) + (48)) \\ 846836 &:= ((C(6,3) \times (8! + (6))) - (4 - 8!)) \\ 846864 &:= (4! \times ((6 + 8!) - ((C(6,4) - 8)!)) \\ 846936 &:= ((6^3) - (-((C(9,6)/4)) \times 8!)) \\ 847224 &:= (((C(4,2)/2) \times 7) \times (4! + 8!)) \\ 847233 &:= (3 \times (C(3,2) - (-7 \times (4! + 8!)))) \\ 847356 &:= ((C(6,5)! + ((3 \times 7) \times (-4) + 8!)) \\ 847359 &:= (((9!/5!) \times 37) + C(4!,8)) \\ 847455 &:= (((5 \times 5) - 4) \times (C(7,4) + 8!)) \\ 847575 &:= (5! + (C(7,5) \times (C(7,4) + 8!)) \\ 847727 &:= ((-((7 - C(27,7))) + 4!) - 8!) \\ 849742 &:= (-2 - (4! \times ((7! - (C(9,4))) - 8!)) \\ 861827 &:= ((C(7,2) \times ((8! - 1) + 6!)) + 8) \\ 865274 &:= (((C(4!,7)/(-2)) \times (-5)) + (6 + 8)) \\ 868624 &:= ((C((4!/2),6) + 8)^{-6+8}) \\ 869784 &:= -((C(4!, (8 + 7)) - ((9! \times 6) + 8))) \\ 874345 &:= (5 \times ((C(4!,3!) - 47) + 8!)) \\ 886862 &:= (-2 - (-((6 - C(8,6))) \times (8 - 8!)) \\ 887544 &:= (((4! \times (C(4!,5) \times 7)) - 8!)/8) \\ 888384 &:= ((4! \times (C(8,3) + 8!)) - (8! + 8!)) \\ 888734 &:= (C((4! + 3),7) + (8 \times 88)) \\ 892542 &:= ((-2 + C(4!,5)) \times (29 - 8)) \\ 892584 &:= (C((-((4 - 8)))!,5) \times (29 - 8)) \\ 892856 &:= (((((C(6,5)! + 8)^2) + 9!) - 8) \\ 892862 &:= (-2 + (((6! + 8)^2) + (C(9,8)!)) \\ 893514 &:= ((C((4! - 1), (5 + 3)) + 9!) + 8!) \\ 894313 &:= (((C(3,1)^3)^4) + 9!) - 8) \\ 894321 &:= (((1 + 2)^3)^4) + (C(9,8)!)) \\ 894339 &:= (((9^3!) - 3!) + 4!) + (C(9,8)!)) \\ 894345 &:= (((5 + 4)^3!) + 4!) + (C(9,8)!)) \\ 894465 &:= ((-5 - (-6 \times 4!)) \times C((4! - 9),8)) \\ 898344 &:= (4! \times ((-4 \times 3!!) + ((8! - C(9,8)))) \\ 899264 &:= (C(4!,C(6,2)) - ((9! \times 9)/8)) \\ 901264 &:= ((C(4!,6) \times ((2 + 1) + 0!)) + 9!) \\ 902043 &:= ((3!! - C((4! - 0!), ((2 + 0)!))!) \times (-9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 907362 &:= ((-2 + (C(6,3) \times (7! + 0!))) \times 9) \\ 908514 &:= ((C((4! - 1), -(5 - 8)))! - 0!) \times 9) \\ 908532 &:= ((C(23, -(5 - 8)))! + 0!) \times 9) \\ 908604 &:= (((C((4! - 0!), 6) + 8) + 0!) \times 9) \\ 915431 &:= ((13 \times C(4!, 5)) - (1 - 9!)) \\ 921456 &:= ((C(6, 5)^4) \times (((1 + 2))! - 9)) \\ 922386 &:= (((6! + C(8, 3!))^2) + (2 + 9!)) \\ 922756 &:= (((C(6, 5)^7) + 2) \times 2) + 9! \\ 925344 &:= (4! \times ((C((4! - 3!), 5)/2) \times 9)) \\ 927369 &:= (((9! - (-(C(6, 3)) \times 7!)) \times 2) + 9) \\ 930024 &:= (4! \times (C(20, (03)!) - 9)) \\ 930231 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times C(20, 3!)) - 9) \\ 932796 &:= (-6) \times (((9!/C(7, 2)) - 3!) \times (-9)) \\ 933129 &:= (((C(9, 2)^{-1+3}) \times (3!)!) + 9) \\ 933849 &:= ((C((9 + 4), 8) - 3!) \times ((3!)! + 9)) \\ 934667 &:= ((-(7 - (6 \times C(6, 4))))^3) + 9! \\ 935647 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 6)) - ((-5) - 3!) \times (-9)) \\ 936936 &:= (((6! - 3!) \times (-(C(9, 6) - 3!)) + 9!) \\ 938223 &:= (C((C(3!, 2) - 2), 8) \times (3!! + 9)) \\ 938943 &:= (3!! - (-(C((4 + 9), 8)) \times (3!! + 9))) \\ 941599 &:= -(((9! + ((9!/5!) + 1)) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 942347 &:= (7 \times (C(4!, 3!) + ((2^4) + 9))) \\ 942599 &:= -(((9! + ((9 \times 5)^2)) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 943488 &:= ((8! + ((8! \times 4!)/C(3!, 4))) \times 9) \\ 943859 &:= (((9 \times (-(5) - 8!)) - (3!)!) + (C(4!, 9))) \\ 943893 &:= (((-3 - 9!) - 8) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9)) \\ 943896 &:= -(((6! + 9!) + 8) - C((3! \times 4), 9)) \\ 943897 &:= (((-7) - (C(9, 8))!) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9)) \\ 943902 &:= (((-2 - (09)!) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9))) \\ 943903 &:= ((-(((3 \times 0)!) + 9!) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9))) \\ 943904 &:= (((4 \times 0) - 9!) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9)) \\ 943905 &:= (((((5 \times 0)!) - 9!) - 3!!) + (C(4!, 9))) \\ 943906 &:= -((((6! + 0!) + 9!) - 3) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 943907 &:= -((((7 - 0!)!) + (((9! - 3) - C(4!, 9)))) \\ 943928 &:= ((C(((8/2)!)!, 9) - 3!!) + ((4! - 9!)) \\ 943934 &:= ((4! - 3!!) - ((9! - 3!) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 944504 &:= -((((4 + 0!)!) + (((5 + 4)!) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 944505 &:= -((((5! - 0!) + ((5 + 4)!) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 944508 &:= -((((8 + 0!)!) + ((5! - (4)) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 944509 &:= -((((9! - 0!) + 5!) - (4)) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 944543 &:= ((-(3^4) - ((5 + 4)!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 944579 &:= -(((9! + (C(7, 5))) + 4!) - C(4!, 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 944592 &:= (((-2 - 9!) - (5!/4)) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 944594 &:= (((C(4!, 9) - (54)) + 4!) - 9!) \\ 944597 &:= (((-7) - 9!) - ((5 \times 4))) + C(4!, 9) \\ 944609 &:= -(((9! + C(06, 4)) - C(4!, 9))) \\ 944617 &:= (((-7) - (-(1 - 6) - 4))!) + (C(4!, 9)) \\ 944618 &:= -((((8 + 1)!) + (6)) - C(4!, (4! - 9))) \\ 944619 &:= -(((9! + ((1^6) + 4)) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 944624 &:= (C(4!, ((2 + 6) + C(4, 4))) - 9!) \\ 944628 &:= ((C(((8/2)!)!, C(6, 4)) + (4)) - 9!) \\ 944639 &:= (((-9) - ((3 + 6)!) + 4!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 944644 &:= (4! + ((C(4!, C(6, 4)) - 4) - 9!)) \\ 944648 &:= ((C(((8 - 4)!)!, C(6, 4)) + 4!) - 9!) \\ 944654 &:= -((((4 + 5)!) - 6) - 4!) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 944659 &:= -(((9! - (5 + 6)) - 4!) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 944791 &:= (((-1 - 9!) + (7 \times 4!)) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 944924 &:= ((C(4!, 2) - 9!) + 4!) + C(4!, 9) \\ 945339 &:= -(((9! - ((3 + 3)!) + (5)) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 945589 &:= -(((9! + ((-8) \times 5!) - (5))) - C(4!, 9)) \\ 946395 &:= ((-5) \times (9^3)) + ((C(6, 4)!/9!) \\ 948393 &:= (((3!! - (-(C(9, 3)) + 8!)) \times (-4!)) + 9) \\ 948936 &:= (((6! \times 3!) - 9!) - 8) + C(4!, 9) \\ 949664 &:= (((((4 + 6)!)! / 6!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949704 &:= (((40 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949715 &:= (((51 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949726 &:= (((62 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949728 &:= (((8^2) + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9) \\ 949737 &:= (((73 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949748 &:= (((84 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 949759 &:= (((95 + 7!) - 9!) + C(4!, 9)) \\ 953564 &:= -(((C(4!, 6) + 5!) - (-3 \times (5! - 9!))) \\ 953684 &:= -(((C(-(4 - 8))!)!, 6) - (-3 \times (5! - 9!))) \\ 954729 &:= (((C((9 \times 2), 7)/4) \times 5!) + 9) \\ 954742 &:= (-2 + (((4! + 7) \times C(4!, 5)) - 9!)) \\ 957054 &:= -((C(4!, (5 - 0!)) - ((7! \times 5!) + 9!)) \\ 957744 &:= (((4! \times 4!) + (7! \times C(7, 5))) \times 9) \\ 962675 &:= (((5! \times 7!) - C(C(6, 2), 6)) + 9!) \\ 962684 &:= ((4! \times 8!) - ((C(C(6, 2), 6) - 9))) \\ 963738 &:= -((8 - C((3 \times 7), 3)) \times (6! + 9)) \\ 964785 &:= -((((5! - (C(8, 7))!) \times 4!) + (6 + 9)) \\ 967488 &:= (((-8) + 8!) \times (C(4, ((7 - 6)^9)))! \\ 967555 &:= (((-5 - 5!) + ((5! \times (C(7, 6))!) + 9!)) \\ 967599 &:= -(((9 \times 9) + ((5! \times (C(7, 6))!) + 9!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 967659 &:= (((C(9,5) - (6! \times 7!))/(-6)) + 9!) \\
 967673 &:= (((((3+7)!/6) - C(7,6)) + 9!) \\
 967696 &:= (((6+9!)/6) \times (C(7,6) + 9)) \\
 967728 &:= ((8! + 2) \times (((C(7,7) - 6) + 9))!) \\
 967784 &:= ((4! \times (8! + C(7,7))) - (6!/(-9))) \\
 967815 &:= (((5-1)! \times ((C(8,7))! + 6)) - 9) \\
 967824 &:= ((C(4,2) + 8!) \times (((7+6) - 9))!) \\
 967854 &:= ((4! \times (5 + (C(8,7))!)) + (6 \times 9)) \\
 967894 &:= ((4! \times (9 + 8!)) + ((C(7,6) - 9))) \\
 968346 &:= (6! + (((C(4,3))! \times 8!) - ((6 \times 9))) \\
 968428 &:= ((C(8,2) + (4! \times 8!)) + (((-((6-9))!))!)) \\
 975688 &:= (C((8+8),6) + ((5! \times 7!) + 9!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 984384 &:= (((-((4! - 8!)) + 3!)) \times C(4!, -((8-9)))) \\
 984938 &:= (((8! - 3!) - 9!) + C((-((4-8))!, 9)) \\
 987588 &:= -((C(8, ((8-5))!) \times ((7! - 8!) + 9))) \\
 987768 &:= (((C(8,6) \times 7!) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 987868 &:= (C(8,6) \times ((8! - 7!) - ((8-9)))) \\
 989984 &:= (C((-((4-8))!), 9) - ((9!/(-8)) + 9!)) \\
 994822 &:= (2 \times (C((-2 + ((8-4))!), 9) - 9)) \\
 995324 &:= (4 \times (((2 \times 3!)^5) - C(9,9))) \\
 996732 &:= (2 \times ((3! - (C(7,6))!) \times (-99))) \\
 997942 &:= ((2-4!) \times ((-9 \times 7!) - C(9,9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers using square-root** in reverse order of digits. The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

4.3.1 Symmetrical Representations

$$\begin{aligned}
 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
 376740 &:= 0 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376741 &:= 1 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376742 &:= 2 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376743 &:= 3 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 376744 &:= 4 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376745 &:= 5 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376746 &:= 6 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376747 &:= 7 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376748 &:= 8 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 376749 &:= 9 + C(4 \times 7, \sqrt{\sqrt{6^7-3}}) \\
 394680 &:= 0 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394681 &:= 1 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394682 &:= 2 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394683 &:= 3 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394684 &:= 4 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394685 &:= 5 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3 \\
 394686 &:= 6 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$394687 := 7 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3$$

$$394688 := 8 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3$$

$$394689 := 9 + C(C(8,6), \sqrt{49}) / 3$$

4.3.2 Non Symmetric Representations

$$6435 := C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6)$$

$$9261 := C(1 + 6, 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$06435 := C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 60)$$

$$15502 := C(20, 5) - \sqrt{5-1}$$

$$27648 := \sqrt{8^4} \times 6 \times 72$$

$$32928 := C(8, 2)^{\sqrt{9}} / 2 \times 3$$

$$35937 := (C(7, 3) - \sqrt{9-5})^3$$

$$44521 := (1 + C(2 \times 5, 4))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$45927 := C(7, 2) \times \sqrt{9^{5+\sqrt{4}}}$$

$$46628 := -C(8, 2) + \sqrt{6^{6 \times \sqrt{4}}}$$

$$46655 := C(5, 5) + 6^6 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$48384 := (4 + 8)^3 \times C(8, \sqrt{4})$$

$$58993 := 3^9 \times \sqrt{9} - C(8, 5)$$

$$59974 := -\sqrt{4} + 7 \times C(9 + 9, 5)$$

$$59979 := \sqrt{9} + 7 \times C(9 + 9, 5)$$

$$59997 := 7 \times (\sqrt{9} + C(9 + 9, 5))$$

$$74384 := \sqrt{4} + C(8 \times 3, 4) \times 7$$

$$74622 := C(22, 6) + \sqrt{4} + 7$$

$$91125 := C(C(5, 2), 1 + 1)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$93294 := \sqrt{4} \times (C(9, 2)^3 - 9)$$

$$97979 := (C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 9) + 7) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$98280 := 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$015635 := 5^{C(\sqrt{36}, 5)} + 10$$

$$016394 := \sqrt{4^{C(9, 3)/6}} + 10$$

$$031794 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 9, 7) - 1 \times 30$$

$$039468 := C(C(8, 6), \sqrt{49}) / 30$$

$$083968 := \sqrt{8^6} \times (C(9, 3) + 80)$$

$$104968 := -8 + (6 \times \sqrt{9})^{C(4, 01)}$$

$$113859 := 9 \times C(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}, 3 + 1) + 1$$

$$116279 := C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 2 + 6 - 1) - 1$$

$$125965 := -5 + C(C(6, \sqrt{9}), 5 + 2 + 1)$$

$$129947 := 7 \times C(\sqrt{4} \times 9, \sqrt{C(9, 2)}) - 1$$

$$135408 := C(8 \times \sqrt{04}, 5) \times 31$$

$$139536 := C(C(6, 3), 5) \times \sqrt{9^{3-1}}$$

$$139947 := (-7 + (4 \times 9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times C(3, 1)$$

$$139962 := (-2 + 6^{9-\sqrt{9}}) \times C(3, 1)$$

$$147454 := (4 + 5) \times 4^7 - \sqrt{C(4, 1)}$$

$$147456 := (6 + 54 \times 7)^{\sqrt{C(4, 1)}}$$

$$147474 := (\sqrt{4} + 7) \times (4^7 + \sqrt{C(4, 1)})$$

$$148176 := (6 \times 7)^{\sqrt{1+8}} \times \sqrt{C(4, 1)}$$

$$149224 := \sqrt{4} \times (C(22, \sqrt{9} \times 4) - 1)$$

$$162791 := \sqrt{1 \times 9} \times C(C(7, 2), 6) - 1$$

$$162792 := 2^{\sqrt{9}} \times C(C(7, 2), 6 - 1)$$

$$162793 := 3 \times C(\sqrt{9 \times 7^2}, 6) + 1$$

$$162794 := \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \times C(C(7, 2), 6) \times 1$$

$$169984 := 4 \times 8^{\sqrt{9}} \times (C(9, 6) - 1)$$

$$170544 := C(\sqrt{4} + 4 \times 5, C(07, 1))$$

$$170544 := C(\sqrt{4} + 4 \times 5, C(07, 1))$$

$$194474 := -4 + (C(7, \sqrt{4})^4 - \sqrt{9}) \times 1$$

$$194474 := -4 + C(7, \sqrt{4})^4 - \sqrt{9} \times 1$$

$$194475 := -5 + C(7, \sqrt{4})^{C(4, \sqrt{9})} - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}194475 &:= -5 + C(7, \sqrt{4})^{C(4, \sqrt{9})} - 1 \\194476 &:= -6 + C(7, \sqrt{4})^{C(4, \sqrt{9})} + 1 \\194476 &:= -6 + C(7, \sqrt{4})^{C(4, \sqrt{9})} + 1 \\194481 &:= C(-1 + 8, \sqrt{4})^{-4+9-1} \\194484 &:= 4 \times (C(8 \times \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4}, 9) + 1) \\194574 &:= \sqrt{4} + C(7, 5)^4 + 91 \\194672 &:= 2 \times (7 \times 6 + 4)^{\sqrt{C(9,1)}} \\196548 &:= (C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 5) - 6) \times (\sqrt{9} - 1) \\219961 &:= (C(16, \sqrt{9}) - 91)^2 \\224768 &:= \sqrt{8^6} \times (C(7, \sqrt{4})^2 - 2) \\225794 &:= \sqrt{4^9} \times C(7, 5)^2 + 2 \\234259 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + 5^2)^4 + C(3, 2) \\244985 &:= -5 \times 8 + C(\sqrt{9} \times 4, 4)^2 \\262149 &:= \sqrt{9} + (C(4, 1) \times 2)^6 + 2 \\264537 &:= C(7 \times 3, 5) \times (-\sqrt{4} + C(6, 2)) \\269184 &:= (-4 + C(8 \times 1 \times \sqrt{9}, 6)) \times 2 \\269186 &:= -6 + C(8 \times 1 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) \times 2 \\269189 &:= -\sqrt{9} + C(8 \times 1 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) \times 2 \\269191 &:= -1 + C(\sqrt{9} \times (-1 + 9), 6) \times 2 \\269192 &:= C(2 + \sqrt{9} + 19, 6) \times 2 \\269194 &:= \sqrt{4} + C(\sqrt{9} \times (-1 + 9), 6) \times 2 \\279726 &:= \sqrt{6^{2 \times 7}} - C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, 2) \\279957 &:= C(7, 5) + (9 - \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{7^2}} \\293925 &:= -5 + C(2 \times 9 + 3, \sqrt{9^2}) \\293929 &:= -\sqrt{9} + C(2 \times 9 + 3, 9) + 2 \\293957 &:= C(C(7, 5), 9) + \sqrt{(3 \times 9)^2} \\294835 &:= -5 + 3 \times C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), \sqrt{9} + 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}295239 &:= 9^{3+2} \times 5 - \sqrt{C(9, 2)} \\295255 &:= 5 \times ((5 - 2)^{C(5, \sqrt{9})} + 2) \\295275 &:= 5 \times ((7 + 2)^5 + \sqrt{C(9, 2)}) \\296352 &:= C((-2 + 5) \times 3, 6)^{\sqrt{9}} / 2 \\296595 &:= 5 \times (9 \times 5 - 6)^{C(\sqrt{9}, 2)} \\299568 &:= 8 \times (6 \times (-5 + C(9, \sqrt{9})))^2 \\332744 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (C(4 + 7, 2)^3 - 3) \\339768 &:= C(8 + 6, 7) \times \sqrt{9} \times 33 \\342872 &:= -2^7 + C(8, \sqrt{2^4})^3 \\342995 &:= -5 + C(9 - \sqrt{9} + 2, 4)^3 \\342997 &:= C(7, \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \times 2 \times 4 - 3 \\344344 &:= C(4 \times 4, 3 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 43 \\344569 &:= (9 \times 65 + \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{C(4, 3)}} \\352714 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times 1 + C(C(7, 2), C(5, 3)) \\352719 &:= \sqrt{9} + C(C(1 \times 7, 2), C(5, 3)) \\352967 &:= 7^6 \times \sqrt{9} + 2 \times C(5, 3) \\352974 &:= (4 + 7\sqrt{C(9, 2)} + 5) \times 3 \\354279 &:= (9^{7-2} \times \sqrt{4} - 5) \times 3 \\354294 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (C(9, 2) / 4)^5 \times 3 \\366795 &:= C(5 \times \sqrt{9}, 7) \times (-6 + 63) \\367398 &:= (C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times 3^7 - 6) \times 3 \\372968 &:= 8 \times (6\sqrt{C(9, 2)} - C(7, 3)) \\376719 &:= C((\sqrt{9} + 1) \times 7, 6) - 7 \times 3 \\376738 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{-3 + 7}), 6) - \sqrt{7 - 3} \\376761 &:= C(\sqrt{16} \times 7, 6) + 7 \times 3 \\388949 &:= C(9 \times \sqrt{4}, 9) \times 8 - 8 - 3 \\389073 &:= (3 + 70)^{\sqrt{9}} + C(8, 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$389344 := 4 \times \left(43 + \sqrt{C(9,8)} \right)^3$$

$$389485 := 5^8 - C(4 \times \sqrt{9} + 8, 3)$$

$$389785 := 5^8 - C(7, \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \times 3$$

$$389945 := 5^{\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}}} - C(9 + 8, 3)$$

$$393659 := (9^5 \times C(6,3) - \sqrt{9}) / 3$$

$$393849 := (C(9 \times \sqrt{4}, 8) \times 3 + 9) \times 3$$

$$394385 := (\sqrt{5^8} + 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + C(\sqrt{9}, 3)$$

$$397535 := 5 \times (3 + 5 + C(7, \sqrt{9}))^3$$

$$415872 := 2^7 \times (C(8,5) + 1)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$426888 := C(88/8, 6)^2 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$426892 := 2 \times (C(\sqrt{9} + 8, 6)^2 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$434128 := 8 \times (C(21, \sqrt{4} \times 3) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$436548 := C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times (5^6 - 34)$$

$$438972 := (C(2 + 7, \sqrt{9}) - 8)^3 - 4$$

$$438974 := (C(\sqrt{4} + 7, \sqrt{9}) - 8)^3 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$444528 := C(8, 2) \times C(5 + 4, 4)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$445536 := C(6 \times 3, 5) \times (54 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$458696 := (C(6, \sqrt{9}) - 6) \times (8^5 - 4)$$

$$458764 := \sqrt{4} \times (6 + 7 \times 8^{C(5,4)})$$

$$467544 := 44 \times C(\sqrt{576}, 4)$$

$$472396 := 6^{\sqrt{9}} \times C(3, 2)^7 + 4$$

$$474474 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4) \times 474$$

$$474587 := 78^{\sqrt{5+4}} + C(7, 4)$$

$$474756 := 6 \times (5^7 + C(\sqrt{4} \times 7, 4))$$

$$497025 := (5 + 20 \times C(7, \sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$497418 := C(8 \times 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 7, 9) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$499113 := 3 \times (C(11, 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 4)$$

$$499119 := \sqrt{9} \times (C(11, 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{4})$$

$$524298 := 8^{\sqrt{C(9,2)}} \times \sqrt{4} + 2 \times 5$$

$$531446 := (6/\sqrt{4})^{C(4,1) \times 3} + 5$$

$$544475 := 5 \times (C(7 + 4, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} - 5)$$

$$544495 := -5 + C(9 + \sqrt{4}, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$547757 := 7 \times (5^7 + C(7 + \sqrt{4}, 5))$$

$$589779 := 9 \times (C(7, 7) + \sqrt{9})^8 - 5$$

$$589819 := (\sqrt{9} + 1)^8 \times C(9, 8) - 5$$

$$589829 := 9 \times C(\sqrt{2 \times 8}, \sqrt{9})^8 + 5$$

$$592697 := -7 + C(9, 6)^{2^{\sqrt{9}} - 5}$$

$$592699 := C(9, \sqrt{9})^{6 \times 2 - 9} - 5$$

$$592709 := C(9, \sqrt{07+2})^{\sqrt{9}} + 5$$

$$592799 := C(9, \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{7+2}} + 95$$

$$592839 := 9 \times 3 \times (C(8, 2)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5)$$

$$592999 := C(9, \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} + 295$$

$$627262 := -2 + C(6 \times 2, 7)^{\sqrt{-2+6}}$$

$$627264 := C(4 \times 6/2, 7)^{\sqrt{-2+6}}$$

$$649775 := 5 \times (7 + 7 \times C(9 \times \sqrt{4}, 6))$$

$$657744 := C(-\sqrt{4} + 4 \times 7, 7) - 56$$

$$657985 := (6^5 - C(7, \sqrt{9})) \times 85$$

$$668196 := 6 \times (-\sqrt{9} + C(18, 6)) \times 6$$

$$669438 := C(8 \times 3, 4) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 66)$$

$$672955 := 5 \times (-5 + C(-\sqrt{9} + 27, 6))$$

$$672995 := 5 \times (\sqrt{9} + C(-\sqrt{9} + 27, 6))$$

$$697674 := C(\sqrt{4} \times 7 + 6, 7) \times 9 - 6$$

$$699401 := C(10 \times \sqrt{4}, 9) + 9^6$$

$$706629 := C(-\sqrt{9} + 26, 6) \times 07$$

$$759546 := C(6, 4)^5 + \sqrt{9} \times 57$$

$$887939 := -\sqrt{9} + C(3 \times 9, 7) - 88$$

$$887942 := C(24 + \sqrt{9}, 7) - 88$$

$$892296 := C(6 + 9 + 2, 2) \times \sqrt{9^8}$$

$$941189 := 98^{-C(1,1)+4} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$943488 := 8 \times (C(C(8, \sqrt{4}), 3)) \times 4 \times 9$$

$$979566 := (6^6 - C(5, \sqrt{9})) \times 7 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$979776 := 6^7 \times 7 / \sqrt{C(9, 7) / 9}$$

$$979797 := (7 + C(9, 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 7) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$998196 := -6 \times (9 + (1 - C(8, \sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{9}})$$

$$999995 := -5 + (C(9, 9) + 99)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

4.4 Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial and square-root** in reverse order of digits. Due to high quantity of numbers, below are only numbers up to 5 digits having square-root and factorial:

$$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$$

$$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$0496 := C(6 + (\sqrt{9})!, 4) + 0!$$

$$0699 := -C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) + 6! - 0!$$

$$0748 := C(8, \sqrt{4}) + (7 - 0)!$$

$$0792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 + 0)$$

$$0923 := C(3! \times 2, (\sqrt{9})!) - 0!$$

$$1464 := \sqrt{4} \times 6! + C(4, 1)!$$

$$2688 := \sqrt{8! \times 8!} / C(6, 2)$$

$$3464 := \sqrt{4} \times 6! + C(4!, 3)$$

$$4296 := 6! \times \sqrt{C(9, 2)} - 4!$$

$$4944 := -4! \times 4 + (9 - \sqrt{4})!$$

$$4965 := 5! + C(C(6, \sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$7993 := C(3!, \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} - 7$$

$$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!)$$

$$00395 := -5 + C((\sqrt{9})!, 3)^{0!+0!}$$

$$00789 := (\sqrt{C(9, 8)})!! + 70 - 0!$$

$$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$$

$$00794 := C(4 \times \sqrt{9}, 7) + 0! + 0!$$

$$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!))$$

$$00926 := C(6 \times 2, (\sqrt{9})!) + 0! + 0!$$

$$01299 := \sqrt{9} + C(9, 2)^{1+0!}$$

$$01994 := C(4!, \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{9} \times 10$$

$$02044 := C(4!, \sqrt{4} + 0!) + 20$$

$$02399 := C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times (3 + 2)! - 0!$$

$$02483 := \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \times C(4!, 2) - 0!$$

$$02493 := 3 \times \sqrt{9} \times (C(4!, 2) + 0!)$$

$$02499 := (\sqrt{9})! + 9 \times (C(4!, 2) + 0!)$$

$$02743 := 3!! + C(4!, \sqrt{7+2}) - 0!$$

$$02983 := C(3! + 8, (\sqrt{9})!) - 20$$

$$03464 := \sqrt{4} \times 6! + C(4!, 3) + 0$$

$$03696 := C(6 + (\sqrt{9})!, 6) \times (3 + 0!)$$

$$03983 := (3!! - C(8, \sqrt{9})) \times 3! - 0!$$

$$03984 := 4! \times (C(8 + \sqrt{9}, 3) + 0!)$$

$$04297 := 7! - (\sqrt{C(9, 2)})! - 4! + 0!$$

$$04965 := 5! + C(C(6, \sqrt{9}), 4) + 0$$

$$04987 := 7! - C(8, \sqrt{9}) + 4 - 0!$$

$$04999 := C \left((\sqrt{9})! + 9, (\sqrt{9})! \right) - (\sqrt{4} + 0)!$$

$$05401 := C \left(10, \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5! + 0!$$

$$05537 := 7 \times \left(C \left(\sqrt{3!}/5, 5 \right) - 0! \right)$$

$$05879 := \left(\sqrt{C(9,7)} \right)! \times 8 + 5! - 0!$$

$$05979 := - (\sqrt{9})! + C \left(7 \times \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0! \right)$$

$$05985 := C \left(5!/8 + (\sqrt{9})!, 5 - 0! \right)$$

$$07944 := 4! \times \left(C \left((\sqrt{4} + 9), 7 \right) + 0! \right)$$

$$07999 := C \left((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - (7 \times 0)!$$

$$08569 := C \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6, 5 \right) + (8 \times 0)!$$

$$09246 := 6 \times \left(C \left(4! - 2, \sqrt{9} \right) + 0! \right)$$

$$09829 := \sqrt{9} \times C \left(28, \sqrt{9} \right) + 0!$$

$$09906 := -6! + C \left((0! + \sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9} + 0! \right)$$

$$09955 := -5 + 5! \times \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) - 0! \right)$$

$$12239 := (\sqrt{9})!! \times \left(C(3!, 2) + 2 \right) - 1$$

$$12769 := \left((\sqrt{9})!! / 6 - 7 \right)^{C(2,1)}$$

$$12996 := \left(6! / (\sqrt{9})! - (\sqrt{9})! \right)^{C(2,1)}$$

$$13435 := -5 + \left(3! + \sqrt{4} \right)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13464 := 4! + \left(\sqrt{64} \right)! / C(3, 1)$$

$$13822 := -2 + \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \right)!^{C(3,1)}$$

$$13894 := 4!^{\sqrt{9}} + C(8, 3 + 1)$$

$$14161 := (-1 + (6 - 1)!)^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}}$$

$$14396 := C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3!! - C(4, 1)$$

$$14399 := C \left((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3!! - \sqrt{4} + 1$$

$$14856 := \left(-6 + \sqrt{5^8} \right) \times C(4, 1)!$$

$$15984 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times 8! - (\sqrt{9})!! \right) / C(5, 1)$$

$$16799 := C \left((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7! / 6 - 1$$

$$17294 := 4! \times (\sqrt{9})!! + C(2 \times 7, 1)$$

$$19395 := \left(-5 + \sqrt{9} \times 3!! \right) \times C(9, 1)$$

$$19413 := (3!! - 1) \times \left(4! + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right)$$

$$19447 := C \left(-7 + 4!, \sqrt{49} \right) - 1$$

$$19494 := \left(\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!! \right) \times \left(4! + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right)$$

$$20347 := C \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right), 3! - 0! \right) - 2$$

$$20349 := C \left(-\sqrt{9} + 4!, 3 + 0! \right)$$

$$23343 := C \left(3!, \sqrt{4} \right) + 3!^{3!} / 2$$

$$23751 := C \left(\sqrt{1 + 5! \times 7}, 3! - 2 \right)$$

$$26928 := C(8, 2) + (\sqrt{9})!! \times 6^2$$

$$26978 := -8! + C \left((\sqrt{7+9})!, 6 \right) / 2$$

$$27951 := \sqrt{(1 + 5!)^{\sqrt{9}}} \times C(7, 2)$$

$$29444 := \left(C(4!, 4) + 4^{(\sqrt{9})!} \right) \times 2$$

$$29568 := 8! \times (6 + 5) / C \left((\sqrt{9})!, 2 \right)$$

$$29791 := \left((1 + \sqrt{9})! + 7 \right)^{C(\sqrt{9}, 2)}$$

$$32379 := \sqrt{9} \times (-7 + C(3!, 2) \times 3!!)$$

$$32645 := -5! + \sqrt{4^{C(6,2)}} - 3$$

$$33409 := \left(-(\sqrt{9})!! + C(-0! + 4!, 3!) \right) / 3$$

$$33574 := \sqrt{4} \times \left(7^5 - C(3!, 3) \right)$$

$$33649 := \sqrt{9} \times C(4!, 6) / (3! + 3!)$$

$$35568 := 8! - C \left(\sqrt{6!}/5, 5 \right) \times 3!$$

$$37968 := 8! / 6! \times \left(-(\sqrt{9})! \times 7 + 3!! \right)$$

$$38288 := -8 + 8! - C \left((\sqrt{2 \times 8})!, 3 \right)$$

$$38976 := \left(6! - (\sqrt{7+9})! \right) \times C(8, 3)$$

$$39435 := C \left(5 + 3!, \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 3!! \right)$$

$$39498 := 8! - C \left(9 \times \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{9} \right) - 3!$$

$$39599 := -C(9, 9) + (5 + \sqrt{9})! - 3!!$$

$$39628 := 8! + C \left(2 + 6, (\sqrt{9})! \right) - 3!!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39648 &:= 8! - (\sqrt{4} + 6) \times C(9, 3) \\
 39655 &:= 55 \times (6! + C(\sqrt{9}, 3)) \\
 39748 &:= 8! - \sqrt{4} \times C(7 + (\sqrt{9})!, 3) \\
 39878 &:= 8 \times (7! - C(8, \sqrt{9})) + 3! \\
 39978 &:= 8! - 7^{\sqrt{9}} + C(\sqrt{9}, 3) \\
 39982 &:= -2 - C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - 3!!) \\
 39985 &:= 5! + 8! - C(((\sqrt{9})! + 9, 3)) \\
 40335 &:= (5 + 3)! + C(3!, \sqrt{04}) \\
 40588 &:= -8 + 8! + C((5 - 0!)!, \sqrt{4}) \\
 40698 &:= 8! + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} + 0!, \sqrt{4}) \\
 42348 &:= 8! + C(4!, 3) + \sqrt{2^4} \\
 42503 &:= C((3 + 0!)!, 5) - C(2, \sqrt{4}) \\
 42505 &:= C((5 - 0!)!, 5) + C(2, \sqrt{4}) \\
 42549 &:= -\sqrt{9} + C(4!, 5) + 2 \times 4! \\
 42554 &:= C(4!, 5) + 52 - \sqrt{4} \\
 42952 &:= (-2 + 5!) \times ((\sqrt{9})!! / 2 + 4) \\
 43599 &:= -(\sqrt{9})! + 9 \times C(5! / 3!, 4) \\
 43659 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5) \times 63^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 43839 &:= C(\sqrt{9} \times 3!, 8) + 3^4 \\
 44095 &:= -5 + C(9 + 0!, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 44124 &:= 4! + C(21, \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 45388 &:= 8! + C(8, 3!) + (5 + \sqrt{4})! \\
 45478 &:= 8! + 7! - \sqrt{4} + C(5, 4)! \\
 46593 &:= 3!^{(\sqrt{9})!} - (5! + 6) / \sqrt{4} \\
 46629 &:= -C(\sqrt{9}, 2) + 6^6 - 4! \\
 46634 &:= \sqrt{C(4, 3)} + 6^6 - 4! \\
 47496 &:= 6^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 4! \times C(7, 4) \\
 47502 &:= 2 \times C(\sqrt{0! + 5! \times 7}, 4) \\
 48328 &:= C(8 \times 2, 3!) + (\sqrt{\sqrt{8^4}})! \\
 49296 &:= 6! + C(((\sqrt{9})! - 2)!, \sqrt{9}) \times 4! \\
 49333 &:= C(3^3, 3!) / (\sqrt{9})! - \sqrt{4} \\
 49339 &:= C(9 \times 3, 3!) / (\sqrt{9})! + 4 \\
 49392 &:= 2 \times C(9, 3)^{\sqrt{9}} / 4! \\
 49854 &:= (-C(4!, 5) + 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!) / 4 \\
 51948 &:= 8! + C(\sqrt{4} \times 9 + 1, 5) \\
 53154 &:= 4! + C(\sqrt{5^{1+3}}, 5) \\
 54264 &:= C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4+5})!) \\
 59094 &:= \sqrt{C(4!, \sqrt{9}) + 0!} + 9^5 \\
 59239 &:= C(C((\sqrt{9})!, 3), 2) + 9^5 \\
 59346 &:= (6! + C(4! + 3, (\sqrt{9})!)) / 5 \\
 59445 &:= 5! + C(4!, \sqrt{4}) + 9^5 \\
 59598 &:= C(8 + \sqrt{9}, 5) \times (9 + 5!) \\
 59968 &:= -\sqrt{8^6} + 9! / C((\sqrt{9})!, 5) \\
 60394 &:= -\sqrt{4} + C(9, 3) \times (-0! + 6!) \\
 60396 &:= C(6 + \sqrt{9}, 3) \times (-0! + 6!) \\
 60399 &:= \sqrt{9} + C(9, 3) \times (-0! + 6!) \\
 63744 &:= (C(4!, 4) - \sqrt{7-3}) \times 6 \\
 64814 &:= C(4, 1)^8 - \sqrt{4} - 6! \\
 69264 &:= 4! \times ((6! + 2) \times \sqrt{9} + 6!) \\
 72244 &:= (C(4!, \sqrt{4}) + 2)^2 - 7! \\
 74088 &:= C(7, \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{0!+8}} \times 8 \\
 74244 &:= (-7 + C(4!, 2)) \times C(4!, \sqrt{4}) \\
 74379 &:= -\sqrt{9} + C((7-3)!, 4) \times 7 \\
 74382 &:= C(\sqrt{2 \times 8 \times 3!}, 4) \times 7 \\
 74459 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7 \\
 74644 &:= C(4! - \sqrt{4}, 6) + 4! + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$76793 := C\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{9}\right), 7\right) - 6! - 7$$

$$76896 := 6^{\left(\sqrt{C(9,8)}\right)!} + 6 \times 7!$$

$$77544 := 4! + C\left(4 \times 5, \sqrt{7 \times 7}\right)$$

$$79422 := \left(C\left((2+2)!, 4\right) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!\right) \times 7$$

$$79443 := \left(3!! + C(4!, 4) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 7$$

$$79644 := C\left(4! - \sqrt{4}, 6\right) - 9 + 7!$$

$$79965 := 5! \times 6! - C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 9, 7\right)$$

$$80584 := -\sqrt{4} \times \left(C(8, 5 + 0!) - 8!\right)$$

$$83958 := 8! - 5! + C\left(\sqrt{9} \times 3!, 8\right)$$

$$84944 := \left(C(4!, 4) - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)! - \sqrt{4}\right) \times 8$$

$$84984 := -4! + C\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 4\right) \times 8$$

$$85944 := \left(C(4!, 4) - \sqrt{9} + 5!\right) \times 8$$

$$86948 := -C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!^6 + 8!$$

$$86977 := C(7, 7) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!^6 + 8!$$

$$86996 := C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!^6 + 8!$$

$$88648 := C\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}, 6\right) + 8! + 8!$$

$$89424 := C(4!, 2) \times 4 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}$$

$$90592 := -2 + C(9, 5) \times \left(-0! + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!\right)$$

$$90699 := (9! - C(9, 6)) / \left(0! + \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$91567 := \left(C(7, 6) + 5!\right) \times \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!\right)$$

$$93332 := 2 \times 3!^{3!} + C\left(3!, \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$93594 := \left(4 + C(9, 5)\right) \times 3!! - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!$$

$$94268 := -8 - (6 + 2)! + C\left(4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$94276 := -(-6 + 7 \times 2)! + C\left(4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$94278 := -8 \times 7! + 2 + C\left(4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$94348 := -8! + C(4!, 3!) + 4! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$94968 := 8! + \sqrt{6! + 9} \times C\left(4!, \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$94988 := -8 - 8! + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + C\left(4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$94996 := 6! - 9!/9 + C\left(4!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$95907 := -7! + C\left(-0! + (9 - 5)!, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$97395 := (5! + 9) \times \left(3!! + C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$97489 := -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! \times C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right) + 7^{\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!}$$

$$98448 := 8 \times C(4!, 4) + 8! / \sqrt{9}$$

$$98984 := -4! + 8 \times C\left(9 + 8, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$$

$$99135 := 5 \times C(3, 1)^9 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!$$

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References

- [1] H.E. DUDENEY, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [2] E. FREIDMAN, Problem of the Month (August 2000), <http://bit.ly/2MuWyhU>.
- [3] E. FREIDMAN, Problem of the Month (April 2012) - <http://bit.ly/2waZlm6>.
- [4] J.S. MADACHY, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.

- [5] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers: Consecutive Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **17**(2014), Article 140, pp. 1-57. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v17/v17a140.pdf>.
- [6] **I.J. TANEJA**, Different Types of Pretty Wild Narcissistic Numbers: Selfie Representations - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 32, pp.1-43. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a32.pdf>.
- [7] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers: Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders of Non Consecutive Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 70, pp.1-104. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a70.pdf>.
- [8] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - I: Symmetrical and Unified Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 174, pp.1-94. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a174.pdf>.
- [9] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - II: Six Digits Symmetrical, Unified and Patterned Representations Without Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 175, pp.1-41. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a175.pdf>.
- [10] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - III: With Factorial and Without Square-Root - Up To Five Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 16, pp.1-52, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a16.pdf>.
- [11] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - IV: Addition, Subtraction and Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 163, pp.1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a163.pdf>.
- [12] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - V: Six Digits Symmetrical Representations with Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 164, pp.1-60, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a164.pdf>.
- [13] **I.J. TANEJA**, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.
- [14] **I.J. TANEJA**, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 20, 2019, pp. 1-115, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574136>.
- [15] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers and Binomial Coefficients, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), pp. 1-18, Art. 25, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a25.pdf>.
- [16] **I.J. TANEJA**, Binomial Coefficients Type Selfie Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 102, pp.1-113, <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a102.pdf>.
- [17] **I.J. TANEJA**, Concatenation-Type Selfie Numbers With Factorial and Square-Root, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 08, 2019, pp. 1-43, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2587751>.
- [18] **I.J. TANEJA**, Digit's Order Selfie Numbers: Factorial and Square-Root, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 140, pp. 1-86, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a140.pdf>.
- [19] **I.J. TANEJA**, Digit's Order Selfie Numbers: Fibonacci and Triangular Values, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 141, pp. 1-67, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a141.pdf>.
- [20] **I.J. TANEJA**, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.

- [21] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>.
- [22] **I.J. TANEJA**, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [23] **I.J. TANEJA**, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
- [24] **I.J. TANEJA**, Permutable Powers Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 15, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2566445>.
- [25] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>
- [26] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 18, 2019, pp. 1-116, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571472>.
- [27] **I.J. TANEJA**, Quadratic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 25, 2019, pp. 1-315, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2577472>.
- [28] **I.J. TANEJA**, Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Reverse Order of Digits, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 06, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2585599>.
- [29] **I.J. TANEJA**, Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 12, 2019, pp. 1-150, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591257>.
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